

Understanding strategic nurse leadership in public policy:
an international study

Meghan Louise Bateson

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is of my own composition, based on my own work, with acknowledgements of other sources, and has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

 Personal details withheld.

Meghan Louise Bateson

13th March 2024

Abstract

Background

Despite longstanding calls to expand the policy contribution of nursing, research on strategic nurse leadership in policy at a national or international level is under-developed. Understanding international experiences of strategic nurse leaders in influencing policy is critical to realising ambitions for nursing's growth as a policy influential profession.

Aims

To investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contribution to public policy, and to construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

Methods

This three-phase social constructionist study comprised pre-Delphi interviews (n=8), three round modified Policy Delphi (n=40), and post-Delphi interviews (n=10) with strategic nurse leaders from 39 countries. Post-Delphi interviews with government nurse leaders explored the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement constructed during the Delphi. Pre- and post-Delphi interviews were semi-structured, and framework analysed. The Delphi data were analysed using descriptive statistics and content analysis. Culturally Endorsed Leadership Theory and bases of social power provided theoretical richness to study design and interpretation of findings.

Findings

The findings reveal a disconnection between the rhetoric and reality of policy influence for strategic nurse leaders internationally. Despite international variation marginalisation was identified as the overarching challenge to policy influence. Strategic nurse leaders offered mitigating approaches, which centred on expanding the capacity, capability, credibility, and connectivity of the profession as a policy actor. Application of the theoretical lenses identified threats to nursing's legitimate and expert power and suggested that realisation of nursing's ambitions for substantive improvement to policy influence may require wider cultural change.

Conclusion

This is the first theoretically informed study to investigate the approaches and challenges of a cross-sectoral, international cohort of elite strategic nurse leaders. The synthesis of key points of international agreement into a narrative consensus statement offers a novel contribution to the field of strategic nurse leadership in policy.

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These acknowledgements have been written four times as new names were added, and loves were lost. Now for the final version.

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List of Abbreviations

CLT: Culturally endorsed implicit leadership theory

GCNO: Government Chief Nursing Officer

ICN: International Council of Nurses

IQR: Interquartile Range

USA: United States of America

WHO: World Health Organisation

Chapter 1. Introduction

Comprising almost 60% of the health workforce (World Health Organisation, WHO, 2020), nurses are recognised as critical to delivery of global ambitions including the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015; WHO, 2017a). The high-level policy making required to bring such ambitions to fruition has however tended to exclude nurses partly because of their traditionally perceived role of implementer, rather than influencer of the high-level policy (Salvage and White, 2019; Rasheed, Younas and Mehdi, 2020). The landmark Munich declaration (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2000) recognised the latent potential of nursing, urging governments to involve nurses in all parts of the policy process. Over the subsequent decades, the ambitions of the Munich declaration (WHO, 2000) have been built on by influential publications including the All-Party Parliamentary Group on Global Health (2016) Triple Impact Report, a catalyst for the Nursing Now campaign (Holloway *et al.*, 2021), as well as the Global Strategic Directions for Nursing and Midwifery (WHO, 2021). Despite persistent international endorsements for the inclusion of nursing in policymaking (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2000; Institute of Medicine, 2011; WHO, 2021), there continue to be challenges to realising nursing's policy potential (Fawcett-Henesy and Benton, 2020).

Strategic nurse leadership roles, which exist to varying extents across government, education, professional nursing associations, trade unions, and regulators (Benton *et al.*, 2017; Council of Deans of Health, 2021; WHO, 2015), have been identified as key to the policy influence of the profession (Büscher and Wagner, 2005; International Council of Nurses, 2020). Strategic nurse leaders vary internationally in position, permanence, remit, and authority, with consequent implications for their policy influence. The International Council of Nurses (2020) has had a longstanding focus on the presence and precarity of Government Chief Nursing Officer (GCNO) positions as a route to policy influence. Within the WHO, the position of Chief Nursing Officer has been intermittent, most recently reinstated in 2017 (WHO, 2017b). In their analysis of prior instability of the WHO Chief Nursing Officer position Huffman and Huffman Splane (1994) perceived a link to changes in leadership priorities within the WHO. Even where strategic positions appear permanent changes to structural position of those posts can have implications for their policy influence. In England, for example, while the Chief Medical Officer remained in government, the Chief Nursing Officer was moved out of the government's Department of Health and Social Care, into the National Health Service (Ford, 2018). The move presented a structural barrier to nursing's policy influence in government and prompted lobbying for the position to be returned to government (Royal College of Nursing, 2018). As a result of the lobbying, the Chief Nursing Officer was repositioned to straddle the government's Department of Health and Social Care in 2019, acting as the health secretary's direct

advisor on nursing policy (Mitchell, 2019). Although resolved, such changes suggest that despite espoused rhetoric, the position of nursing as a policy actor is not a certainty.

While momentum has gathered around improving the visibility and perceived value of nursing in policy there is little empirical literature published on the experience of strategic nurse leaders influencing high-level policy, discussed further in the integrative review in chapter 2 and 8.4. The focus of the nursing leadership literature on investigations at the levels of individuals, teams, and organisations, rather than national or international leadership is perhaps unsurprising given the number of nurses in organisational roles. The nursing leadership evidence base at the level of team or organizational leadership is large enough to support systematic reviews in specific topics including patient outcomes (Wong, Cummings and Ducharme, 2013), nurse burnout (Wei *et al.*, 2020), and educational interventions (Cummings *et al.*, 2021). In sharp contrast the literature on strategic nurse leadership is underdeveloped, and few strategic nurse leadership studies have focused on high-level policy making. The lack of empirical research on strategic nurse leadership in public policy is contrasted by a burgeoning editorial and opinion literature (Crisp, 2018; Salvage and White, 2019; Daly *et al.*, 2020; Hasmilller, 2022; Morone *et al.*, 2022; Stilwell and Newman, 2022). This thesis will argue that the existing body of empirical knowledge about international strategic nurse leadership in policy is insufficient to scaffold the development of nursing towards realising its ambitions as a policy actor. Expanding the small knowledge base is important to the operationalization of the espoused future direction and policy influence of strategic nurse leaders across sectoral and cultural contexts.

Calls to increase nursing's policy engagement have regularly focused on encouraging nurses to become more involved as individual policy actors (Groenwald and Eldridge, 2019; Salvage, Montayre and Gunn, 2019; Disch, 2020). While it might be tempting to frame policy influence as requiring more action at an individual level, this oversimplification neglects the role of cultural and contextual interdependencies on policy influence. The variation in status, influence and image of nursing makes it critical that international leadership and policy research foregrounds a nuanced understanding of culture and context. The traditional domination of Global North voices in the nursing leadership literature (Cummings *et al.*, 2021; Chiu *et al.*, 2023) threatens the transferability of research findings to the Global South. Research in strategic nurse leadership could benefit from cultural humility, the continuous cycle of learning and adaptation informed by the dynamic intersection between diversity, context, and power dynamics (Foronda, 2020). Cultural humility and cultural competence, sometimes interpreted as inferring that cultural competency can be 'achieved' (Greene-Moton and Minkler, 2020), could help generate research insights which could inform development of contextually sensitive approaches to support strategic nurse leaders in influencing policy. This thesis

foregrounds cultural and contextual variation through the lens of social constructionism and theoretical perspective of Culturally Endorsed Leadership Theory (House *et al.* 2014).

This thesis will extend the current understanding of international strategic nurse leadership, focusing on the approaches nurse leaders consider important to developing the policy influence of the profession. It will also offer potential strategies which could be adopted to prepare and position nursing as a legitimate policy actor. This original contribution to knowledge will be delivered by addressing two research aims:

1. To investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contribution to public policy.
2. To develop a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

1.1 Background to the research

I was not a strategic nurse leader when I started this thesis, and I am not one now. As a registered nurse I was keen to build on my unit and hospital level understanding of policy influence and understand how nursing could progress beyond calls for nurses to be involved to the actual influence of the profession in national and international policy making. While teaching nursing in Egypt during the 2013 revolution I was struck by differences in the societal and professional expectations of nursing compared to my Scottish reference point. The experience tested my assumptions about what it means to be a nurse and offered me an insight into the cultural and contextual variation in role and status of nursing internationally. On returning to Scotland, I had the opportunity to pursue my curiosity around international strategic nurse leadership through a PhD following speculative discussions between the university, where I worked as a lecturer, and the International Council of Nurses (ICN). Initial scoping revealed that surprisingly little was known empirically, and I recognised that undertaking a thesis would give me the opportunity to understand the topic in greater depth. My international experience left me with an appreciation for multiple realities in nursing and leadership, which later brought me to social constructionism when starting this PhD. Although the collaboration between the university and the ICN only extended to the end of the Delphi study in 2016, I was fortunate that the link to international strategic nurse leadership continued via my supervisory team.

1.2 Defining key concepts

Several key concepts are critical to understanding the scope of this study: nurse, strategic nurse leadership, public policy, and policy influence.

Nurse

This thesis defines a nurse as an individual who has completed the educational requirements to practise as a professional nurse in their national context. The International Labour Organization (2012, p.43) International Standard Classification of Occupations definition states: “nursing professionals assume responsibility for the planning and management of the care of patients, working autonomously or in teams with medical doctors and others.” Acknowledging variation in nursing internationally, the ILO (2008) highlights that nations may choose to classify nurses as professionals (ISCO code 2221) or as technicians and associate professionals depending on the role of nurses in that country (ISCO code 3221). The ILO definition of a professional nurse, while adopted by the State of the World’s Nursing Report (WHO, 2020), does not foreground other components of nursing such as leadership or the safety critical nature, highlighted in the updated Royal College of Nursing (2023) definition of nursing. In view of the complexity of the international nursing context, defining a nurse by their permission to practice as a professional nurse in their country was a pragmatic approach to describing the population of nurses who could become future strategic nurse leaders.

Strategic nurse leadership

Strategic nurse leadership in the context of this thesis is defined as being a nurse leader with a remit at a national or international level. In practical terms, this means nurses in roles which are considered in this study to represent the elite of the profession, including GCNOs, registrars of national nursing regulators, presidents of professional nursing associations, and deans within nurse education. This thesis is focused on the global perspectives of strategic nurse leaders on their approaches and challenges in enacting their leadership through influencing policy. Individual leadership styles and theories were not under study in this thesis.

This thesis required a definition encompassing nursing leadership and influence at a strategic level. The literature is replete with definitions, theories, and conceptualisations of leadership (Northouse, 2021). When debating the most appropriate definition, one of the first to be considered was the definition of leadership within Culturally Endorsed Leadership Theory (CLT, House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014), one of the two theoretical perspectives adopted in this thesis. Although CLT provided a useful assumption about the culturally mediated nature of leadership (discussed further in 3.2.2), the definition of leadership used in the initial GLOBE research was limited to influence within an organisation (House *et al.*, 2004). An organisational leadership definition was too narrow for the focus in this thesis on strategic leadership and public policy.

Yukl's (2013) description of leadership as both a role and a social process was attractive to the social constructionist epistemology of the study. Yukl (2013, p2) defines *leadership* as "the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives". Yukl's (2013) definition is sufficiently broad to include the influence of strategic nurse leaders beyond their organisation and profession. It is also action oriented, which fits with the focus in this thesis on leadership for policy influence. A potential criticism of the adoption of Yukl's (2013) definition is that it does not include the values of the leader. Considering the values-based character of nursing, it could be argued that definitions specific to a leadership theory more usually aligned to nursing, such as transformational (Alanazi, Alshamlani and Baker, 2023) or moral focused leadership theories, including authentic leadership (Luthans and Avolio, 2003; Alilyyani, Wong and Cummings, 2018; Lemoine, Hartnell and Leroy, 2019) would have been useful. Whilst the values of nurse leaders will inform their policy positions, exploring this was beyond the scope of this thesis. Yukl's (2013) more inclusive definition had a clear focus on influence, the subject of interest, and was therefore adopted.

Public policy

To support exploration of policy influence this thesis used Dye's (2011, p2) often-cited definition: "public policy is anything a government chooses to do or not to do". While this broad definition is an oversimplification of the intricate nature of policymaking, it indicates the far-reaching nature public policy. In its breadth Dye's (2011) definition enables public policy to be perceived as important to nursing rather than an intangible high-level irrelevance. The definition also provides an inclusive frame for nursing's policy activity within and beyond traditional boundaries of health or nursing specific policy engagement. Health is critical to achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals as a whole, not just those explicitly orientated to health (Greer *et al.*, 2022). Adopting a broad definition of policy offered an opportunity to generate insights about the approaches and challenges of strategic nurse leaders in maximizing the impact of their expertise across public policy.

Policy influence

The term policy advocacy is often used in the nursing literature to discuss policy activity in nursing (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012; Chiu *et al.*, 2023). Advocacy is, however, argued by Start and Hovland (2004) to be one approach to a broader concept of 'policy influence'. They delineate advocacy as the approach used when on the 'outside track' compared with advising on the 'inside track' (Figure 1.1). The use of policy advocacy in this study, therefore, could have created an assumption from the outset that nursing is limited to the outside track of policy influence.

Figure 1.1 Approaches to policy influence (Adapted from Start and Hovland, 2004, p5)

Taking a more inclusive approach, this thesis uses the term 'policy influence' to refer to the ability of individual strategic nurse leaders and/or the profession to set policy agendas or affect the direction of existing policy issues, enabling a broader understanding of nursing's engagement with policymaking.

1.3 Overview of the thesis

Chapter 1 highlights the perpetual call for involvement of strategic nurse leaders in public policy. Although the need to expand nursing engagement in policy and decision-making is routinely espoused, threats to the development of nursing's policy influence remain. The lack of a consistent nursing presence at key policy fora during COVID-19 demonstrated that the position of nursing as a credible policy actor cannot be assumed.

Chapter 2 critiques the small body of published literature on strategic nurse leadership and public policy between 2004 and March-2015, used to inform the first round of the modified Policy Delphi (reported in Chapter 6). The integrative review argues that research on factors impeding or enabling policy influence at a national or international level is underdeveloped. Consequently, the research question arising from the integrative review was: *What are the internationally shared and unique perceptions of strategic nurse leaders on their current and potential policy influence?* The research question was addressed via research aims which aimed to extend the existing knowledge by investigating strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contributions to public policy, as well as to develop a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

Chapter 3 debates and defends the methodological and theoretical choices of the study. The social constructionist underpinning and its congruence with a consensus-building design are explored. The chapter examines arguments for undertaking a modified Policy Delphi study to achieve the research aims. It constructs strategies to strengthen the rigour of the Delphi, particularly the use of pre- and post-Delphi interviews. The theoretical lenses borrowed from CLT (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014) and bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) are set out. Key ethical considerations to the conduct of the research are explored. Chapter 3 provides important context to the procedural conduct of the research described in Chapter 4.

Chapter 4 details the methods used to deliver the three-phase study: pre-Delphi semi-structured interviews with key informants, a three-round modified Policy Delphi, and post-Delphi semi-structured interviews with government nurse leaders. Procedures for the framework analysis of interviews and content analysis of qualitative Delphi data are described. The descriptive statistical analysis of the quantitative data is outlined, and a defence is provided for setting the threshold for agreement at 67% (interquartile range ≤ 1). In addition to strategies for promoting rigour, the application of ethical principles is addressed.

Chapter 5 reports the findings of the pre-Delphi interviews with eight nurse leaders from across different sectors of strategic nursing leadership. Framework analysis highlighted challenges including a surprising emphasis on the marginalisation of nurses in policy and establishing policy influence as legitimate nursing work. Approaches proposed by participants to improve nursing's policy influence included the preparation of future nurse leaders and collaboration to support a collective policy voice for nursing. Along with the literature review, the pre-Delphi findings informed the structured first round of the Delphi.

Chapter 6 provides the findings of each of the three rounds of the modified Policy Delphi study. The Delphi panel comprised forty strategic nurse leaders recruited from thirty-two countries. The panelists were drawn from across nursing sectors, world regions, and national income levels. The findings identify areas of divergence and consensus on the challenges, centering on marginalisation, and proposed approaches to improve the profession's influence. Key points of agreement in the Delphi were constructed into a draft consensus statement to establish global perspectives on approaches to the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders, presented to the Delphi panel for consideration in the final round. The consensus statement demonstrated the potential for international consensus on approaches to policy influence.

Chapter 7 sets out the perspective of government nurse leaders (n=10) on the resonance and potential utility of the draft Delphi consensus statement derived through individual interviews. Participants agreed with the draft statement content, offered ideas to expand it, and emphasised the need for nurse leaders to strengthen their policy influence. There were mixed views on the benefits of showing their impact versus persuading others they should be involved in policy discussions. They highlighted a need to strengthen the capability of strategic nurse leaders to better articulate their policy positions in the context of the broader socio-political context and return on investment.

Chapter 8 discusses the findings in the context of the research aims, theoretical perspectives and contemporary literature. Interpretation of the findings is tempered by recognition of the merits and limitations of the study. Antecedents to the overarching challenge of marginalisation included culturally mediated expectations of nurse leaders and prevailing power dynamics, contributing to nurses being seen but not heard. Approaches to improving policy influence centred on shifting culture to perceive strategic nurse leaders as credible policy actors, while building the policy capacity and capability of strategic nurse leaders. Application of the theoretical lenses suggested that nursing's ambitions for substantive improvement to the strength and breadth of its policy influence may require societal and cultural change beyond the profession. The thesis concludes with recommendations for policy, practice, education, and research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter presents an integrative review of the small body of empirical and theoretical literature exploring the relationship between strategic nurse leadership and public policy. It follows the principles of an integrative review as set out by Whitemore and Knafl (2005): problem identification, literature search, data evaluation, data analysis, and presentation. The literature review was designed to inform the first round of the Delphi study, reported in Chapter 6. Therefore, only literature published between 2004 and March 2015 were included, with the exception of seminal or landmark work. Relevant literature published after March 2015 is critically considered in the discussion (Chapter 8). The chapter concludes with the presentation of the research question arising from the findings of the integrative review.

2.1 Literature Review Question

What is known from existing literature about strategic nurse leadership in relation to influencing public policy?

2.2 Literature Review Methodology

The purpose of the review was to reveal what is known and not known from existing literature and generate an overview of the international research activity in this field of inquiry. Despite a burgeoning literature on nursing leadership and leadership aspects of management, the body of empirical work focussed on strategic nurse leadership is small. In selecting the type of review to undertake, preliminary searches indicated that it would be premature to embark on a systematic review. An integrative review was selected because of its capacity to synthesise literature from across paradigms to shape a thorough understanding of the topic (Cronin and George, 2023). To promote rigour Whitemore and Knafl's (2005) five-stage framework for integrative reviews was used:

1. Identifying the problem under study and development of the review question,
2. Searching the literature to identify relevant studies,
3. Data evaluation to enable selection of studies to include,
4. Data analysis informed by Miles and Huberman (1994),
5. Presenting the data.

The conventions of an integrative review allow inclusion of both empirical and theoretical literature (Whitemore and Knafl, 2005; Toronto, 2020). A reflexive stance to the review was taken, whereby steps in the review process were refined and repeated to ensure that a thorough search was undertaken within the defined search parameters as understanding of the body of work deepened.

The initial search strategy followed procedures recommended for integrative reviews method described by Whittmore and Knafl (2005), comprising:

1. an initial search of databases, followed by analysis of the text words contained in the title and abstract, and of the index terms used to describe the article,
2. a second search using all identified keywords and index terms was conducted in all included databases, and
3. the reference lists and citations of all papers included in the review were searched for additional studies.

A preliminary search of the research and wider literature informed the setting of search parameters including database selection and development of search strings using Subject Headings and keywords. As this thesis is focused on strategic leadership and public policy influence at a national or international level the search was restricted to the decade preceding data collection to promote relevance to the subsequent empirical data collection of this study. The initial inclusion criteria were refined post hoc with the benefit of familiarisation with the retrieved publications to ensure that papers that would give insight into the breadth of research activity were included.

2.2.1 Search Strategy and Results

A range of databases were searched: Medline, Cinahl, SocIndex, Biznar and PsycInfo. Key words used to identify relevant literature included: Health policy, public policy, policy development, policy advocacy, reform, knowledge brokerage, nursing, nurse leadership, strategic leadership, power, and influence. The key words were used alone and in combination as key words, subject headings, and subject terms.

In order for the integrative review to inform the first round of the Delphi which commenced in March 2015, only articles published between January 2004 and March 2015, inclusive, were eligible for consideration. The search was limited to articles published in English due to lack of resources to translate. The reference lists of included publications were scrutinised to identify other relevant literature. Additional searches were made of major nursing organisation websites to identify relevant grey literature. Zotero software was utilised as the reference management package.

Literature identified by the searches was screened for relevance using broad inclusion criteria that included reference to one or more of the domains of interest (nursing/midwifery/professional associations; government chief nursing or midwifery officers; government nurse; regulatory councils/boards/ bodies/orders/chambers; nursing/midwifery/health unions/syndicates; educational/academic institutions/schools/faculties; policy/health policy/reform). Where there was

insufficient evidence in the title and abstract to decide, full-text papers were retrieved. Studies were included if they pertained to nursing leadership at national, international, or global levels and to the public policy process. Articles examining organisational or practitioner level leadership or influence on policy were excluded. Some of this important work is selectively referred to, to provide contextual and conceptual background to inform the interpretation of review findings. Studies solely reported within grey literature were excluded.

The full text was obtained of all papers remaining in the review following broad screening. These papers were screened and all papers remaining in the review were subject to methodological appraisal and data extraction.

This literature review included empirical studies and papers which extended the knowledge of how strategic nurse leaders shape public policy. Figure 2.1 presents the PRISMA flow diagram of the literature search. The excluded studies predominantly comprised discussion papers and editorials on strategic nurse leadership and policy, and empirical literature with a primary focus on unit or organisational level leadership and policy influence.

Figure 2.1 PRISMA flow diagram

From a pool of 1727 publications, 19 satisfied the inclusion criteria for original empirical studies. Two empirical studies (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Hennessy and Hicks, 2003) published in the two years prior to the time period reviewed (2004-2015, inclusive) were included in the 19 studies due to the relevancy to the topic. Following identification of the two earlier works the literature was searched for the period 2002-2003 inclusive. No further empirical studies met the criteria for inclusion.

In addition to the 19 original studies, five theoretical and conceptual papers and two non-empirical papers relevant to strategic nurse leadership and policy influence were included, giving a total of 26 papers in the integrative review. The five theoretical papers comprised one concept analysis (Arabi *et al.*, 2014), three conceptual models (Adams and Erikson, 2011; Russell and Fawcett, 2005; Shamian, 2014), and one framework (Cohen *et al.*, 1996). Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework for

nursing's political development was included despite its age because of relevance to the topic, illustrated by its use in underpinning one of the empirical papers (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012), and having not been superseded by a newer framework in the literature.

The non-empirical papers included: one scoping review using a socio-ecological lens to examine priority setting and policy advocacy by nursing associations (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012), and a review of the epistemological foundations of nursing's policy advocacy and discussion of associated challenges (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006). These two papers were included for their theoretical richness and depth of discussion they offered to exploring strategic nurse leadership in public policy.

2.2.2 Quality assessment and appraisal

A review panel of the PhD candidate, two researchers and an Information Scientist worked collaboratively to select papers for inclusion. In line with the inclusive conventions of an integrative review, articles were considered for inclusion irrespective of the research design. Theoretical and conceptual papers were also eligible for inclusion, as well as literature reviews. Each article reporting empirical research underwent detailed critical appraisal using a tool appropriate to the study's methodology. Qualitative studies were appraised using QARI (Joanna Briggs Institute, 2014), quantitative studies and mixed methods studies were appraised using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, Pace *et al.*, 2012). Delphi studies were reviewed in tandem with the wider Delphi methodological literature, particularly Diamond *et al.* (2014), the most recent systematic review on Delphi methodology at the point of conducting the integrative review.

A method to indicate strength of the evidence was sought in line with Whitemore and Knaf's (2005) recommendations for integrative reviews but this was challenging given the breadth of the studies under consideration. This challenge was reflected by Hopia, Latvala and Liimatainen (2016) who reported a lack of consistency in the quality assessment of literature included in published integrative reviews. This is unsurprising given that integrative reviews tend to transcend more than one research paradigm. Cronin and George (2020) argue that assessment of quality should be aligned with the expectations of papers published in their field. Although Whitemore and Knaf (2005) suggest a two criteria assessment of rigour and relevance to the review question, there was insufficient detail to support execution, raising questions about the robustness of the approach. Further, it could be argued that calculating or allocating a compound quality score would have lacked the detail required to make an informed assessment of quality, and risked obscuring flaws in methodology or reporting. For this reason, further methodological discussion of the papers is detailed in section 2.3.

2.3 Characteristics of the included empirical studies

The capacity of integrative reviews to synthesise knowledge from across disciplines (Toronto, 2020) was particularly useful in the context of this review, due to the small body of research specifically focused on strategic nurse leadership in public policy. Only nine empirical papers had a primary focus on investigating strategic nurse leadership and public policy (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; McCarthy *et al.*, 2013; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.* 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a). Three of those papers (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) pertained to one study. A further three studies described roles, responsibilities and skills required to be a global nurse leader (Kim *et al.*, 2006) or GCNO (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Hennessy and Hicks, 2003). These perspectives were enriched by inclusion of studies focused on strategic leadership practice and development (Swenson, *et al.*, 2005; Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; Ross *et al.*, 2014; Wilson, *et al.*, 2014), or policy influence (Lewis, 2006; Thompson, *et al.*, 2009). An external perception of nursing leadership was provided through Khoury *et al.*'s (2011) reporting of a Gallup study.

There were a mix of methodological approaches used across the 19 empirical papers. Five were qualitative studies (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.* 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). All seven quantitative papers used survey methods (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Thompson *et al.*, 2009; Khoury *et al.*, 2011; McCarthy *et al.* 2013; Ross *et al.*, 2014; Wilson *et al.*, 2014). Mixed methods were deployed in two studies (Lewis, 2006; Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014). Of the five articles reporting three Delphi studies, one undertook a Policy Delphi (Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013), one used a modified Delphi (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a), and one appeared to use a two round classical Delphi (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003) with an unstructured first round.

The following summary tables provide an overview of the empirical qualitative (Table 2.1), quantitative (Table 2.2), Delphi (Table 2.3) and mixed methods papers (Table 2.4) included. The tables are ordered by year of publication.

Table 2.1 Integrative Review Qualitative Papers

Author(s) (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants, Country	Key Findings
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2006), 8 countries	Exploring global nurse leader competencies, their experiences of education and training, and approaches to developing global nurse leaders	Interviews: Oral (n=10) Written (n=7)	Nurse leaders (n=17) with international experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of relationships to global nurse leaders. • Need for formal and informal education including international opportunities. • Rec: Further research on global strategic nurse leaders to understand leadership development.
Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012), New Zealand	Perceptions of policy and political leadership in nursing	Interviews In person (n=16) Telephone (n=2)	Nurse leaders from Professional Nursing Association (n=18)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nurses need to learn how to communicate using policy language. • A need for succession planning for nurse leadership in the nursing association. • Behaviours designed to discredit nurse leaders. • Nurse leaders who do not support the development of other nurses.
Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014), Iran	To identify factors which influence nurse engagement in policy making	Interviews (n=20)	Nurse leaders in policy making positions, including from Board of nursing, professional nursing organisation, Ministry of Health, academia (n=18). Physicians in the Iranian Ministry of Health and Medical Education (n=2).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor performance of nurse leaders related to preparation, lack of intra-professional collaboration, and lack of expectation of nurses to contribute to policy. • Responsibility to take up policy making opportunities. • Medical dominance and paternalism over nursing. • Health system focused on treatment rather than prevention. • Lack of interdisciplinary teamworking.

Table 2.1 Integrative Review Qualitative Papers continued

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key Findings
Ditlopo <i>et al.</i> (2014), South Africa	Exploration of nurses' participation in four national policies	Multiple descriptive case study design: Interviews (n=101) Underpinned by policy analysis framework	Key informants (n=28) from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National government (n=6) • Provincial government (n=8) • Private sector (n=1) • Academia (n=7) • Statutory body (n=1) • Professional nursing association (n=4) • Non-profit global health org (n=1) Frontline nurses (n=73)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More opportunities for nurses to engage in policy than previously. • Nurse leaders included in policy, but views not always listened to • Lack of communication back to frontline nurses about policy developments • Dominance of medicine and non-nursing decision makers in policymaking • Nursing as passive in policy and onus on profession to improve policy influence. • Lack of collaboration between nurse leaders, making a collective voice problematic • Low position of nursing in the decision-making hierarchy.
Juma, Edwards and Spitzer (2014), Kenya	Exploration of nurse involvement in national health policy making	Interviews (n=32)	Interviews with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-nursing leaders (n=9, of which national level: n=6) • Nurse leaders (n=7, of which national level n=3) • Frontline nurses/managers (n=16) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nursing involvement in national policy limited and focused on nursing related issues. • Nurse leaders criticised for being nursing-centric and lacking broader policy view. • Structural barriers to policy engagement. • Nursing as an isolated profession. • Medical dominance in policymaking. • Responsibility on nursing to improve policy influence. • Need to improve nursing's policy preparation

Table 2.2 Integrative Review Quantitative Papers

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key Findings
Khoury <i>et al.</i> (2011), USA	To understand perceptions of the present and future of nursing leadership	Survey: structured telephone interview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics (n=257) Executives in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurance (n=237) • Corporate (n=232) • Health service (253) • Government policymakers (n=253) • Industry/trade association thought leaders (n=253) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nurses perceived as least likely to shape health reform – most likely were leaders in government and health insurance. • Nursing influence was recognised in relation to improving quality and safety of care. Barriers to nursing leadership included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physicians and not nurses considered to be key decision maker. • Lack of preparation for leadership. • Lack of appetite to engage in policy process. • Lack of collective voice on policy issues.
McCarthy <i>et al.</i> (2013), 13 countries from east, central and southern Africa	Describe perspectives of cross-sector nursing and midwifery leaders and their involvement in regulatory and educational reform	Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chief Nursing Officers (n=11) • Presidents of professional associations (n=11) • Academics (n=10) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes to roles and responsibilities of nurses not always reflected in regulatory framework. • Different stakeholders reported variation in responsibilities in relation to regulation. • Chief Nursing Officers most likely to be represented and involved in Nursing Council decision making. • Concerns about the capacity of the council to perform as a regulator.

Table 2.2 Integrative Review Quantitative papers continued.

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key Findings
Salmon and Rambo (2002), international, 50 countries	Understand Chief Nursing Officers (CNOs) worldwide including: key issues for CNOs and the knowledge and skills required	Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Official nursing officer positions, e.g. CNOs (n=38) • Nursing as part of wider portfolio (n=4) • Knowledgeable about role of government nursing nationally or regionally (n=8) 	Key knowledge and skills required included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workforce planning • Analysis and development of policy • Strategic thinking and planning Collaboration also noted as a key skill.
Swenson <i>et al.</i> (2005), international	Evaluate impact of Global Nursing Partnerships Conference	Survey	Chief Nursing Officers and National Nursing Association Leaders: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immediate evaluation (n=61) • Follow-up evaluation (n=13) 	Delegates valued conference as an opportunity to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • develop knowledge and skills, • connect with peers to collaborate around shared challenges, Limited long-term follow-up, however, findings suggested that the key benefit centred on the conference as a catalyst for longer term relationship building between strategic nurse leaders
Thompson <i>et al.</i> (2009), USA	Determine health commissioner advocacy and public policy involvement, perceived barriers, enablers, and self-efficacy	Survey	Health commissioners (n=327)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 69% responding health commissioners had not been active in changing policy in preceding 4 years. • Lack of time and competing priorities were key barriers to policy engagement. • 56% self-reported their knowledge about how to influence policy as good or excellent. • Conferences and peers were the most common source of education to support policy influence

Table 2.2 Integrative Review Quantitative papers continued.

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key Findings
Ross <i>et al.</i> (2014), USA	Transformational leadership practices of nurse leaders in professional nurse associations.	Survey	Professional nurse association nurse leaders (n=134)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling others to act and encouraging the heart self-reported as the most commonly enacted transformational leadership approaches. • Transformational leadership practices more likely to be reported by nurse leaders in receipt of more leadership education.
Wilson <i>et al.</i> (2014), 8 countries	Evaluation of 3 cohorts of an international nursing and health care leadership development program	Survey	Participants 2008 (n=16) 2010 (n=25) 2012 (n=25) Faculty (mentors and coaches) 2008 (n=11) 2010 (n=20) 2012 (n=10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive short-term evaluation of the program, note challenges in collection of 1 year follow up data. • Participants valued cross-cultural design of the program. • Mentor/mentee relationship evaluated more favourably by participants than by mentors. • 3-week period of mentorship and coaching better evaluated than 2-week period. • Opportunities to improve program included more unscheduled time and a longer program duration. • Challenges in communication barriers.

Table 2.3 Integrative Review Delphi papers

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key findings
Hennessy and Hicks (2003), 12 European countries	To identify ideal attributes of Chief Nursing Officers in Europe	Two Round modified Delphi	Panellists (n=75): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directors of Public Health (n=2) • Directors of planning (n=4) • Directors of finance (n=3) • Chief Nurses (n=10) • Chief Medical Officers (n=5) • Ministers of Health (n=3) • Senior postholders in professional associations (n=48) 	Top 3 ideal attributes of Chief Nursing Officers in Europe were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • communication, • promotion of nursing, and • strategic thinking. Ranked bottom 4 ideal attributes were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • conflict management, • information handling, • research skills, and • skills to make decisions and solve problems.
Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013), international	To develop an international consensus definition of professional nurse regulation, identify characteristics of a highly performing regulatory body and consider how these might be achieved	Three round Policy Delphi	Panellists (n=75) Nurse leaders from clinical practice, regulatory bodies, national nursing associations, academia, as well as patient representatives and other health related professions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identified five components of a definition for regulation. • Consensus developed on features of high-quality regulation. • Preference identified towards two options for regulatory models.

Table 2.3 Integrative Review Delphi papers continued.

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key findings
Shariff and Potgieter (2012), Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania	Extent of nurse leader participation in policy making	Three Round modified Delphi	Nurse leaders (n=37) In: Regulator (n=6) Ministry of Health (n=17) Professional Nursing Association (n=4) Academia (n=10)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed picture in relation to the extent of nurse leader policy participation. Shared understanding that nurse leaders do not lead on setting the health policy agenda. • Facilitators and barriers to nursing's policy influence included the influence of capacity and capability of the profession, the constraints of institutional structures, and negative perception of nurses. • Attributes required for nurse leaders to participate in policy development included: influence, relational skill, agency, and credibility.
Shariff (2014)	Facilitators and barriers to nursing's policy influence in East Africa			
Shariff (2015a)	Essential attributes of nurse leaders engaging in policymaking			

Table 2.4. Integrative Review Mixed Methods Papers

Authors (year), country	Aim	Methods	Participants	Key findings
Lewis (2006), Australia	Examination of whether doctors have lost power in health policy by analysing the personal and positional health policy influence in Victoria, Australia	Social network analysis and semi-structured interviews	Network analysis: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nominees identified (n=218) • Nominees contacted (n=115), • Nominees responding (n=62) Interviews (n=20)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doctors are influential in policy. • Challenging for non-medical actors to become influential in policy.
Abhicharttibutra <i>et al.</i> (2014), Thailand	To understand the context, processes, actors, and content of a policy aimed at resolving a nursing shortage in Thailand	Policy Analysis and semi-structured interviews	Interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Committee working on the policy (n=13) • Nursing faculty (n=15) Documents for analysis (n=65)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power of collaboration and leveraging strategic networks to successfully lobby to have nursing recognised as a workforce in critical shortage. • Recognition of the importance of intelligence led lobbying but also using different routes to influence policy

2.3.1 Participant characteristics in the empirical literature

The literature includes perspectives of nurse leaders in strategic positions from across education, government, healthcare providers, regulators, and professional nursing associations. Eight papers included nurses from across more than one sector of nursing leadership, giving breadth of perspective to the findings (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; Abhicharttiburtra *et al.*, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a). Non-nursing leaders offered a useful perspective to understanding nursing leadership in five studies (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Khoury, *et al.*, 2011; Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014). The inclusion of non-nurses and front-line nursing staff while enriching the body of knowledge, partially conceals the small size of the strategic nurse leadership voice in the literature. For example, in Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) study on ideal attributes of GCNOs, only 10 of the 75 Delphi panellists were Chief Nursing Officers. In addition to the findings reported presenting additional analysis of the responses of Chief Nursing Officers could have deepened the insights about the influence of any similarities and differences in perspectives about the ideal attributes of a GCNO on the overall output of the study. The small number of empirical papers eligible for inclusion in the integrative review and the mixed composition of participants within them suggests an opportunity to further develop the body of knowledge on strategic nurse leadership.

2.3.2 Geographical dispersion of included empirical studies

Within the empirical literature reviewed, nine studies collected data from participants in a single country (Lewis, 2006; Thompson *et al.*, 2009; Khoury *et al.*, 2011; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Abhicharttiburtra *et al.*, 2014; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ross *et al.*, 2014). Ten papers included participants from more than one country (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2006; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; McCarthy *et al.*, 2013; Wilson *et al.*, 2014; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a), including one Delphi study that reported its findings across three publications (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a). Table 2.5 illustrates the geographical dispersion of studies with a specific focus on nursing (thereby excluding Lewis, 2006 and Thompson *et al.*, 2009). Of the ten studies conducted with participants from more than one country, five collected data from participants in multiple continents (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2006; Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; Wilson *et al.*, 2014). Of the single continent studies one study was reported for

each of: South-East Asia (Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014), Europe (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003), Eastern Mediterranean (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014) and Western Pacific (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012). While the strategic nurse leadership population will be small by the elite national nature of their roles, the thin body of empirical literature specific to strategic nurse leadership and public policy suggests that knowledge of the experience of international strategic nurse leaders in policy influence is underdeveloped. This gap indicates an opportunity for this thesis to contribute to the small body of international work on strategic nurse leadership and public policy.

Table 2.5. Geographical dispersion of the strategic nurse leadership empirical literature

WHO World Region	Countries by publication
Africa	Kenya (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff, 2014) South Africa (Ditlopo <i>et al.</i> , 2014) Tanzania (Shariff, 2014) Uganda (Shariff, 2014) Zambia (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) 13 countries (unspecified) - McCarthy <i>et al.</i> (2013)
Americas	Brazil (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) Chile (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) Colombia (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) Mexico (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) Peru (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014) USA (Khoury <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Ross <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
South-East Asia	Thailand (Abhicharttibutra <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Europe	12 countries (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003)
Eastern Mediterranean	Iran (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian 2014)
Western Pacific	New Zealand (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012)
>1 World Region	Global (undefined) (Benton, González-Jurado, Beneit-Montesinos, 2013) 5 continents (undefined) (Kim <i>et al.</i> , 2006) Global (undefined) (Swenson <i>et al.</i> , 2005) 50 countries (Salmon and Rambo, 2002) Africa and Americas (Wilson <i>et al.</i> , 2014)

2.3.3 Methodological aspects of the empirical studies

The methodological quality of this body of work was variable. Six empirical studies benefited from theoretical richness (see further discussion in 2.3.3.5). The following section sets out key methodological observations of the included research literature.

2.3.3.1 Survey based studies

The popularity of survey approaches (7 papers) is understandable in terms of cost and convenience particularly when seeking data from dispersed informants. A known limitation of self-report survey instruments is that they can yield relatively superficial data based on the individual perspective (Adams and Cox, 2008). It is disappointing that in most of the reported surveys the validity and reliability of the survey instrument was overlooked (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Swenson *et al.* 2005; Khoury *et al.*, 2011; McCarthy *et al.* 2013; Ross *et al.* 2014; Wilson *et al.* 2014) with the exception of Thompson *et al.* (2009). Although preliminary testing of the questionnaire is implicit in most of the studies the failure to address this issue reduces confidence in the validity of the results.

In other issues of rigour Khoury *et al.* (2011) present findings from analysis of open-ended questions in their survey of opinion leaders but the number of responding participants and method of analysis of the qualitative data is unclear. This makes it difficult to assess whether the emergent themes were based on a robust dataset. Compounding this, the findings are unsupported by direct quotes. Use of quotes is a well-established tradition in qualitative research and appears in guidelines such as Consolidated criteria for Reporting Qualitative research (COREQ, Tong, Sainsbury and Craig, 2007) as one characteristic of good practice in research reporting. The purpose of the generally accepted convention of use of quotations is explored by Eldh, Årestedt and Berterö (2020) who argue that they have a limited role in promotion of rigour but are useful for illustration of findings or the analytical process. Eldh, Årestedt and Berterö (2020) argument could be considered somewhat circular in that by its nature illustrating the analytical process offers insights into the credibility of the findings to some extent. Eldh, Årestedt and Berterö (2020) argue for thoughtful use of quotations in line with the epistemological positioning of the study. In Swenson *et al.* (2005) publication, while they do provide some quotes to support their findings, the quotes were separate from the main narrative of the article and presented in a table. The structure of the table did not follow the structure of the findings section of the article making it difficult to know which quotes supported which key finding. Integrating the quotes into the wider reporting of the findings could have more clearly evidenced a link between the raw data and reporting and made it easier to hear the voice of the participants.

Several of the studies might have benefited from a mixed methods approach to strengthen the rigour of their work. For example, Ross *et al.* (2014) in their study of transformational leadership practices of nurse leaders in professional associations were only able to report on the statistical analysis of the self-report Leadership Practices Inventory® (LPI, Kouzes and Posner, 2003). While the LPI® is considered a robust tool (Posner, 2016) to assess behaviours within transformational

leadership, triangulation of Ross *et al.*'s (2014) quantitative results with qualitative data might have elucidated a better understanding of some of the study results. For example, it would have been interesting to understand why 'challenging the process' was the lowest scoring subscale on the LPI®. This is particularly pertinent given suggestions that nurses may tend towards conflict avoidance (Mahon and Nicotera, 2011).

2.3.3.2 Delphi studies

Five publications referred to Delphi studies with one study reported across three publications (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a). Counting the multiple reported study as one, the three original studies used Delphi as a consensus building method, to: define and describe the components of high quality nurse regulation (Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos 2013), identify the ideal attributes of GCNOs (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003) and explore the extent and influences on nurse leader participation in health policy development in East Africa (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a). The international panel in all three of the studies demonstrates the value of Delphi in developing consensus across a geographically dispersed Delphi panel. One strength of Delphi studies is that they are completed in rounds using structured feedback processes and simple statistical devices to move from individual views to shared or polarised perspectives. An advantage over non-validated questionnaires is that the panel of experts taking part in the Delphi inform the content and direction of the research. While there is no set desired panel size for a Delphi, all three had relatively large panel sizes of 75 (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003), 59 (Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013), and 37 (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) when considering Diamond *et al.*'s (2014) systematic review which reported that 46% of the 100 Delphi studies reviewed had more than 25 panellists.

The three studies illustrate the flexibility of Delphi as a method, with Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013) using a three-round Policy Delphi, Shariff (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) using a three-round modified Delphi and Hennessy and Hicks (2003) a two-round Delphi. This flexibility is a characteristic of Delphi research that has been both lauded and criticised in the literature (Jünger *et al.*, 2017).

A central methodological decision in Delphi is the approach to assessing consensus. Interestingly, Shariff and Potgieter (2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) elected to reduce the threshold for consensus as the Delphi progressed. After requiring a near perfect agreement of 90% in Round 2 they reduced the threshold of consensus to 70% agreement in Round 3. Items which did not reach 90% consensus in Round 2 were discarded and not retested in Round 3. As a consequence, items which could have been significant findings were discarded, and all those which progressed to Round

3 continued to enjoy wide agreement. Limiting the findings to those with 90% agreement means that opportunities to understand key points of divergence were missed, and risks limiting the output of the Delphi to broad generalities, reducing the impact of the research. Reducing the threshold of consensus infers that the researchers expected a reduction in consensus over time. The reasons for changing the threshold, which run counter to the usual convention of Delphi of a consistently applied level of consensus (Diamond *et al.*, 2014), are not explained and threatens the rigour of the findings. Alongside percentage agreement Shariff (2014; 2015a) also used mean and standard deviation of <2 to demonstrate convergence of opinion and consensus. The use of mean and standard deviation is not defended by Shariff (2014), nor is there assurance given about normal distribution of data which would justify the use of mean rather than median. The apparent flaws in Shariff's (2014) consensus methodology demonstrate the criticality of setting stable threshold values and the inherent challenges of rigour within consensus measurement techniques. Shariff's papers (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) were retained within this review because, despite the methodological threats to their trustworthiness, they provided sufficient data as to provide helpful insights into the enablers, challenges and potential attributes of nurse leaders influencing policy across three countries in East Africa.

While there is significant variation in Delphi panel size in the literature, the three Delphi studies all had sample sizes larger than 25, making them in the upper half of the 100 Delphi studies included in Diamond *et al.*'s (2014) systematic review. Demonstrating the variation in approaches to assessing consensus in Delphi studies, Hennessy and Hicks (2003) applied Kendall's coefficient of concordance, a non-parametric statistic which calculates rank correlation, at the end of Round 2. Although Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) report small Kendall *W* values, the low p-values indicate that concordance has been achieved. While a recognised method of assessing consensus (Meijering, Kampen and Tobi, 2013), it would have been helpful to understand how Hennessy and Hicks (2003) supported their expert panel to interpret Kendall's coefficient of concordance since the between round feedback to inform participants of the findings from the preceding round is one of the core tenets of Delphi (Barrett and Heale, 2020). Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013) took a different approach, applying a consensus threshold of 67% agreement based on Robert's rules (Robert *et al.*, 2011) agreement alongside an interquartile range of ≤ 1 . Robert's rules (Robert *et al.*, 2011), used for decision making in politics and discussed in further detail in Chapter 3, provide what is known as a 'super majority'. In terms of assessing dispersion, the advantage of using interquartile range rather than standard deviation adopted by Shariff and Potgieter (2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) is that it is unaffected by extreme values and does not require normally distributed data (Field, 2017). The variation in threshold and measurement of consensus between

the three Delphi studies is a recognised challenge within the method. It underlines the importance of predetermined threshold selection and in rigorous reporting.

2.3.3.3 Mixed Methods studies

A strength of both Abhicharttibutra *et al.*'s (2014) and Lewis' (2006) studies was the use of multiple methods to triangulate their findings. Triangulation using different lenses to study a phenomenon can strengthen the rigour of research findings by providing a fuller perspective (Fielding and Fielding 2008). Lewis' (2006) study comprised a quantitative network analysis followed by 20 interviews with people identified as influential policy actors in the network analysis. While the network analysis provided oversight of the breadth and structure of health policy networks in Victoria, Australia the addition of interviews brought the quantitative data to life data by hearing from influential actors about their personal perceptions of the network and their own position within it. The opportunity mixed methods offers to build a compelling picture was also evident in Abhicharttibutra *et al.*'s (2014) study which used policy documents and qualitative interviews to understand the path and outcome of policy influence. The two mixed methods studies included here illustrate the value in using more than one method to access different perspectives on a topic, with the potential to deepen understanding and the trustworthiness of the findings.

2.3.3.4 Interview based studies

Individual interviews were the primary method used to collect data within all five qualitative studies. Rigour was addressed to differing degrees in each qualitative study. Juma, Edwards and Spitzer (2014) provided a concise and informative paragraph describing the key strategies to address the Lincoln and Guba (1985) trustworthiness criteria. Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014) provided a less persuasive account but did briefly describe some of the measures taken to promote rigour, including use of an audit trail. While other authors did not explicitly discuss issues of rigour (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014) their detailed reporting, particularly that of Kim *et al.* (2006) and Ditlopo *et al.* (2014) provided reassurance that rigour was likely to have been considered, even if not detailed. Nonprobability sampling techniques were used across all five studies, as is typical in interview-based studies. The only study with an international sample of interviewees was Kim *et al.* (2006). Although approaches to promoting rigour and assessment of the challenges associated with cross-cultural or cross-language research were not unpacked in the reporting of the study, Kim *et al.* (2006) did share one strategy, which was sending the interview questions to participants in advance of the interview but did not provide an explanation for this decision.

The length of interview was only reported by Juma, Edwards and Spitzer (2014). The omission from reporting by the other four was a missed opportunity to contribute to the body of knowledge around the practicalities of engaging with strategic nurse leaders in the context of the many demands on their schedules. Kim *et al.* (2006) was the only study to reflect on the challenges in engaging elite leaders in research. Challenges with finding suitable interview times meant that 7 of their 17 interviews were written submissions. While this could be considered a threat to the richness and trustworthiness of the data it could also be argued to be a pragmatic approach to enable inclusion of willing participants from a small target population who have valuable insights to contribute. Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) also adapted their data collection to enable two participants to conduct their interview by phone rather than in person. They did not elaborate on the reasons necessitating the change. Content analysis was the most common analytical approach, used in three studies (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014), with a fourth describing 'thematic content analysis' (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014). Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) used constant comparative analysis.

2.3.3.5 Theoretical underpinnings

Within the empirical research explicit theoretical, conceptual and or philosophical influences were identified in six studies (Table 2.6), predominantly qualitative (n=4). How the theoretical underpinnings influenced the data analysis as well as the broader design and execution of the study could have been more explicitly described. A transparent approach to describing the role and lens of the theory in research can support assessment of rigour and sensemaking of findings, clarifying the contribution of the study to the wider body of knowledge (Collins and Stockton, 2018). Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) appeared to actively use their theoretical underpinning. Their interview schedule was described as framed around Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) stages of nursing's political development framework and the participants were asked to assess the stage of political development they considered various professional organisations to be at. Despite clearly setting its use from the outset Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) do not describe any further influence of the framework on the analysis or interpretation of the findings of the study. This was a missed opportunity to understand the merits and limitations of how the framework supported understanding of the perceptions of policy and political leadership in nursing under study. Ross *et al.* (2014) whilst clearly using transformational leadership theory across the study through the Leadership Practices Inventory®, could have taken a more critical approach, acknowledging the debates around what the theory can explain. For example, Hutchinson and Jackson (2013) critique the lack of explicit focus on the integrity of the individual leader or the value of follower resistance. More recently Siangchokyoo, Klinger and Campion (2020) advocate for investigation of followership

transformation in the context of transformational leadership, an area they argue has been neglected.

The only evidence of overlap in the theoretical or conceptual underpinning used across the empirical literature was the use of a policy analysis framework by both Abhicharttbutra *et al.* (2014) and Ditlopo *et al.* (2014). Although Abhicharttbutra *et al.* (2014) did not however explicitly adopt a particular analysis framework they did provide a detailed description of their framework. Out with analysis of contribution to specific policies, no established theoretical foundation for research into strategic nurse leadership and public policy was identified. Therefore, there was no obvious theoretical influence for this thesis to adopt.

Table 2.6. Theoretical underpinnings of empirical literature

Paper	Explicit	Implicit
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Three tenets of leadership: 1. leaders are born and made 2. leaders bring sustainable results 3. leaders find your voice and inspire others to find theirs And use of McCall Jr and Hollenbeck's (2002) global competencies	
Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012)	Cohen <i>et al.</i> 's (1996) stages of nursing's political development used to inform interview guide	
Abhicharttbutra <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Policy analysis framework (undefined)	
Ditlopo <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Walt and Gilson (1994) policy analysis framework	
Ross <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Transformational leadership	
Juma, Edwards and Spitzer (2014)	Critical and feminist theory	
Salmon and Rambo (2002)		X
Hennessy and Hicks (2003)		X
Swenson <i>et al.</i> (2005)		X
Lewis (2006)		X
Thompson <i>et al.</i> (2009)		X
Khoury <i>et al.</i> (2011)		X
Shariff and Potgieter (2012) and Shariff (2014, 2015a)		X
McCarthy <i>et al.</i> (2013)		X
Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013)		X
Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014)		X
Wilson <i>et al.</i> (2014)		X

2.4 Characteristics and methodological insights from the theoretical and non-empirical papers

Four of the five theoretical and conceptual papers draw on a North American context to unpack: nursing's political development (Cohen *et al.*, 1996), the influence of nurse leaders (Adams and Erikson, 2011; Shamian, 2014), and a nursing lens on health policy (Russell and Fawcett, 2005). The remaining paper, Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) concept analysis is an Iranian publication but in drawing on the existing literature is inevitably heavily influenced by the perspectives of researchers from the UK and North America. What this means is that the theoretical perspectives are limited to a segment of the Global North and their resonance with the experiences of leadership and policy influence in other contexts are untested.

When reviewed in light of the empirical literature the propositions of each paper have some degree of credibility, however for two of the papers (Cohen *et al.*, 1996; Shamian, 2014) assurance of rigour and trustworthiness is threatened by lack of explicit evidence of their empirical and philosophical foundations or sufficient testing in research studies. For example, Shamian's (2014) emergent model does not offer a persuasive narrative as to the origins of its construction and has only been tested in one more recent paper (Chiu, Villeneuve and Paul, 2020). Cohen *et al.* (1996) framework has been cited in a wider range of papers including Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) and Ellenbecker *et al.* (2017) to structure understanding of political development. The framework is, however described in the original paper (Cohen *et al.* 1996) as based on a review of the literature and unspecified analysis of the political engagement of nurses. The lack of specificity undermines confidence in the trustworthiness of the approaches and consequently limits the contribution Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework can currently make to the body of knowledge.

One model which did set out its underpinning philosophical assumptions was Russell and Fawcett's (2005) updated conceptual model to extend understanding of the connections between nursing and health policy. While explication of the assumptions is a strength of the model, discussion of how the assumptions were formulated could have made it easier to assess for transferability and use in other contexts. For example, the model assumes that nursing practice is guided by models and theories but provides no supporting evidence.

Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) concept analysis using Walker and Avant's (2005) widely used approach, drew on the empirical literature, and demonstrated that nursing's policy influence as a concept is under-developed in nursing theory. Of the five available theoretical papers Adams and Erikson (2011) present the most robust model, tested, and refined as part of an empirical research study, promoting the rigour of the model. In sum, the theoretical literature was not only limited in terms of

rigour and number of publications, but perspectives external to North America and the UK were absent.

Of the two non-empirical studies MacDonald *et al.*'s (2012) interpretive scoping review was theoretically rich using a socio-ecological whole systems lens to understand the policy priorities of nursing associations, and what influences their engagement in cross-sector policy issues. Rather than adopting a particular theoretical lens Spenceley, Reutter and Allen (2006) debated the epistemological foundations of what they described as nursing's policy advocacy, and potential approaches to its development. These more conceptual contributions offered a dimension of meta commentary to the more granular findings of the empirical literature.

2.5 Themes arising from the review

The discourse around nursing's policy influence during the review period is characterised by Spenceley, Reutter and Allen's (2006) observation of a perpetual call for further engagement in, and influence on, policy making. Such expansion of policy influence was argued by Arabi *et al.* (2014) to offer the potential for a larger, better equipped nursing workforce who experienced improved job satisfaction and contribute to improved population health. Although the literature did evidence existing engagement in public policy (Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014; Juma Edwards and Spitzer, 2014), there was also an appetite to increase policy activity with greater influence over a wider range of topics (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012).

Due to the small size of the evidence base the literature included studies with a focus on at least one of strategic nurse leadership and policy influence. The strategic nurse leadership research was largely exploratory with a focus on roles, responsibilities, attributes, and skills. The political and policy focused research considered approaches to enablers and barriers to policy engagement, including leadership approaches.

The reviewed literature indicates that the ambition to increase nursing's policy influence is constrained by a number of factors internal and external to the profession. Central to these constraints is the perception that despite being widely trusted, nursing is not considered an influential decision maker (Khoury *et al.*, 2011). The findings which are presented next explore nursing as a policy actor followed by a discussion of the antecedents of strategic nurse leader policy influence identified in the literature, broadly categorised as: the legacy of traditional norms, preparation of nurses for policy engagement, and approaches to policy influence.

2.5.1 Nursing as a policy actor

Nursing's presumed mandate and responsibility to policy influence (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012) is sometimes contested by non-nursing decision makers (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014), and nurses themselves and argued to remain unrealised in practice (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014). Scholars describe the potential nursing contribution to policy as poorly recognised and under-used (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012). Even among strategic nurse leaders with a remit for shaping the future of health care in their country, being active in policy was not universal (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). It is worthy of note that a range of policy activity was reported across the literature, from engagement through voting, all the way through to agenda setting. The literature offers several reasons for poor policy engagement among nurses. First, Khoury *et al.* (2011) reported a perception by non-nursing decision makers that nurses are not interested in participating in policy. Although this was not supported explicitly in the literature reviewed here, it provides an important perspective. Second, a lack of opportunity was identified by Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, (2014) as a central reason for poor visibility of nursing in policy making, and finally, being ill-equipped to participate (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006).

In two studies there was divergence in the perceptions of nursing and non-nursing leaders about the adequacy of nursing's policy input, with a call from the nurses to be more involved (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). Some non-nursing decision makers in Juma, Edwards and Spitzer's (2014) study stated that, if nurses were better equipped to contribute to broader issues, they would welcome further nursing involvement in national policy making. There were, however two of the nine non-nursing leaders interviewed who indicated that they perceived nurses already had sufficient input. This finding was in strong contrast to the nursing leader perceptions within the study who considered themselves to have insufficient opportunity to influence policy (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). There was a similar parallel in Ditlopo *et al.*'s (2014) study where nursing leaders contested a government narrative that a specific policy had been developed with nurses, saying that they had not been consulted and questioning whether any nurses had been involved. While these are two specific examples which do not confirm a widespread problem, they do give an insight into a context where there are differences in perspective between nurses and non-nurses as to the desirable level of policy involvement. This is important because if external actors, who often hold more power than nurses in policy making networks, do not consider nurse leaders to be credible policy actors who can add value to policy making, they are unlikely to afford nurses more opportunities to contribute.

To convince non-nursing leaders that nurses have a substantive policy contribution to make there is a need for nurses to persuasively articulate the expertise and perspective they offer. The literature

suggested that level and locus of nursing expertise is not always clear to external decision makers seeking policy input. Nurses do not always position themselves sufficiently as having expertise (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014) making it less likely that they will be given opportunities to contribute to policy making. MacDonald *et al.* (2012) argued that professional nursing associations with clear policy roles and priorities were more likely to be perceived as policy competent. Organisations that non-nursing leaders perceived to be policy competent were also more likely to be policy active and influential (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012), which may suggest that the visibility associated with being policy active and influential, compounds the external perception of policy competence. The challenge in demonstrating policy activity was illustrated in a systematic website review of nursing organisations with English speaking websites found that fewer than half (6/15) set out their policy activity clearly including their priorities, positions or responses to policy issues, and options for members engage (Catallo, Spalding and Haghiri-Vijeh, 2014). While the lack of policy presence on organisational websites does not mean that they are not policy active or influential, it does provide an insight into the public facing window of the organisation. If perceived competence and confidence in policy contribution is linked to non-nursing policy makers providing nursing organisations opportunities to engage in policy (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012) then the public absence of their policy priorities and credentials may have a negative impact.

Although the literature largely focused on the challenges of policy influence, there was evidence of policy activity among strategic nurse leaders (Abhicharttibutra, *et al.* 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012). More than two fifths (46%) of the 37 strategic nurse leaders in Shariff and Potgieter's (2012) Delphi study had experience of participating in problem formulation and agenda setting, indicative of involvement and influence over the direction of policy. Unfortunately, the data presented by Shariff and Potgieter (2012) did not allow assessment of whether all the panellists participated in at least one part of the policy process, or whether some engaged in multiple ways and others were policy inactive. It could be interpreted positively that 46% of strategic nurse leaders had experience of policy formulation, contradicting the perception reported by Ditlopo *et al.* (2014) of nurses as policy implementers rather than influencers. However, 92% of panellists in Shariff and Potgieter's (2012) Delphi stated that nurses do not lead in health policy agenda setting. These findings suggest a distinction between participating in and leading agenda setting for policy. This distinction is important for the accurate evaluation of the extent to which strategic nurse leaders are leading in policy influence. If nurse leaders are included but not actually leading, there is a risk that their presence is positioned in a way which obfuscates the reality of the challenges they face in influencing policy. An inaccurate representation could lead to missed

opportunities to strengthen nursing's policy influence further, beyond participation, to leading on setting the agenda.

2.5.2 Legacy of traditional norms

The persistent gap between the espoused desired and real-world policy influence is linked to inequalities affecting nursing. Nurses were perceived as least influential in USA healthcare reform behind doctors and patients in a large telephone survey of opinion leaders (n=1504) (Khoury *et al.*, 2011). Connotations of nursing as a feminine and vocational role (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014), characterised by direct care giving (Khoury *et al.*, 2011) are argued to contribute to negatively impact on the external perception of nurses as legitimate policy actors. The assumption, reported by Khoury *et al.* (2011) that nurses prefer direct care and don't want to be leaders sets up direct care and leadership influence as mutually exclusive. Such conflation, if accepted in social discourse, risks non-nursing decision makers disregarding nurses as credible policy actors. If nurses are not perceived as credible policy actors, then logic would suggest that this infers that nursing expertise is not valued out with the profession. As a consequence non-nursing decision makers may be less likely to prioritise seeking nursing input in policy discussions.

The impact of gender related inequality on nursing's policy influence was not explicitly prominent in the literature with several noting women in leadership as an under-researched area (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Hutchinson and Jackson, 2013). The lack of focus on gender in the literature is interesting given the female majority in the profession and the recognised challenges for women in leadership both within and beyond nursing (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Ellemers *et al.*, 2012). More prominent in the literature, and linked to gender inequality, was discussion about the impact of the power imbalance between nursing and medicine. Medicine, a traditionally male profession, is the prevailing voice of health professionals in policy. Its dominance was demonstrated in Lewis's (2006) Australian network study of influential people in health policy. The nominations, which deliberately started out with medicine were predominantly male (73%) and doctors (72%). The influence of medicine as a policy actor both inside and outside government is argued to contribute to the marginalisation of nursing's policy contribution (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). For example, the prolonged dominance of medicine has perpetuated the primacy of the biomedical model in health policy. The biomedical model, which considers health to be the absence of ill-health (Rocca and Anjum, 2020), is a treatment focused perspective, devalues the potential influence of nursing's expertise in an asset based and holistic lens of health (Arabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014). In practice if policymakers use the biomedical model as the primary lens for establishing policy priorities in health the consequent disconnection from the

nursing lens could lead to a lack of understanding of the relevance of nursing expertise making it less likely to be actively sought. Lewis's (2006) study demonstrated the propensity for influential actors to nominate people who were similar to them as influential, in that study most often male medics. It is therefore logical that where the senior policy actor is male and medical, a female nursing voice may find it challenging to make a policy impact.

In light of the suggested dominance of medicine in policy and the respect it commands within society, it is perhaps unsurprising that physicians are generally considered a reliable source of expertise internationally. Such societal reverence means doctors are more likely to be considered legitimate policy actors across a broad range of issues, further compounding their power (Lewis, 2006). In contrast, nursing has been criticised as too introspective, tending to focus on policy issues directly related to the profession (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). The criticism of introspection is contested in the literature in two ways. First, MacDonald *et al.* (2012) found that half of the reviewed publications reported policy activity of professional nursing associations relating to professional issues, and that targeted health issues or populations accounted for more than one third of policy issues addressed by professional nursing associations. While only one review, MacDonald *et al.*'s (2012) findings suggests that whilst professional issues are important targets for policy activity for the profession, they are not the sole focus. The second rebuttal against introspection in the literature are the structural or procedural constraints, which in some countries restrict nursing policy input to nursing specific policies, such as workforce (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer., 2014; Ditlopo, *et al.*, 2014). There are also a range of professional issues which legitimately require advocacy, often by professional nursing associations in response to the needs of their members, to improve the working lives of nurses. Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) used Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework for political competence and identified that the stage of political development of organisations was dependent on its policy focus, meaning that professional associations would be more likely to be in stage two (self-interest) of the framework. Cohen *et al.* (1996) described Stage 2 'political self-interest' as where the profession gives primacy to creating policy positions for nurses and has a policy agenda that is primarily focused on professional issues. Although professional issues are crucial to staff wellbeing and safety at work, the remit of strategic nurse leaders is often not limited to nursing, with government nurses reporting wide responsibility for issues such as disease and health system priorities (Salmon and Rambo, 2002). The literature reflects two policy focuses of interest to nursing: issues relating to the profession, and wider health and public policy. If nurses are not permitted to contribute to broader policy topics, or where they are allowed, are not considered credible actors in the wider policy subsystem, the cause of any introspection is at least partially due to factors external to nursing itself. These challenges are not

faced by medicine which enjoys broad, culturally mediated rights to legitimately input into a wide range of policy arenas.

The route by which nurses are excluded from policymaking appears to be ingrained in organisational and societal structures. Jobs available to nurses, even elite policy positions for the profession, tend to be hierarchically lower, and less positionally influential relative to senior policy makers and non-nurses. In some contexts, this is even enshrined in law (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014), actively preventing nurses from attaining elite appointments. The consequence of this is that even when nurses ascend to policy making positions the combination of organisational structures and top-down policy making mean that they may still be excluded from final policy decisions (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). In some cases, the scope of this exclusion included nursing focused policy decisions being made by non-nursing decision makers, most commonly doctors (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Shariff, 2014). For example, in Iran Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014) described doctors approving nursing curricula. The nursing contribution can be enabled through creation of new policy making positions for nurses and structures such as a national nursing directorate in government (Shariff, 2014), and a national Chief Nursing Officer (Fyffe, 2009). If, however, these positions remain lower in organisational hierarchies than comparative positions for medicine, they will continue to be structurally disadvantaged. While the literature describing structural exclusion of nursing in policy making is small and predominantly from African and Eastern Mediterranean regions it suggests that solutions to nursing's policy influence require systemic change and will not be completely resolved by simply increasing the number of nurses appointed to policy making positions.

While broader policy issues would often benefit from input from strategic nurse leaders, the ability for them to fulfil this was constrained by a number of factors internal and external to nursing. Being recommended to contribute to a broader range of policy issues is a challenge when such contribution requires nurses to be perceived as influential decision makers. A potentially cyclical issue could be constructed from the literature where nurses are mainly consulted and prepared to contribute on nursing related issues, are then criticised for narrow focus, but are not afforded the opportunity to contribute more widely due, at least in part, to lack of credibility in broader issues and perceived competence. The following sections discuss the studies which called for improvement in the preparation of nurses for policy making and propose approaches to support nurse leaders to make and take opportunities for policy influence.

2.5.3 Preparation for policy influence

The capacity and capability of nursing's credible policy contribution is partly contingent on sufficient nurse leaders being equipped to contribute effectively to policy (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). Education and preparation of nurse leaders for policy influence was a common theme, across the review (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2006; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff, 2014; Wilson *et al.*, 2014). There were two main areas of discussion: baseline education and the continued development of nurse leaders already in strategic leadership positions.

The range of baseline nursing qualifications in use within and between countries was considered by Khoury *et al.* (2011) to muddy the external understanding of the level of expertise held by nurses. The implication is that the lack of clarity about the knowledge and skills of nurses degrades the credibility of the profession and therefore reduces the opportunities afforded to nurses for policy influence. The knowledge and status conferred by education can improve the perceived or actual quality of the contribution nurses make (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). For example, in contexts that value education, a higher qualification can positively affect the external perception of a nurse as a knowledgeable policy actor (Kim *et al.*, 2006). Education can also enable nurses to understand and work to the scope and boundaries of their policy reach (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012).

Nurse education prior to practicing as a professional nurse has been criticised as insufficient to support effective policy participation by scholars in North America (Khoury *et al.*, 2011), the Eastern Mediterranean (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014), and Africa (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014). Strikingly there were no European research studies published 2002-March 2015 on the policy content of nurse education retrieved to add to this discourse. Better preparation of nurses for leadership in policy was proposed by Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014) as an internationally shared priority, with several authors calling for more comprehensive leadership (Kim *et al.*, 2006) and policy (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014) curricula. Particularly, there was a call in three papers for nurse education to include wider socioeconomic, cultural, and political contexts and their relationship with health systems and population health (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). Improving education on wider issues, including finance and management identified by Shariff (2014) and Hennessy and Hicks (2003) respectively, could support development of technical competence in skills which support effective policy influence. Not only would a broader base of expertise support the breadth of responsibility of some strategic nurse leaders, highlighted in Kim *et al.*'s (2006) study but it could enable nurses to leverage knowledge of the broader context to frame policy positions.

2.5.3.1 Professional development of strategic nurse leaders

Once strategic nurse leaders are in post, they require further education and support to flourish in their policy role. Scholars recommend making formal education in policy more available (Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014) and leadership (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Ross *et al.*, 2014) to support strategic nurse leaders. Despite the recognition of the importance of preparation, there was limited evidence in the literature of investigations to scope the preparation of strategic nurse leaders. In Ross *et al.*'s (2014) study of transformational leadership in professional nursing associations, almost one third of the nurse leaders reported little or no leadership education. Similarly, only 38% of health commissioners in Thompson *et al.*'s (2009) study reported having some form of policy education. These findings are particularly striking given that policy advocacy is a key function of both health commissioners (Thompson *et al.*, 2009) and professional nursing associations (Catallo, Spalding and Haghiri-Vijeh, 2014).

National and international nurse leadership programmes can provide opportunities for strategic nurse leaders to develop their leadership knowledge, skills, and peer network. The ICN's Global Nurse Leadership Institute is among the most well-known programmes. Beyond full programmes of education, evaluation of international learning opportunities such as forums and conferences highlight connecting with peers as a key takeaway for delegates (Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Wilson *et al.*, 2014). Wilson *et al.*'s (2014) evaluation of a cross-cultural leadership programme demonstrated that it not only widened networks and gave new opportunities for collaboration but also strengthened cross-cultural understanding of similarities and differences in the contemporary issues between countries. Although short term experiences and reactions are amenable to evaluation, evaluating longer term outcomes of international conferences and programmes is more difficult to assess (Wilson *et al.*, 2014). This was reflected in Swenson *et al.*'s (2005) evaluation of a Global Nursing Partnerships Conference which attempted longer-term evaluation with a one year follow up questionnaire. Challenges included attrition over the evaluation period with a drop off from 63 responses at Swenson *et al.*'s (2005) initial evaluation at close of conference to 13 responses at one year. Swenson *et al.*'s (2005), albeit limited, findings reported that collaborative working relationships established during a conference could be sustainable beyond the period of structured learning. This finding should be interpreted with caution not only because of the small sample size but that people choosing to respond might have been more likely to have positive experiences of building longer term relationships following the conference. Understanding the reasons for non-responses could have given a fuller picture in the evaluation. Although the longer-term benefits of international leadership and policy conferences or time limited programmes would benefit from

more robust evaluation, they are generally considered beneficial to ongoing development and networking.

In addition to attendance at conferences and leadership programmes, individualised support, and development through mentorship (Kim *et al.*, 2006) and experiential learning (Fyffe, 2009) was considered important to the ongoing development and policy influence of strategic nurse leaders. A lack of mentorship and encouragement was identified as a barrier to policy engagement by 88% of nurse leaders in Shariff's (2014) study. Unfortunately, despite being a potentially important finding, as Shariff (2014) took the arguably flawed decision to set a 90% threshold for consensus (discussed earlier in 2.3.3.2) it was excluded as a key barrier to policy participation. In order for mentors to be able to support mentees in developing their strategic nurse leadership Kim *et al.* (2006) argues that they need to be fluent in the cultural context of the mentee. The need to pair mentors and mentees from the same country or region has implications for international models of mentorship. Some international leadership programmes have a coaching or project component with associated mentorship (Wilson *et al.*, 2014). A key takeaway from Wilson *et al.*'s (2014) programme evaluation was that participants valued the opportunity to interact with people from other cultures and that they identified a need for the programme to dedicate sufficient time to make coaching activity meaningful. A limitation of the evaluation was that it could have more fully explored the benefits, limitations, and outcomes of international mentoring relationships.

Mentorship may have potential to better support strategic nurse leaders to build on the experience of earlier leaders if embedded in a succession planning strategy. Succession planning within nursing was only highlighted by Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012), who described it as poorly executed in New Zealand, due to a lack of dedicated time and resource. The identification of succession planning seems pertinent given the context of a profession which the literature suggests does not have consistent opportunities to equip strategic nurse leaders with skills in policy making.

2.5.4 Policy skills of the individual nurse leader

The relational nature of both leadership and policymaking makes individual interpersonal skills important to the policy influence of the wider profession. Spenceley, Reutter and Allen (2006) even argue that relationships are more important than knowledge in policy influence. Relationships are critical to enabling the collaboration required to maximise policy influence within and beyond the profession (Salmon and Rambo, 2002). The following section examines the attributes and skills of strategic nurse leaders identified within the literature and then goes on to discuss the identified benefits and challenges of collaboration within and beyond nursing.

In addition to knowledge of their socio-political context and the policy process, the literature suggests a range of attributes, skills and approaches which strengthen policy influence. While two studies describe 'attributes' (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Shariff, 2015a) rather than skills, these tended to be a mix of innate qualities of an individual, the definition of an attribute (Oxford University Press, 2023), and those which may be developed as a skill. The literature around attributes and skills of strategic nurse leaders is briefly discussed followed by approaches to influence policy: the use of tactics and timing, adopting policy language, and collaboration.

2.5.4.1 Skills for strategic nurse leadership

Several papers identify individual attributes and skills suggested to strengthen the leadership (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Kim *et al.*, 2006) and policy influence (Shariff, 2014) of strategic nurse leaders. Individual approaches to effective policy influence largely centred on relational skill, personal integrity, and resilience. Shariff (2015a) reported skills necessary for nurse leaders to participate in policy making as influence, effective communication, relationship development, empowerment, and professional credibility. What was striking was that every skill achieved >95% consensus in both Round 2 and Round 3. While this can be interpreted as demonstrating the relevance of the skill and the between round stability of the Delphi findings, there was an unexploited opportunity to apply a more nuanced lens to understand more about their role in policy leadership. High concordance was also seen in Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) two round Delphi study to identify the ideal attributes of Chief Nurses in Europe.

Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) study, commissioned by the WHO, suggested striking differences between countries of western Europe, and countries of central and eastern Europe in the ranking of the characteristics of an ideal GCNO. For example, leadership skill was ranked third by respondents from western Europe but only 12th out of 16 by respondents from central or eastern Europe. Conversely, respondents from central or eastern Europe ranked decision-making/problem-solving as most important while western European panellists ranked it 9.5 out of 16. The validity and reliability of this result is compromised by the limitation that there were only two countries represented in the central and eastern European group, compared to nine from western Europe. There are also some findings within Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) data which are not explained by the data tables presented, for example decision-making/problem-solving is reported as being ranked last for the whole sample however no individual country is reported as ranking it lower than 13 out of 16, which would make it improbable for it to be last. While it is possible that some of the procedures for analysis were not available for review, this highlights the importance of transparent and detailed reporting in promotion of rigour and confidence in the findings. Analysis of responses by type of respondent may have helped unpack some of the inconsistencies in Hennessy and Hicks (2003)

article. By not analysing the responses segmented by type of respondent some added value was lost in not understanding the unique perspective of the 10 responding Chief Nursing Officers. The proportionately small sample of nurses in Hennessy and Hicks (2003) nursing specific study could be interpreted in a number of ways. First, it could be considered a helpfully rounded approach to prioritising the attributes required for the role, hearing from other disciplines and perspectives. Including a mix of perspectives could also be interpreted as a reflection of the small target population size, and a pragmatic approach to generating a larger sample size. Finally, it could be argued that the inclusion of non-nurses in a study about 'ideal' attributes is a natural consequence of a system which has allowed others to speak for nursing. It is unlikely that any one of the considerations is wholly true, but all are pertinent when critically considering research in nurse leadership.

There was cross-over in the attributes and skills identified by Shariff (2015a), Hennessy and Hicks (2003) and Kim *et al.* (2006), for example being politically astute was identified as key in all three studies. There were also similarities in other identified attributes such as credibility and integrity. There were areas of divergence. Shariff (2015a) for example, had a greater emphasis on interpersonal skills such as relationships and collaboration, compared to Hennessy and Hicks (2003, p446) who had more of a focus on the individual leader. Hennessy and Hicks (2003) for example suggested physical characteristics as attributes of an ideal Chief Nursing Officer, such as being "attractive" and of "acceptable appearance". Appearance was also included as an influence factor in the Adams Influence Model (Adams and Erikson, 2011) and has been investigated more broadly as a component of occupational success (Sczesny and Kühnen, 2004; Little and Roberts, 2012).

Some of the differences observed in the attributes and skills identified may be explained by the aims of the individual studies: policy engagement (Shariff, 2015a), global nurse leadership (Kim *et al.*, 2006) and ideal attributes of a GCNO (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003). On the other hand, the variation in findings may simply reflect Northouse's (2021) criticism of the infinite number traits associated with trait-based theories of leadership and the importance of connecting leadership traits with the context in which the individual is working.

Building on the attributes and skills identified earlier, three skills to strengthen policy influence were identified in the literature: conflict management, communication (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Shariff, 2015a) through adoption of policy language (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012), and the use of tactics and timing (Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014).

2.5.4.2 Strategic nurse leadership and conflict

Policy activity requires engaging in debate and conflict, and sometimes taking calculated risks. Conflict has been argued to be a challenge for nursing sometimes perceived to be risk and conflict averse (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006; Mahon, Nicotera, 2011; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Engaging or disengaging in conflict can take a range of forms. Several scholars reported a lack the agency or sense of self-determination among nurses (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian's 2014) to become the assertive (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014) and self-confident (Kim *et al.*, 2006) leaders needed to influence policy. Lack of assertiveness was linked to low impact policy contributions in Ditlopo *et al.*'s, (2014) study of South African nurse leaders in policy making positions. This lack of assertiveness may be partially explained by the traditional lack of autonomy afforded to nurses (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012) meaning that they did not have the opportunity to develop and consolidate assertiveness skills.

Studies of the conflict management styles of nurses and nurse managers have yielded mixed results, at least partly due to the culturally sensitive nature of effective approaches to conflict. In one Spanish study of 130 academic and clinical nurses, Losa Iglesias and Becerro de Bengoa Vallejo (2012) reported compromising (27.7%) competing (26.2%) and avoiding (23.1%) as most often used styles. Using a different assessment of conflict management Al-Hamdan, Norrie and Anthony (2014) reported that Jordanian nurse managers were most likely to use an integrating style, a collaborative problem-solving approach, and least likely to use an avoiding style. Although these studies rebut positioning of nursing as conflict avoidant, there have been no specific conflict management studies of strategic nurse leaders working at a national level. Hennessy and Hicks' (2003) Delphi panel ranked conflict resolution as 13.5 out of 16 attributes of an ideal GCNO. That conflict management was not considered a more important skill for GCNOs is intriguing given that policy is a core component of their role (WHO, 2015), and conflict is considered an inherent part of policy influence (Cairney, 2022). The mixed nursing and non-nursing Delphi panel in Hennessy and Hick's (2003) study, critiqued earlier in 2.3.1, means that it is not possible to extract the perceptions of nurses from non-nursing decision makers about the need to prioritise conflict management skills. If conflict resolution is not required as a key skill of government nurse leaders, it might be inferred that they do not encounter conflict regularly. Further, if conflict is accepted as a core part of engaging in the policy process, then not encountering conflict might suggest a lack of policy influence.

2.5.4.3 Speaking the policy language

The use of policy language rather than nursing terminology was argued by Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) to generate credibility in policy advocacy. Although tensions in changing the way nursing perspectives are described were acknowledged, being able to make nursing knowledge

tangible, and an accessible lens to view broader health and public policy issues was recognised as an important route to increasing nursing's policy contribution (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012). Building the evidence base to underpin the communication of policy positions was advocated by Fyffe (2009) as a key approach to strengthening nursing's policy influence.

2.5.4.4 Tactics and timing

Tactics and timing are generally accepted as important in policymaking. Opportunities such as system disruption, a media or government focus on an issue of interest can increase the visibility of the policy position of nursing on the topic (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Abhicharttibutra *et al.*'s (2014) study demonstrated the difference that maximising windows of opportunity can make. After identifying a nursing shortage in Thailand, a group of nurse leaders submitted evidence to the permanent secretary of the Minister of Public Health, in a first attempt to influence a change in policy to address the nursing shortage. Despite presentation of credible evidence of the problem, the permanent secretary did not support its progression to the Minister. Using their cross-sector networks the group flexed their approach, repackaging their policy position and progressing via the alternative route of deans of nurse education. After securing sponsorship from the Ministry of University Affairs the government approved the proposal to increase production of nurses and improve the quality of education. The experience explored in Abhicharttibutra *et al.*'s (2014) study demonstrates the impact that effective cross-sector collaboration within nursing can have in securing the support of influential leaders to influence government decision makers. Crucially though, it also illustrates Ditlopo *et al.*'s (2014) argument for nursing to become more proactive in anticipatory development of policy positions so that when opportunities arise, they are well positioned to pursue them. The literature does not explore the extent to which the strategic nurse leadership community consider the profession's policy approach to be proactive or reactive. The proactive or reactive nature may be context bound but is important in terms of considering potential improvements the profession could make to strengthen policy influence.

2.5.5 Collaboration within and beyond nursing

As an approach to policy influence collaboration was one of the most frequently cited method of improving policy influence in the nursing literature. Collaboration within and beyond nursing have been separated in order to understand the related but distinct intricacies and challenges.

2.5.5.1 Collaboration within nursing

To achieve persuasive policy influence several scholars describe an appetite for, and potential benefits of, a united nursing voice (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Khoury *et al.*, 2011; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). The criticality of a

united nursing policy voice is debated by Fyffe (2009) who suggests that assessment of nursing's policy influence might be better measured by the outcomes of that influence, rather than the presence of a united nursing voice. The breadth of the profession is a challenge to a unified policy voice (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006). The spread of perspectives and high number of competing policy issues associated with nursing raises the risk of splitting the profession's policy focus and position. Splitting the policy focus was of concern to MacDonald *et al.*, (2012) and Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) on the basis that it could make it more difficult for nursing to find common ground and gain traction on a particular policy issue (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012). Recognising the existence and legitimacy of multiple priorities across the profession, Donovan, Diers and Carryer (2012) called for a mechanism for nursing to find common ground on key issues which could accelerate policy influence. Bringing disparate sectors of nursing together to coalesce around a common purpose requires highly developed communication and relationship building skills (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012), claimed by Spenceley, Reutter and Allen (2006) to be more important than knowledge.

Purposeful development of collaborative relationships within nursing can be enabled through structured opportunities to connect. The GCNO Network formed in 2001, providing the first formal opportunity for government nurse leaders to connect with their peers to learn from each other, and coalesce around shared priorities (Salmon and Rambo 2002). International collaboration was identified as one route to strengthening policy influence (Kim *et al.*, 2006; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014) although the research in this area is under-developed.

One enabler of collaboration within nursing is a secure understanding of the individual expertise and policy roles of each sector. McCarthy *et al.*'s (2013) study on nurse leader involvement in regulatory reform provides an insight into the practical remits of the different nursing sectors. Presidents of professional nursing associations reported being responsible for collaborating with the regulatory body to make decisions, as well as bringing the voice of nursing practice whilst government nurse leaders provided oversight and advised the regulator on policy, a complementing but distinct role (McCarthy *et al.*, 2013). Interestingly while 90% of government nurse leaders stated that their input mattered to the decision making of the regulator, only 60% of nursing association presidents thought the same. Although the reasons for this difference are not explored in McCarthy *et al.*'s (2013) study this perhaps suggests power differentials between different sectors of nursing in different contexts. Illustrating the differences in remit, three papers (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006; Khoury *et al.*, 2011; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012) each noted the additional complexity of policy influence for nursing organisations with a dual role of trade union and professional association because of the need to balance the policy priorities of their members and the population. The remit

of professional nursing associations often means that they have a duty to progress the priorities of their members which will often centre on professional issues such as pay and conditions (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). If the professional nursing association of a country is the most visible policy active sector for nursing, there is a consequent risk that their appropriate focus on professional issues reinforces a perception of nursing as introspective (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006). Adding to the body of knowledge on the roles and responsibilities of different sectors Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013) identified advocacy within healthcare reform, particularly focused on professional issues, as a key role of a high performing regulator in delivering on their purpose of protecting the public. Benton, González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos (2013) also highlighted the value of cross-sector collaboration in policy engagement. Collaboration across sectors requires effective intraprofessional communication, which Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian (2014) assessed as weak in Iran. The literature pays little attention to cross-sectoral dynamics within strategic nurse leadership and does not provide confidence that there is cross-sectoral clarity about the roles, resources, and remits of each sector.

While taking a coordinated approach to policy influence across sectors of nursing internationally seems logical, there is a lack of empirical research on the pre-requisites for collaboration and evidence of conflict within the profession (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012; Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006). The origins of such conflicts were not well conceptualised within the empirical literature but included diverging opinions on policy activity as legitimate nursing work, and difficulty in the finding common ground on a policy issue, essential to policy progress. The proliferation of smaller specialty organisations in North America has been linked to narrower policy foci (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012), and incurred consequent challenges in developing a cohesive nursing policy coalition (Fyffe, 2009, MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Persistent division without resolution is likely to negatively impact collaboration (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006) and is a critical risk to the progress and policy influence of nursing (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Importantly, division and conflict within the profession can make it difficult for policy makers to decipher the nursing position, to the advantage of other, more cohesive groups (Donovan, Diers and Carryer, 2012; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014).

Cross-sector collaboration provides opportunities to share evidence, develop coordinated approaches and coalesce around a common purpose. A focused collaboration of strategic nurse leaders with a shared vision could enable progression on multiple types and levels of policy targets. In their study of nurse leaders in professional nursing associations Ross *et al.* (2014) found that the most frequently enacted transformational leadership practices were: enabling others to act through strengthening and collaboration and valuing the contribution of others.

2.5.5.2 Collaboration beyond nursing

Collaboration beyond professional boundaries was considered a strategic approach to developing policy influence (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Lewis, 2006; MacDonald *et al.*, 2012; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). The risks of not taking a collaborative approach include the political isolation of individual leaders as noted by Salmon and Rambo (2002), as well as the profession as a whole (Spenceley, Reutter and Allen, 2006). Collaboration with organisations and professions out with nursing offers opportunities to access and influence policy issues not traditionally within the nursing domain (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Framing policy positions in a broader socio-political context, rather than with a nursing only interest, provides a route to respond to criticisms of introspection (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Collaborations can offer a more robust challenge to traditionally dominant positions and also facilitate access to wider skills and resources which can allow diversification of the type and level of policy activity (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Although a diverse collaborative group can improve legitimacy and capacity for influence (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012), it can also increase conflict and make it more difficult to find the common ground required to progress an issue.

The development of collaborations and networks may be particularly important for nursing policy influence because length of time in a network is associated with strengthening personal policy influence (Lewis, 2006; Weible *et al.*, 2012). This has implications for the short to medium expectations nursing can have for policy influence in contexts where such collaborations are in the early stages and emphasises the importance of good relationships. In view of the often short tenure of politicians and consequent challenges of building long term relationships (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012) there is an evident need to invest in a range of connections.

2.6 Theoretical and conceptual contributions to the field

In addition to the empirical and review literature, five theoretical and conceptual papers were uncovered as part of the literature review. These are examined here in chronological order to allow any patterns in the development of the field to emerge. One pattern of note is the movement from the Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) focus on 'political development' to 'policy influence' in Shamian (2014) and Arabi *et al.* (2014).

Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework identified four stages of nursing's political development: buy in, self-interest, political sophistication, and leading the way. Within Cohen *et al.*'s (1996, p. 60) framework each stage of political development was assessed in four dimensions: nature of action, language, coalition building and nurses as policy shapers. There are links between the dimensions and the themes from the empirical literature. For example, Cohen *et al.* (1996) considered nursing to be just starting to reach stage four, 'leading the way', in 1996. A hallmark of 'leading the way' is that

nurses are proactive in setting policy agendas and have influence beyond traditional boundaries (Cohen *et al.*, 1996). The literature reviewed has demonstrated that there continues to be international variation in the extent to which nurses are involved beyond the traditional policy jurisdiction of nursing, and that agenda setting is not undertaken by all strategic nurse leaders (Shariff, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). Although Cohen *et al.* (1996) state that the later stages of the framework are not more important they contradict themselves by proposing a range of approaches to support progression to stage four.

What is useful about Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework is that by acknowledging that the political development of the profession as a whole is likely to lag behind that of individual nurse leaders it allows for nurse leaders to be at different stages of political development simultaneously. Cohen *et al.* (1996) also encourages proactive connection between the profession and high achieving nurse leaders to maximise the communal benefits of their success. This connection is pertinent to this study given the assumption that by appointment to a strategic nurse leadership position all strategic nurse leaders are highly successful individuals. Although Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework broadly resonates with the literature on strategic nurse leadership and policy influence, its origins were insufficiently described and has undergone limited testing in empirical research. It was used in Donovan, Diers and Carryer's (2012) study, however their findings do not indicate the influence of the framework on the study beyond asking the participants to pinpoint the stage of political development of particular organisations. Out with empirical literature Cohen *et al.*'s (1996) framework has been used in other ways including Ellenbecker *et al.*'s (2017) paper which used the framework to inform the level of content appropriate for each stage of health policy education for nurses. While assessing the political development of the profession is interesting, the framework does not offer a conceptual basis from which to understand the opportunities and challenges to improving policy influence at the level of strategic nurse leadership.

Moving away from considering how nurses influence policy, Fawcett and Russell (2001) published a conceptual model of nursing and health policy, which they updated in 2005 (Russell and Fawcett, 2005). The updated model takes a policy centric approach, and the authors' reported that it has been used to analyse policy, underpin nurse education, and to plan policy-based research (Russell and Fawcett, 2005). The model sets out its philosophical assumptions which include that nurses are engaged in all stages of policymaking and that the policies pertinent to nursing span everything from the health of communities to professional issues (Russell and Fawcett, 2005). The review of the literature presented in this chapter challenges the reality of these assumptions, having established that nurse engagement in all stages of policy making is not yet universal (Shariff, 2014), and that the policy focus of the profession has been criticised as self-focused (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014).

Demonstrating that Russell and Fawcett's (2005) assumptions are not consistently realised in practice could be considered both a strength and limitation of the model. As a strength, it allows the model to move beyond constraining factors and allows scholars to analyse policy as if all the conditions were in place to influence a policy position. Arguably, however it also limits real-world application of the model by ignoring known complexities of nursing's interaction with the policy process. Although Russell and Fawcett's (2005) model offers a useful mechanism for a nursing lens to be applied to policy its focus on policy analysis rather than the process of influencing policy did not meet the criteria for understanding the broader concepts under study in this thesis.

Although not specifically structured for policy influence the Adams Influence Model (Adams and Erikson, 2011) sets out five influence factors for nurse leaders: knowledge, authority, status, communication traits, and use of time and timing. The influence factors, developed from the literature and refined through empirical research, are further split into 21 associated attributes. Several of the attributes in the Adams Influence Model (Adams and Erikson, 2011) resonate with proposals of scholars interested in strategic nurse leadership in public policy. One example is the attribute of socio-political knowledge which recognises the benefits of possessing a broad knowledge of the socio-political context, identified as important by Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, (2014). Adams and Erikson's (2011) model was, however, designed to understand the influence of Chief Nursing Executives at an organisational rather than national or international level. Further, its person-specific focus perhaps made the model more suitable for investigations of individual leaders, rather than the broader approaches to strategic nurse leadership studied in this thesis. Finally, although the Adams Influence model (Adams and Erikson, 2011) describes the different 'systems' in which individuals operate and acknowledges that a leader may be influential in one context and not in another, the model wasn't sufficiently focused on the leadership context to explore the implications of context on strategic nurse leadership of this thesis.

In the first of two conceptual papers in 2014 focused on nursing's policy influence Shamian (2014) proposed what she called an 'emerging policy model'. Acknowledging that nursing is strong within its own sphere, Shamian (2014) argues that it does not yet share the nursing contribution reliably with other spheres such as at regional, national, or global levels. Echoing the focus on collaboration beyond nursing reported earlier (2.4.5.2), Shamian (2014) describes the need to develop networks in order to bridge spheres as essential to nursing's policy influence, with antecedents to success including visible, active, and credible nurse leaders. While the models focus on taking the nursing lens beyond the profession is relevant to this thesis, it would not enable an unpicking of the approaches, opportunities, and challenges of doing so.

In the final conceptual paper Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) concept analysis used Walker and Avant's (2005) approach to identify three attributes of policy influence: policy awareness, power, and advocacy. The development of policy awareness was conceptualised as a spectrum of policy literacy, acumen, competence, and finally policy influence. The inclusion of power as an attribute of policy influence was intriguing and the first time that power had been raised explicitly in the review of the literature. It was however under-developed with Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) recommendations limited to nurses understanding and strengthening power. The final attribute of advocacy was framed from the traditional and narrow perspective of nurses as patient advocates, rather than the broader concept of policy influence (Start and Hovland, 2004). The antecedents of policy influence described by Arabi *et al.* (2014) were broadly in line with the empirical literature already reviewed, for example the importance of collaborative teamwork. The consequences of policy influence were, however, focused on its benefits to nursing with only one which described benefits to patients and communities. Adopting Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) conceptualisation of policy influence would have set up a frame of nursing's policy influence as via advocacy and giving primacy to the needs of the profession. These considerations dismissed it from more formally influencing this thesis. The inclusion of power in Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) analysis did however stimulate exploration of power as a theoretical perspective.

2.7 Key findings from the literature review

This integrative review has demonstrated that the literature focused specifically on strategic nurse leadership and public policy is small and largely exploratory. International studies were largely limited to regional work, with only five investigating more than one continent. There is a need to develop research which offers insights relevant to strategic nurse leaders leading in contexts traditionally neglected in the nursing and leadership literature. While there were limitations to the literature available for review, it did generate useful insights to inform the research aims and first round of the Delphi study (reported later in Chapter 6). If it is accepted that national and international policy making tends to include strategic policy actors, the small number of studies focused on strategic nurse leaders suggests that expanding that body of knowledge would merit exploration. Identifying approaches and challenges to policy influence, shared and unique between sectors and nations would also offer the opportunity for future strategic nurse leaders to build on an otherwise tacit body of knowledge.

The narrative around the appetite to improve nursing's policy influence did not appear to have developed significantly during the period of review. Future momentum could be supported by empirical insights into the feasibility of developing internationally agreed approaches to

strengthening policy influence. Such insights could be generated through construction of a consensus statement on global perspectives on strategic nurse leadership and policy influence.

2.7.1 Research question arising from the integrative review

The findings of the integrative review gave rise to the following research question: *What are the internationally shared and unique perceptions of strategic nurse leaders on their current and potential policy influence?*

The research question was addressed through twin research aims:

- Investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contribution to public policy
- Construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

The research aims take a deliberately broad view of policy influence, to resist the temptation to focus on nursing or health policy, positioning the research aims in public policy.

Opportunities to strengthen the use of theory were variable but in general terms under exploited within the empirical studies. The conceptual underpinnings reported in the integrative review were not considered to offer a substantive foundation to shape this thesis. The subsequent theoretical and methodological choices are debated in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3: Methodology and Theoretical Perspectives

This chapter focuses on the methodological and theoretical influences underpinning the study. It begins with an exploration of the pertinent methodological and theoretical perspectives and justification for the use of social constructionism as the epistemological foundation. Arguments for the selection of a consensus building design and framing this investigation around a Delphi study are debated alongside strategies to promote rigour including the use of additional pre and post Delphi methods. The discussion is contextualised by linking to the key theoretical and conceptual considerations influencing nurse leadership to expose some of the challenges of international consensus building. The chapter closes with an examination of the ethical considerations that needed to be addressed to ensure ethical integrity of the research.

3.1 Philosophical perspectives

The philosophical foundation of this thesis will be unfolded through discussion of the four layers: ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (the nature of knowledge), methodology and method (the instruments by which data are collected and analysed). Orientating the thesis within a world view of science enables explanation of how coherence between philosophical layers underpinned the design and execution of the study. The relationship between ontology and epistemology is contested by some authors (Kant, 2014; Grix, 2019) and their nomenclature and subdivisions vary within the methodological literature (Cresswell, 2014; Marsh, Ercan and Furlong, 2018). For clarity, this thesis has adopted Bryman's (2008) ontological and Crotty's (1998) epistemological divisions to describe the philosophical decisions associated with this study.

The constructivist ontological orientation of this thesis considers the nature of reality to be created and revised through interaction with social actors (Bryman, 2008). Since the purpose of this thesis was to explore international perspectives on strategic nurse leadership and public policy it was important that the existence of multiple realities was recognised and that the uncovering of meanings, reasons, and contexts within and across these realities was facilitated. Adoption of an objectivist ontology, which considers social entities to exist independently of interaction with society (Bryman, 2008), would have assumed there was an objective reality to be revealed about the policy influence of international strategic nurse leaders. It therefore limited the ability of the study to acknowledge international variation.

This thesis assumes that meaning is constructed from the interaction between the phenomenon of strategic leadership in policy and the nurse leaders themselves, and that different meanings can be constructed from the same concept. Such meanings are considered in this thesis to be context-

bound and may change over time. These considerations are not fitting with either subjectivist or objectivist epistemological positions as the former requires attachment of meaning to an object by people without any interaction from the object (Crotty 1998) and the latter considers social entities to exist independent of human interaction (Bryman, 2008). Constructionism, however, is congruent with the assumptions of this thesis since it takes the view that the nature of knowledge and meaning does not exist without engagement with society and, that multiple meanings of the same phenomena can co-exist (Crotty, 1998; Bryman, 2008).

Constructivism and social constructionism both fall within the broader category of constructionism. In social constructionism reality is considered to be unfixed and influenced by contextual dimensions including politics, culture, and history (Berger and Luckmann 1966). Where social constructionism is the construction of shared reality (Burr, 2015), constructivism is concerned with the construction of meaning by an individual, i.e. the individual experience (Crotty, 1998). In adopting a social constructionist perspective this thesis considers the experiences of international strategic nurse leaders in public policy to be socially constructed by and between the nurse leaders rather than being created within an individual alone.

3.1.1 The Tenets of Social Constructionism

To evidence the adoption of a social constructionist approach Burr (2015, p2-5) proposes that at least one of the four tenets of social constructionism must be present: a critical stance towards taken for granted knowledge, historical and cultural specificity, knowledge as being sustained by social processes and the pairing of knowledge and social action. How each of the tenets manifest in this thesis is now considered.

A critical stance towards taken for granted knowledge is demonstrated through the challenging and testing of conventional interpretations of nursing in the policy sphere via a Delphi study. An understanding of the implications that contextual dimensions, including historical and cultural norms, have on the social construction of reality (Berger and Luckmann, 1966) and the differences in interpretation of international nurse leadership in policy, was embodied through the iterative research design and international recruitment. For example, as a predominantly female profession, nursing is generally accepted to be historically and culturally bound to women. Indeed prior to establishing the International Council of Nurses prominent nurse leaders including Ethel Gordon Fenwick and Lavinia Dock were active in the suffrage movement (Gordon Fenwick, 1901; Garofalo and Fee, 2015; Carney, 2019). While it was recognised that the status of women in a country may have implications for the status of nursing and the profession's policy influence this was explored, rather than assumed. Challenging taken for granted knowledge also provided a mechanism to

reflexively consider assumptions about nursing leadership and policy from the Global North, which has previously dominated the leadership literature (Dickson *et al.*, 2012).

The methods adopted in this thesis give primacy to knowledge development through interaction between the individual participant and the wider group, mirroring Gergen and Gergen's (2008) appreciation for the reciprocal contribution between the individual and the whole in social constructionism. Doing so allows the development of a shared meaning around how the studied group of strategic nurse leaders interpret international nurse leadership in public policy.

In the final tenet of social constructionism, the pairing of knowledge and social action, Burr (2015, p. 5) suggests that "our constructions of the world are bound up with power relations because they have implications for what is permissible for different people to do and for how they may legitimately treat others". The interaction between power dynamics and how people behave is important in the context of understanding variation in the experiences and opportunities available to international strategic nurse leaders in public policy. Adoption of the tenet allows this study to explore the frame strategic nurse leaders hold about their influence on policy in conjunction with the theoretical perspectives of bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) discussed in the next section.

3.2 Theoretical perspectives

After considering the theoretical perspectives used in the nurse leadership in policy literature, previously discussed in Chapter 2 (see sections 2.3.3.5; 2.3.4; 2.5), wider theoretical influences were considered. Two theoretical perspectives that aligned with the philosophical underpinnings of social constructionism were selected; bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and Culturally Endorsed Leadership theory (CLT) (House *et al.*, 2014).

When planning an international study to understand strategic nurse leadership and public policy there was no single 'right' theoretical underpinning to use, rather a suite of options from within and beyond the nursing literature. Each option would have foregrounded a different aspect of the topic under study. Feminist theory for example, could have been used to explore the known patriarchal challenges in nursing (Sundean and Polifroni, 2016). While feminist theory is established as a useful theoretical lens in nursing research, this study sought a theoretical perspective which did not foreground any particular issue from the outset. Theories in the public policy literature were predominantly policy centric (Weible *et al.*, 2012) rendering them unhelpful in the context of this thesis, which did not focus on a specific policy. Within the nursing literature several theoretical and conceptual papers with face validity were retrieved, however as discussed in Chapter 2 none offered sufficient depth or specifically focussed on national strategic nurse leadership (Cohen *et al.*, 1996;

Russell and Fawcett, 2005; Adams and Erikson, 2011; Arabi *et al.*, 2014; Shamian, 2014). A range of theoretical orientations could have provided valid routes of inquiry.

Social constructionism recognises power dynamics as linked to the pairing of knowledge with social action (Burr, 2015). Linking power with action resonates with Yukl's (2013) description of influence as an enactment of power, making adoption of a theoretical perspective relating to power relevant to studying the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders. It also links back to Arabi *et al.*'s (2014) concept analysis which highlighted power as an antecedent of policy influence. Power was therefore considered a useful lens through which to explore the opportunities and challenges for strategic nurse leaders in influencing policy. There are a range of theoretical perspectives relating to power which could have been adopted in the context of investigating policymaking (Topp *et al.*, 2021). French and Raven's (1959) bases of social power offered a mechanism through which to explore the bases of power used by strategic nurse leaders in policy activity, associated challenges, priorities, and strategies to amplify their influence.

The bases of social power do not include social or cultural interactions, which made them an incomplete theoretical underpinning. This gap was addressed by the use of CLT (House *et al.*, 2014), which theorises that leadership behaviour is influenced by societal expectations of how effective leaders behave. CLT's acknowledgement of the contextually and culturally bound nature of leadership (House *et al.* 2014) is clearly consistent with the social constructionist tenet of the historical and cultural specificity of knowledge. Use of CLT allowed an international exploration, which expected culture and context to impact on the experience and policy influence of strategic nurse leaders.

The next two sections further describe and defend the bases of social power and CLT as useful theoretical perspectives in this thesis.

3.2.1 Bases of social power

French and Raven (1959) define power as the ability of an individual or group to influence an individual, which results in a psychological change. To influence change in policy, nurse leaders need to be able to operate effectively within a policy environment, often dominated by external narratives. While the bases of social power are designed to understand influence by an individual, role, or group, on a person, and not a group (French and Raven, 1959), they have previously been applied to explore the assets available to nursing to support policy influence (Abood, 2007) and application of power in medicine (Gabel, 2012). Understanding how strategic nurse leadership in public policy maps to bases of social power, and how interpretation of those could illuminate new

perspectives on future focus and potential impact of approaches offered by the nurse leaders, could provide a novel contribution to the field.

In their seminal paper, French and Raven (1959) described five bases of social power: legitimate, reward, coercive, referent, and expert power. Raven (1965) later added informational power to the taxonomy, originally excluded due to a disagreement between French and Raven (Raven, 2008). Further extensions and differentiations have been proposed (Raven, 1993; Mittal and Elias, 2016) but this thesis adopted the original five bases of social power (see Figure 3.1) (French and Raven, 1959), broadly categorised as positional and personal power.

Figure 3.1 Bases of Social Power (French and Raven, 1959)

Within positional power, legitimate power is determined by the person or group being influenced. It includes the perception of the leader's right to influence. Legitimate power may originate in social, organisational, or professional structures and hierarchies as well as cultural norms such as those related to gender. Although Abood (2007) claim that nurses have legitimate power by virtue of their registration to practice and also by the policy statements of nursing organisations, the extent to which they actually confer legitimate power is unknown. The link between legitimate power and cultural norms clearly links to the second theoretical perspective, CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) which describes culturally mediated societal leadership expectations of what a good leader does as influencing leadership behaviour. French and Raven (1959) set out that if a leader attempts to influence beyond the boundaries of their legitimate power, their legitimate power will be decreased. The implications for nursing's policy influence are that realising the rhetoric around broadening nursing's policy influence might be difficult in contexts where nurses do not hold legitimate power.

This interpretation is supported by MacDonald *et al.*'s (2012) cautions around the effectiveness of nursing's policy reach beyond the profession.

Reward and coercive power are also features of positional power and describe power over another. Reward power includes the perception that the leader controls resources valued by the target individual or group. In the context of nurse leadership, the power to reward or punish has been more frequently reported within the nursing hierarchy (Crawford *et al.*, 2019; Park, Kang, 2023) rather than between professions.

Personal power comprises referent and expert power bases (French and Raven, 1959). Referent power is generated through the target person's desire to be more like the individual or group trying to influence them. Although some countries in the Global North consistently identify nursing as the most trusted profession (Roy Morgan, 2021; Ipsos, 2023a; Brenan and Jones, 2024) its image as a desirable profession continues to vary internationally. Interestingly despite nursing's trusted status in the United Kingdom (UK) Ipsos (2023b) omit nurses from their Global Trustworthiness of Professions index raising questions about the image and status of nursing more broadly. Coupled with a mixed picture of positive (Gündüz Hoşgör and Coşkun, 2024) and negative public perceptions of nursing (Elmorshedy *et al.*, 2020; Joarder *et al.*, 2021), suggests a lack of certainty about the referent power of the profession. The second personal power base, expert power is contingent on the target person perceiving the leader as a trusted and credible expert in a topic (Isaac *et al.*, 2023). If an individual or group tries to assert themselves as an expert outside their scope of expert power as perceived by others, it will undermine their existing expert power (French and Raven, 1959). This is particularly pertinent given the tensions in the literature about nursing's policy focus (MacDonald *et al.*, 2012). Nurses' ability to articulate their expertise has however been questioned by non-nursing leaders (Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014). In sum, while nurses hold significant expertise, if it is unseen or undervalued, it might be difficult for nurses to deploy expert power.

Nurse leaders possess aspects of social power within the nursing hierarchy by virtue of their position. Their wider social power however could be argued as constrained by the position of nursing and women in society, which could impact on their ability to influence policy. Whilst the social constructionist tenet of the contextual and historical specificity allows for the social power of strategic nurse leaders to vary internationally, its lens also contests taken for granted knowledge, encouraging scrutiny of historically accepted perspectives, such as the traditionally disempowered image of nursing. Social constructionism also recognises the presence of dominant perspectives and that these may serve the interests of particular, often powerful groups (Burr, 2015).

Considering the approaches of and challenges for strategic nurse leaders in policy from the perspective of the bases of social power supports a deeper exploration of the research aim, situating the experiences of strategic nurse leaders in the context of broader power dynamics and external perceptions.

3.2.2 Culturally endorsed implicit leadership theory (CLT)

CLT extends Lord and Maher's (1991) implicit leadership theory which holds that leadership behaviours and preferences are influenced by culture and context (Dorfman *et al.*, 2012). The CLT extension is that perspectives on expected leadership behaviour are mediated at a cultural, rather than individual level (House *et al.*, 2004). Focusing on strategic leaders in their 2014 research House *et al.* (2014) posited that culture influences societal expectations of how effective leaders in their society behave which in turn influences the actual behaviour of strategic leaders. House *et al.*'s (2014) research on CLT in strategic leaders found that leaders who behaved in line with the cultural expectations of the context they were operating in were more likely to lead dedicated teams and successful companies. While this thesis did not seek to test CLT it did borrow its premise that the effectiveness of strategic nurse leaders will be mediated by the degree to which they meet or exceed the leadership expectations of the society they work in, which are influenced by the cultural values of that society.

CLT is underpinned by a significant empirical investigation (Chhokar, Brodbeck and House, 2007; House *et al.*, 2004, House *et al.*, 2014). The original research conducted by the Global Leadership and Organizational Behavior Effectiveness (GLOBE) research programme investigated the cultural practices and values of 62 societies and included a sample of more than 17000 middle managers in business (House *et al.*, 2004). In the subsequent strategic leadership study, the GLOBE team recruited more than 1000 Chief Executive Officers and 5000 senior executives from organisations across 24 countries (House *et al.*, 2014). CLT comprises six global dimensions of leadership behaviour (House *et al.*, 2004). While the GLOBE studies did identify a small number of apparently universally accepted leadership behaviours, the majority were culturally contingent (Hange *et al.*, 2016). Appreciating this variation is important when choosing approaches aimed at expanding nursing's policy influence internationally. Rather than a direct link between cultural values and leadership behaviour, CLT holds that cultural values affect what society considers effective leadership behaviour. Leaders are then induced to behave in line with the leadership expectations held by society of how a prototypical leader behaves. If leaders do not behave in line with those expectations, they will not be effective leading in that context (House *et al.*, 2014).

Although CLT provides a useful lens for understanding international variation in leadership approaches, the 1:9 ratio of women to men in GLOBE's research sample is an inverted gender balance when compared to nursing (WHO, 2020), and a recognised limitation of the theory (House *et al.*, 2014). The male biased sample could be considered problematic given that in addition to nursing being predominantly female (WHO, 2020) and characterised as a care giving profession (Khoury *et al.*, 2011), the literature recognises separate considerations for the societal expectation of the behaviour of successful female leaders (Bullough *et al.*, 2022) as well as cultural variation in the status of women (WHO, 2019). Women can, for example, be penalised for leadership styles that are incongruent with societal expectations of how female leaders are expected to behave, even if this approach would be acceptable if enacted by a male leader (Vial, Napier, and Brescoll, 2016), meaning that CLT might apply differently to women. CLT has however been used successfully to explore women's political and entrepreneurial leadership (Bullough and de Luque, 2015).

While gender imbalance is a limitation of CLT, the only assumption borrowed from CLT for this study is that culture has a mediating effect on perceived leader effectiveness and consequently on the behaviours of those leaders. This assumption is congruent with the social constructionist tenet of knowledge construction as context bound and sustained by social processes (Burr, 2015).

Exemplifying this in CLT, House *et al.* (2014) state that the success of leaders is not only about the level to which they are able to perform leadership behaviours, but that they choose approaches which fit with the leadership expectations of that cultural context. The CLT assertion that the effect of culture on leadership is mediated by the expectations each society holds about the way effective leaders lead links to social constructionism's principle of knowledge as tied to social action. In the context of this study for example, the leadership approaches described by strategic nurse leaders are assumed to be shaped by the cultural context in which they work. CLT was considered particularly pertinent in the construction of a consensus statement exemplifying the global perspectives of strategic nurse leaders and their policy influence.

3.3 Selecting the research methods

Using a social constructionist approach to this thesis necessitated a research design which facilitated critical exploration and construction of a shared reality to understand international strategic nurse leadership and public policy. Philosophical, theoretical, and practical issues were considered when selecting the research methods. Practical considerations in relation to researching international, elite participants with English as an additional language are outlined in 4.3. In the following section, a range of methods considered for use in this study are debated with the philosophical and practical requirements of the study.

3.3.1 Survey research

Survey research, either postal or online, would have facilitated access to an international sample. While a survey could have elicited individual perspectives, it would have been limited in its capacity to provide in-depth insights (Polit and Beck, 2010) into strategic nurse leadership in public policy. Although the principles of good survey design were attractive, its merits did not fulfil the purpose of the study fully. For example, it does not, without repeated contact between researcher and participant, allow for clarification of perspectives or meanings (Bryman, 2008). The ability to clarify interpretation of the questions being asked would seem particularly important in the context of cross-cultural research conducted in English, with participants for whom English is an additional language (discussed further in 4.3.1). Standalone surveys are not designed to facilitate interaction between individuals. As such they cannot support iterative development of agreement or divergence, thereby falling short of delivering on the social constructionist tenet of developing knowledge mediated through social processes. This constraint made survey research unsuitable to deliver on the research aim to construct a consensus statement and was consequently rejected.

3.3.2 Focus groups

Focus groups would have allowed the construction of shared meaning and satisfied the social constructionist tenet of interaction between the collective and individual in the social construction of that meaning. Usually, however, focus groups aim to explore understanding of topics rather than facilitate the development of consensus (Krueger and Casey, 2015). As one of the aims of this thesis was to develop a consensus statement around international strategic nurse leadership and public policy, the lack of direction in focus groups towards uncovering areas of consensus and divergence made it an unsuitable method for the study.

Focus groups also present challenges in the management of group dynamics in the context of a potential hierarchy between participants (Stewart and Shamdasani, 2015). Minimising potential loss or repression of quieter or outlying voices was particularly pertinent in this thesis. This was rooted in an appreciation for the multiplicity of experiences among nurse leaders across the world, foregrounded by the epistemological and theoretical underpinnings. Requiring participants to be confident in whole group conversational English could have further restricted the diversity of nurse leaders meeting the criteria for inclusion in the study. Further, the quest for an international perspective with a geographically dispersed group of potential participants coupled with resource constraints made face to face focus groups infeasible.

3.3.3 Individual interviews

The integrative review established that individual interviews have been successfully used in strategic nurse leadership research (2.3.3.4). Interviews offered an in-depth understanding of individual perspectives on nursing leadership in public policy, and supported development of a rich narrative about the experiences of nurses and non-nursing decision makers. The ability of interviews to elicit rich data and depth of perspective (Ogden and Cornwall, 2010), made them a useful method for supplementing the literature to inform the main Delphi study. They were also used during the post-Delphi inquiry, designed to explore the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement constructed during the main study (detailed in 4.6). The international focus of this study made in-person interviews infeasible and required interviews designed to be suitable via telephone or online platforms.

Individual interviews used in isolation, however, do not facilitate consensus building as there is no interaction between participants. Using individual interviews alone would have therefore missed the opportunity to fulfil the social constructionist tenet of knowledge as being sustained by interaction between people. It also could not have wholly addressed the research aim to develop a consensus statement on international strategic nurse leadership and public policy.

3.3.4 Consensus methods

In the context of a constructionist exploration of international strategic nurse leadership and public policy with the aim of developing a consensus statement, there was a clear steer towards consensus building methods. Consensus building research methods are often recommended in the context of a research problem about which little is known or where there are conflicts in the existing knowledge base (Avella, 2016). Given the underdeveloped body of knowledge around international nurse leadership in public policy, consensus building methods seemed appropriate. The three main methods used in consensus building research are: nominal group technique, consensus development conference and Delphi (Waggoner, Carline and Durning, 2016).

3.3.4.1 Nominal group technique

Historically, nominal group technique, developed by Van de Ven and Delbecq (1972) involves a face-to-face meeting of participants where they are initially presented with a theme or problem. More recently online variants have been developed (Mason *et al.*, 2021). The technique then uses silent idea generation followed by volunteering of one idea from each participant. Clarification and group discussion of the ideas then takes place before private voting on each idea. The results of the voting are then collated and presented anonymously to the group (McMillan, King and Tully, 2016). McMillan, *et al.* (2014) suggest a maximum of seven participants per nominal group technique

session. Limiting the group numbers makes the method more resource intensive and less attractive for establishing consensus across a larger and diverse group. Using nominal group technique in this thesis would have required a number of groups and then between group analysis.

Nominal group technique does retain the benefits of group interaction, such as clarification of meaning in the moment for both researcher and participant (de Loë, 1995) and also requires parity in contribution. The voting in nominal group technique, while anonymous is still in person which Fletcher and Marchildon (2014) caution threatens the rigour of the method in the context of a group with significant power differentials, similar to focus groups. In addition to concerns about the impact of group dynamics, while online video calls with polling functionality are routinely in use post-pandemic at the time of data collection in 2015, nominal group technique would have required convening an in-person event. The consequent expense and complexity of coordinating a geographically dispersed group as required in this thesis compounded the other disadvantages identified and made nominal group technique an infeasible method.

3.3.4.2 Consensus development conference

Like nominal group technique, consensus development conferences traditionally require face to face meetings (Waggoner, Carline and Durning, 2016). Participants in consensus development conferences are often presented with the contemporary evidence on a topic and then have focused discussions around central questions with the aim of producing a consensus statement at the end of the conference. The National Institutes of Health (NIH, 2023) had a consensus development program until 2013 which used a systematic review based approach to consensus development conferences and produced consensus statements on a range of clinical areas.

Interactions at consensus development conferences are not as structured as techniques such as nominal group or Delphi (Nair, Aggrawal and Khanna, 2011). The lack of structured interaction has the potential to allow disproportionate influence of a small number of participants leading to issues with bias related to group dynamics. Contrastingly, Delphi studies mitigate issues pertaining to in-person consensus development through quasi anonymity, where the responses of individual participants are known to the researcher but not to each other (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). Although hosting a consensus conference was appealing to some extent, limited study resources and cost made it infeasible to deliver a consensus conference with equitable distribution of participation. A consensus development conference would have therefore been likely to have had skewed participation with a higher proportion of members of the host country, high income countries, and for those countries where visa arrangements to the host country were most straight

forward. Low income countries would have therefore been more likely to be underrepresented, threatening the transferability of the conference findings.

3.3.4.3 Delphi

Delphi is a consensus method named after the site of an oracle in Greek mythology which was said to convey the prophecies of the God Apollo (Marchais-Roubelat and Roubelat, 2011). It was developed as a research method by the United States Airforce in the 1940s and 50s to garner expert consensus in forecasting potential hostile action by foreign powers and the number of bombs they would require for retaliation (Dalkey and Helmer, 1962). The use of the method has subsequently proliferated and broadened from forecasting into wider consensus building, priority setting and exposing distribution of perspectives (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna 2011). The most common products of Delphi studies in healthcare research include clinical guidelines (Colucci, *et al.*, 2018), construction of role-based competencies (Albarqouni *et al.*, 2018), and development of research agendas (Hoekstra *et al.* 2017). Delphi has also been successfully used in strategic international nurse leadership research (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Benton, González-Jurado and Benoit-Montesinos 2013), including in investigating the barriers and facilitators for Africa nurse leader involvement in policy making (Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; Shariff, 2014; Shariff, 2015a) as discussed earlier (2.3.3.2). The ability of the Delphi to support construction of shared perspectives of strategic nurse leadership in public policy with an international panel, made it attractive as the main research method to fulfil the research aims of this thesis.

The range of products and purposes of Delphi studies reflects the array of adaptations of the method which are now in use. There are a wide range of Delphi variants reported in the literature (Jünger *et al.*, 2017; Flostrand, Pitt and Bridson, 2020; Lund, 2020). The consequent lack of methodological standardisation, and inconsistency in reporting, has resulted in the absence of a complete definition of the Delphi and invited criticism and debate (Day and Bobeva, 2005; Brown, 2007; Diamond *et al.*, 2014; Jünger *et al.*, 2017). The flexibility of Delphi means that it continues to be a popular method in published research.

Despite variation of approach there are four characteristics considered by Rowe and Wright (1999) as common to all Delphi studies:

1. Quasi anonymity where responses from individual panellists are known only to the researcher but the panellists are privy to the group findings between rounds.
2. Iterative approach to data collection through a number of questionnaire-based rounds,
3. Structured feedback to panellists between rounds.
4. Statistical analysis of the group response.

How the four characteristics are employed varies across studies. There are no agreed operational definitions for key deliverables, including approaches to selection of appropriate panellists, number of rounds, or criteria for consensus (Rowe and Wright, 1999; Day and Bobeva, 2005; Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006; Jünger *et al.*, 2017).

Three of the most common types of Delphi reported in the literature are: classical, modified and policy. The aim of the research can be used to shape the type of Delphi adopted (Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn, 2007; Belton *et al.*, 2019). Classical and modified Delphi studies both aim to generate consensus but differ in the structure of their first round. Policy Delphi studies, first described by Turoff (1970), are designed to explore policy issues for which there could be a range of prospective routes forward. A Policy Delphi can ask panellists to consider dimensions such as the importance, feasibility, or desirability of particular approaches to policy issues (Turoff, 1970). Studies using a Policy Delphi approach do not always aim to develop consensus (von der Gracht, 2012), but can do so whilst also exposing and understanding divergence (Rayens and Hahn, 2000; Meskell *et al.*, 2014; de Loë *et al.*, 2016). The capacity of Policy Delphi studies to seek the reasons for divergent views can also generate useful insights (Kattirtzi and Winskel, 2020). The anticipated cultural, sectoral, and contextual variation in approaches to strengthening nursing's policy influence internationally therefore made the policy Delphi an attractive choice.

In a classical Delphi the first round questionnaire seeks perspectives on an open question generating a list of qualitative perspectives from the panellists (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). The modified and Policy Delphi differ from classical in that the researchers may construct a more structured first round based on the existing literature or pre-Delphi inquiry (Rayens and Hahn, 2000; Hsu and Sandford, 2007). Such pre-Delphi inquiry can take the form of focus groups or semi-structured interviews (Day and Bobeva, 2005).

Using a structured approach to round one can shorten the total duration of the Delphi as it reduces the volume of data generated in Round 1 thereby condensing time required for between round analyses. Minimising the interval between rounds can be important to the retention of panellists (Donohoe and Needham, 2009), particularly when researching elites with busy schedules. Critics of a structured first round argue that it could introduce ideas to panellists that wouldn't have otherwise been raised or given prominence, thereby introducing bias into the Delphi findings (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006). Day and Bobeva (2005) refute that stating that a structured first round based on the key themes of the published literature or interview data mitigates the threat to rigour of the unstructured polling of panellists in classical Delphi studies. Keeney, Hasson and McKenna (2006)

suggest a compromise where a structured round one questionnaire offers sufficient opportunity for panellists to raise additional issues.

For the purposes of this study the merits of a structured first round outweighed its potential limitations, particularly with the integration of opportunity for panellists to include additional free text about aspects of the topic they felt may have been missed from the first round. Pre-Delphi interviews with international strategic nurse leaders were conducted to supplement the small body of empirical literature on strategic nurse leadership and public policy. Together the literature review (Chapter 2) and analysis of the pre-Delphi interviews (findings reported in Chapter 5) informed the development of the first round of the Delphi.

Once the first round of the Delphi is complete the researchers analyse the responses (discussed in detail in 3.6.1, and 4.5.8.3) and return a synopsis of the analysis to the panellists. As discussed earlier, structured feedback is a cardinal feature of Delphi studies (Rowe and Wright, 1999). In classical Delphi, the new statements derived from the qualitative analysis of the unstructured Round 1 are returned to panellists for judgement. If the first round was structured, as in modified Delphi studies, the panellists may be sent the first round analysis with both their individual score and that of the whole panel (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). In some Delphi studies all statements are returned to the panellists for re-consideration to measure stability in judgement, however, this can lead to overly long questionnaires that can contribute to attrition (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). Whether all statements are retested, or only those which did not achieve consensus in the preceding round, panellists are invited to review their original response to an individual statement, alongside the median of the whole panel, and make a judgement about whether they wish to revise it. The second round questionnaire can also include new statements derived from qualitative analysis of any open ended questions in Round 1.

Participant agreement with statements within the Delphi questionnaire is ascertained using a rating scale (Jünger *et al.*, 2017), commonly a Likert scale (de Loë *et al.*, 2016). The number of response options on the Likert scale varies widely in the Delphi literature (de Loë *et al.*, 2016; Belton *et al.*, 2019) and is discussed further in 4.5.6.2. Decisions around the specific approaches to quantitative and qualitative analysis of Delphi data are detailed in 4.5.8. Delphi studies commonly continue for between two and four rounds (Diamond *et al.*, 2014; Jünger *et al.*, 2017). The implications of the number of rounds for rigour and the practical considerations of this thesis are discussed in 3.6.4 and 4.5 respectively.

The ability of Delphi to develop consensus and uncover areas of divergence whilst minimising the impact of group dynamics such as power gradients and personalities through the use of quasi

anonymity makes it an attractive research method for this thesis. This is particularly true in the context of the social constructionist underpinning where developing a shared reality values the contributions of all. Additionally, distributing the Delphi electronically makes it a feasible and time efficient method for elucidating the international perspectives of a geographically dispersed group of nurse leaders (McPherson, Reese and Wendler, 2018). Based on these considerations and, crucially, its ability to address the research aim, Delphi was progressed as the primary research method for the study. Before final decision to adopt Delphi, the philosophical underpinnings, coherence with social constructionism, and issues of rigour pertaining to Delphi were considered.

3.4 Philosophical underpinnings and the Delphi

Delphi has no archetypal underpinning theoretical or philosophical influences and did not emerge from a particular research tradition. Although Mitroff and Turoff (2002) states that there is no best philosophical fit, there are a range of alignments offered and debated within the literature (Powell, 2003; Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011; Guzys, *et al.*, 2015).

The collection of both qualitative and quantitative data within Delphi studies and variation in the orientation of Delphi research aims gives rise to epistemological tension (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011; Guzys *et al.*, 2015). The quantitative data from Likert scale ranking allows anonymous aggregation of responses to the Delphi statements and an interpretation of the emergence of consensus or divergence. Threshold of consensus is discussed in detail in 3.6.4 and 4.5.3. The qualitative data provides the panellists with an opportunity to both offer their reasoning behind their quantitative responses and also to add additional ideas they consider to be missing from the Delphi. The use of both types of data within one research method challenges the simplistic view of inextricable alignment of qualitative data with constructionist research designs and quantitative data with a positivist or objectivist research design (Stewart, 2001). As such, Delphi is considered by some authors to be at a juxtaposition with objectivism and constructionism while others advocate a fit with pragmatism (Brady, 2015). Stewart (2001) argues that it is the philosophical orientation of the research rather than the type of data collected which governs the paradigm in which Delphi sits.

Delphi studies most commonly develop consensus around a topic whilst retaining the capacity to uncover divergent positions. Some authors argue that if the contribution of the expert panel or the product of the Delphi are regarded as fact e.g., in guideline development, Delphi is then positioned within an objectivist paradigm (Stewart, 2001; Day and Bobeva, 2005). If, however Delphi is considered as the construction of a shared reality among a specific group of people at a particular

time (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011; Powell, 2003) this challenges an objectivist fit and situates Delphi more comfortably within constructionism.

Epistemological clarity is important for rigour, framing and interpretation of the Delphi findings but is often neglected in study reporting (Powell, 2003). Although Delphi is lamented in the literature for not having a singular philosophical position, this thesis takes the position of Stewart (2001) that it is the philosophical orientation of the research rather than the type of data collected which governs the paradigm in which Delphi sits. As such, in the context of a Delphi which aims to understand the multiplicity of experiences and construct a shared reality among the panellists, as in this thesis, it is considered to be situated within a constructionist epistemology.

3.5 Delphi and Social Constructionism

When making the final decision to adopt Delphi as the primary research method for this thesis it was important to understand how the Delphi could operationalise the four tenets of the social constructionist underpinnings (detailed earlier in 3.1.1): a critical stance towards taken for granted knowledge, historical and cultural specificity, knowledge as sustained by social processes and pairing of knowledge and social action.

Delphi tests conventional perspectives by asking panellists to rank their agreement with statements derived from either their peers or the published literature. The Delphi's iterative approach where, at each round, panellists have the opportunity to review their individual position alongside the judgement of the panel as whole, embodies the social constructionist principle of developing knowledge through interaction between the individual and the whole.

The variation of cultural and historical influences on nursing around the world is preserved within the transparent approach to presenting the Delphi findings at each round meaning that divergence is not lost in analysis. Further, the setting of a level of consensus from the outset (discussed further in 4.5.3) prevents inadvertent post-hoc imposition of the researcher's cultural and historical perspectives.

The pairing of knowledge and social action is interesting in the context of a Delphi study where panellists may experience reframing or deepening of their position as a product of the ongoing construction of a shared understanding of the topic under study. This capacity of the Delphi to evolve thinking has the potential to have implications which extend beyond the lifetime of the study and is discussed further as part of authenticity in rigour (3.6.5).

3.6 Delphi and Issues of Rigour

The ability to evaluate the integrity and quality of research is essential to the development of knowledge. Hasson and Keeney (2011) report that rigour is often not reported in Delphi research but included as a methodological limitation. Omitting rigour from study reporting opens the method to criticism and compromises the strength of research outputs. Where Delphi studies have discussed rigour both constructionist (Kelly *et al.*, 2017) and objectivist approaches (von Briel, 2018) have been used. This is unsurprising given the epistemological tensions in Delphi research and that the criteria used for the assessment of rigour is contingent on the philosophical orientation of the study at hand.

Evaluation of rigour in Delphi studies is complicated by the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data within one instrument. Traditionally, reliability and validity are used to assess the quality of quantitative data which is usually collected in objectivist studies (Topping, 2006). Evaluation of the rigour of qualitative data differs in that it is usually contained within a non-objectivist paradigm, which does not consider there to be a single true version of reality (Bryman, 2008). Lincoln and Guba (1985) proposed trustworthiness criteria for qualitative data as an alternative to reliability and validity to allow evaluation of research, which considers there to be multiple realities.

Hasson and Keeney (2011) recommend the assessment of reliability, validity, and trustworthiness in Delphi studies due to the presence of both quantitative and qualitative data. Such an approach is countered by Guzys *et al.* (2015) who argues that the presence of quantitative data does not make objectivist rigour criteria appropriate if an objectivist epistemology is not being adopted. Justifying this stance, Guzys *et al.* (2015) posits that if the philosophical underpinnings would consider the findings of the study to reflect the collective perceptions of an expert group rather than indisputable facts trustworthiness criteria is more appropriate than reliability and validity.

Using reliability and validity to assess the quality of the study in this thesis would have given primacy to seeking objective truth thereby setting up tension with the social constructionist view of the existence of multiple realities within one topic. For this reason, Lincoln, and Guba's (1985) four trustworthiness criteria were applied: credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. In addition, to consider the broader implications of the research, Guba and Lincoln's (1989) authenticity criteria were also adopted. The authenticity criteria, discussed in detail in 3.6.5, are rooted in a constructivist ontology and deviate from the trustworthiness criteria which are sometimes considered parallel to the objectivist concepts of reliability and validity (Johnson and Rasulova, 2016). The authenticity criteria map well to social constructionism due to its recognition

and appreciation of the presence of multiple realities, which are bound by context, culture, and time.

Opportunities to enhance the trustworthiness and then authenticity of the data in this thesis are explored next.

3.6.1 Credibility

Assessment of credibility explores the degree to which the findings are a truthful representation of the panellists' contribution (Polit and Beck, 2010). Strategies recommended to promote credibility include prolonged researcher participant engagement and member checking (Morrow, 2005). Within Delphi studies credibility is enhanced by its iterative nature which provides multiple points of engagement between the researcher and participant. Primarily, however, credibility is enriched in Delphi research through the feedback of individual and group ratings of statements to panellists between rounds. The ability of Delphi to include quieter or outlying perspective exposes panellists to explore areas of divergence or aspects of a topic they may not have originally considered through provision of both the individual and whole panel ratings. They can then revise or maintain their initial ratings as they wish, provide additional perspectives, and clarify their reasoning for responses (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006; Rowe and Wright, 1999). This iterative process develops the credibility of the findings incrementally across the study by giving the panellists an explicit opportunity to reflect on their initial judgements.

A potential threat to credibility in Delphi studies is the concern that individuals may change their ratings to conform to the group response rather than because they have altered their perspective (Hsu and Sandford, 2007). Approaches to mitigate this threat include requesting a reason for any maintenance or change to position, anonymity of responses between panellists and, impartial instructions in relation to adjustment of judgements.

The credibility of this study was also strengthened by triangulation of methods as recommended by Polit and Beck (2010) to understand similarities and differences with other perspectives on the same topic. Specifically, there was triangulation between the Delphi constructed draft consensus statement, and the post-Delphi interviews which explored its resonance and potential utility with a different group of strategic nurse leaders.

3.6.2 Dependability

Dependability describes "the stability of findings over time and conditions" (Polit and Beck, 2010, p492). An audit trail, advocated to support assessment of dependability (Lincoln and Guba, 1986; Korstjens and Moser, 2018), detailed the decisions made throughout the study. Delphi studies also

provide panellists with more than one opportunity to review, revise or maintain their perspectives throughout the research, supporting understanding of the dependability of the findings. The addition of the post-Delphi interviews also served to strengthen the dependability of the draft consensus statement, by exploring its resonance with participants separate to the Delphi panel.

3.6.3 Transferability

One of the key criticisms of Delphi, as with social constructionist research, is that it is unknown how transferable the findings are beyond the group of original panellists leading to cautions around interpretation in the absence of further investigation (Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn, 2007).

Sackman (1975), in a widely cited criticism of the Delphi method, recommended that Delphi findings be tested by replicating the study with a new cohort of panellists. Such testing of the Delphi findings, although rarely reported in the literature, would be resource intensive but provide an opportunity to explore how the findings resonate with perspectives and contexts beyond those in the original study (Day and Bobeva, 2005; Hasson and Keeney, 2011). To enhance the transferability and contribution of this thesis, the findings of the Delphi were explored in the post-Delphi interviews with a separate international cohort of government nurse leaders. The post-Delphi interviews are further discussed in 4.6 which also offers a detailed description of the methods, advocated by Guba and Lincoln (1989) to support external assessment of transferability.

3.6.4 Confirmability

Confirmability concerns the ability of the researcher to demonstrate that the findings are rooted in the data (Polit and Beck, 2010). The confirmability of the qualitative data from both the Delphi and interviews within this thesis was supported through a detailed audit trail as recommended by Morrow (2005) and Kyngäs, Kääriäinen and Elo (2020). The thick description of the analysis process, provided in 4.5.8, also increases confidence in confirmability, evidencing the relationship between the raw data and the findings (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Within the Delphi confirmability is influenced by choices including number of rounds and measurement of consensus since these two stopping points shape the findings of the study. Although the number of Delphi rounds varies across studies (Jünger *et al.*, 2017), three rounds are usually considered to provide sufficient opportunity for panellists to contribute ideas, receive feedback and consider revision of their choices, whilst minimising unnecessary repetition (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006; Hsu and Sandford, 2007). As the rounds progress, knowledge is built between the panellists and the researcher, and the iterations lead to increasingly focused and nuanced contributions from the panellists (Hsu and Sandford, 2007). A Delphi with insufficient

rounds could compromise confirmability by not allowing the expert panel sufficient opportunity to explore all perspectives and risks being stopped prematurely (de Meyrick, 2003).

The choices made during any research, but particularly the Delphi and the construction of a narrative consensus statement foregrounded the importance of a reflexive approach to the overall trustworthiness, and particularly the confirmability of the study. Reflexivity is the process of unpacking the researcher’s influence on the research process. A reflexive journal is recommended by Lincoln and Guba (1985) as an approach to capture data which supports assessment of confirmability and dependability. Green and Thorogood (2018) propose four dimensions of reflexivity awareness (Table 3.1) to enhance rigour. The practical application of reflexivity is discussed in 4.7.2.

Table 3.1. Dimensions of reflexive awareness (adapted from Green and Thorogood, 2018, p.277)

Dimension of Reflexivity	Application in Practice
Methodological openness	Transparent, thick description of decision making, data collection and analysis
Theoretical openness	How theoretical influences have shaped the research.
Awareness of the social setting of the research	Awareness of influence of the interactions which lead to data generation.
Awareness of the wider social context	Awareness of how social, cultural, and political values and norms influence the research.

Published Delphi studies usually give primacy to reporting which statements achieve consensus. The integrity of the assessment of consensus is central to confirmability but is a contested topic with no consistent guidance in the literature. Unfortunately, decisions about consensus are often poorly defined and described in the published literature (von der Gracht, 2012; Belton *et al.*, 2019) serving as a methodological threat to the trustworthiness of the findings. A consistently agreed principle is that the criteria for consensus must be made prior to data collection (Grant, Booth and Khodyakov, 2018) to protect confirmability. Applying criteria post-hoc would give the researcher free rein to decide retrospectively which findings achieve consensus and, therefore, determine the key findings reported from the study. The level of agreement indicative of consensus in this study was decided a priori as 67% or more of the responding panellists in either agreement or disagreement, and an interquartile range of less than or equal to one. The reasoning for decisions relating to consensus are further described in 4.5.3.

3.6.5 Authenticity criteria

Guba and Lincoln's (1989) authenticity criteria comprise fairness plus four dimensions of authenticity: ontological, catalytic, tactical, and educative. These criteria were renamed by Nolan *et al.* (2003) to make them more accessible and also mapped to the planning, process, and product of research. Adapting the authenticity criteria embeds rigour prospectively into the research process rather than limiting it to a post-hoc evaluation of quality. The application and mapping of the authenticity criteria to this thesis is detailed in 4.7.3.

The principle of fairness, Nolan *et al.*'s (2003) equal access, is an evaluation of how evenly the contributions of each participant were treated. Within Delphi studies this can be achieved by reporting the findings of both items where there was consensus as well as those characterised by polarisation and divergence of opinion. Doing so allows the preservation of the principle of multiple realities within a social constructionist Delphi. All consenting Delphi panellists were sent all rounds of the Delphi strengthening fairness by maximising their opportunity to contribute even where other commitments precluded them from participating all rounds. Wider fairness of the study for strategic nurse leaders was evidenced by the opportunity in the post-Delphi interviews to give other strategic nurse leaders an opportunity to contribute and comment on the Delphi findings.

The principles of ontological (the extent to which the research improves the participant's own understanding of the topic) and educative authenticity (the extent to which the research improves the panellists' understanding of each other's views) (Bryman, 2008) are evidenced well within Delphi studies due to the regular feedback to panellists of both their own perspectives and those of the wider expert panel. The Delphi does not, however, specifically ask panellists if this has been their experience, adding a caveat to the strength of the demonstration of ontological and educative authenticity.

Catalytic authenticity, known by Nolan *et al.* (2003) as encouraging action, is the extent to which the research stimulates change (Bryman, 2008). In the context of this thesis this criterion can be applied to examine the extent to which Delphi findings reflected actions that could be instigated to improve nursing participation in policy. It was further explored in the final round of the Delphi and post-Delphi interviews where participants had an opportunity to explore whether the Delphi findings reflected priorities for action in their country.

Tactical authenticity, described by Nolan *et al.* (2003) as enabling action, considers the level to which participants become empowered to act based on the findings of the research. Tactical authenticity was explored to some extent in the final Delphi Round exploring how panellists might use the statement, and in the post-Delphi interview questions about how the draft consensus statement

resonated with their plans for policy influence in their country. While tactical authenticity could have been further evaluated in a follow up study, this was out with the scope of this thesis.

3.7 Interviews and issues of rigour

The principles and arguments for the use of trustworthiness and authenticity criteria as described in 3.6 also apply to the pre-Delphi and post-Delphi interviews. The interviews were conducted within the social constructionist epistemology of the overall research study. The inclusion of the post-Delphi interviews to enhance the rigour of the Delphi was justified in the subsections of 3.6. Additional considerations particular to interview rigour are detailed in 4.7.

3.8 Ethical principles

Ensuring the safeguarding of research participants through the application of ethical principles is an essential component of research design. Participants are protected under the Declaration of Helsinki, most recently updated in 2013, which sets out principles to which all research must adhere. Under the Declaration, primacy is given to the welfare of the participant over the need for research (World Medical Association, 2013). The declaration also requires comprehensive research governance via independent ethical committees to prevent poorly conceived or ethically flawed research from being conducted (Johnsson *et al.*, 2014).

Four principles of ethical research underpin research governance: autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice (Beauchamp and Childress, 2019). The Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013) protects autonomy, the fundamental right for an individual to make autonomous decisions about their participation in research without coercion. Participant autonomy can be assured through the process of obtaining informed consent as well as ensuring and operationalising the right of an individual to withdraw at any point in their research participation without giving a reason (Orb, Eisenhauer and Wynaden, 2000). Within Delphi studies and qualitative interviews, informed consent can be gained from the outset through provision of information about the study and opportunities to ask questions about the research. Consent is revisited at the start of qualitative interviews whilst, within Delphi, the panellists can opt to not participate in subsequent rounds. In both cases, the participant is free to withdraw at any point.

The principles of beneficence, to do good, and non-maleficence, to do no harm, require evaluation of the potential risks and benefits of research to the participants at the outset of the study. Beneficence and non-maleficence are operationalised through the independent confirmation by the ethics committee of the presence of a sound scientific underpinning, an appropriate research team, a well-considered research design and strategy for adverse events. In reporting the findings, the

small size of the strategic nurse leadership population led to a wide assessment of what could be potentially identifiable information. Information including the countries of Delphi panellists was subsequently redacted and replaced with the world region of the individual countries, to protect confidentiality. Protecting the identities and preventing attribution of data to individuals is a central part of good research practice. It requires anonymization of data together with secure data storage where the identities of participants are kept separately from the data itself (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

The final principle of justice requires fairness in the research (Beauchamp and Childress, 2019). It includes processes to fairly select and interact with participants during the research as well as the capacity of the research to advance equity (Pratt, 2021). There is a need to actively select participants from a diverse range of contexts and engage research with potential to generate the insights required to reduce international disparities (Pratt, 2021). In the context of the known variation in the presence, status, and opportunities of nurses internationally (ICN, 2020; WHO, 2020), research aiming to understand international strategic nurse leadership in public policy and produce insights transferable to other contexts requires careful design. In this study for example, the post-Delphi interviews specified 'government nurse leaders' rather than GCNOs, to support inclusion of perspectives from countries without a GCNO.

In their framework for justice in global health research Pratt (2021) highlights management of power dynamics, providing equal opportunities for participants to contribute and to be heard as key. The quasi-anonymity of the Delphi helps mitigate the impact of power dynamics between Delphi panellists, who are unknown to each other. Within the pre- and post-Delphi interviews power dynamics could be assumed to be more tilted towards the interviewee in elite compared to non-elite research. Mason-Bish (2019) and Glas (2021) both argue however that power dynamics within an interview cannot be assumed and are dependent on how the relationship and rapport develops. Taking a reflexive approach to interactional justice could support better execution of the principle during the research process.

3.9 Key messages from methodology and theoretical perspectives

This thesis is set within a social constructionist worldview of science. The theoretical perspectives of bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) offer a novel frame to this study of strategic nurse leadership and public policy, recognising the international variation in power dynamics and cultural context. Following debate of options for methods mapping of Delphi to social constructionism demonstrated coherence between the design and philosophical foundations of the study. The development of a narrative consensus statement during the Delphi would offer an original contribution to the field, setting out global perspectives on shared approaches to expansion of strategic policy influence. Although the modified Policy Delphi was attractive as a method to elucidate points of consensus and divergence, this chapter has identified important threats to rigour. The chapter presented a comprehensive plan for the promotion of rigour. Central to the plan were post-Delphi interviews to explore the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement with participants separate to the Delphi. The next chapter discusses the translation of the methodology to the applied methods of the study.

Chapter 4: Methods

This chapter begins by outlining the research design and mapping the methods to the research aims. The research aims were to:

- Investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contribution to public policy
- Construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

The chapter goes on to describe the ethical approval process and detail the execution of the methods in chronological order.

4.1 Research Design

The research design comprised a three round modified Policy Delphi with an international, cross-sector panel of strategic nurse leaders (Figure 4.1). The Delphi was modified so that the first round was informed by a review of the literature and analysis of semi-structured interviews with strategic nurse leaders rather than the unstructured polling used in classical Delphi (3.3.4.3). The Delphi was followed by post-Delphi interviews with government nurse leaders to strengthen the rigour of the findings.

Figure 4.1. Research Design

Figure 4.2 maps the research aim to the methods. The pre-Delphi interview findings, together with the literature review (Chapter 2), informed the Delphi study which produced a draft consensus statement on international strategic nurse leadership and public policy addressing the second research aim of consensus statement construction, whilst also enriching the first aim. The resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement was subsequently explored using semi-structured interviews with government nurses. The post-Delphi interviews enhanced the rigour of the Delphi and deepened the understanding of findings relating to both research aims.

The qualitative data of the Delphi were analysed using content analysis. The pre- and post-Delphi interviews were subject to framework analysis. To avoid repetition of description, the process of framework analysis is elaborated in 4.4.4. Issues particular to framework analysis of the post-Delphi interview data are also detailed in 4.6.4.

Figure 4.2. Map of research aim to methods

4.2 Ethics committee approval

Ethical approval for the study was granted by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee on January 19th, 2015 (Appendix 1). Although the ethics application was completed by the PhD candidate, the lead supervisor submitted the ethics application and therefore the letter confirming ethical approval is addressed to them. An amendment to ethical approval (Appendix 2) was subsequently logged to make clear that the research was being undertaken as part of doctoral study. The amendment also included the addition of post-Delphi interviews as the final phase of data collection.

Ethical considerations for the pre-Delphi interviews, Delphi study, and post-Delphi interviews are detailed in 4.4.1, 4.5.1, and 4.6.1, respectively.

4.3 Considerations common to recruitment across the research design

Addressing the research aims of this thesis required international recruitment of strategic nurse leaders to each phase of the study. Achieving geographical breadth and recruiting nurses at the top of their profession necessitated consideration of issues relating to language and elite research across the methods employed.

4.3.1 English as an additional language

The participants for the study were recruited internationally and therefore English was an additional language for some. As the researcher is monolingual the only options for undertaking international research were to either use interpreters in the construction and conduct of the research or only recruit individuals fluent in English. Both options have merits and limitations, however, in the context of this thesis resource constraints meant that the use of interpreters was not an option. Even if translation costs had been feasible, multiple interpreters would have been required due to the multiplicity of native languages among potential participants. Such multiplicity would have compounded existing ethical (Tiselius, 2019), technical (MacKenzie, 2015; Squires and Sadarangani, 2020), and analytical (Abfalter, Mueller-Seeger and Raich, 2021) complexities in the use of interpreters.

Employing English as the lingua franca, a shared language between people with different native languages, is common in international business (Ujii, 2020), research (Littig and Pöchhacker, 2014), and has been reported in the context of Delphi studies (Avella, 2016). It is cautioned however, that participants for whom English was an additional language in a study conducted in English may omit information they are not able to express in English and their contribution may be less detailed due to the demanding nature of communicating in an additional language (Wylie and Evans, 2023). If only participants with English as a primary language had been included, however, it would have perpetuated the dominance of the Global North narrative in the leadership literature. It would have also philosophically jarred with social constructionism in the context of seeking a rounded view of international nurse leadership in policy. The roles occupied by all participants meant that they were likely to be engaging in international nursing leadership dialogue via key organisations including WHO and ICN. The WHO (2018) includes English as one of their six main languages, and the ICN (no date) translate their publications in English, French, and Spanish. As such, it could be argued that strategic nurse leaders were well positioned to accurately self-assess whether or not they were sufficiently proficient in English to take part in the study.

4.3.2 Researching strategic nurse leaders

The strategic nurse leaders researched in this thesis occupied some of the most senior nursing specific positions available in their country, such as Chief Nursing Officer and President of the professional nursing association. As such the participants in each phase of the study were considered 'elite' in line with Lilleker's (2003) definition as being close to policy making, and Mikecz's (2012) interpretation as holding positions of power. Considering the definition of 'elite' as context bound as proposed by Harvey (2011) allows strategic nurse leaders to be considered elite even where that perception may not be shared beyond the nursing profession.

The methodological literature from across disciplinary fields offers a range of considerations when researching elite groups (Harvey, 2021; Liu and Buckingham, 2022; Cousin, Khan and Mears, 2018). The three most pertinent to this thesis are outlined here and explored further in the rigour section (see 4.7) are: gaining access, considering positionality, and conducting the research.

Challenges in gaining access to elite participants can lead to difficulties in both attracting recruitment to the study and, if initial interest is secured, actually completing the research in the context of busy schedules (Delaney, 2007). This study successfully adopted the commonly recommended (Welch *et al.*, 2002; Goldman and Swayze, 2012; Ryan and Lewer, 2016) approach of using a sponsor to help gain access to elite participants as detailed later (4.4.1, 4.5.1, and 4.5.2.3).

The positionality of the researcher, which can be perceived via multiple lenses, has implications for researching elites (Glas, 2021). Congruent with its social constructionist underpinnings, this thesis takes Herod's (1999) widely cited position that the insider outsider position is co-constructed by the interviewer and researcher, and that this can change within and between interviews. For example, the researcher might be an insider in terms of profession but outsider in terms of culture in one interview but an insider in both of those in the next. Consequently, there is no one approach to researching elites which will be appropriate and successful in every context. Reflexivity was used in this study to navigate and reflect on the impact of the perceived positionality of the researcher on the data generated. Reflexivity is further discussed in 4.7.2 and 8.9.4.

Two of the considerations when conducting research with elite participants revolve around the central concern of generating rich data relevant to the topic under study. Developing rapport is recognised as essential to producing useful data (Solarino and Aguinis, 2021). The particular power dynamics which elite research can bring are linked, in part, to the positionality of the researcher and the rapport developed between the researcher and participant (Mikecz, 2012; Glas, 2021). For example, when preparing for the interviews the researcher was mindful of the propensity, described in the literature, for elite participants to assume a directive role and not directly answer the

questions posed (Delaney, 2007; Mikecz, 2012). When planning the interviews, the researcher was prepared to be flexible in the direction and order of the interview and subtly guide the interview back towards the topic (4.4.3).

The considerations briefly explored here illustrate the fine and moving line that the researcher must walk in order to not only access elite participants but also to set up an environment through which to engage them most fruitfully.

4.4 Preparing for the Delphi Study: pre-Delphi interviews

Modified Delphi studies allow the content of the first-round questionnaire to be informed by what is already known in the literature or through new empirical data (Hsu and Sandford, 2007). The first round of the Delphi study reported in this thesis was informed by both a literature review and data from pre-Delphi interviews. The pre-Delphi telephone interviews were semi-structured and undertaken with an international, cross sector group of strategic nurse leaders.

4.4.1 Ethical Considerations for pre-Delphi interviews

Ethical approval was obtained to identify potential participants through the ICN. Participant information was distributed to potential participants via a letter of invitation (Appendix 3) and covering email (Appendix 4). The letter outlined the purpose and aims of the study. The email described what their contribution would entail if they decided to take part, including that their permission would be sought to audio record the interview. The initial letter and email were sent from the supervisory team of credible nurse leaders, in line with recommended use of sponsors to lend legitimacy to the study and aid recruitment due to the elite status of the potential participants (Welch *et al.*, 2002; Goldman and Swayze, 2012).

Potential participants were invited to contact the research team if they wished to find out more or take part. Individuals who expressed interest in taking part were asked to complete and return a consent form as an email attachment (Appendix 5). The consent form detailed their right to stop the interview at any time and this was reinforced by the researchers at the beginning of each interview. The consent form also assured potential participants of the confidentiality of their responses and preservation of their anonymity in the dissemination of the research.

The interview transcripts were anonymised, and each transcript was allocated a numerical code. One password protected file linking the strategic nurse leader and their numerical code was kept separately from the transcriptions on an encrypted password protected university server.

4.4.2 Pre-Delphi interviews: Sampling and Recruitment

A diverse sample of international strategic nurse leaders was sought from across the sectors of nursing including government, education, regulation, and professional nursing associations. To be eligible for recruitment potential participants who self-assessed as fluent in English and had access to an internet connection that would allow email communications. Following an informal approach by a member of the supervisory team who is also a strategic nurse leader, a convenience sample of potential participants were invited to take part in a semi-structured telephone interview.

4.4.3 Pre-Delphi interviews: Data collection

Due to the geographical dispersion of the participants the interviews were completed via telephone. Each interview lasted approximately 30-35 minutes and was audio recorded. Telephone interviews, although sometimes associated with shorter interview duration (Irvine, 2011), provided a more stable and accessible medium than internet-based platforms. The flexibility of telephone compared to in person interviews also considered to be advantageous in the context of interviewing elite participants (Harvey, 2011).

Establishing a good relationship with gatekeepers such as personal assistants who often coordinate the potential participant's diary is recognised by Goldman and Swayze (2012) as one approach to enable successful interview arrangements. In this study most participants scheduled their own interview directly with the researchers.

The interview schedule (Appendix 6) was designed to explore the opportunities, challenges, and contribution of strategic nurse leaders in public policy. The schedule was informed by the literature and structured starting with more general questions, moving to more specific and nuanced topics, in accordance with usual interview conventions (Doody and Noonan, 2013). As recommended by Harvey (2011) a flexible approach to interview conduct was adopted from the outset to allow the interviewer to respond to the mood and context of each elite interview. Van Audenhove and Donders (2019) also encourage flexibility to allow the development of a conversational flow in elite interviews. A rehearsal interview was undertaken with an international strategic nurse leader who met the recruitment criteria but did not form part of the main sample. Following the rehearsal interview minor alterations were made to the interview schedule. It also provided an opportunity to test the recording equipment, instructions to participants and data analysis.

An outline of the interview schedule was sent to participants at least a week in advance of the interview to allow them time to consider their perspectives and recall examples of policy influence where this was requested. Provision of advance sight of the interview schedule also was considered

as beneficial to participants with English as an additional language to help with cognitive load before and during the interview, with the purpose of optimising the richness of the data.

Due to the logistics and challenges of completing international interviews with elite nurse leaders, two research assistants (both experienced academic researchers) supported the telephone interviews. Their involvement was limited to the data collection of the pre-Delphi interviews and the peer debrief of the subsequent framework analysis undertaken by the PhD candidate.

4.4.4 Pre-Delphi interviews: Data analysis

The primary purpose of the pre-Delphi interviews was to identify topics which would benefit from further exploration in the first round of the Delphi study. The broad options for analysing the data were thematic, content or framework analysis. Thematic analysis was considered but rejected because the level of abstraction and interpretation in the analysis process was beyond the level of granularity required for the design of statements for the Delphi. Because of the focus on using the data to develop the first round of the Delphi, there was a need to promote rigour by adopting an approach which maximised transparency and development of a robust audit trail. As such, although content analysis was a feasible option, framework analysis, first described by Ritchie and Spencer (1994), offered a systematic method which preserved the link between the context of the raw data and emergent analysis (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009). Framework analysis was also sufficiently elastic as to allow deductive exploration of issues identified in the literature whilst encouraging inductive emergence of new ideas (Gale *et al.*, 2013; Parkinson *et al.*, 2016). This combination facilitated a comprehensive examination of the data and, without a particular philosophical orientation of its own (Gale *et al.*, 2013) framework analysis provided a good fit with the social constructionist tenet of a critical stance towards taken for granted knowledge.

The five stages of framework analysis as described by Ritchie and Spencer (1994) comprise familiarisation, constructing a framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation. The stages are interconnected rather than linear meaning that each stage was revisited several times in different orders, over the course of the analysis (Smith and Firth, 2011; Swallow *et al.*, 2011).

4.4.4.1 Familiarisation

The interviews were transcribed verbatim by a professional transcribing service, returned in a password protected file. All other aspects of data processing and analysis were undertaken by the PhD candidate. The transcript was anonymised on receipt, allocating each participant a numerical code. To check for transcription accuracy and develop data familiarisation each interview recording was listened to twice while reading the full transcript. Whilst Ritchie and Spencer (1994) states that familiarisation does not require the review of all data Gale *et al.* (2013) recommends review of all

data where the researcher undertaking the analysis was not present for the original interviews. During the second reading of the transcripts recurring ideas were identified and noted in the margins.

4.4.4.2 Constructing an analytical framework

Following familiarisation each line of each transcript was open coded. The resulting long list of codes were added to an inclusive list of recurring ideas identified during familiarisation together with topics from the interview schedule and literature review. These potential codes informed the preliminary analytical framework. The potential codes were then clustered and mapped on paper to allow grouping and development of a tentative hierarchy of main themes, subthemes, categories, and codes. Initially this was manually constructed as recommended by Ward *et al.* (2013) to enable the draft framework to be viewed as a whole.

The content of each theme was then transcribed into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and checked for overlap, omission, and clarity of wording. Moving to an electronic format at this point enabled easier adaptation and tracking of the framework development than on paper. As recommended by Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor (2003), an 'other' category was added to each subtheme to allow space for emergent topics in the later stage of refining the framework during indexing.

4.4.4.3 Indexing

The preliminary analytical framework was then tested by applying it to the whole dataset. Every transcript was printed and read again in conjunction with the analytical framework. Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor's (2003) guidance was applied with indexing comprising the attachment of category labels where the meaning of a transcript segment, e.g. sentence, was considered to fit with a particular category. Indexing was undertaken manually using coloured pens and writing in the margins. A digitised excerpt of an indexed transcript is presented in Appendix 7.

Where a single segment of data was relevant to more than one part of the index it was multi-coded. Where a transcript section did not fall into the existing index, it was allocated to the 'other' category of the appropriate subtheme to be reviewed at the end of indexing. Phrases or sentences which did not fit with any of the subthemes were allocated to a separate 'other' category to ensure no valuable data was lost. An example of a transcript segment which did not fit with the preliminary framework was "*Nurses can be divisive*" (P5). It was allocated to the 'other' category to ensure it was not omitted in the data analysis process. The items in the 'other' category were then reviewed and added as either new categories or codes. In addition to new categories, the framework was also refined through the division and collapsing of existing categories, subthemes and themes as the indexing progressed, in line with guidance from Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor (2003).

Following initial indexing the refined analytical framework was tested by the PhD candidate and the two experienced research assistants who had supported data collection. Each researcher independently indexed the transcripts and then compared to explore indexing similarities and differences. During the post-indexing discussions further adaptations were made to the analytical framework. Undertaking this team approach to reviewing the analytical framework promoted rigour, particularly in relation to credibility and confirmability.

The refined analytical framework was then applied by the PhD candidate to the corpus on clean copies of the anonymised transcripts. Each transcript was reviewed to ensure that the framework captured all interview content. Where meaningful data had not yet been captured the framework was further refined until no new codes were generated. Codes in the 'other' categories were reviewed, as recommended by Parkinson *et al.* (2016) and mapped appropriately. The final framework consisted of codes, clustered into categories, with direct quotes from the transcripts. Following finalisation, the framework was applied to each transcript by highlighting the text, using a different colour for each category. The coded transcripts were reviewed once more to check the framework encompassed all the data.

The refined hierarchical analytical framework of codes, categories, subthemes, and themes were discussed with the research assistants who had undertaken the interviews. On the basis of this discussion amendments were made to three subthemes and their allocated categories.

4.4.4.4. Charting the data into a matrix

A matrix was constructed in Microsoft® Excel to chart data from each participant by indexed category. The data for each participant for each code are summarised and condensed without loss of context or meaning (Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor, 2003). The wording of the summarised data was kept as close to the raw data as possible. The matrix comprised one row per participant and one column per category. The transcript line and page numbers were also retained to allow easy retrieval of raw data and direct quotes. Where a data segment was multi-indexed it appeared in more than one category in the matrix. In the full matrix the categories were groups by subthemes and themes.

Once all the data had been charted, the matrix was then reviewed per participant to check for errors and omissions between the chart and the indexed transcription.

4.4.4.5 Mapping and Interpretation

The mapping and interpretation stage is described by Parkinson *et al.* (2016) as often poorly described in the literature. The purpose of this final phase is to move the analysis beyond managing

the data towards the formulation of descriptive and then explanatory understanding of the dataset as a whole (Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor, 2003). Developing descriptive accounts was achieved by identifying key themes and exploring the diversity of perspectives within and across the charted matrix. For example, when considering the role of collaboration as an approach to strengthening policy influence, there was divergence in experience around the extent to which strategic nurse leaders were collaborative, and where there were tensions. Exploring the breadth of views required fluidity of moving between the matrix and the original transcripts to check that the meaning within the raw data was preserved in the interpretation. It is important to note that, within the descriptive account, frequency of recurrence in the data was not given primacy. This ensured that a full picture of the dataset was preserved (Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor, 2003) and could be used to inform the Delphi study. The categories, subthemes and themes were revised as recommended by Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor (2003) to reflect the higher level of abstraction and interpretation.

The explanatory accounts were then developed from the application of a higher level of abstraction and helped answer the first research aim of investigating strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges, and contribution to public policy. The construction of the explanatory accounts was rooted in Ritchie, Spencer and O'Connor's (2003) guidance on the identification of relationships and patterns within and between the themes. This was enabled by the construction of a central chart which comprised key phenomena identified within the descriptive analysis organised by theme and participant. Potential explanations for the linkages detected within the data were then developed using both reasons explicated by the participants as well as drawing on the theoretical underpinnings of bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and Culturally Endorsed Leadership Theory (House *et al.*, 2014), observations from which are discussed in Chapter 8. The explanatory phase of the analysis, whilst abstracted, was heavily grounded in the raw data and a dialogue between the transcripts and the analysis continued throughout. The final themes from the central chart and the charted matrix, informed the construction of the statements in the first round Delphi questionnaire (Appendix 8).

4.5 The Delphi Study

The modified Policy Delphi comprised three iterative rounds, illustrated in figure 4.3. Although making an a priori decision on number of rounds is debated in the literature (Humphrey-Murto and de Wit, 2019), two and three round studies are most frequently reported (Diamond *et al.*, 2014; Sossa, Halal and Zarta, 2019). An open-ended study, without a predetermined number of rounds, was also judged to be a risk to recruitment of elite nurse leaders with busy schedules. The use of the pre-Delphi interviews to inform a structured first round helped to mitigate the potential threat of

premature stopping of the Delphi allowing panellists to rank agreement in round one rather than round two as in a classical Delphi. The post-Delphi interviews enabled testing of the draft consensus statement constructed during the Delphi, which also helped confirm that three rounds of the Delphi were sufficient to obtain trustworthy findings.

The first round of the Delphi was informed by the findings of the pre-Delphi interviews and literature review. The second-round re-tested items which did not achieve consensus in round one and added new statements from the qualitative responses in round one. The final round re-tested some items which did not reach consensus in Round 2 and presented a draft consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives of strategic nurse leadership in public policy. The consensus statement was constructed from items which had achieved consensus in rounds one and two. The Round 3 questionnaire explored reflections on, and reactions to the draft consensus statement. The utility of the consensus statement was further explored in post-Delphi interviews with government nurse leaders as discussed in 4.6.

Figure 4.3 Diagrammatic representation of the Delphi study

4.5.1 Ethical Considerations for Delphi

Potential participants were sent individual emails with a personalised invitation letter (Appendix 9) inviting them to take part together with the Delphi participant information sheet (Appendix 10). A decision was made for the initial approach to be made by the supervisory team due to the seniority of potential participants, in line with the recommended use of a sponsor when accessing elite groups (Scheele, 2002). Potential participants, known in Delphi research as panellists, were asked to indicate their interest by contacting the PhD candidate via the project email address.

Both the invitation letter and participant information sheet explicitly set out the content and time commitment required for participation in the Delphi. As recommended by Shariff (2015a) the researcher's details, along with that of the Director of Studies, were provided on all communication to enable participants to get in contact with any queries or concerns. Strategic nurse leaders who expressed interest were asked to sign and return a consent form (Appendix 11) via email.

Panellists were allocated a numeric code, and all data were anonymised. One key linking the panellists and their numeric code was kept in an encrypted file on a password protected University server. The key file was kept separate from the anonymised data. All anonymised data were stored in encrypted, password protected files. All communication with panellists was made on a one-to-one basis with no group emails sent. The identity of the panellists was known only to the researcher and supervisory team. This is in line with the convention of using a quasi-anonymous approach in Delphi studies where the panellists are known to the researcher, but their individual responses are confidential and anonymous to the other panellists (Meskell *et al.*, 2014). Quasi-anonymity allows the researcher to prepare the individualised feedback between rounds and to follow up non-responding participants whilst maintaining confidentiality. All potentially identifiable information was removed when preparing the subsequent rounds of the Delphi and in the feedback to participants.

The recruitment of panellists from across the world, whilst a merit of the research design, had some ethical considerations. As a number of the panellists held English as an additional language and the research was conducted in English potential participants were asked to self-assess their English language proficiency. It was anticipated that as international strategic nurse leaders they were likely to be experienced in cross-national communication in which English is largely lingua franca and would be able to make their own decision about their suitability to participate. Piloting was undertaken for each phase of the Delphi with particular consideration given to language (see 4.5.5).

4.5.2 Composition of the expert panel

Within Delphi studies, as with other methods, the trustworthiness of the findings is partly predicated on the recruitment of appropriate individuals to the study (Powell, 2003). Delphi studies usually report recruitment of an expert panel of participants. The characteristics of an expert are ill-defined and, arguably, dependent on the purpose of the Delphi (Hasson and Keeney, 2011). A common criterion for Delphi panel recruitment is credible topic expertise (Powell, 2003; Hsu and Sandford, 2007; Jünger *et al.*, 2017). Donohoe and Needham (2009) conceptualise the expertise as including those with academic, professional, or legal remit related to the topic as well as people who are experts by personal experience.

In order to mitigate the potential threat to rigour of an ill-defined expert panel, an operational definition of an expert was developed prior to panel recruitment. The expert group of interest were international strategic nurse leaders who were assumed in this thesis to be both credible topic experts and have the potential to operationalise the findings of the Delphi. Experts in this study were defined as individuals in a formal nurse leadership position which included a national or international remit. Although no minimum length of service was required the demographic data collection captured how long they had held their current appointment together with any prior leadership positions.

4.5.2.1 Delphi panel size

There is no agreed optimal panel size for Delphi studies in the literature and no criteria for assessing adequacy (Akins, Tolson and Cole, 2005; Hsu and Sandford, 2007). In Diamond *et al.*'s (2014) systematic review of the Delphi method, the most common panel size was between 11 and 25, accounting for 40% (40/100) of included studies. A pragmatic decision on sample size was based on factors identified by Akins, Tolson and Cole (2005) including the number of experts in the field of study, time available to complete the study, and administrative implications of managing a large Delphi study. Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn (2007) suggest there is a balance between a manageable panel size and one which is sufficiently large to provide confidence in the findings and minimise group attribution error. Beyond this point Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn (2007) argue that the minimal gains are outweighed by an increasing burden of data analysis.

Whether a homogeneous or heterogeneous sample is required is also considered to impact on the required number of participants (Hsu and Sandford, 2007; Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). Heterogeneous panels are considered to require higher participant numbers than homogeneous panels because it is assumed there will be a broader range of perspectives and expertise requiring exploration (Keeney, Hasson, and McKenna, 2011). Homogeneous panels, where participants have a

similar level of expertise in a particular area, are argued to produce effective findings with smaller sample sizes than heterogeneous samples (Hsu and Sandford, 2007). Homogeneous panels, however, may miss key perspectives on a topic, thereby compromising the trustworthiness of the findings.

Despite the broad homogeneity of strategic nurse leaders as a group there is significant heterogeneity in terms of sector, orientation to policy, cultural and contextual factors. Given the research aim to construct a consensus statement comprising global perspectives, such heterogeneity was valued and, the Delphi panel recruitment plan sought maximum diversity across national income level, region, and sector of nurse leadership.

4.5.2.2 Sampling strategy

Heterogeneity was sought for the Delphi panel in sector of nurse leadership, national income level, country, and world region. Whilst there are risks of selection bias with non-probability sampling, such as convenience or purposive sampling, this was balanced against the challenges of real-world application of probability sampling in the context of a small, elite population of strategic nurse leaders. National income levels were defined as per the World Bank classification for 2015, the year in which data collection took place. The WHO (2022) regions were used to understand geographical dispersion. As described earlier, to be eligible to participate in the study individuals were required to be nurse leaders in their country with a strategic national or international remit in their current role. All participants had to be fluent in the English language, computer literate and have access to the internet. It is noted that the prerequisite of an internet connection may have biased the sample towards participants with access to more resources (Arksey and Knight, 1999). Further, conducting the study in English will also have limited the participation from regions such as South America where Spanish is the dominant language. This is reflected in the panel characteristics as set out in 6.2. As discussed in 4.3.1 translation into multiple languages would have introduced additional rigour considerations and was beyond the resources available to the study.

4.5.2.3 Delphi Recruitment

Potential participants were identified through the International Council of Nurses and WHO Collaborating Centres. Similar to the interview procedure, the initial approach to potential participants was made by members of the supervisory team with an invitation letter (Appendix 9) and participant information sheet (Appendix 10). This was in recognition of the seniority of potential participants, who were all strategic nurse leaders, and the known challenges of online security and firewalls. It was also supported by Scheele (2002) who recommended the use of a high-level sponsor to aid recruitment of potential Delphi participants. Potential participants interested in learning more

about the study were asked to contact the PhD candidate via the project email address. Interested participants were sent a consent form via email, attached as a Microsoft Word document (Appendix 11).

The burden of the iterative Delphi process is recognised in the literature to contribute to panellist attrition (de Meyrick, 2003). It was important, therefore, to make potential panellists aware of the time commitment associated with participation and to give sufficient information in relation to the frequency of contact, duration of the study and anticipated length of completion for each questionnaire. A preliminary schedule of three questionnaires over a 12-week period was outlined in the initial invitation letter and participant information sheet in order to allow potential panellists to assess their availability to complete the process. They were also informed that each Delphi questionnaire would take a maximum of 30 minutes to complete. The length of questionnaires aligned with recommendations for completion times of 20 to 30 minutes (Rodríguez-Teruel and Daloz, 2018; Belton *et al.*, 2019) to minimise non-response and optimise the quality of answers provided.

4.5.3 Defining Consensus

Measurement of consensus is contentious with a range of approaches reported in the literature (von der Gracht, 2012; de Loë *et al.*, 2016; Lange *et al.*, 2020). Consensus is most commonly measured by calculation of the percentage agreement or disagreement with a statement, together with a mean or median score plus a measure of distribution (Diamond *et al.*, 2014; Jünger *et al.*, 2017). In addition to agreement and central tendency stability of responses between rounds is proposed by some authors as a criterion for deciding when to stop the Delphi (Linstone and Turoff, 2011; von der Gracht, 2012). In common with other methodological considerations in Delphi research, the application of stability assessment is contested (Trevelyan and Robinson, 2015).

This Delphi adopted the guidance of Rayens and Hahn (2000) to omit items as they reached consensus to keep the questionnaire length manageable and minimise panel attrition. It was also considered that as the statements were being judged for agreement rather than ranking it was less important that items which achieved consensus were retained in each round. Removal of items as they reached consensus did, however, mean that repeated measurement of the stability of items after they achieved consensus was not possible. The stability of individual panellist responses to statements retested in rounds 2 and 3 were assessed for interest post-hoc using the method detailed in Manzano-García and Ayala (2017) and reported in 6.19. In their method Manzano-García and Ayala (2017) assessed the stability of each individual panellist by calculating the percentage of items where their response didn't change between the second and third round. They then calculated

the mean percentage stability giving an understanding of the stability of the panel responses between rounds. The epistemological connotations of measuring stability were also considered. The tenet of social constructionism of knowledge as socially constructed, implies that views of individuals and the group may change as their interaction progresses throughout the study. The Delphi itself is an iterative, consensus building method by nature, and therefore it is arguable that rigidity in perspectives is neither sought nor desirable. As such stability was assessed for interest, rather than for informing decisions about ending the Delphi.

In terms of percentage agreement as a measure of consensus, there is no consistency in the literature around the level at which consensus should be set, with published cut-offs of between 51-100% consensus (von der Gracht, 2012; Diamond *et al.*, 2014). Setting the level of consensus too high would have risked Rennie's (1981) criticism of Delphi studies achieving consensus only to the level of common generalities. Too low a cut off could threaten the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings. A middle ground was found in the influential Robert's Rules of Order (Robert *et al.*, 2011) which requires a two-thirds majority to pass parliamentary decisions. Robert *et al.*, (2011, p401) recommend the use of a supermajority as "a compromise between the rights of the individual and the rights of the assembly". Such acknowledgment of the interaction between the individual and the whole also resonates with the social constructionist tenet of knowledge as being sustained by social process. The operationalisation of the two-thirds vote in this Delphi meant that the agreement or disagreement of 67% or more of the responding panellists was considered to be one indication of consensus.

In order to understand the spread of perspectives for each statement a measure of dispersion was also required (von der Gracht, 2012). As the data were not normally distributed the median score for each statement was calculated and presented to panellists along with interquartile range as the measure of dispersion. In the context of a four-point Likert scale (discussed further in 4.5.6.2), an interquartile range of less than or equal to one was adopted as per the recommendations of Rayens and Hahn (2000). An interquartile range of less than or equal to one means that at least 50% of all opinions are within one point on the Likert scale.

The threshold above which consensus is considered to have been achieved has significant implications for Delphi findings. To prevent unregulated post-hoc analysis and potential for selective reporting bias, consensus in this study was defined a priori, in line with literature recommendations for promotion of rigour (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011; Jünger *et al.*, 2017; Grant, Booth and Khodyakov, 2018).

4.5.4 Delphi administration

All participants were allocated a numeric identification code which was attached to each Delphi round. This allowed tracking of responses and follow up of late submissions whilst ensuring data was de-identified at source. The identification coding system also facilitated the management of provision of individualised feedback between rounds. Individualised feedback included the participant's scores for each statement as well the aggregated group median score, interquartile range, percentage agreement, and disagreement. A single master code sheet linking the anonymised participant codes and the participant personal information was kept in a password-protected file on a password protected university server.

Delphi administration is complex and requires good planning (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011). A spreadsheet database was created which tracked the Delphi for each anonymised participant in relation to distribution of rounds, receiving responses and sending of reminders. It also captured the progress with construction of the personalised questionnaires for Rounds 2 and 3 where participant individual scores were included along with the group median. Maintaining this database ensured seamless progress with data collection. All aspects of the Delphi were designed and delivered by the PhD candidate.

Each round of the Delphi comprised a questionnaire which was attached to an email as an editable Microsoft Word form. A completely online platform was considered however, the stability of each participant's internet connection could not be guaranteed. Therefore, to minimise technological barriers to participation, the email attachment format was used. On two occasions a participant had technical problems with questionnaire completion. This was rectified by providing the Microsoft Word document with the additional functionality, such as drop-down boxes, removed. Identical descriptors were added to provide consistency.

4.5.5 Pilot testing the Delphi Questionnaire

Four panellists, who were not included in the main sample, were recruited to pilot each Delphi questionnaire, instructions and associated materials including the consent form, invitation letter and participant information sheet. The panellists were asked to complete and return each pilot questionnaire as per the instructions. They also provided feedback and recommendations on specific aspects of the questionnaires and associated material including on the use of language, clarity of instructions and statements, and physical ease of completion of the questionnaire. The pilot data was not included as part of the final sample or data analysis.

The four pilot panellists comprised an international nursing dean with English as an additional language, a Chief Executive Officer of a national regulatory body, a researcher, and a senior nursing

academic. The presence on the test panel of a nurse leader with English as an additional language was particularly valuable in relation to the clarity of wording for statements and instructions. Their input helped strengthen the likelihood that the intending meaning was explicit and comprehensible to the participants. For example, the international panellist highlighted that the phrase “registered nurse” did not equate to qualified nurse in their context. Use of the word registration in statements relating to qualified nurses was therefore removed from the Delphi in an effort to avoid confusing nomenclature.

4.5.6 Delphi Round 1: questionnaire development

A structured approach was taken to the Delphi first round to test some of the key ideas derived from the literature and pre-Delphi interviews. Although a structured approach was taken, there were also open-ended questions to allow panellists the opportunity to add further perspectives and raise pertinent issues not uncovered during the literature review or pre-Delphi interviews. The structured approach also benefited from shortening the Delphi process which is theorised to enhance panel retention whilst also mitigating Linstone’s (2002) caution to avoid the participants feeling as if they are having to educate the researcher on basic perspectives within the field.

The Round one questionnaire (Appendix 8) comprised three sections. The first covered demographic information, the second presented statements for the panellist to rate their level of agreement, and the third solicited responses to two open-ended questions. The statements together with the open questions were designed to contribute to the first research aim of investigating the approaches, challenges, and contribution of strategic nurse leaders in public policy. Each statement in Round 1 and each new statement in subsequent rounds was allocated a unique identifier (ID) to enable tracking of the statements through the rounds.

4.5.6.1 Demographics

The demographic variables of interest included: gender, nation of employment, sector of current leadership role, length of service in current role and, sector of previous leadership roles. Self-assessed gender was included in recognition of the historic link between nursing and women’s work and its implications for the status and development of nursing (Timmons, Evans and Nair, 2016). It was therefore of interest to note the gender distribution of the panellists.

Establishing the geographical distribution of the panel was important since the study sought to elicit global perspectives. There is known variation in the position of nursing internationally (World Health Organisation, 2020) and Culturally Endorsed Leadership Theory (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014) supported the assumption that some leadership approaches and perspectives can be culturally contingent.

It was anticipated that the priorities and position of nurse leaders in relation to policy influence would vary across sectors of nursing leadership as well as by geography. To reflect this diversity panellists were sought from each of five key sectors which include elite roles with remits at a national or international level: education, government, regulation, trade unions and professional associations. In their integrative review Benton *et al.* (2017) distinguish between the primary purposes of nursing regulators, trade unions, and professional associations. For example, the regulator has a responsibility to protect the public, trade unions provide professional advocacy, and professional associations have a remit to develop the profession (Benton, *et al.*, 2017). Some countries have combined professional associations and trade unions which can complicate understanding of roles and responsibilities in policy influence (MacDonald, *et al.*, 2012).

Understanding the length of service and prior appointments provided an opportunity to understand the level of experience of the panellist as well as provide an insight into the tenure of such high-level roles.

4.5.6.2 Round 1 Statement and Scale Development

Following the demographic information, the questionnaire presented 46 statements in two sections: the policy influence of nursing and the development of strategic nurse leadership. The statements were constructed both from the findings of the literature review presented in Chapter two and from the framework analysis of the pre-Delphi interviews. Each statement in each round was allocated a unique identifier (ID). The application of an ID enabled easier analysis and improved the transparency of reporting the findings.

Culturally Endorsed Leadership theory (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014) together with social constructionism framed the questionnaire development from the perspective of curiosity of the international variation in perspectives of strategic nurse leaders and policy influence. Exploring the international variation, drawing on the findings of the integrative review (Chapter 2) and pre-Delphi interviews (Chapter 5) the first-round questionnaire sought to understand the approaches and challenges of policy influence from the perspectives of legitimate and expert bases of power (French and Raven, 1959). In line with the conventions of a Policy Delphi (Rayens and Hahn, 2000) the study valued both convergence and divergence in the findings.

The panellists were asked to rate their level of agreement with each statement on a four-point Likert scale. The use of a four-point Likert scale removed the usual neutral option making it a forced choice approach. There is no agreement within the Delphi literature about the optimal number of response points for the Likert scale, nor the presence of a midpoint (Trevelyan and Robinson, 2015; de Loë *et al.*, 2016). Although Chyung *et al.* (2017) argue that the absence of a midpoint risks biasing findings

by not allowing a legitimate neutral option, Nadler, Weston and Voyles (2015) recommend its removal to help mitigate social desirability bias. Nadler and colleagues (2015) also report findings that participant interpretation of the meaning of the midpoint varies and represents a threat to the credibility of the findings. Within the Delphi literature a number of authors (Rayens and Hahn, 2000; Turoff, 2002; Meskell *et al.*, 2014), argue for the removal of the midpoint, particularly in Policy Delphi, to create the conditions for panellists to have to take a position rather than return a neutral opinion.

A range of Likert-like scales have been used for rating Delphi statements including feasibility, desirability, importance, and confidence (Rayens and Hahn, 2000; Meskell *et al.*, 2014). The international nature of this study meant that such measures would be highly context bound and dependent on existing health care delivery models. Additionally, the clarity of content and instructions was essential to the participation of panellists with English as an additional language. It was therefore decided that panellists would be requested to rate one dimension only: their agreement with the statement. Adoption of agreement as the rating scale allowed identification of consensus and divergence in key topics within this relatively under researched area. Each point on the Likert scale was presented as words (e.g., strongly agree, agree) rather than numbers to minimise misunderstanding of the scale and reduce cognitive load (Weijters, Cabooter and Schillewaert, 2010). Consistent use of language to describe the choices in rating was considered to be particularly beneficial for panellists with English as an additional language.

4.5.6.3 Open ended question development

Panellists were asked to list up to five key barriers and facilitators which they considered to impact on the ability of nurses to make an effective leadership contribution to policy. Limiting the number of responses in this section was recommended by Keeney, Hasson and McKenna's (2006) to keep the volume of responses manageable and to require panellists to identify priority issues. There was also a free text box where panellists were encouraged to submit any additional perspectives that had not already been covered. Including open ended questions is considered by Keeney, Hasson and McKenna (2006) as good practice in modified Delphi studies as a compromise between a fully structured round one which could introduce ideas to panellists that wouldn't have otherwise been raised or given prominence and an unstructured round one, argued to be a threat to rigour due to unstructured polling (Day and Bobeva, 2005). Providing the open-ended questions ensured that issues or perspectives not covered in either the empirical literature or pre-Delphi interviews were heard.

4.5.7 Delphi Round 1: data collection

Following piloting and refinement (detailed in 4.5.5), the Round 1 questionnaire was sent out to participants as a Microsoft Word email attachment. The questionnaire was accompanied by a covering letter (Appendix 12) which included completion instructions, the response date and provided an approximate timeline of the subsequent questionnaires. The covering letter was personalised to help establish a rapport, recommended by Keeney, Hasson and McKenna (2011) as a method of minimising attrition, a recognised challenge in Delphi studies (Bloor *et al.*, 2015; Belton *et al.*, 2019).

It was appreciated that the panellists, as elite leaders, had very high workloads and busy email inboxes. As such, panellists who had not returned their questionnaire by the two week return date were contacted via email to invite them to respond. The personalised reminder contained all the required documentation for the Delphi round and, as per Keeney, Hasson and McKenna's (2011) recommendation, emphasised that their contribution to the research was highly valued. Reminder emails increased response rates in each of the three Delphi rounds. As per the conventions of a Policy Delphi (Brown 2007) every consenting panellist was sent every Delphi round regardless of whether they had participated in the preceding round. The approach of sending all panellists all rounds was also argued by Boel *et al.* (2021) to promote preservation of the originally recruited panel.

4.5.8 Data analysis Round 1

4.5.8.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

Demographic data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Percentage agreement was calculated for each statement together with the median Likert score and interquartile range. The denominator for calculation of percentage agreement with each item statement was the number of panellists who completed each item. Calculations therefore took account of missing data and reported this transparently.

4.5.8.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

Answers to the open-ended questions for each round were content analysed using an adaptation of Burnard's (1991) framework (figure 4.4) as recommended by Keeney, Hasson and McKenna (2011). Content analysis and thematic analysis have both been reported in in Policy Delphi studies (de Loë *et al.*, 2016). The epistemological flexibility of content analysis (Graneheim, Lindgren and Lundman, 2017) is well suited to Delphi studies. It was important for credibility of the findings to ensure that the diversity of participant responses was preserved and that perspectives which only appeared once or twice were included in the statements presented to the panel in Round 2.

Figure 4.4 Process of content analysis for qualitative Delphi data (adapted from Burnard, 1991)

The transformation of the open responses of barriers and facilitators to policy influence into statements for consideration in Round 2 required a reflexive approach which went back and forth between the raw data and new statements.

4.5.8.3 Between Round Feedback

The process for constructing the between round feedback shared with the panel following Round 1 and Round 2 was identical. The Round 1 feedback document (Appendix 13) was constructed alongside the Round 2 questionnaire (Appendix 14). It was important that the between round feedback was user-friendly and did not require any advanced statistical knowledge (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006). The between-round feedback detailed the statements which had achieved consensus, including their median Likert score and interquartile range (IQR). A descriptive interpretation of IQR was also included for clarity.

4.5.9 Delphi Round 2: questionnaire development

The Round 2 questionnaire included Round 1 statements that had not achieved consensus. These statements had not achieved the requirement of both at least 67% panellists holding the same opinion, which may be agreement or disagreement with the statement and an IQR of less than or equal to one. Each statement was presented with the panelist's individual Round 1 Likert score plus the panel's median Likert score and IQR (Figure 4.5).

Figure 4.5 Example of Delphi Round 2 structure

Statement	My Round 2 Answer	My Round 1 Answer	Median	IQR
<i>Statement</i>	Choose an item.	Agree	Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			

Panelists were asked to review their original score and revise it if they wished. They were encouraged to provide qualitative comments about their chosen rating to help illustrate their reasoning for either changing or retaining their original rating. Providing the facility for qualitative comment is recommended in Delphi studies for developing understanding of both the underlying perspective itself and uncovering divergence in perspectives between individuals who hold the same view (de Loë *et al.*, 2016).

Items which achieved consensus in Round 1 were not retested in subsequent rounds. This decision was made on the basis of Keeney, Hasson and McKenna's (2011) position that panel retention would be improved if subsequent questionnaires were condensed, minimising the time burden for participants. Dropping items during the Delphi was not critiqued in the Delphi methodological systematic reviews of Diamond *et al.*, 2014 or Jünger *et al.*, 2017, other than the need to transparently report. The elimination of items from future rounds would have been problematic if the Delphi had aimed to rank the statements or had a central focus on stability (previously discussed in 4.5.3), but neither was required for the purpose of this study.

New statements constructed from the analysis of responses to the Round 1 open-ended questions were also included in the Round 2 questionnaire where they offered a new perspective or angle on the topic. The final section of the Round 2 questionnaire was an open question seeking the panellists' perspectives about what the key policy focus of nursing should be. This question was constructed to explore an area of divergence observed in the Round 1 responses (discussed further in 6.14).

4.5.10 Delphi Round 2: data collection

In Round 2 the panelists were individually sent an email with three attachments: the Round 1 feedback document (Appendix 13) and the individualised Round 2 data collection questionnaire (Appendix 14) together with a personalised covering letter (Appendix 12). As per the process for Round 1 (4.5.7), a personalised email reminder was sent to panellists who had not returned their questionnaire by the deadline to encourage response rates.

4.5.11 Delphi Round 2: data analysis

The Likert scores for each statement were analysed as previously described in Round 1 (4.5.8). The qualitative responses to the open-ended question around the perceptions of policy focus for nursing were content analysed using the same process as detailed in 4.5.8.2. A between round feedback document (Appendix 15) presenting the statements which had reached consensus in Round 2 was constructed and sent to each panellist.

4.5.12 Delphi Round 3: consensus statement and questionnaire development

In preparation for Round 3 a draft consensus statement of perspectives on nurse leadership in public policy (presented in 6.15.1) was constructed from items which reached consensus in Round 1 or 2. For brevity and coherence the statement was not formulated as a list. The purpose of synthesising the statements which had achieved consensus into a cohesive statement was to provide the strategic nurse leaders with an opportunity to reflect on their perspectives on nursing policy influence as a whole, rather than as discrete points. The reflexivity of the researcher was particularly important in statement construction to acknowledge the influence of their perspective and decisions on the statement. As illustrated in figure 4.6, which details the process by which the statement was drafted, input was sought from the supervisory team and topic expert. The final statement was mapped back to the original statements which had achieved consensus in earlier rounds, to check the confirmability of the statement. The draft statement was designed to provoke further discussion in Round 3.

Figure 4.6 Flow diagram of consensus statement development

The Round 3 questionnaire (Appendix 16) presented the draft consensus statement together with a combination of open and closed questions relating to it. The questions explored perceptions of the content, language, and potential utility of the statement. It also asked explicitly if the statement reflected the views of the individual strategic nurse leader and what they perceived to be missing from the statement.

Several statements which had not reached consensus at the end of Round 2 were not retested in Round 3 following discussion with the supervisory team and a topic expert. Aside from minimising unnecessary repetition there were two reasons for not retesting statements in Round 3: polarisation and individual country or leader experience. Firstly, there were statements where the underlying divergence was persistent and had been explored in the previous two rounds. It was considered unlikely that an item was going to reach consensus after demonstrating polarisation across two rounds. It was not the aim of the study to force consensus and statements demonstrating persistent divergence demonstrated the diversity of experiences within the panel. The other key reason for exclusion was that some statements clearly referred to individual country or leader experiences which would be unlikely to change over the duration of the Delphi. As von der Gracht (2012) observes, it is the process of consideration rather than the achievement of consensus which results in a clearer understanding of the perspectives on a topic.

4.5.13 Delphi Round 3: Data analysis

The statements presented for rating in Round 3 were analysed as in previous rounds (4.5.8). Descriptive statistics were completed on the quantitative data and content analysis was undertaken on the qualitative responses from Round 3 as previously described in 4.5.7.

4.6 Post-Delphi interviews

A criticism of Delphi rigour is a question over the broader application of the findings (de Meyrick, 2003). Although verification of Delphi findings is not routinely undertaken in the published literature (Hasson and Keeney, 2011) it was considered that doing so would promote rigour through enhancing the trustworthiness of the findings, particularly the dimensions of credibility and transferability. The purpose of the post-Delphi phase of the research was to explore the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement with strategic nurse leaders who had not participated in the Delphi study.

Survey research was an option for post-Delphi data collection and could have accessed a larger sample of strategic nurse leaders. It would have been limited, however, in its ability to facilitate a contextualised exploration of the potential use of the draft consensus statement, which was important to enhancing the trustworthiness of the findings. A qualitative approach was best suited to such a purpose. The ability of semi-structured interviews to yield rich data made it a favourable method for exploring the Delphi findings with an international sample.

4.6.1 Post-Delphi interviews: Sampling and recruitment

The post-Delphi interviews were limited to strategic nurse leaders in government in positions including GCNO. Broader cross-sector recruitment, for example including professional nursing association leaders, would have provided a fuller understanding of the resonance and potential utility of the consensus statement, however it would have also required a larger sample in order to meaningfully analyse the heterogeneity of perspectives. Restricting the sample to one sector of strategic nurse leaders allowed a deeper analysis of the resonance and utility of the draft consensus statement. The policy remit of government nurse leaders, and their unique position in straddling government and the profession was considered to offer unique insights which could support the post-Delphi interview purpose of promoting the rigour of the Delphi findings.

The optimal number of interviews in qualitative analysis is debated in the literature with the conclusion being that there is no one equation which provides the 'correct' answer (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006; Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). In a recent systematic review Hennink and Kaiser (2022) observed that sample sizes of 9-17 interviews provided indications of saturation. They did however note that this was more likely in studies with a small scope and homogeneous population.

A key consideration for the sample size in this study was the total population of nurses in government. It was noted that not all countries have a governmental position for nurses (WHO, 2020), and following a review of the literature and discussion with researchers experienced in recruiting strategic nurse leaders it was decided that a sample of 8-12 participants would be sought.

Recruitment was facilitated by the WHO which provided names and contact details for their network of government nurse contacts. The researcher individually invited government nurses to participate in the research via email. The invitations were spread across world regions and national income levels with an aim to maximise diversity of respondents. The researcher then completed recruitment as per the process described in 4.6.1. As recommended by Delaney (2007) recruitment was personalised and emphasised the value of their expertise and potential contribution to the research.

A convenience sample of government nurses from a range of countries and income levels were recruited. The use of the term 'government nurse leader' was deliberately more inclusive to protect against bias towards the subset of countries with GCNOs. To be eligible for inclusion as a participant in the study government nurse leaders required fluency in the English language, computer literacy, and an internet connection. One possible implication of the inclusion criteria was a lack of representation in the dataset from regions where English is not routinely spoken as an additional language, such as South America. Government nurse leaders who were members of the original Delphi panel were not invited to take part in the post-Delphi interviews. This exclusion allowed the government nurse leaders to explore the consensus statement unencumbered by any pre-conceptions or experience which they might have acquired by being part of the Delphi consensus building process.

4.6.2 Ethical Considerations for post-Delphi interviews

Potential participants were sent an invitation letter (Appendix 17) and participant information sheet (Appendix 18) via email. Individuals who expressed interest in taking part were asked to complete and return a consent form (Appendix 19) and state whether they would prefer a Skype or telephone interview. Audiovisual interviews would have benefited from the ability to be able to draw on non-verbal cues from body language as well as cues relating to the silence and intonation available in telephone calls (Johnson, Scheitle, and Ecklund, 2021). It was anticipated that there would be variation in access to an internet connection sufficient to support audiovisual calls, hence offering the telephone option.

Data were anonymised at point of transcription and each participant was allocated an anonymous identification number. One copy of the anonymisation master sheet linking the participant to their code was stored separately to the data, in a password protected file on a password protected university server.

4.6.3 Post-Delphi interviews: Data collection

Prior to data collection a briefing paper (Appendix 20) was developed and shared with the participants. The briefing paper comprised the draft consensus statement and an outline of the interview guide. To help them prepare, the participants were sent the briefing paper, a week in advance, as suggested by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009). This preparatory time was designed to enable reflection on the statement prior to the interview, and to support preparation of participants with English as an additional language. The interview guide was designed to explore the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement which was constructed during the Delphi study. The interview guide was based on a plan for a thirty-minute interview, recommended by Gillham (2005) as the maximum duration of a telephone interview. Additionally, the time of elite individuals is often pressed (Green and Thorogood, 2018) and planning for a tight interview from the outset would maximise the opportunity for recruitment. The interviews were designed to get a sense of how the consensus statement constructed during the Delphi resonated with a separate group of strategic leaders. Smith, Flowers and Larkin's (2009) recommendation of six to ten questions for 45-90 minutes of discussion informed the design of the interview schedule. As such the schedule comprised four broad questions relating to the draft consensus statement and its potential interaction with the professional context of the participant. It also gathered demographic data and offered an opportunity to add any additional information. All interviews were conducted by the PhD candidate.

As recommended by Legard, Keegan and Ward (2003) the interview opened with straightforward questions, including participant demographics, to help the participant and researcher settle into the interview before focusing on the draft consensus statement. Prompts for probing such as "Can you tell me a little more about [insert topic point just covered]?" were added to the interview guide to support elicitation of richer data in the moment. The interview topic guide was reviewed and refinements to sequencing and wording were made following discussion with the supervisory team.

One rehearsal interview was undertaken with a strategic nurse leader who did not form part of the final sample. This interview offered an opportunity to test the participant information sheet, consent form, draft consensus statement and interview schedule. The clarity of wording across the information, instructions and interview questions were reviewed and refined. As recommended by

Liu (2018) the rehearsal interview enabled critical consideration of the practicalities of interviewing an elite nurse leader including use of audio recording equipment. The participant taking part in the rehearsal interview was sent the consensus statement and interview schedule in advance of the interview. The interview itself was conducted via Skype, lasted 36 minutes, was audio recorded and transcribed verbatim. Minor refinements to the flow and wording of the interview schedule were made on the basis of the rehearsal interview.

Participants chose the mode of interview along with the date and time of their preference. Time zones were accommodated, and the researcher accepted the first interview slot suggested by each participant. As recommended by Van Audenhove and Donders (2019) a reflexive approach was taken during the interviews with short field notes on the researcher's perception of how well rapport had been established, where particular questions were maybe more or less fully discussed. The interview guide (included in the briefing paper in Appendix 20) was used to help structure the interview, but the PhD candidate adopted Van Audenhove and Donders (2019) guidance on researching elites, taking a flexible approach to the order of interview questions. Where the participant gave particularly full answers, sometimes these strayed into the territory of subsequent questions. The participant was not interrupted and any questions which had been covered in previous answers were adapted or omitted. As described earlier probes were employed to help encourage, deepen, and clarify responses. During the interview credibility was enhanced through checking and clarifying understanding by summarising key points and checking that they reflected the participant's intended meaning. At the end time was taken to ask the participants if there was anything they would like to add that had not otherwise been covered. Where a response was given but the question wasn't answered, the interview moved on to a different question and later returned to the outstanding question in a different way as per Harvey's (2011) recommendation for deploying the interview schedule in elite interviews.

During the interview the PhD candidate was mindful to keep to the 30 minutes which had been agreed with the participants. Where interviews ran over, time was discussed with the participant as the interview approached the 30-minute cut off to give participants an opportunity to end the interview if they had other diary commitments. At the end of each interview the PhD candidate thanked the interviewee and reiterated the plan for data analysis and write up. Participants were offered a transcript of their interview. No participant requested this.

4.6.4 Post-Delphi interviews: Data analysis

The data were transcribed verbatim and analysed using framework analysis as per the process outlined in section 4.4.4. Member checking, whilst often advocated, was not undertaken in either the pre- or post-Delphi interviews because of the lack of evidence for its benefit in enhancing rigour (Thomas, 2016). Morse (2015) raised concerns around the use of member checking and the potential dilemmas for researchers if individual participants disagreed with the overall analysis. As each individual participant would only know the content of their own interview asking them to review analysis which covers all the interviews is arguably of limited use. Further, while sending each participant a copy of their interview transcript may have confirmed the credibility of the raw data it cannot provide assurance about the rigour of the analysis process (Birt *et al.* 2016). Finally, it was considered that member checking would increase the burden of participation for an elite group with limited time.

4.7 Promotion of Rigour

A three part framework was constructed to support promotion of rigour across the study using trustworthiness criteria (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), dimensions of reflexive awareness (Green and Thorogood, 2018), and authenticity criteria (Guba and Lincoln, 1989).

4.7.1 Trustworthiness Criteria

The trustworthiness and authenticity considerations for the study was discussed in detail in 3.6 and 3.7 and addressed at pertinent points throughout this chapter. The key measures used for promotion of rigour are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Trustworthiness Criteria

	Delphi	Pre-Delphi interviews	post-Delphi interviews
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Between-round feedback • Iterative and prolonged engagement • Opportunity to revise judgements • Reflexive journal • Triangulation with post-Delphi interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer debriefing of analysis. • Audit trail • Reflexive journal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion of analysis with other researchers • Audit trail • Reflexive journal
Dependability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to review and revise judgements • Between round feedback including individual member checking • Post-Delphi interviews • Reflexive journal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of framework analysis • Audit trail • Reflexive journal • Delphi study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audit trail • Reflexive journal
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purposively sampled, cross sector, international, heterogeneous panel • Post-Delphi interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delphi study • Thick description of methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triangulating with Delphi findings • Thick description of methods
Confirmability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For each of Delphi, pre-Delphi, and post-Delphi interviews: • Audit trail including thick description of analysis and methodological decisions. • Peer debriefing of analysis with other researchers. • Reflexive journal and field notes 		

Reflexivity is an integral contributor to rigour (Berger, 2015) and as such is discussed next followed by a mapping of how the authenticity criteria were embodied with the research (4.7.3).

4.7.2 Reflexivity

This study takes the social constructionist position that the researcher is not value neutral in the research process (Koro-Ljungberg, 2008; Losantos *et al.*, 2016). Reflexivity requires the researcher to position themselves within the research and unpack the impact they have on the research process and product (Olmos-Vega *et al.*, 2023). Given the international nature of this study it was crucial for the researcher to explore her own assumptions about the topic and anticipated differences across sectors and nations. Indeed, developing an awareness of how the culture, professional background and gender of the researcher shaped their position on the topic was important in the design and execution of data collection and analysis and featured frequently in the reflexive journal and field notes.

As discussed in 3.6.4 Green and Thorogood's (2018) dimensions of reflexive awareness structured the reflexive process. Applying the dimensions developed the researcher's ability to critically consider the implications of their position in the research on its process and product. The operationalisation of the four dimensions: methodological openness, theoretical openness, awareness of social setting of the research and awareness of the wider social context, are discussed briefly here.

Methodological and theoretical openness were facilitated through both supervision and a reflexive journal. The reflexive journal was maintained as part of the audit trail which was constructed over the course of the study. The journal exposed the researcher's assumptions, feelings, and contribution during the research process. During the interview data collection, the journal was used before and after each interview. It captured anticipatory assumptions, concerns, and reactions to participant responses. The reflexive journal was used also during data analysis and provided a space for the researcher to consider how she was shaping the process of analysis and ensure that the analysis was consistently grounded in the data. Theoretical openness and the influence of theoretical decisions on the data collection and analysis of the study is discussed further in 8.9.4.

In line with a social constructionist perspective, the social setting of the research was assumed to interact with both the process and product of the research. For example, during the post-Delphi interviews, the researcher perceived a power imbalance between her, as an outsider to strategic nurse leadership, and the participants, all strategic nurse leaders of international standing. Although interviewers are often considered to be more powerful than interviewees (Wang and Yan, 2012), the reflexive journal in this study reflects the researcher's perception of not being a peer of the participants and how this had the potential to reduce confidence in asking deeper probing questions in the interviews.

In addition to the sense of being an outsider in the research because of not being a strategic nurse leader, the researcher was also aware that conducting an international research study in English and being a Caucasian citizen of a high-income economy would have an impact on the product of the research. The potential impact of using English as the lingua franca is explored further in 4.3.1. The researcher was particularly mindful of the influence of their own cultural background and undertook activities, for example noting decisions made in the data analysis process of the Delphi to consider them in relation to the original views of the panellists.

4.7.3 Authenticity Criteria

As discussed in 3.6.5 Guba and Lincoln's (1989) authenticity criteria were used to explore the extent to which participation in the study alters the perspectives and understanding of participants. Johnson and Rasulova (2016) posit that the authenticity criteria can be characterised as a negotiation between the participants and the research, each influencing the other, which resonates well with social constructionism, as well as the iterative nature of the Delphi and its interaction between the individual and whole. Table 4.2 reviews each of the authenticity criteria, both as originally named by Guba and Lincoln (1989) and renamed by Nolan *et al.* (2003) and considers some of the strategies used within this thesis to strengthen the authenticity of the inquiry.

Table 4.2 Authenticity Criteria

Authenticity Criteria	Strategies used in this study
Fairness (Guba and Lincoln 1989) Equal Access (Nolan <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	Planning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delphi recruitment aimed for maximum diversity in sector, world region, and national income level. • All time zones accommodated for data collection for pre-Delphi and post-Delphi. Process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iterative approach of the study from pre-Delphi to post-Delphi to allow uncovering of divergence. • Multiple opportunities for Delphi panellists to amend or supplement their judgments. • Less frequently voiced or divergent perspectives included in every stage e.g. single qualitative responses represented in Delphi rounds for ranking alongside more frequently expressed views. Product: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity for Delphi panellists to comment on draft consensus statement. • Primacy will be given to Open Access publication of findings
Ontological authenticity (Guba and Lincoln, 1989) Enhancing Awareness of Self (Nolan <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iterative nature of Delphi • Between round feedback of individual and group judgements and option to revise or maintain position. • Exploring the resonance of the draft consensus statement with Delphi panellists in Round 3 • Focus in post-Delphi interviews about how the draft consensus statement linked to their own priorities for policy influence.
Educative authenticity (Guba and Lincoln, 1989) Enhancing Awareness of Others (Nolan <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Between round feedback during Delphi giving insight into the perspectives of other international strategic nurse leaders. • Exposure to perspectives from other sectors, cultures, countries, and resource levels without the power dynamics associated with face-to-face discussion. • Post-Delphi interview exploration of the content of the draft Delphi consensus statement
Catalytic authenticity (Guba and Lincoln, 1989) Encouraging action (Nolan <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delphi Round 3 question about how, if at all, could panellists imagine using the draft consensus statement in their work. • Post-Delphi interview question around which parts of the draft Delphi consensus statement are a priority for action for the participant.
Tactical Authenticity (Guba and Lincoln, 1989) Enabling Action (Nolan <i>et al.</i> , 2003)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction and negotiation of the draft consensus statement during the course of the Delphi • Barriers and facilitators to policy influence identified by Delphi panellists. • Negotiation of content and positioning of draft consensus statement in post-Delphi interviews • Post-Delphi interview schedule inclusion of consideration of individual priorities based on the issues raised in the draft consensus statement.

4.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter has detailed the key procedures undertaken for ethical and rigorous conduct of each of the three phases of the study: pre-Delphi, Delphi, and post-Delphi. Approaches to support successful recruitment and research of strategic nurse leader 'elites' were outlined. The rigour of the study's approach to addressing the research aims was described, in part through the application of trustworthiness and authenticity criteria. The following three chapters present the study findings in chronological order of the research design.

Chapter 5: Pre-Delphi Interview Findings

This chapter reports the findings from the pre-Delphi interviews with strategic nurse leaders. The main purpose of these semi-structured interviews was to generate data to inform the first round of the Delphi in addition to the review of published literature.

A convenience sample of eight key informants, recruited as described in 4.4.2. Each individual interview was conducted by telephone and audio recorded. All interviews, except one were transcribed as the audio recording equipment failed to record for participant 6. Seven transcripts and the detailed field notes from participant 6 were subject to framework analysis. The interviews were transcribed by a professional transcribing service for efficiency. To support immersion in the data, and as per the analysis plan detailed in 4.4.4.1 the PhD candidate read each transcript in full before starting to take analytical notes on the second full read of all transcripts.

This chapter opens with a description of the characteristics of the participants. The findings are then structured around the three areas of focus from the framework analysis: the policy contribution of strategic nurse leaders, leadership approaches and attributes of strategic nurse leaders in policy, finishing with challenges and opportunities in policy engagement.

5.1 Characteristics of the pre-Delphi interview participants

The sample comprised seven women and one man. The participants held a range of strategic leadership roles including GCNO, Registrar of the National Nursing Council and President of the professional nursing association. Two participants held combined roles, e.g., president of the professional nursing association and associate professor in education. As such, Table 5.1 which sets out the distribution of sector representation has 10 entries rather than 8.

Table 5.1 Sector of leadership role

Sector	Single sector roles (n=6)	Dual sector roles (n=2)
Education (e.g. Dean of Higher Education Nursing Faculty)	1	1
Government (e.g. Government Chief Nursing Officer)	3	1
Professional Nursing Association (e.g. President of the Professional Nursing Association)	0	1
Health Providing Organisation (e.g. nurse director)	1	0
Professional Regulation (e.g. Registrar for the National Nursing Council)	1	1
Other: Independent consultant	1	

When considering their roles in the preceding ten years, all of the participants reported holding roles with national or international responsibilities. Interestingly there was evidence of career change across sectors of leadership for seven out of the eight participants. Two participants were past presidents of their professional nursing association but were currently working in other sectors of nursing leadership. Similarly, four had previously served in government roles, including one as Chief Nursing Officer, before changing sector.

Interview participants were recruited from five of the six World Health Organisation Regions (Table 5.2). Although no nurse leaders from the Eastern Mediterranean participated, contributions from the region were subsequently included in both the Delphi (6.2) and post-Delphi interviews (7.2).

Table 5.2 Geographical dispersion of participants: World Health Organisation Regional Classification

Region	Countries No. (n=8)
Africa	1
Americas	2
South-East Asia	1
Europe	2
Eastern Mediterranean	0
Western Pacific	2

Most participants were from high income countries, with no participants from nations with low incomes (Table 5.3). Six of the eight participants spoke English as a first language.

Table 5.3 Participant dispersion by World Bank income level (2015 income classification)

World Bank Income Level	Countries No. (n=8)
High	6
Upper-Middle	1
Lower-Middle	1
Low	0

5.2 Overview of pre-Delphi interview findings

In line with the approach recommended by Parkinson *et al.* (2016) the framework analysis focused on areas of interest based on the research aims:

- The public policy contribution of strategic nurse leaders
- Approaches and attributes of strategic nurse leaders in policy
- Challenges and opportunities for nursing policy influence

5.3 The policy contribution of strategic nurse leaders

The distinctive policy contributions of different sectors of nursing leadership were outlined by several participants. There was a sense that it was important for each sector to understand which areas of policy were best served by their focus. The lenses brought by different sectors was discussed with one example considering the role of trade unions in policy:

“they [trade unions] also have a role to play and sometimes, because their role of course is to protect the individual and to promote the individual nurse ... I mean their role is important ... but sometimes their view is skewed by industrial issues and sometimes what I would call facile solutions, sometimes to big service delivery problems.” P1 (Government, previous role Professional Nursing Association)

Several participants described the different contributions of the sectors of nursing and how these were sometimes misinterpreted. When describing the roles of trade unions and government nurse leaders one participant, who had previously been a GCNO contended:

“you’re not there to represent the profession either ... People tend to forget that as well. They tend to say, ‘oh the chief nurse is there to represent the profession in government’. Well, you’re not. That’s what the trade unions are there for, you know. You’re there to interpret policy, to influence it, and to then make sure it happens.” P7 (Education)

The influence of government nurses was referred to several times as rooted in their access to policy tables by virtue of their position. Government nurse leaders however reflected on their contractual constraints in relation to policy influence, and the demands on them to balance the competing priorities of government, protecting the credibility of government ministers, and their relationship with the wider nursing profession. Several participants with current and previous experience of government roles argued that nurse leaders out with government had more freedom to be aggressive in promoting policy positions than their government nurse counterparts, but that these opportunities were not consistently leveraged.

Many of the examples of policy contribution provided by the participants were directly related to nursing as a profession. Describing an example of a workforce focused policy contribution one participant shared:

“we were able to change our health insurance act to allow nurse practitioners and ... eligible midwives access to our ... public health insurance scheme which means they can work independently outside of an employed environment ... so we had been agitating for that for about 10 years or more actually.” P1 (Government)

The participant elaborated that their individual contribution was in interpreting what was needed, and what would or wouldn't work, and translating that to the bureaucrats who would listen and had the technical expertise in legislation. Other examples of broader policy influence, such as to public health, included engagement in work to ban smoking in public places, and provision of Universal Health Coverage to children. Universal Health Coverage was perceived as a policy area which benefited from nursing expertise.

"I'm proud that I was at the table doing that and making sure that even though we didn't go universal health care for all our people at least let's focus on the children and then we were cleverly able to not only focus on the children but to expand so we could focus on their moms... You can have a healthy child, but most children aren't healthy if they don't have a healthy mom." P8 (Independent consultant)

The policy contributions shared by participants illustrated the nature of policy making in stages, with the desired outcome sometimes several steps away. These observations linked to later reflections on the need for strategic nurse leaders to have the appetite for persistence (5.4).

5.3.1 Effectively communicating nursing contributions to policy

In addition to specific policy topics several participants identified communication of the nursing perspective as a key contribution of strategic nurse leaders. They described having a role in making it easier for policymakers to understand the nursing perspective as well as enabling understanding of policy among the profession. Focusing on interpretation of health-related language for policy makers, one participant elaborated:

"most government bureaucrats don't, in the health ministries anyway, come from health professional backgrounds, or even having worked in the health system. They've worked their way up through government channels and so they are both intimidated and confused by the language around the healthcare systems that as nurses we take for granted." P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Being able to articulate the position of nursing in language which is accessible to people out with healthcare was considered essential to facilitating nursing's inclusion in the policy process. This, along with media training were offered as two opportunities to raise the public and policy profile of nurses. Even where policy advocacy had been successfully converted to contribution it sometimes was not attributed to nursing activity and required additional steps by nurse leaders to publicise their involvement:

“we had a lot of working on this issue [better staffing in psychiatry] and we tried to influence everywhere... and when we saw what the government and minister came out with, we could exactly look into a lot of our statement ... so we were joining and saying yeah, it’s our work, it doesn't say it but we can see it, they listened ... and what we're doing then is we make a press release on that, and we have close connection with the ministry” P3 (Professional Nursing Association)

This example of how nurse leaders promoted their contribution to the government decision, whilst maintaining their relationship with ministers, was echoed by other participants who also alluded to an invisible aspect of influencing policy. One participant described articulation of the nursing contribution as the key to unlock policy influence:

“we can shape as a coordinated voice, we can write something, but if we’ve nobody to act as an expert and really articulate then people will not know where we are coming from, or where we are going, and we get to be ‘just nurses’” P4 (Regulator)

Without the skills to effectively communicate the nursing perspective and contribution, participants warned of perpetuating invisibility, and consequent powerlessness.

5.4 Approaches and attributes of strategic nurse leaders in policy

The participants identified leadership approaches and attributes which they considered critical to success in policy both as an individual and for the profession as a whole. Leadership approaches to maximise policy influence were largely characterised by relationships, preparation, and ongoing development in order to make and take the maximum number of opportunities to influence policy.

5.4.1 Building credibility as a policy actor

Positioning of nursing as a legitimate voice in policy making was described by participants as essential to maximising their access to, and influence in, policy making. Participants reported a persisting belief both within and beyond nursing that nurses are not policy makers.

“The big challenge is that there are still a lot of stereotypes out there that nurses are not policy makers” P8 (Independent Consultant)

The legitimacy of their contribution to policy was considered contingent on their individual credibility as well as the external credibility of the wider profession. Participants described how they built their individual credibility by being well informed by the available evidence, and intelligence from clinical practice, evidence of building their expert power. Achieving credibility as a policy actor

required high-quality relationships and wide-ranging networks, with particular value placed on connecting with clinical practice:

“You've got to keep close to service. You've got to understand what's going on, you've got to be influencing policy, you've got to be able to advise your ministers, your politicians and you've got to have that credibility with them. You've got to have that network sitting around the so that when you speak you know that you're speaking not just with [my] view, you're speaking with this is the view of the people around me.” P7 (Education)

Alongside building the credibility of their contribution, participants highlighted the role of acting with integrity, following through on their commitments, to be important to their ongoing success and influence. Both credibility and integrity were described as fragile, requiring continuous maintenance.

5.4.2 Relationships and political will

Good working relationships with politicians were acknowledged as essential for advancing policy positions. One participant described their approach to building fruitful working relationships in government:

“I worked with four different ministers of health, and you have to re-orient every minister of health and ... get them up to speed, ... understand their style ...helping people to make the connections between what it is you want to advance and what might be the government's agenda ... and how you can help manoeuvre that.” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Considering the return on investment for developing political alliances participants described a tangible difference of good relationships on policy influence. In addition to focusing on developing trusting relationships with senior politicians, two participants prioritised getting to know key players within and beyond health, including more junior bureaucrats who write the briefings for government ministers. Their inclusive and strategic approach suggests that those strategic nurse leaders were aware of the importance of understanding what matters to influential members of the policy discourse, and the opportunity to build a wide coalition to support advancement of future policy priorities. Building a strategic coalition and keeping the team engaged was considered essential to policy success:

“You've got to learn how to build your infrastructure and your team around you. You just can't be the nurse and so like the secrets of my success is that I'm always the best friend of anybody who is head of finance because I always need money.” P8 (Independent consultant)

Understanding the policy community and its dynamics enabled participants to develop and sustain political interest in their policy positions. The influence of relationships in policy making was described by one participant who recalled the importance of not only knowing the people but also accessing different routes of influence:

“when we were changing the nurses bill, it had been on the board for 20 years and it was not going through. So, we were able to use the politician and we have somebody in government who was able to present that as a private member’s bill and it went through very quickly. ... if there were not politicians it would not have gone through.” P4 (Regulator)

Developing and leveraging relationships within government provided access to policy tables but also a nuanced understanding of how best to position issues for maximum influence, progress, and success. Being able to leverage relationships in order to flex the approach beyond that which could be achieved solely within by nursing suggests benefits from wider collaboration.

5.4.3 Collaboration and the value of a collective voice

Coalition building between sectors of nursing was considered important for policy influence with one participant advocating for the breakdown of siloes and a globally coordinated call to action. Achieving such a collective and coordinated voice was considered by another as partially challenged by the large size of the nursing workforce, often framed as a lever for policy influence. Two participants described internal conflict within nursing, with one referring to problematic and ‘divisive’ (P5) individuals in the profession, and its consequently negative impact on progressing policy issues. Reflecting on the impact of a split nursing voice one participant recalled:

“I think we have experienced over the years when government sees different nursing organisations having different points of view they can actually use that as an excuse for not doing anything and they’ll say you don’t agree with each other so we don’t need to listen to any of you.” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Mobilising coordinated policy engagement across sectors of nursing was advocated by participants as an approach which can allow a shared policy problem to be tackled from different angles, which can lead to greater cumulative influence and movement. Several participants argued for development of a shared policy vision for nursing:

“we have a lot of what I call specialty nursing organisations ... as a result sometimes our messages get watered down ... I’m not saying you have to have one voice ... give people choice, but I am saying that you should be able to come on one accord to have an agenda where everybody can build a consensus around at least one issue that everybody can champion to advance nursing.” P8 (Independent consultant)

Developing and presenting a united front by coalescing around a common purpose was highlighted by three participants as an effective way of increasing the strength of nursing’s policy voice. One nurse leader described their experience of the power of cross-sector collaboration:

“It’s traditional that we work close together [nursing and government] but this time they [government] didn’t want such a process, so what we did instead, we joined with all the other healthcare professions in doing our own project ... when they heard about it in the ministry they just got very anxious and said ‘what’s going on?’... and now its ended up that we collaborate because they say okay, we hear you, we see what you mean, let’s join. ... and that’s a way we tried to, in a way, collaborate.” P3 (Professional Nursing Association)

The power of building a team with a shared vision was recognised by many participants. Three expanded on this idea, arguing that to strengthen policy influence nurse leaders should proactively seek alternative perspectives on policy positions. The purpose of this was not only to try to convert others but to be better prepared to anticipate and mitigate competing arguments:

“you need to understand what other issues might trump your issue, or what other bodies who have an opposing view may spring forward. You know, you have to work collaboratively with other people, especially those who don’t agree with you, and be very clear on what their positions are ... sometimes you’re going to be able to influence people to come sort to your way of thinking but you often won’t and you know you sort of have to keep at it.” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

A resilient approach to developing and nurturing high quality strategic relationships was identified by most of the participants as critical to policy influence. Understanding different policy perspectives promotes development of important skills in compromise and negotiation, reported by one participant as scarce within the skillset of nursing leaders in policy. Managing relationships in the context of clashing priorities and perspectives was noted as a common challenge for strategic nurse leaders:

“even if you don't always agree with what they're talking about and all the rest of it, you want to keep them close. That's essential. And in fact, I do know chief nurses who don't do that, and they are singularly unsuccessful” P1 (Government)

The participants noted that their professional credibility was contingent on their ability to successfully navigate complex collaborative relationships. Several discussed taking a strategic approach to relationships to enhance their credibility. Connection to practice, for example, provided the opportunity to develop policy positions reflective of contemporary issues. Several participants reflected that their strategic relationship building held reciprocal benefits. For example, sharing intelligence and providing opportunities for policy influence to nurse leaders in other sectors through signposting and access to policy conversations.

The challenges of the small numbers of strategic nurse leaders both per sector and collectively in a country, highlighted the need to build wide coalitions, beyond nursing. Participants also reported use of regional and international networks to maximise policy influence. International collaborators were valued both for lending credibility to national policy positions but also for providing additional evidence and resources which may be scarce at a national level, particularly for example in countries which do not have a nurse in government. Even where government nurses were in place, they were reported by two participants as having limited resources:

“most of the government Chief Nursing Officers end up with very small units ... it's pretty difficult in a large government machinery to be able to influence a lot with that very small number of people but I think those that have been successful have connected very well with the nursing organisations that are outside of government” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Demonstrating the added value of the nursing contribution through high quality policy participation was one approach advocated to help secure further resources. It is however also indicative of a circular challenge for strategic nurse leaders that securing more resource is dependent on increasing impact, which is partially constrained by team size and capability. The challenges of a small team were converted into an opportunity by one participant who offered nurse leaders out with their immediate team a chance to participate in policy related projects. Not only did this approach improve the policy reach of the government nurse leader but it also contributed to succession planning and capacity and capability building of nurse leadership in policy.

5.4.4 Preparation for strategic leadership in policy

Preparing nurses for strategic nurse leadership was described as including formal education, mentorship, and experiential learning. Whilst one participant stated that nurses are already well prepared to contribute to policy making, due to their broad knowledge base, this was contested by five others who considered there to be much to be done to equip nurses to take part in policy making. This seemed to be particularly true for government nurse leadership:

“You can’t just be a director of nursing and walk into government and think that you can do it. You know, you’ve got to prepare people for it.” P7 (Education)

The preparation proposed included via initial nurse education, preparation for taking up strategic leadership roles, and ongoing development once a strategic nurse leader. Participants described a range of education required for effective strategic nurse leadership including policy, leadership, and a wide knowledge base including financial acumen, and an ability to assess the broader socio-political landscape. Five participants perceived current education provision to be insufficient to develop the policy skills required with one elaborating:

“Our schools of nursing in many instances still have curricula that either don’t teach it [policy development, political skills, and leadership], or they teach it the last semester when they’re [student nurses] are getting ready to go out and it should be the first semester ... because everything you do, I mean for god’s sake the nursing process is the policy process.” P8 (Independent consultant)

While the increasing number of nurses undertaking higher degrees was lauded by one participant, they and others reported few nurses seeking and achieving policy making positions. Reflecting on this, two participants highlighted a need to identify and nurture the next generation of nurse leaders.

“We have to do more talent spotting and get them. It is a responsibility for us sitting on a high level to look [to see] if there are ones coming up, because we can see- there are not so many on the way up.” P3 (Professional Nursing Association)

Once a future strategic nurse leader is identified half the participants advocated for mentorship as an important tool for supporting their development.

“I’m a great believer in mentoring. I don’t necessarily mean formal mentoring programmes, but I do think it’s very important for people in leadership positions to identify those who have the potential and to guide them in their career ... I’ve done that with quite a lot of people” P1 (Government)

Aside from formal education and mentoring, six participants also recommended experiential learning in policy, to prepare nurses for strategic leadership positions. Experiential learning offered benefits including exposure to the practical application of theory, and also the opportunity to learn about the culture and processes which characterise policymaking and would otherwise be opaque to an outsider.

“I really encourage people to look for opportunities to work in government because I think that it helps you but certainly as nurses who are wanting to advance policy change, understanding the culture and those processes is pretty critical.” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Once in post as a strategic nurse leader ongoing personal and professional development was considered essential to continued success:

“You’ve always got to be in a constant state of improvement as a leader otherwise you become stagnant and stale and next thing you know, you’ll be gone.” P8 (Independent consultant)

Several participants described their personal approach to continued professional development. Formal and informal educational opportunities were valued, including seeking development out with the confines of the profession. Reflecting on their own strengths and areas for future growth was perceived to positively impact on their performance.

5.4.5 Personal qualities and skills for success in strategic nurse leadership

Resilience was central to the personal qualities and skills identified as important to thriving in a strategic leadership and policy position. When describing the role of the strategic nurse leader participants shared experiences of stress, loneliness, slow policy progress, and difficult relationships. They described navigating uncharted territory and the tensions which come with aligning the needs of the population, the profession, and wider public policy networks. The strain of managing ongoing tensions was highlighted by several participants. Assertiveness and courage were two skills identified as important to surviving in what one participant called a ‘semi-hostile environment’ (P1). This courage was required for interactions both within and out with nursing:

“We have to be very courageous. We need to have more the moral courage to be able to stand on what we think is right and applicable for the profession.” P5 (Government and Regulator)

Where participants described strategic nurse leaders in distress due to conflict, their comments about the need for change were predominantly focused on the approaches adopted by nurse leaders rather than in the structures and systems, which they were operating within. Communicating confidently and with clarity to speak truth to power was described as key to ensure that decision makers understand the nurse leader's perspective and the potential implications of a particular policy for patients and families:

"being able to manage the tensions and conflicts that can sometimes exist in that context [as Chief Nursing Officer] and being able to stand your own. You know having the confidence to actually stand up to a cabinet secretary or a minister and say 'but wait a minute right, that might be what you wanted to do, but I am telling you that if you do that then this will happen' ... and at the end of the day the decision is theirs but you would have had an audit of the briefing that had been given to the appropriate minister" P7 (Education)

Being able to operate decisively within a complex environment and function at speed, often with no one clear path was highlighted as an essential skillset for the strategic nurse leader. Strategic nurse leaders reflected feeling misunderstood by members of the profession and sometimes having to take positions which are not broadly supported. Illustrating the frustration expressed by two participants at tactics and approaches taken by nurses' one government nurse leader recounted:

"they're [nurses] frustrated with what's happening and so their solution is ... to tell me I'm not doing the job properly. Well, they don't really understand my job ... And so, they don't have any political nous and I think political nous is very hard to teach... I think it's probably because nurses and midwives are so busy doing their job day to day ... that they don't always understand what the big picture is and what the ultimate goal is." P1 (Government)

Participants reflected that their personal resilience was important to surviving and thriving in what could otherwise be a lonely position working in a semi-hostile environment. Reflecting on the resilience and persistence required to repeatedly re-engage after thwarted or unsuccessful policy engagement, one participant offered advice to upcoming nurse leaders:

"Don't take on something that you aren't absolutely passionate about because you're going to get very tired. This is going to be a long process, so you have to have that passion that spark to keep you going." P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Protracted processes in achieving policy advancement were recognised by some as contributing to burnout, but one participant took an alternative view:

“You know how some people will say to you ‘I’m burned out’ well maybe the light was never lit, you know. Because don’t tell me that because the issue is even if there’s just a little bit of smoke and flame left you ought to be able to blow on it and bring it back to life ... we’ve got too much to do now, you can’t just give up.” P8 (Independent consultant)

The passion with which this participant, along with several others, spoke about their role in policy seemed to transcend job requirements. It tended to return to the argument of the moral responsibility of nurses to engage with the direction and content of public policy for the benefit of population health and wellbeing.

5.5 Challenges and opportunities in policy engagement

The key challenges and opportunities identified by the strategic nurse leaders comprised of issues relating to the tensions between leadership positions and the profession and the impact of insufficient preparation to understand the bigger picture. Participants critically discussed the perception of policy as legitimate nursing work and the policy focus of nursing. Participants highlighted the implications of structural constraints and the fragility of the nursing position in government on progression of nursing policy influence.

5.5.1 Tensions between policy leadership positions and professional imperatives.

Three participants described the tensions for government nurses between their position and the priorities of the wider profession. These most commonly focused on the difference between the profession’s expectations of government nurse leaders and the actual role government nurse leaders were contracted to deliver on. Those who were or had previously been Government nurse leaders described experiences of being obliged to advocate for policies or positions which were unpopular in the profession, even when they personally may not agree with them, and the negative impact this could have on their standing and integrity within nursing. Maintaining good working relationships in the context of such tensions was reported by one participant to have even led to the resignation of a nurse leader. Illustrating the leadership challenges faced by strategic nurse leaders in balancing their professional background with their role specific responsibilities, one participant recalled:

“One of the really big issues is again not being able to be honest. I've said that because you're not allowed to divulge things, and secondly there is, there is always a tension between the loyalty, so loyalty to the profession versus loyalty to the employer, and I found that quite difficult especially when you're making decisions, mostly to do with money, which generally speaking the profession is not going to like so yeah, that can be quite, well its very demanding ... and quite stressful quite frankly.” P1 (Government)

Part of the source of such tensions appeared to be in the contractual constraints to the policy influence of government nurses. Several participants described how they circumvented this problem through recognising their privilege in being able to provide opportunities for others to improve their policy influence:

“You sign you know a confidentiality agreement with the government so if internally we were told that we were not going to talk about oh say nurse patient ratios then there was no way I could talk about them, but other people could and ... I would just encourage people to be sure that they were gathering evidence on the things that were important to them and to continue to bring them forward cause the government can't put a, you know, a muffle on people outside of their own employee[s]. So that happened very often actually.” P2 (Health Provider Organisation)

Indirect policy activism enabled by networks was frequently mentioned as an effective approach to advancing policy positions however, it is not without risk. When considering whether government nurses have a responsibility to influence public policy one participant reflected:

“Oh definitely. It's just that they have to be clever on how they do that [influence public policy] because they might lose their job.” P8 (Independent consultant)

The idea of helping to position others to bring forward issues that employees of government could not personally progress was highlighted as a mutual benefit of good working relationships across sectors of nursing and beyond. It also helped nurse leaders have influence disproportionate to their resource which two participants noted was often small.

5.5.2 Challenges and opportunities in understanding the big picture

Internal and external awareness were considered critical for both policy success and the personal credibility of the nurse leader. Five participants highlighted the lack of opportunities available to develop the skills and confidence required for policy competence, particularly ability to interpret the broader socio-political landscape. Understanding the 'big picture' enables leaders to make an informed assessment about the optimal timing and framing of a policy position.

“You’ve got to be clever because in policy making and politics, timing is everything. ... That’s why you have to be internally and externally aware of what’s going on in your environment so that you don’t ... go and ask for something stupid that shouldn’t even have been brought up in the context of what the country’s going through or what the government is going through.” P8 (Independent consultant)

Lack of understanding of the broader political landscape can lead not only to conflict between the government nurse and their peers but may contribute to ineffectual policy activity. The challenge for nurse leaders out with government, who may have a single priority focus for change, is that they may not see the competing priorities within government in the same way that nurses in government are privy to. One participant shared her experience of the consequences when lack of external awareness led to a policy failure.

“We wanted to change a policy of enrolled nurse training so that we have the basic training as diplomas. ... I’ll tell you why we didn’t succeed, because we did not look at the external environment. We didn’t look at the political environment. The government wanted cheap labour and they want people who are available in every small village, but we were looking at nurses and nursing.” P4 (Regulator)

The impact of immature policy skills appeared to hinder advancement of the policy under focus, and also represented an opportunity wasted, and a potential reputational risk to the credibility of the nurse leader as a policy actor.

5.5.3 Policy influence as legitimate nursing work

Almost all participants described nursing as not currently sufficiently policy active to maximise potential for influence. The participants described how policy engagement was not universally considered legitimate nursing work, compounded by medical dominance. Only one participant explicitly raised the issue of gender at any point in the interviews but did so briefly in the context of nurses not perceiving themselves as having the legitimacy to influence policy. Even where policy ambitions do exist within the profession the nurse leaders reported a lack of self-efficacy amongst nurses in leading policy related activity.

5.5.3.1 Challenges and opportunities in engaging nurses in policy

Several participants considered nursing to have a moral responsibility to engage in policy, and a mandate from the public to do so. The trust that the public has in nurses was identified by three participants as a key opportunity for nursing’s policy influence. One participant argued that the public are becoming increasingly policy active and, if nursing does not step up to the opportunity of

becoming their professional voice patients will seek other groups and professions to progress their policy priorities. Despite this perceived mandate for policy engagement, participants also described nurses as not generally perceiving policy as a desirable, or priority role in the profession, beyond an operational level:

“The breadth of the profession doesn’t see itself as having that kind of responsibility. ... If you were to speak to a nurse for example ... they could understand the desire to influence policy locally, so they might be involved in a working group locally but if you say to them but what about what’s happening at a government level, “oh no, that’s nothing to do with me”. Now medicine, education ... tend to be closer to public policy.” P7 (Education)

This was reinforced by participants who reported a mixture of apathy and active resistance to policy engagement with nurses as referring to themselves as ‘just nurses’. Several participants identified a need to change attitudes to policy engagement, and an opportunity to move beyond a traditional ‘just nurses’ mind-set through higher levels of education. The development of an appetite for policy engagement was tempered by the competing demands of direct caregiving on nurses:

“Nurses carry very heavy operational workloads. Influencing policy or contribution to policy formulation tends to get less priority.” P6 field notes (Education and Professional Nursing Association)

Another participant argued that rather than it being an issue with prioritisation the structures of health care providing organisations could make policy engagement difficult, even at an operational level.

“In the hospital levels where we have the nurses, the work [is] primarily to manage and develop the organisation and they are not very involved in the policy making. We would prefer them to do it a bit more than they do but they find it difficult because they are in a middle position ... they are referring to a director at a regular level and ... it’s difficult for them to make a big impact on the policy” P4 (Professional Nursing Association)

Although recognised as difficult, participants framed policy making as a legitimate nursing role for the benefit of the population. One participant, discussing mechanisms to broaden nurses’ appreciation for the role and power of policy to improve the health and wellbeing of the communities they support, explained:

“Influencing or developing public policy and evaluating it is really one of the best levers that you can do. So, it’s about changing the world or changing the society at large without just doing it one by one, and I think many nurses don’t appreciate that. They get really focused on

... often it's a group of patients and families that they develop expertise in, and they don't understand that they're just going to keep having to address issues one by one as these people come forward if they don't go upstream and work at policy at the larger table" P2
(Health Provider Organisation)

This quote further highlights the gap between how participants described their own views on the responsibilities and potential contribution of nursing to policy making compared to their perception of the views of the wider nursing population. The implications of nursing not pursuing and prioritising policy influence was argued by one participant to confine nurses to implementation only roles in policy.

5.5.3.2 Medical dominance in policy

Several participants were optimistic about improvements in nursing's policy engagement. There was, however, acknowledgement that medicine continues to dominate nursing in the policy sphere. One participant observed that physicians innately command influence without a requirement to substantiate their views. Suggesting a lack of legitimate power, participants highlighted the contrast for nurses who are required to justify their policy credentials before gaining access to discussions:

"...we are not very good in telling all the politicians why it's very important that we're there. The doctors don't have to tell why they are important" P3 (Professional Nursing Association)

Not only were doctors considered more influential in policy, but participants reported instances where medics still spoke for nurses on nursing specific issues, or even represented nurses in government. One participant however, framed medical dominance differently, arguing that cultural norms in nursing also contribute to its perpetuation:

"Nurses, by nature, knowing that they are very reticent about things, and sometimes like to take a backseat on issues. And, usually we let the doctors and administrators run the show and decide what, and how nursing can be run, so we need to inspire the nurses to know that they actually are just as capable if not better than the other non-nursing professionals" P5
(Government and Regulator)

By characterising medical dominance as something which nursing has some control over, the participant presented a historic challenge as an opportunity to uplift nurses to see, and believe, in their own potential through effective preparation and practice. Evaluating the importance of nursing expanding and owning its policy contribution one participant finished their interview by saying:

"It's better to be at the table, than on the menu, so I will leave you with that." P8
(Independent consultant)

5.5.3.3 The invisibility of nurse leadership in policy

The invisibility of nursing at policy level, compounded by insufficient nurses in senior policy roles, was identified recurrently as a problem both for the internal and external perceptions of policy as legitimate nursing work. Interestingly two participants highlighted how there were a proportion of nurses who, particularly when promoted in roles not traditionally held by nurses, would no longer externally identify themselves as a nurse:

“They do not want to say they are nurses. They want to call themselves Chief Executives, but you know, you became a chief executive because basically you are a nurse... my idea is if you work that position because you are first and foremost a nurse really maintain your relationship with us.” P4 (Regulator)

The participants contended that this external abdication of the nursing identity contributes to the invisibility of nursing to non-nursing decision makers.

Even where nurses were reported as interested in engaging with policy a lack of confidence was noted by several participants. One participant postulated a potential for linkage of lack of confidence to the status of women and gender disparity. A further two participants noted the impact of context on the confidence of nurse leaders:

“We are natural leaders within the domain of nursing ... but I’m speaking in the context of the nurse in relation to other non-nursing colleagues that we deal with in partnership. The nurses, somehow by nature, will not ... naturally rise up to the occasion of leadership, so we really need good mentors who can guide us” P5 (Government and Regulator)

In addition to mentorship a separate participant reported role modelling as having a mobilising effect in the policy engagement of nurses. They reflected on their experience of their own visible policy engagement or advocacy triggering other nurses to follow in support.

5.5.4 The policy focus of nursing leaders

Although three participants identified that nurse interest in policy making tended to focus on nursing, rather than patients and communities, several participants sought to be involved in policy topics beyond nursing, such as environmental issues. This ambition was however constrained by external perceptions and structures which contributed to the exclusion or restriction of nursing policy influence. For example, one participant described having a nursing-only remit:

“I’m not responsible for policies that affect services, development, or functional roles unless there’s nursing input or they’re talking about nursing resources, in which way I’ll come in.” P5 (Government and Regulator)

Having either an enforced or chosen policy focus on nursing rather than on patients and communities presented two problems in the eyes of several participants. Firstly, it restricted relationship building beyond nursing, which contributed to the second problem of limiting the policy influence of the profession to purely nursing centric issues. Arguing for a reframing of how the profession talks about policy and leadership one participant contended:

“I never use the word nursing policy ... there’s no such thing in my opinion as nursing public policies ... that’s some crazy thinking and that’s why we’re where we are ‘cause we get too insular. We get too insular in thinking you know this is nursing leadership. It’s not nursing leadership; its leadership and you happen to be a nurse who’s leading.” P8 (Independent consultant)

Taking a broader view made theoretical sense to some participants. Others reflected that demonstrating a balanced understanding of the wider political landscape improved their policy influence. The wide scope of individual nurse leaders’ policy responsibility and potential contribution of nursing underlined the participants’ call for expanding the number of nurses assuming policy making positions.

5.5.5 Fragility of nursing in government

The presence and position of nursing within government varied between countries with three of the eight participants reporting that their country did not currently have a Chief Nursing Officer. The government of the day was acknowledged to have a significant role in determining the presence, absence, and power of nursing in government. Two participants described changes in the position of nursing in the government hierarchy as a consequence of fluctuations in political attitude and appetite for nursing:

“When we had our last elections, nurses have been marginalised and they are not visible. We used to have a divisional nursing then we became a departmental nursing where I would be talking directly to the director of medical authorities, but since last year we are a nursing unit, so for the first time there was no nursing in Geneva [at the WHO World Health Assembly] in the delegation because we are a unit so they are not speaking directly to the minister.” P4 (Regulator)

Increasing the number of layers of bureaucracy between the strategic nurse leader and the minister for health reduced the visibility and influence of the nurse leader, and nursing generally, in government.

5.6 Chapter Summary

Analysis and interpretation of the pre-Delphi interview findings offered insights into the policy contribution, challenges and opportunities facing strategic nurse leaders. Particularly striking was the focus of participants on collaborative relationships and preparation of nurse leaders to surmount the challenges encountered in policy influence. The challenges focused on tensions within and beyond the profession about the practice of policy influence as legitimate nursing work, and the precarity of strategic nurse leadership. Strategic nurse leaders indicated a need and appetite for support in growing the breadth and impact of their engagement in policy. The interview findings were used to inform the first round of the Delphi, the findings of which are presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: Delphi Findings

This chapter presents the findings from the three round modified Policy Delphi. The Delphi was designed to address the primary aims of the study: to investigate international strategic nurse leadership in policy and to construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

The chapter commences with a description of the Delphi panel. Presentation of each round begins with the preparation for the round and an overview of the findings. Detailed reporting of the findings of each round begins with items that reached consensus, items that did not reach consensus, and qualitative findings, as applicable. As part of Round 3 preparation key findings from the first two rounds were synthesised into a consensus statement on strategic nurse leadership and public policy. The Delphi panel's reflections on the content, orientation, and key messages of the consensus statement form the final section of this chapter.

6.1 Delphi Timeline

The three round Delphi was completed over the course of 8 months. Round 1 was sent out March 11th, 2015, Round 2 on May 25th, 2015, and Round 3 on November 13th, 2015. The development of the consensus statement took place between the second and third round.

6.2 Delphi Panel

Diversity in setting of nurse leadership was sought during recruitment. A total of 87 invitations were sent to potential panellists as per the recruitment strategy described in chapter 4 (4.5.2.3). Forty strategic nurse leaders, 32 women and 8 men, from 32 countries consented to participate in the Delphi panel. Seven countries had more than one panel member, bringing perspectives from different sectors of nurse leadership. To preserve panellist confidentiality the geographical dispersion of the panel is grouped by WHO region (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1 Geographical dispersion of panellists: WHO Regional Classification

Region	Countries No. (n=32)	Panellists No. (n=40)
Africa	21.9% (7/32)	20% (8/40)
Americas	9.4% (3/32)	10% (4/40)
South-East Asia	3.1% (1/32)	2.5% (1/40)
Europe	40.6% (13/32)	42.5% (17/40)
Eastern Mediterranean	12.5% (4/32)	10% (4/40)
Western Pacific	12.5% (4/32)	15% (6/40)

Diversity in country income level was also sought. Although more than one third of panellists were from countries out with an income below the high-income definition, high-income countries were disproportionately represented, as shown in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2 Panel dispersion by World Bank income level (2015 income classification)

World Bank Income Level	Countries No. (n=32)	Panellists No. (n=40)
High	59.4% (19/32)	65% (26/40)
Upper-Middle	15.6% (5/32)	12.5% (5/40)
Lower-Middle	18.75% (6/32)	15% (6/40)
Low	6.25% (2/32)	7.5% (3/40)

The panellists held a range of strategic positions across government, regulation, education, professional nursing associations, and trade unions. Roles of panellists included Chief Nursing and Midwifery Officer, Registrar of the national professional regulator, university dean, and President of the Professional Nursing Association. Of the 40 panellists, 23 (57.5%) indicated a single primary sector for their leadership, while 17 (42.5%) indicated that they held combined roles which straddled more than one sector (Table 6.3). Note that the sum of the column of combined roles in Table 6.3 is greater than 17 due to panellists holding complex cross-sector positions. Two examples of the combined roles included remits extending across education and their national Professional Nursing Association, and another combining government nurse leadership with regulation. The diversity of leadership roles and those with multiple functional responsibilities is indicative of the complexity and variation in elite nurse leadership roles internationally.

Table 6.3 Sector of leadership role

Sector	Single Sector Roles No. (n=23)	Combined Roles
Education	8	9
Government	4	7
Health Providing Organisation	0	8
Professional Nursing Association	4	11
Professional Regulation	6	6
Other: Non-governmental organisation	1	0
Trade Union	0	2

More than half the panellists had at least five years of experience in their current nurse leadership role (Table 6.4). For panellists in post for less than five years (n=13) six had held prior leadership positions in the same sector or combination of sectors, three had changed sector and four had changed one sector within a combined role.

Table 6.4 Years in current strategic leadership role

Years in current role	Panellists No.
<1	3
1-4	10
5-9	12
10+	12
Missing Data	3

6.2.1 Delphi Panel: Completion of Rounds

All 40 consenting panellists were invited to participate within each of the three rounds, although response rates and engagement varied across the rounds. Of the 40 panellists who completed at least one round of the Delphi, 22 completed all three rounds (Table 6.5). Of the 10 panellists who completed one round, eight completed Round 1 and two only completed Round 2. For the eight panellists who completed two rounds, six completed Rounds 1 and 2, and two panellists completed Rounds 2 and 3. As described in the Delphi consent form (Appendix 11) no explanation was required for nonresponse. During the distribution of the third-round questionnaires five panellists were uncontactable due to being on long term leave (n=1) or no longer in post (n=4), with no forwarding email address, reducing maximum Round 3 completion to 35.

Table 6.5 Number of rounds completed by panellists

	No. panellists
Completed at least one round	40
Completed 3 rounds	22
Completed 2 rounds	8
Completed 1 round	10

As 40 panellists contributed to at least one round the response rate per round is calculated based on a denominator of 40 (Table 6.6). As per the procedure detailed in 4.5.7 email reminders were sent to all panellists to promote engagement with respective rounds. Reduction in completion rates is a recognised limitation of Delphi research (de Loë *et al.*, 2016; Belton *et al.*, 2019), and discussed further in the merits and limitations of the study (8.2).

Table 6.6 Number of questionnaires returned per round.

	No. returned questionnaires	% response rate (n=40)
Round 1	36	90%
Round 2	32 (4 who did not respond in Round 1)	80%
Round 3	24	60%

The panel composition of Round 3 is set out in Appendix 21 and demonstrates similar patterns in distribution of responding panellists in terms of income level, world region or sector of leadership, with the exception of proportionately fewer participants from professional nursing associations in the final round.

6.3 Preparation for Round 1

The purpose of the first round of the Delphi was to establish the initial position of the panel on key topics identified during the literature review and analysis of the pre-Delphi interviews. The structured first round questionnaire comprised 46 item statements for rating and three open ended questions (Appendix 8). The questionnaire items were developed as discrete statements mapped from the findings of the pre-Delphi interviews (Chapter 5) and the literature review (Chapter 2). The mapping, presented in a table in Appendix 22, strengthens the rigour of the Delphi by identifying for each statement whether it was developed from data in the pre-Delphi interviews, the literature review, or both. The questionnaire items comprised two overarching topics: the public policy influence of nursing (32 items) and the development of strategic nurse leadership (14 items). There was space beside each item for panellists to make free text comments relating to the statement if they wished. Two open-ended questions at the end of the questionnaire explored perceived barriers and potential ideas for facilitating nursing's policy influence. These questions allowed panellists to freely express their opinions and raise issues, which may have otherwise been missed. Finally, there was an invitation for any other comments, which 14 panellists used as an opportunity to comment further on their perspectives of nursing in policy.

Each round of the Delphi was pilot tested by the test panel as detailed in 4.5.5, prior to distribution to the main sample. The pilot findings are not reported as part of the main panel.

6.4 Round 1: Overview of findings

Of the 46 statement items presented in Round 1, 28 (60.8%) reached consensus (Tables 6.7, 6.8, and Appendix 13). As per the threshold set a priori (4.5.3), consensus was identified where greater than or equal to 67% of panellists were calculated to hold the same perspective, which may be agreement or disagreement, plus an interquartile range of less than or equal to one. Of the statements, which reached consensus in Round 1 only two had missing data, for one participant each. The 18 items that

did not meet the threshold for consensus were re-presented to the panel in Round 2 and are reported in 6.12 and 6.13. Each item statement in each round of the Delphi was allocated a unique identifier (ID), as planned in 4.5.6. The ID is used within the narrative reporting of the findings in each round the next sections. The first column of each findings table contains the statement ID next to the corresponding item statement.

6.5 Round 1 Statements reaching consensus: Public Policy Influence of Nursing

Of the 32 statements exploring the public policy influence of nursing, 17 reached consensus in Round 1 (Table 6.7). The findings reflect confirmation of policy influence as a priority for the profession, and a need for change to fulfil nursing's policy potential (Table 6.7, Statement 8 and 23). Panellists across income levels agreed that policy influence was a priority for the profession, but the findings also reflect cross-sectoral consensus that the panel perceived nurses to be marginalised in policy making, being rarely in policy discussions (Table 6.7, Statements 23, 7, 12).

More positively, collaboration and networking within and beyond the profession was identified as a key approach to strengthen policy influence (Table 6.7, Statements 3, 16, 22, 25, 27). The panel recognised international variation in opportunities for nurses to contribute to policy (Table 6.7, Statement 9). There was, however, an appetite for developing the collective international nursing voice and its potential to improve the policy influence of the panellists at a national level (Table 6.7, Statements 30, 32). The panel also identified a need for a structure to facilitate collaboration between sectors of nursing leadership (Table 6.7, Statement 15).

Table 6.7 Round 1 statements reaching consensus: Public Policy Influence of Nursing, ordered by strength of consensus

R1 ID	Statement	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
16	All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities.	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
22	Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing.	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
25	There is no benefit from nurse leaders from different countries working together.	Strongly Disagree	1 (2.8%)	35 (97.2%)	1
27	The impact of the contribution that nurse leadership can make to public policy is directly related to their networks and how they manage their networks.	Agree	34 (94.4%)	2 (5.6%)	1
32	A collective international nursing voice would strengthen my policy influence in my country.	Agree/ Strongly Agree	34 (94.4%)	2 (5.6%)	1
8	We don't need to change anything about nursing policy influence at a national level.	Strongly Disagree	2 (5.6%)	34 (94.4%)	1
15	An agreed structure is required to facilitate the collaboration of different sectors of nursing.	Agree	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)	0.25
30	Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health.	Strongly Agree	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)	1
6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	Agree	32 (88.9%)	4 (11.1%)	0.25
9	Nurses around the world have the same opportunities to contribute to public policy	Disagree	4 (11.1%)	32 (88.9%)	1
7	Nurses are marginalised (seen and treated as less important than other disciplines) in policy making	Agree	31 (86.1%)	5 (13.9%)	1
3	Nurse leaders seek support from healthcare and other disciplines to achieve influence.	Agree	30 (83.3%)	6 (16.7%)	0
28	Nurses make an important contribution to public policy.	Agree	29 (80.6%)	7 (19.4%)	1
23	Policy influence is not a priority in nursing.	Disagree	7 (20%*)	28 (80%*)	1
29	Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy.	Disagree	9 (25%)	27 (75%)	0.25
12	Nurses are rarely at the policy making table.	Agree	25 (71.4%*)	10 (28.6%*)	1

* n=35: missing data (n=1)

6.6 Round 1 Statements reaching consensus: Developing Strategic Nurse Leadership

Of the 14 statements addressing the development of strategic nurse leadership, 11 achieved consensus in Round 1. Table 6.8 presents the statements reaching consensus by strength of collective perspective. The need for a strategic plan for building policy capacity and capability within nursing reached almost unanimous agreement together with development of structures for systematic succession planning (Table 6.8, Statements 36, 43).

Table 6.8 Round 1 statements reaching consensus: Developing Strategic Nurse Leadership ordered by strength of consensus

R1 ID	Statement	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
44	Understanding the public health context (situation) is important to effective policy influence.	Strongly Agree	36 (100%)	0 (0%)	1
39	Effective nursing leadership in the policy process requires a range of approaches	Agree	36 (100%)	0 (0%)	1
43	There should be a strategic plan for developing the capability and capacity of nursing for policy	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
36	There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	Strongly Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
34	Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
35	Cultural understanding is important to effective global policy influence	Agree	34 (94.4%)	2 (5.6%)	1
41	There should be a standardised mentorship programme for potential nurse leaders.	Agree	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)	1
42	Nurse leadership preparation begins at the pre-registration (student) stage.	Agree	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)	1
40	Nurses need to be formally educated to take up strategic nurse leadership roles	Agree	32 (88.9%)	4 (11.1%)	1
38	Succession planning needs more resources in order to be provided systematically.	Agree	30 (83.3%)	6 (16.7%)	0
45	Policy and leadership education is available in my country.	Agree	29 (80.6%)	7 (19.4%)	0

The findings of Round 1 show a recognition of variation in the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders internationally. It also demonstrates the role of understanding cultural and contextual nuances when engaging in policy.

6.7 Round 1 open-ended questions: Barriers and facilitators for nursing policy influence

In the final section of the Round 1 questionnaire, the panellists identified up to five barriers to nurse leaders making an effective leadership contribution to public health policy and five facilitators that could strengthen the contribution of nurse leaders. The panel generated 165 responses relating to barriers to nursing leadership in policy. A further 158 responses offered ideas for the enhancement of nursing policy contribution. Content analysis, conducted as per the process detailed in section

4.5.8.2, revealed commonalities in the responses to both questions. For example, lack of access to education was identified as a barrier whilst improved access to education was advocated as a route to improving policy influence. As such, analysis of the two questions was combined.

Two themes emerged from the content analysis: positioning nursing as a policy capable profession and preparing nurses for leadership in policy making (figure 6.1). The development of statements for the Round 2 questionnaire from the categories within the themes and subthemes is described in 6.8.

Figure 6.1. Round 1 barriers and facilitators in policy influence: themes and subthemes.

6.8 Preparation for Round 2

Preparation for Round 2 comprised development and testing of the Round 2 questionnaire together with construction of between-round feedback, prepared as described in 4.5.8.3. The feedback comprised a detailed summary of statements that had reached consensus in Round 1, including the median Likert score for the panel and interquartile range (IQR) for each statement (see excerpt in Table 6.9) (Appendix 13).

Table 6.9 Excerpt of between-round feedback

Statement	Median	IQR
Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence	Agree	1
There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	Strongly Agree	1

The new Round 2 statements were derived from the content analysis of the open-ended questions. Table 6.10 presents four examples of how the content analysis of the data from the open-ended questions led to the construction of the new statements presented in Round 2.

Table 6.10 Translation of raw data to Round 2 statements

Raw data: facilitators and barriers to policy influence	Content Analysis Category	Round 2 Statement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Develop a nursing strategy as nurses e.g. from regulation, clinical, education and union side, that will guide the leadership being it public or political on where we want to take nursing”</i> P32 (Professional Nursing Association, Upper Middle income) • <i>“Nursing strategy for the country”</i> P13 (Education, High Income) 	<p>Need for a strategic plan</p>	<p>Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy, which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“In my experience the policy agenda is not addressed (except in passing) in the majority of undergraduate or postgraduate programmes”</i> P7 (Education, High Income) • <i>“Start to create an awareness of key related subjects to leadership from undergraduate level”</i> P21 (Regulator, High Income) • <i>“Preparation in pre-registration programmes to lobby government on health related policy matters”</i> P31 (Education, Upper Middle Income) 	<p>Embedding leadership and policy education at every level</p>	<p>Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Politicians and other health professionals often feel that nurses are not capable of doing anything other than nursing and therefore do not invite nurses to be a part of policy making”</i> P22 (Government, Upper Middle income) • <i>“Other more experienced players in policy development do not see nurses as relevant contributors”</i> P5 (High income, Education) • <i>“Stereotyping nurses that they are only there for patient care”</i> P31 (Government, High income) 	<p>External perception of the role of nursing in policy</p>	<p>In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision-making process</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Ministries have all position for doctors at province and federal level and there is no nurse appointed at federal level”</i> P9 (Education/ Professional Nursing Association / Regulator, Lower Middle Income) • <i>“Voice of physicians trumps nursing”</i> P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income) 	<p>Influence of traditional role on policy contribution</p>	<p>In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing.</p>

Appendix 23 maps the relationship between the 33 statements developed and included in the Round 2 questionnaire (Appendix 14) and the categories, subthemes, and themes of the Round 1 content analysis. Figure 6.2 provides an example using one of the categories included in the subtheme ‘Recognising nurses as legitimate policy influencers’. The category labels in the content analysis were kept deliberately close to the data rather than being further abstracted. Doing so enabled construction of Round 2 statements with language close to the raw data. Keeping subsequent statements close to the original data is in line with Delphi conventions to preserve original meaning and promote rigour (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2011).

Figure 6.2 Mapping of Round 1 content analysis to Round 2 statements

6.8.1 Categories not included in Round 2

The categories in the content analysis from Round 1 were assessed against the quantitative statements already presented in Round 1. To minimise duplication and panel fatigue, categories already examined in the Round 1 questionnaire were not included in Round 2 unless they offered a new perspective (see 4.5.9). Four categories were identified as mapping to existing statements in the Round 1 questionnaire and were therefore excluded from Round 2 (Table 6.11).

Table 6.11 Categories excluded from Round 2

Category	Round 1 Statement which tested the category
Lack of time for policy participation	Statement 29: Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy (Table 6.7)
Developing a unified nursing voice	Statement 30: Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health (Table 6.7)
Increasing collaboration and networking intra and inter-professionally	Statement 22: Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing. Statement 16: All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities. (Also: Table 6.7, Statements 3, 15, 25; Table 6.15, Statements 11, 18)
Adopting a policy focus beyond nursing	Statement 20: To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing. (Table 6.7, also statements 6, 10)

As the purpose of the Delphi was to develop broad perspectives on policy influence rather than to study the individual characteristics of successful leaders, Round 2 also excluded the category relating to personal leadership qualities.

6.9 Round 2 Statements: Overview of findings

The Round 2 questionnaire (Appendix 14) comprised three sections: 33 new statements derived from the analysis of barriers and facilitators, retesting of 18 statements which did not reach consensus in Round 1, and a qualitative exploration of the divergence around the proposed policy focus of nursing (6.14).

Of the 33 new statements presented, 19 (57.6%) achieved consensus in Round 2 (see Table 6.12). Following analysis of the 14 statements that did not reach consensus, eight proceeded to further testing in Round 3 (see 6.17 and 6.18) and six were not retested (further discussed in 6.11). In the responses to the 33 new statements there were eight items of missing data from six panellists, distributed across six statements, annotated in Tables 6.12, 6.13, 6.17, and 6.18.

For the 18 Round 1 statements retested in Round 2, panellists were presented with their personal Round 1 rating for each statement, as well as the panel median and the IQR. Eight of the retested statements reached consensus in Round 2 (Table 6.14) and 10 demonstrated persisting divergence (Table 6.15). In the responses to the 18 retested statements there were seven items of missing data from six panellists, distributed across six statements, annotated in Tables 6.14 and 6.15. Qualitative comments provided by panellists have been used to aid interpretation of consensus and divergence.

6.10 Round 2: Statements reaching consensus

The panel reached consensus on a number of Round 2 statements relating to the preparation of policy capable nurse leaders. Panellists were particularly focused on strengthening education, mentorship, and succession planning (Table 6.12, Statements 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 23, 24, 27).

Table 6.12 Round 2 statements reaching consensus, ordered by strength of consensus

R2 ID	Round 2 Statement	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
21	There is a need to embed an expectation amongst nursing students that they should be able to understand and engage with policy making.	Agree	32 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1
33	Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.	Strongly Agree	32 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	1
8	Nursing needs a more visible and positive media profile nationally and internationally.	Agree	32 (100%)	0 (0.0%)	1
19	Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes	Agree / Strongly Agree	31 (96.9%)	1 (3.1%)	1
32	Nurses who are active in public policy need to be more visible.	Agree	31 (96.9%)	1 (3.1%)	0
17	The quality of education on policy needs to be improved.	Agree	31 (96.9%)	1 (3.1%)	1
1	In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing.	Agree / Strongly Agree	30 (93.8%)	2 (6.3%)	1
24	There is a need for a defined leadership career pathway to enable more deliberate succession planning.	Agree	30 (93.8%)	2 (6.3%)	1
9	In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision making process.	Agree	29 (93.5%*)	2 (6.5%*)	1
23	Mentorship should be provided by nurse leaders who know and understand the culture and environment where the person being mentored works.	Agree	29 (90.6%)	3 (9.4%)	1
25	We need more nurse leaders who have a clinical academic profile.	Agree	29 (90.6%)	3 (9.4%)	1
7	There is a need for more nurse research which is designed to support policy making decisions.	Agree	29 (90.6%)	3 (9.4%)	1
22	Policy and leadership education should be provided by professional nursing associations and organisations as well as educational institutions.	Agree	29 (90.6%)	3 (9.4%)	1
20	In my country the education system needs to change to make nurses fit for purpose for participating in policy making.	Agree	28 (87.5%)	4 (12.5%)	0
6	There are not enough nurses in policy making positions in my country.	Agree	27 (84.4%)	5 (15.6%)	0
16	Nursing is reactive rather than proactive in policy making.	Agree	26 (81.3%)	6 (18.8%)	0
27	Succession planning should be undertaken on the basis of the nurse's competence, attributes, and ability to lead, not their clinical skill.	Agree	25 (78.1%)	7 (21.9%)	0
18	In my country access to education on policy needs to be cheaper and more accessible.	Agree	24 (75%)	8 (25%)	0.3
29	The political stability of my country has a significant impact on the nursing contribution to public policy.	Agree	22 (68.8%)	10 (31.3%)	1

*n=31, missing data n=1

Several challenges and opportunities in positioning nursing as a policy influencing profession reached consensus in Round 2 (Table 6.12, Statements, 6, 7, 8, 9, 32, 33). One example was the need for change in order for nurses to be recognised as legitimate decision makers within policy making identified in Statement 9 (Table 6.12). The qualitative comments relating to the need for a cultural shift demonstrated challenges for the nursing policy voice in both high and lower income countries:

“Nurses are not expected to contribute to decision making in my country and unfortunately they lack experience in this area” P19 (Education, High Income)

“Nurses should be involved at every stage of policy making. But even nursing matters are sometimes decided upon by non-nurses” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

Reflections on lack of expectation and consequent lack of experience were consistent with panel responses in relation to the barriers and facilitators of nursing’s policy influence in Round 1 (Table 6.7). It was interesting that for some participants, the responsibility for changing the perceptions of the nursing role in high level policy making appeared to lie firmly with the profession:

“...but the burden of responsibility of achieving this [recognition of nurses as key players in decision making] rests with us, not waiting for others to do it for us” P7 (Education, High Income)

The focus of the panel on working to develop the antecedents to, rather than enactment of policy influence appeared to be linked to a disconnect between the policy ambitions of the profession and the real-world experience of the strategic nurse leaders.

6.11 Round 2 statements which did not reach consensus: Not retested

Six of the 14 new statements that did not reach consensus in Round 2 were not retested in Round 3 (Table 6.13). Each of the six statements were context sensitive to the individual panellist. The culturally endorsed leadership theory and social constructionist underpinning of the study recognised multiplicity of experience (detailed earlier in 3.1.1, 3.2.2 and 3.5). As such, although the issues captured in the statements, generated from the Round 1 data, were internationally relevant their culturally mediated and context bound nature suggested that panellist perspectives were unlikely to change, making retesting redundant. The purpose of the Delphi was not to create artificial consensus. Rather, it was to identify points of shared understanding and points where diversity of perspective can be expected.

Table 6.13 Round 2 statements which did not reach consensus: Not retested, ordered by strength of consensus

R2 ID	Round 2 Statement	Median	%Agree	% Disagree	IQR
2	In my country gender inequality has an impact on the ability of nurse leaders to influence public policy.	Agree	20 (62.5%)	12 (37.5%)	1
5	In my country we do not have enough strong professional nurse leaders.	Agree	20 (62.5%)	12 (37.5%)	1
26	In my country there is a clear policy vision for nursing	Disagree	12 (38.7%*)	19 (61.3%*)	1
28	In my country nurses are often forced into leadership because there is no one else to do the job.	Disagree	14 (43.8%)	18 (56.3%)	1
30	Corruption affects policy making in my country.	Agree	17 (53.1%)	15 (46.9%)	1
31	The policy process in my country is slow and dysfunctional.	Agree	17 (53.1%)	15 (46.9%)	1

*n=31: missing data (n=1)

The responses to the six statements provided interesting contextualisation to the Delphi findings, for example, more than half of the panellists identified corruption as an issue in policy making in their country (Table 6.13, Statement 30) with one commenting:

“Yes, and it [corruption] is rampant.” P33 (Professional Nursing Association, Lower middle Income)

Of the 17 panellists who stated corruption was a factor, seven were from high income countries. In contrast, two of the 15 panellists who did not perceive corruption to affect policy making in their experience were from high income countries.

Although panellists from countries of all income levels recognised gender inequality as a factor in nursing’s policy influence in their country it did not reach the threshold for consensus (Table 6.13, Statement 2). There was a difference in perception between the male and female panellists. Of the 12 panellists who perceived gender inequality to not have an impact on the ability of nursing to influence policy, five were men, and seven were women. As a proportion of responding panellists this meant that 71.4% (5/7) male panellists responding in Round 2 perceived gender as not having an impact on policy influence, compared to only 28% (7/25) of female panellists.

The qualitative data provided some insights into the complexity and variation of gender as a factor in policymaking internationally. For panellists who considered gender as having a significant impact, there was linkage to culture, and gender inequality as an unresolved issue for strategic nurse leadership. In qualifying her strong agreement on the impact of gender inequality one strategic nurse leader stated:

“We just need to admit that gender role stereotyping exists” P21 (Regulator, High Income)

Others stated that gender inequality was either not a problem or not a factor in nursing’s policy influence. Two panellists who stated that gender inequality was not an issue in their quantitative rating then provided a more nuanced qualitative comment:

“Gender inequality exists to a degree depending on the industry but the main factor here is the relative power of doctors, many of whom are women.” P6 (Government, High Income)

“but men’s influence is [more] highly valued than women.” P16 (Education, Low Income)

Reference to the dominance of medicine, which the panel agreed was pervasive (Table 6.13, Statement 1), was also reflected by a panellist who considered gender inequality as having a role in nursing’s policy influence:

“It is more subordination to medicine but also inherent bias that women and, thus nurses, are less knowledgeable about healthcare financing and overall policy” P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income).

Several participants highlighted the dominance of medicine in the context of few high-level nursing roles:

“All high and middle positions in health care are held by medical doctors, from minister of health to those heading departments in the ministry and hospitals” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

The role of such institutional and legislative structures in perpetuating the influence of doctors was noted by one participant explaining:

“The Public Health Act, which allows doctors to be the heads of ministerial departments, as well as provincial, and district health offices, affords doctors this role” P8 (Education/Government, Lower-Middle Income)

Whilst more than half of panellists indicated that there was a clear policy vision in their country (Table 6.13, Statement 26), just over one third stated that there was no policy vision in place. As one panellist commented on the statement:

“...you have identified a serious policy gap” P7 (Education, High Income)

Rate limiting factors in the development of a policy vision were identified, including finding common ground between nurse leaders:

“Professional associations each have their own vision – sometimes it is shared but there is not a national nursing policy vision” P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

“Nurse leaders cannot agree” P36 (Regulator, High Income)

6.12 Retested Round 1 statements reaching consensus in Round 2

Of the 18 Round 1 statements retested in Round 2 (Public Policy Influence of Nursing n=15, Development of Strategic Nursing Leadership n=3), eight reached consensus (Table 6.14).

Table 6.14 Retested Round 1 statements reaching consensus in Round 2 ordered by strength of consensus in Round 2

R1 ID	Round 1 Statement	Round	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
5	Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy	1	Agree	22 (61.1%)	14 (38.9%)	1
		2	Agree	28 (87.5%)	4 (12.5%)	1
13	In my country, there are public health policy priorities, which are shared in the global nursing community.	1	Agree	24 (66.7%)	12 (33.3%)	1
		2	Agree	28 (87.5%)	4 (12.5%)	0
17	There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy	1	Agree	23 (63.9%)	13 (36.1%)	1
		2	Agree	24 (75%)	8 (25%)	1
37	Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	1	Disagree	14 (38.9%)	22 (61.1%)	1
		2	Disagree	9 (29%*)	22 (71%*)	1
14	Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	1	Disagree	17 (47.2%)	19 (52.8%)	1
		2	Disagree	9.5[†] (29.7%)	22.5[†] (70.3%)	1
1	Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy	1	Disagree	13 (36.1%)	23 (63.9%)	1
		2	Disagree	10 (31.3%)	22 (68.8%)	1
4	Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	1	Agree	20 (55.6%)	16 (44.4%)	1
		2	Agree	22 (68.8%)	10 (31.3%)	1
31	Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions.	1	Agree	27 (75%)	9 (25%)	1.25
		2	Agree	22 (68.8%)	10 (31.3%)	1

*n=31: missing data (n=1), †one participant opted to both agree and disagree, so their score was split evenly across the two categories.

On retesting, the panel considered nursing as able to articulate its contribution to policy (Table 6.14, Statement 1), and contribute to policy discussions (Table 6.14, Statement 31). The qualitative comments however reinforced the earlier finding of nursing as sometimes overlooked by decision makers (6.10):

“Nurses don’t have strong hold in [my country]. I have met many who have tried to change things, including myself, to no avail. Hopefully someone is listening somewhere.” P15 (Education/Health Providing Organisation, High Income)

“Nursing leaders are able to articulate the contribution nursing makes to healthcare very well. However, they are often not heard!” P6 (Government, High Income)

The perception that nursing’s potential was communicated but not listened to was consistent with the panel consensus that nursing struggles to influence public policy (Table. 6.14, Statement 5).

“Nurses in my country are seldom included in the public policy process. They are expected to concentrate on clinical care and services.” P22 (Government/Professional Nursing Association/Regulator, Upper Middle Income)

Marginalisation of nursing in policy making (Table 6.14, Statements 5 and 12) appeared to be linked to the perception of the profession as ill equipped to engage in policy activities (Table 6.14, Statement 37). Mitigating negative perceptions included approaches to strengthen the credibility of the individual nurse leader:

“Nurses are often dismissed as ‘stupid’ by health administrators and doctors and that is why they must appear as credible at every opportunity presenting” P6 (Government, High Income)

The perception of nurses as lacking expert or legitimate power to influence policy seems to centre on both the knowledge held by the profession, as well as it as having a primary focus on care delivery. Despite the challenges of external perception and internal preparedness, the panel considered nursing to be making an effective contribution to strategic policy (Table 6.14, Statement 31).

6.13 Retested Round 1 statements not reaching consensus in Round 2

Ten statements initially presented in Round 1 demonstrated persisting divergence in Round 2 (Table 6.15). A common theme among the diverging statements was their dependence on context and culture. For example, the extent to which national structures and processes exclude nurses from policy (Table 6.15, Statement 26) and the image of nursing (Table 6.15, Statement 19) are both known to vary internationally.

Whilst there was agreement in Round 1 that nurses should work collaboratively to influence policy (Table 6.7, Statement 16), there were polarised experiences of cross-sectoral coordinated working (Table 6.15, Statement 11). Several panellists provided specific examples of success in coordinated activity such as:

“Since the inception of [anonymised organisation], nurse leaders from the four legs [sectors] of nursing have started working together” P32 (Education/Trade Union/PNA, Upper Middle Income)

Contrastingly, others elaborated on a lack of collaborative working between nurse leaders:

“Nurse leaders are often out for their own glorification and do not understand the power of working as a united front” P6 (Government, High Income)

“We are dismally poor at speaking with one voice on key issues” P7 (Education, High Income)

The quantitative and qualitative data illustrate international variation in the enablers and challenges to realising the ambitions of working collaboratively.

Table 6.15 Retested Round 1 statements not reaching consensus in Round 2, ordered by strength of consensus in Round 2

R1 ID	Round 1 Statement	Round	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
18	Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	1	Disagree	16 (45.7%*)	19 (54.3%*)	1
		2	Disagree	10 (33.3%†)	20 (66.7%†)	1
21	Nursing has an effective political voice	1	Disagree	15 (41.7%)	21 (58.3%)	1
		2	Disagree	11 (34.4%)	21 (65.6%)	1
19	Nursing has a strong, credible professional image, which helps them to influence public policy.	1	Agree	20 (55.6%)	16 (44.4%)	1
		2	Agree	19 (61.3%*)	12 (38.7%*)	1
24	There are unique public health policy issues in my country.	1	Agree	24 (66.7%)	12 (33.3%)	1
		2	Agree	19 (61.3%*)	12 (38.7%*)	1
46	There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	1	Agree	23 (63.9%)	13 (36.1%)	1
		2	Agree	19 (59.4%)	13 (40.6%)	1
11	Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	1	Disagree	16 (44.4%)	20 (55.6%)	1
		2	Disagree	14 (43.8%)	18 (56.3%)	1
10	Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	1	Disagree	15 (41.7%)	21 (58.3%)	1
		2	Agree	16 (53.3%†)	14 (46.7%†)	1
33	Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	1	Agree	23 (63.9%)	13 (36.1%)	1
		2	Agree	17 (53.1%)	15 (46.9%)	1
2	There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	1	Disagree	19 (52.8%)	17 (47.2%)	1
		2	Disagree/Agree	16 (50%)	16 (50%)	1
26	National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.	1	Agree/Disagree	18 (50%)	18 (50%)	1
		2	Agree/Disagree	16 (50%)	16 (50%)	1

*missing data (n=1), † missing data (n=2)

Several panellists felt that whilst the nursing image was strong (Table 6.15, Statement 19), as evidenced by being trusted by the public, it did not translate into policy influence:

"...Registered Nurses rated most trusted and ethical profession in [my country]; strong image but not as influential as we would like" P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

"Nursing has a good, sympathetic image, which helps them be loved by populations/clients, but yet not strong and credible enough to influence policy" P2 (Education, High Income)

The idea of nursing's lack of credibility as a policy actor as a reason for weak policy influence was reflected in other free text responses including:

"In my country nurses are perceived more as medical doctor helper than profession that is able to contribute to public policy making" P19 (Education, High Income)

The perception of nurses as not a natural choice for policy making also pervaded the comments around the polarised views of national structures and systems as obstacles to nursing participation in policy (Table 6.15, Statement 26):

"I do not think nurses are deliberately excluded it's just the people in power don't think of nurses from the outset unless they are reminded" P21 (Regulation, High Income)

"...there is no overt exclusion, but the structures and processes do not favour nursing inclusion" P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

Where panellists reported nursing as embedded in broader structures policy engagement was achieved:

"Nursing is an integral part of government hence is involved in policy development on health issues" P16 (Education, Low Income)

Action by nursing associations and government nurses was one proposed approach to build nursing into national structures:

"A combined effort by the nursing organisations and chief government nurses can ensure that nursing is included in all relevant national structures" P6 (Government, High Income)

One panellist reflected on their perception of nursing as having an ineffective political voice (Table 6.15, Statement 21) in their country due to the lack of a senior role for nursing in government:

"The fact that there is no CNO [Chief Nursing Officer] positioned in the MOH [Ministry of Health] is a case in point that nursing still needs to make its position recognised" P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

The image and status of nursing seemed to impact on the policy influence of the profession, manifesting in the lack of government nurse leadership roles in government, and being excluded or overlooked in policy discussions. International variation was evident with some participants noting the positive impact on policy influence of being integrated into the structures of government decision making.

6.14 Persisting Divergence: Nursing’s Policy Focus

In Round 1 panellists reached consensus that nursing would benefit from a broader policy focus (Table 6.16, Statement 20) and that there was an existing tendency to focus on policies directly related to nursing (Table 6.16, Statement 6). When asked whether policy should focus more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues, the panel was polarised (Table 6.16, Statements 20, 6 and 10 respectively). To understand this divergence, the policy focus of the profession was retested and explored in an open-ended question in Round 2.

Table 6.16 Nursing’s Policy Focus: Patients or the Profession

ID	Statement	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
R1 20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	Agree	35 (97.2%)	1 (2.8%)	1
R1 6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	Agree	32 (88.9%)	4 (11.1%)	0.25
R1 10	Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	Round 1	Disagree 15 (41.7%)	21 (58.3%)	1
		Round 2	Agree 16 (53.3%*)	14 (46.7%*)	1

*n=30, missing data n=2

Retesting of Statement 10 in Round 2 revealed persisting divergence within the panel about whether the policy focus of nursing should be directed more towards patients and communities rather than professional issues (Table 6.16, Statement 10). Qualitative comments were analysed for both the retesting of the statement itself and the following open-ended question in Round 2:

‘In Round 1 there was agreement that to increase policy influence nursing needs to focus on broader policy issues, yet there was disagreement about whether there should be a focus on professional issues or patients and communities. What do you think the policy focus of nursing should be?’ (Round 2 Questionnaire, Appendix 14)

The qualitative responses reflected the divergence in the quantitative data with seven panellists providing statements in support of a policy focus on professional issues, eight in support of giving policy primacy to patients and communities, and three advocating for dual focus. Five of the

panellists argued for a primary focus on professional issues on the basis that this would improve patient care. Three examples of the argument for a profession-oriented focus included:

“The policy focus of nursing should be related to nursing professional issues (such as political positions, funding and manpower) and then the patients and communities will get higher standardised care” P30 (Professional Nursing Association/Health Providing Organisation, High Income)

“A focus on the profession must/should have positive effects on care for patients and communities, e.g. by lobbying for time off to undertake continuing education will enhance patient care as the nurse will be cognisant with contemporary treatments and care modalities.” P6 (Government, High Income)

“Nursing should focus more on professional issues that will in return influence improvement in caring of patients and quality services in communities” P10 (Regulator, Low Income)

Several panellists who preferred a patient and communities orientated policy focus framed it as a strategy to improving the policy influence of nursing:

“I think we turn the public and other professions off when we go on about professional issues, but it is less easy to deny what we are saying when we are advocating for patients and communities.” P2 (Education, High Income)

“The policy should focus on health and health related issues and the role of nursing in effecting positive change. This would be more supported by stakeholders and nursing issues can also be brought into focus. On the other hand, focusing more on nursing issues may not receive stakeholder support as might be expected.” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

The conflicting perspectives on what should be given primacy in the policy focus of the profession is an interesting finding and is discussed further in Chapter 8.

6.15 Preparation for Round 3

The final round of the Delphi had dual purposes. The first was to present a draft consensus statement crafted from statements that had achieved consensus in Rounds 1 and 2. The consensus statement was drafted to give panellists an opportunity to consider a synthesised view of their perspectives on strategic nurse leadership in public policy and reflect on its resonance and potential practical utility. The second purpose of Round 3 was to re-test eight statements which did not reach consensus when introduced in Round 2. The eight item statements did not include any leadership approaches relevant to the content of the consensus statement. They focused instead on

understanding experiences and perceptions relating to enablers and challenges in policy influence (Tables 6.17 and 6.18). Re-testing the eight statements therefore partially supported work to address the first research aim, in regard to understanding the challenges for international nurse leaders in public policy.

6.15.1 Development of the draft consensus statement

The purpose of the consensus statement was to offer a concise, high-level global perspective on strategic nurse leadership in public policy and provoke further reflections from the panel. Directly incorporating all 55 statements that had reached consensus by the end of Round 2 would have been unwieldy and cumbersome. Developing a cohesive statement rather than reporting discrete items enabled the panel to consider the findings relating to approaches to strengthening nursing's policy influence of Rounds 1 and 2 as an interlinked whole.

Drafting the consensus statement was undertaken in line with the process outlined in 4.5.12. The original statements were grouped by concept and then reviewed for inclusion, with reference to the purpose of the consensus statement. The grouped concepts were then synthesised into a narrative statement with critical review from the supervisory team and a topic expert, external to the Delphi panel. The purpose of this input was to help capture the higher-level strategic essence of the statements, which had achieved consensus, remove repetition and debate exclusions reflexively. Statements were excluded where they were reflections on current context, e.g. dominance of medicine, operational detail, e.g. that professional associations should be involved in delivery of education, or at the level of individual leaders.

The draft consensus statement, presented in Figure 6.3, highlights the statements synthesised from the Delphi findings in grey, annotated with the relevant statement identifiers. Minor editorial and grammatical changes were made to some statements for clarity or brevity. To confirm that the consensus statement stayed close to the data each draft was compared to the original list of statements. Appendix 24 maps the original statements that achieved consensus to the content of the consensus statement.

Figure 6.3 Draft Consensus Statement annotated with underpinning statement ID numbers.

Draft Consensus Statement

The advancement of public health and wellbeing through policy making must be informed by nursing expertise^{R1 17,28}. Ensuring that this expertise is used effectively for the benefit of global health requires more nurse leaders to hold policy making positions^{R2 6} and to possess policy influence, the development of which is a key priority for the nursing profession^{R1 23, 8}.

To improve policy influence nurses must be recognised as active and influential decision makers^{R2 9, 32}. To achieve this there is a need to establish a credible and collective nursing voice developed through international collaboration of strategic nurse leaders^{R1 16, 25, 30, 32}. National nursing strategies will inform this collaboration by providing clarity and direction of vision tailored to the needs of each country^{R2 33}. This will enable the application of cultural and contextual understanding to internationally shared priorities^{R1 35, 44} which will ensure the formulation of responses which are effective and appropriate at a national level.

Proactively expanding the scope of nursing's policy activity beyond issues directly related to the profession will progress nursing's policy influence^{R1 20}. The credibility of nurse leaders' contributions across a wider range of issues relevant to society will be strengthened by collaboration out with nursing and health care^{R1 3, 27, 34}. Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking^{R1 15}.

Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles^{R1 37, 40, R2 11, 19}. Additionally, an overarching plan to improve the capacity and capability of nursing for policy making^{R1 43} would provide a framework to optimise the quality and impact of the nursing contribution to policy. This framework is expected to include the development of a defined leadership pathway^{R2 24} and structures for systematic succession planning^{R1 36, 38}.

Annotation Key: grey highlighting: synthesised statements from Round 1 (R1), Round 2 (R2), annotated with statement identifier.

After drafting, the consensus statement was reviewed and refined on the basis of feedback from the test panel of four nurse leaders who pilot tested each Delphi round prior to distribution to the panel. Refinements included splitting it into four paragraphs and adding some linking phrases (Figure 6.3, unhighlighted text) to improve the readability and coherence of the statement. The consensus statement was presented with the Round 3 questionnaire (Appendix 16). The questionnaire asked the Delphi panel to consider the draft consensus statement and answer questions relating to its resonance, key messages, potential utility, and suggested refinements.

6.16 Round 3: Overview of findings

The Round 3 questionnaire (Appendix 16) presented panellists with eight item statements which did not reach consensus in Round 2 for review, and the draft consensus statement. A series of questions accompanied the consensus statement. The questions related to the resonance and potential utility of the statement and suggestions for refinement. It also sought to elicit panellist perspectives on the statement's key messages.

6.17 Retested Round 2 statements reaching consensus in Round 3

Eight statements, which did not reach consensus in Round 2, were retested in Round 3 and of those, two achieved consensus. Across all eight statements retested in Round 3 there were two items of missing data (Table 6.17, Statement 14, and Table 6.18, Statement 12).

Table 6.17 Retested Round 2 statements reaching consensus in Round 3, ordered by strength of consensus in Round 3

R2 ID	Round 2 Statement	Round	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
11	Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.	2	Agree	19 (59.4%)	13 (40.6%)	1
		3	Agree	17 (70.8%)	7 (29.2%)	1
14	Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy.	2	Agree	18 (56.25%)	14 (43.75%)	1
		3	Agree	16 (69.6%*)	7 (30.4%*)	1

*n=23, missing data n=1

While the consensus should be interpreted with caution given the change in the numbers of completing Delphi panellists. The data however demonstrates that for Statement 11, “Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy” seven of the responding panellists in Round 3 changed direction from disagreement in Round 2 to agreement with the statement in Round 3. Only three changed their perspective from agreement to disagreement between rounds. Similarly for Statement 14 (Table 6.17), 13 panellists moved from disagreement to agreement that generally nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to policy. Only three panellists changed from agreement to disagreement. These analyses promote confidence that the findings were due to a change in panellist perspective rather than an artefact associated with the attrition in Round 3.

Nurses were perceived to generally not expect that they should prioritise contributing to policy (Table 6.17, Statement 14). As two panellists observed:

“Often nurses feel that they cannot influence and therefore don’t even attempt to.” P13
(Education, High Income)

“Generally, nurses perceive themselves as consumers of policy implications.” P1 (Non-governmental Organisation, Lower Middle Income)

Almost a third of panellists disagreed, with lack of opportunity, rather than interest offered as one obstruction to policy participation:

“Perhaps a few [lack interest] but they lack the opportunity to contribute.” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

These qualitative reflections provide an insight into the variation in perceptions and experiences of international nurse leaders.

6.18 Retested Round 2 statements not reaching consensus in Round 3

Six statements did not reach consensus on retesting in Round 3 (Table 6.18). There was persisting divergence about whether nurses lack interest in policy making (Table 6.18, Statement 13) or whether they perceive policy involvement to be beneficial (Table 6.18, Statement 15). Qualitative responses again reflected a sense that it was often lack of opportunity rather than lack of interest, which was a primary barrier to participation:

“It is beneficial but the chance for decision making, and policy participation are very limited”
P8 (Education/Government, Lower-Middle Income)

Some panellists considered policy participation to not be seen by nurses as beneficial (Table 6.18, Statement 15). One panellist expanded on their perspective linking lack of tangible benefit and policy engagement, stating:

“If nurses see no positive outcomes of their involvement in policy making, they will lose interest.” P6 (Government, High Income)

The link to contextual and cultural norms within and beyond nursing appeared to reinforce each other with lack of expectation contributing to lack of engagement, and a perception of similar in reverse.

Table 6.18 Retested Round 2 statements not reaching consensus in Round 3, ordered by strength of consensus in Round 3

R2 ID	Round 2 Statement	Round	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
12	Nurse leaders do not take an active role in policy making.	2	Agree	20 (66.7% [†])	10 (33.3% [†])	1
		3	Agree	14 (60.9%*)	9 (39.1%*)	1
4	The hierarchy within nursing is complicated and this adversely affects policy contribution.	2	Agree	16 (51.6%*)	15 (48.4%*)	1
		3	Disagree	11 (45.8%)	13 (54.2%)	1
13	Nurses lack interest in policy making	2	Agree	16 (51.6%*)	15 (48.4%*)	1
		3	Disagree	11 (45.8%)	13 (54.2%)	1
10	It is difficult to gain access to the decision makers in policy.	2	Agree	19 (59.4%)	13 (40.6%)	1
		3	Agree	13 (54.2%)	11 (45.8%)	1
15	Involvement in policy making is not perceived by nurses as beneficial.	2	Disagree	14 (46.7% [†])	16 (53.3% [†])	1
		3	Disagree	11 (45.8%)	13 (54.2%)	1
3	Nurse leaders are not in a stable position which makes it difficult to develop policy influence and to take risks	2	Agree	21 (65.6%)	11 (34.4%)	1
		3	Agree	13 (54.2%)	11 (45.8%)	1

*missing data (n=1), [†]missing data (n=2)

Just over half of the panellists considered nurse leaders as not in a stable position (Table 6.18, Statement 3). In the qualitative comments, three of those who agreed with the statement elaborated that in their context:

“They are all in easy to fire positions” P37 (Education, High Income)

“When one tries to change something, it is a long process which may result in one losing their job because they speak out of their role” P15 (Education/Health Providing Organisation, High Income)

“Nursing leadership position in the Ministry of Health no longer exists” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

One participant who disagreed added:

“Disagree, but they fear so much they fail to make decisions” P16 (Education, Low Income).

This inference suggests that even where there is stability there is fear, which has the potential to affect the ability of some nurse leaders to take risks, perhaps suggesting that this could constrain their policy influence.

6.19 Considerations of Stability

Although achieving stability between rounds is considered to promote confidence in the trustworthiness of the findings and indicative of rigour, the social constructionist approach to a modified Policy Delphi (3.5) does not particularly value a fixed perspective. The social constructionist epistemology of this study, and its tenet of knowledge construction as a social process anticipated that panellists may change their minds following further reflection on the topic, and the between round feedback. As such the stability is included for interest only. Using the method in Manzano-García and Ayala (2017), as detailed in 4.5.3 the stability of individual panellist judgements was calculated as the percentage of statements where their level of agreement was unchanged between rounds. The mean stability of the group was then calculated. The mean stability of the group for Round 1 statements retested in Round 2 was 73.2%. For the Round 2 statements retested in Round 3 the mean stability of the group was calculated as 79.7%. The narrative responses in Round 3 provide more nuanced insights into the resonance of the content of the consensus statement from the perspective of the Delphi panel.

6.20 Round 3: Resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement

All responding panellists (n=24) agreed that the draft consensus statement would be useful to nurse leaders and that it reflected their views (n=23, missing data n=1) (Table 6.19).

Table 6.19 Reflections on the Draft Consensus Statement

	Median	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	IQR
This statement would be useful to nurse leaders	Strongly Agree	24 (100%)	0 (0%)	1
This statement would be useful to me in influencing policy	Agree	21 (91.3%*)	2 (8.75%*)	1
This statement reflects my views	Strongly agree	23 (100%*)	0 (0%*)	1

*n=23: missing data (n=1)

Almost all panellists indicated that the statement would be useful to them in influencing policy (Table 6.19). One of the two panellists who did not feel that the statement would be useful to them argued that the statement was:

“Too nurse focused without making strong case to public policy power brokers.” P20
(Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

More than three quarters of panellists (79%, 19/24) indicated that they could imagine using the statement in their work. The two most frequently identified uses were within expanding the policy capacity and capability of nurses (n=19) and supporting the lobbying of external actors for nurse perspectives to be included in policy discussion (n=8).

6.20.1 Use of the statement: building capacity and capability

The use of the statement to support expansion of capacity and capability of nursing in policy revolved around both using the statement as an educational tool but also as a stimulus for the inclusion of leadership and policy in nursing curricula.

“It [the statement] would also be useful when addressing or debating on it [policy influence] with senior nurse students and other nurses” P26 (Regulator, Low Income)

“To support changes in curriculum at baccalaureate and Masters level in nursing education provided at our faculty” P19 (Education, High Income)

6.20.2 Use of the statement: lobbying for nursing inclusion in policy making

Several panellists viewed the statement as a call to action to lobby for nurses to be included in high level decision making:

“Using this statement or at least having it as background can provide a framework for lobbying in all senses of this term for the inclusion of nursing at decision making tables” P6 (Government, High Income)

“I would use this to lobby for nurses to be recognised as active and influential decision makers to improve policy influence.” P23 (Government, High Income)

6.20.3 Reasons the statement would not be used

Five of the 24 responding panellists stated that they could not imagine using the statement in their work. Four of the five were from high income countries. Two indicated that the statement required further alteration elaborating:

“Good principles but don’t think it would have much impact as currently worded and presented.” P7 (Education, High Income)

“At present format, still vague.” P1 (Non-governmental Organisation, Lower Middle Income)

A further two panellists considered that the statement did not add anything to the current perspective in their country:

“It does not establish anything more than is already known.” P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

with the second panellist adding:

“Because, in all modesty, I think my country’s health system already know that. The main difficulty is to find adequate skilled nurse having the willing to engage herself at national policy/leadership level... also from my point of view, it is not the system that miss to engage nurses at important position, but nurses who have to take the power.” P37 (Education, High Income)

Finally, one panellist stated that they would not use the statement due to

“Shortage in nurses and economic crisis” P29 (Education/Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

This mixture of perspectives reflects the diversity of contexts that nurse leaders work in internationally, and the importance of seeking views out with the Global North, to understand what would help the global nurse leadership community at large enhance their policy influence.

6.21 Refining the Draft Consensus Statement: panellist suggestions

Almost all the Round 3 panellists (83.3%, 20/22) agreed that the statement was easy to understand. Two panellists did not provide an opinion or comment on ease of comprehension. Of the two panellists who did not find the statement easy to understand one had a general comment and one had a specific sentence they found problematic. The broad comment was:

“It is understandable but feels a bit rambling, slightly off centre and repetitive – needs to be more punchy to have impact” P7 (Education, High Income)

The sentence identified as not easy to understand by P1 (Non-government Organisation, Lower-Middle Income) was:

“Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking”

They did not expand on the way in which the sentence was problematic.

Five panellists made suggestions for specific edits of which two were related to minor wording changes. The first noted that a sentence had too many words beginning with ‘p’. The second made

an interesting observation about the use of the word 'must' in the first sentence of the statement: 'The advancement of public health and wellbeing through policy making must be informed by nursing expertise'. Panellist 19, a nurse leader in education, stated:

"I think the word 'must' in the very first sentence could be considered too demanding in my country as nursing is traditionally not perceived to be an 'expert' here and there is currently huge issue related to nursing education at university level that is unfortunately presented as not beneficial. Maybe 'is necessary to' wouldn't sound so irritating to some opponents" P19 (Education, High Income)

Highlighting the use of the word 'must' raises two interesting points. First, the ongoing challenges for nursing including in high income countries, and the lack of agreement about the need for nurse education. The quote also surfaces an aversion to appearing irritating, or difficult, potentially linked to culturally mediated expectations of nursing and nurse leadership. Contrastingly, three participants advocated for a more direct, outward facing and aim orientated statement. As one panellist proposed using the statement as a call to action:

"Change tone to be action oriented and targeted to others in policy making decisions" P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

Panellist 20 (High Income, Professional Nursing Association) also advocated for framing the statement to connect with professions out with nursing:

"The statement should make a strong case as to why nurses should be influencing policy. It should be directed to an audience other than nurses with an imperative to include and embrace nurses' viewpoints as essential to improving health and wellbeing around the globe" P20 (Professional Nursing Association, High Income)

This well placed critique of the potential risk of such a statement only reaching people already bought into the principles is a helpful point. It does however also suggest that the statement contains shared global perspectives on nursing's policy influence. Panellist 7 (High Income, Education) echoed the need to mandate a nursing policy contribution within the statement:

"Something around the goal being nursing having a seat at every health policy table/forum" P7 (Education, High Income)

Contextualising the statement by describing the drivers underpinning its development was suggested by one panellist:

“emphasise what influenced the development of the consensus statement.” P1 (Non-governmental Organisation, Lower Middle Income)

6.22 The Draft Consensus Statement: Identifying key messages from the text

The panellists were asked to identify the three most important key messages within the statement (Table 6.20). The most popular key message was around the need to equip strategic nurse leaders with leadership and policy education. In addition to education, there was a clear focus on changing perceptions as well as approaches to increase the visibility and contribution of nursing in policy making.

Table 6.20 Key messages within the draft consensus statement

Most important messages	Frequency
Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles.	15
Nurses must be recognised as active and influential decision makers	9
Development of a collective voice	7
International collaboration of nurse leaders	7
More nurse leaders to hold policy making positions	5
Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking	3
Development of a defined leadership pathway and structures for systematic succession planning	3
Policy making to be informed by nursing expertise	3
Expanding policy activity beyond issues directly related to nursing	3
Development of policy influence is a priority	3
Development of national nursing strategies	2
Active participation in policy wherever there is opportunity	1
To improve policy, nurse influence must be active	1
Collaboration with wider health system	1
Infrastructure for policy implementation	1
Nurse leader contributions to policy	1
Country specific recognition of cultural differences.	1
Clear goals	1
Identification of needed actions and activities	1
Guidelines and clear reasons for actions	1

The statements selected as important by at least one panellist are highlighted in grey in Figure 6.4. The only statement not chosen was the proposal for *“an overarching plan to improve the capacity and capability of nursing for policy making”*. This is interesting given that the most frequently identified key message was in the preceding sentence:

“Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles” (Table 6.20). Almost all of the key messages identified by one panellist only were personal interpretations rather than verbatim statements.

Figure 6.4 Draft Consensus Statement: key messages identified by panellists (highlighted in grey)

Draft Consensus Statement

The advancement of public health and wellbeing through policy making must be informed by nursing expertise^{R1 17, 28}. Ensuring that this expertise is used effectively for the benefit of global health requires more nurse leaders to hold policy making positions^{R2 6} and to possess policy influence, the development of which is a key priority for the nursing profession^{R1 8, 23}.

To improve policy influence nurses must be recognised as active and influential decision makers^{R2 9, 32}. To achieve this there is a need to establish a credible and collective nursing voice developed through international collaboration of strategic nurse leaders^{R1 16, 25, 30, 32}. National nursing strategies will inform this collaboration by providing clarity and direction of vision tailored to the needs of each country^{R2 33}. This will enable the application of cultural and contextual understanding to internationally shared priorities^{R1 35, 44} which will ensure the formulation of responses which are effective and appropriate at a national level.

Proactively expanding the scope of nursing’s policy activity beyond issues directly related to the profession will progress nursing’s policy influence^{R1 20}. The credibility of nurse leaders’ contributions across a wider range of issues relevant to society will be strengthened by collaboration out with nursing and health care^{R1 3, 27, 34}. Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking^{R1 15}.

Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles^{R1 37, 40, R2 11}. Additionally, an overarching plan to improve the capacity and capability of nursing for policy making^{R1 43} would provide a framework to optimise the quality and impact of the nursing contribution to policy. This framework is expected to include the development of a defined leadership pathway^{R2 24} and structures for systematic succession planning^{R1 36, 38}.

Annotation Key: R1: Round 1, R2: Round 2, No.: statement identifier

6.23 Key Findings from the Delphi study

This chapter has presented the findings of the three round modified Policy Delphi including the novel construction of the draft consensus statement on global perspectives of strategic nurse leadership in policy. The findings indicate dimensions of cultural and contextual divergence, which while expected, enable identification of aspects, which may particularly benefit from contextually specific approaches. The development of the consensus statement also demonstrates that there is common ground around which nurse leaders could coalesce to progress the policy influence of the profession. Key points from the consensus statement included a focus on preparation of future nurse leaders, shifting perceptions and approaches to increasing the visibility and contribution of the profession. The post-Delphi interviews, reported in the next chapter, build on the findings of the Delphi, and further explore the resonance and potential usefulness of the statement.

Chapter 7: Post-Delphi Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the final research activity: post-Delphi interviews with government nurse leaders. The purpose of these interviews was to explore their perspectives on the resonance and potential utility of the consensus statement. The chapter opens with the recruitment and characteristics of the participants. The findings of the framework analysis are then presented illustrated by quotes and focused directly on the interview questions. Key messages and potential utility of the consensus statement are explored, followed by participant suggestions on what next for the consensus statement. The discussions around the statement were richly contextualised by the participant's reflections on their experiences of leadership in policy.

7.1 Background to the interviews

The purpose of the post-Delphi interviews was to strengthen the rigour of the Delphi. Government nurse leaders were recruited to allow exploration of the consensus statement with nurse leaders occupying roles closest to policy making at a national level. The sampling frame was informed by the list of GCNOs and government nurse leaders supplied by the WHO (4.6.1).

Potential participants were each sent a personalised email, covering letter, and participant information sheet (Appendix 18). Those who expressed interest were sent the consent form (Appendix 19), and briefing paper (Appendix 20) containing the consensus statement, and interview guide. The papers were sent at least one week before the arranged interview date to allow for preparation and reflection (full details in 4.6.3). At the beginning of each individual interview consent was reaffirmed and the participant was reminded of their right to withdraw from the study. The semi-structured interviews were audio recorded and lasted an average of 31 minutes. The interviews were deliberately concise following consideration of the participants' elite position and the focussed nature of the interviews. Four of the ten interviews were transcribed verbatim by the PhD candidate to promote familiarisation and immersion in the data. For efficiency, the remaining six interviews were transcribed verbatim by a professional transcribing service.

7.2 Participant Characteristics

Thirty-four nurse leaders with a government role were invited to take part in the post-Delphi interviews. Only one of the 34 had been previously involved in the study. Initially ten government nurse leaders indicated interest in taking part. Unfortunately, three did not progress to interview. One was uncontactable following initial expression of interest, a second withdrew citing a self-assessment of insufficient English language skills, and a third was unable to complete the interview despite arranging three successive dates.

Seven interviews were completed however the researcher assessed that due to a European dominant sample, further data were required to improve the trustworthiness of the findings. Initial framework analysis also suggested that there were still new insights being generated by the seventh interview. Whilst social constructionism recognises the multiplicity of experiences (Burr, 2015), expanding the number of interviews was sought in order to strengthen the rigour of the findings. In line with the guidance for recruitment in elite research (Goldman and Swayze, 2012; Solarino and Aguinis, 2021) a member of the supervisory team made an initial approach to a further four potential participants who had not been part of the initial invitations. Three indicated their interest to the researcher and progressed to interview, giving a final cohort of ten government nurse leaders. The government nurse leaders were interviewed, eight via telephone and two via Skype (one audio, one audiovisual).

The participants comprised nine women and one man. They ranged in experience in strategic government related roles (Table 7.1) with more than half (n=7) holding their current strategic leadership position for at least five years. Nine were located directly within the government structure and one was a government advisor within a country which did not have a designated position for nursing in government.

Table 7.1 Years in current government nurse role

Years in current role	No. Panellists (n=10)
<1	0
1-4	3
5-9	3
10+	4

Five of the six World Health Organisation regional office areas were represented among the ten countries (Table 7.2). Ten government nurse leaders from African nations were invited to take part, 2 expressed interest but were unable to complete the interview. There was also no representation from Spanish speaking countries, a limitation explored further in 8.2.

Table 7.2 Geographic dispersion of participants

Region	No. Countries represented (n=10)
Africa	0
Americas	2
South-East Asia	1
Europe	2
Eastern Mediterranean	4
Western Pacific	1

Despite inviting potential participants across national income levels high income countries were disproportionately represented, as shown in Table 7.3.

Table 7.3 Participant dispersion by World Bank income level

World Bank Income Level	No. Panellists (n=10)
High	7
Upper-Middle	2
Lower-Middle	0
Low	1

7.3 Resonance of the consensus statement: government nurse leader perspectives

Each participant selected and shared what they perceived as the key messages from the consensus statement. Several of the government nurse leaders stated that the statement as a whole resonated with them.

“First of all, I think this has captured a lot of the key messages which are really dear to my heart and things I think are critical to nursing...I don’t think health and policy making has capitalised on the potential of nurse leaders to inform policy. I think it is a resource which is very underutilised, and I believe that this consensus statement does capture this in a very, solid way” P6 (Americas, High Income)

Almost all the participants highlighted that the contribution nursing offers policy making continues to be under-used. Several participants built on the potential for nurses to contribute further in the future:

“I liked actually the statement, and it is really touching our hearts that this is the future... because it is showing how the nurses can actually [be] influential for the decision making and for the health of the whole ... country” P7 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

The need to shift to recognise nurses as legitimate policy actors was a key message for three participants.

“I think nursing expertise ... should be used effectively in policy making, I think it will benefit global healthcare... I think this is really important because nurses should be recognised that they have this role... on a country level where they can influence decision making when it’s related to health policy in general” P5 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

Three participants identified national nursing strategies as an important part of the consensus statement. Together with welcoming the acknowledgement of a need for context sensitive approaches, the role of a strategy in establishing a shared vision was also recognised:

“One thing that is very important is the national nursing service strategy, the vision and direction to have nurs[ing]...in the same specific direction” P9 (South East Asia, Upper Middle Income)

Building on the need for a national shared direction of travel several participants identified strengthening the international nursing voice as a priority:

“Another priority that you mention in the consensus is making a voice led by international nursing collaboration...that’s going to benefit all the countries... to be speaking the same language, that’s very important.” P7 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

Beyond boosting the nursing voice, the benefits of international collaboration in facilitating connection and learning were highlighted by several participants. Participant 4 stated that this was particularly important in lower income countries:

“If we work with each other, we can do many things. But I strongly recommend if you recommend in your statement to make an international collaboration. This will help us. This is, it will help us in developing country. Because there is still a gap between our country as a developing country and the high [income] country.” P4 (Eastern Mediterranean, Low Income)

For Participant 4 the international nursing community represented a resource for strengthening their own influence at home by learning from other countries as well as benefiting from the strength and legitimacy of an international nursing voice. Interestingly a high income country participant expressed a differing perspective noting that international collaboration was not an essential component to their policy influence because they could collaborate with nurse leaders inside their country:

“My international collaboration does not predicate me being able to deliver my job because I look at expertise within my country ... it’s so strong to suggest you can’t do your job without, it has to be developed through international collaboration ideally yes, but you could do it, still do a lot of this consensus statement without it.” P10 (Europe, High Income)

The divergence here is one example of the variation international nurse leaders experience in opportunities and challenges, further explored in the discussion in Chapter 8.

7.3.1 Key messages from the consensus statement: personal priorities for participants

Four participants offered key messages which were a priority for them, the remaining six explored topics in the consensus statement without concretely identifying them as a priority for them individually. The statement seemed to prompt many of the nurse leaders to reflect on their own leadership. One participant described a key priority for them from the statement:

“This consensus paper you provided me with is clear framework on how to inform decision maker ... this consensus paper gives me directions that should look, should try to [balance] between strategic futuristic issues and operational issues. Being a leader sometimes you are pushed to do operational things, but you have to think always strategically” P8 (Eastern Mediterranean, Upper Middle Income)

The appetite for guidance on the ‘how to’ of policy influence was surprising and appeared in several interviews. It appeared to suggest that policy influence was still an ambition rather than reality for some participants. The importance of developing strategic leadership skills to support policy influence was a topic of particular interest to the participants:

“The one that is dearest to my heart though ... the statement here that leadership and policy education and you’ve got ‘is required to prepare nursing for strategic leadership roles’... I would word it probably even more strongly to say that it is critical for success of nurses in strategic leadership roles. So that one is, to me the one that is most uhm critical in my context and ... from my experience across the region it is critical to success at strategic nursing leadership roles” P6 (Americas, High Income)

Almost all participants supported this point, advocating for deliberate preparation of nurses for strategic roles. A lack of leadership and policy curricula across all levels of nurse education was highlighted as a widespread and persisting issue. Several participants recommended building on formal qualifications with mentorship and practical experience as a route to developing policy competence:

“[to] have chance to do experiences as eh policy ideas is much more important than only education... like with policy makers” P9 (South East Asia, Upper-Middle Income)

For several participants building the skills of nurses to lead in policy was also to develop the perception within the profession of nurses as influential leaders:

“...for me the priority must be nurse be aware she or he is significant part of leadership and policy. Not only outsiders but also nursing insiders that need nursing expertise can make a difference for policy influence.” P3 (Western Pacific, High Income)

In addition to nurses recognising themselves as leaders in policy, reorientating political decision makers to also share this view was considered a priority. One participant reflected on how the perception of nurses impacts on her own experience and influence as a nurse leader:

“...the [Professional Nursing Association] and you know the public tend to think of nurses as hands-on and, and possibly a bit in government so if you actually look ... our comms [communications] team go for the chief medical officer rather than the Chief Nursing Officer for a comment on things that are slightly wider than medicine” P2 (Europe, High Income)

In addition to decision makers seeking perspectives from medics rather than nurses, participants described the effects of medical dominance in policy making including resistance of medics to the inclusion of nurses and medics talking for nurses. One participant mooted the option of lobbying medics to advocate for nursing involvement in policy.

Whilst education was considered to hold a key role in improving the capacity of nurse leaders to influence policy, the implications of medical dominance and gender inequality did not escape the participants.

“A bit of an elephant in the room for me, remember I do these sorts of things internationally, is to do with the status of nursing and to do with the status of women. So, I don’t know how far ... you’re expecting this to go, this consensus statement. It’s fine in my country and nursing has got a good reputation. ... In other parts of the world nurses don’t have access to the minister, in fact it won’t be a nurse ... it’ll be held by a doctor, and that doctor will probably be male because nursing is seen as a low-level gender, women’s gender issue. So, we won’t be seen as having a credible voice, so in trying to determine some of this leadership ... it is as much about the status of women in society and the status of women’s work, which is associated with nursing that has to be tackled before you can get to any of this.” P10 (Europe, High Income)

The points made in this quote about gender, political relationships, and the wider challenges for women and nurses echo in some of the findings in the literature review (2.4.2), the pre-Delphi interviews (5.5.3), and qualitative comments in the Delphi (6.11). The international variation in the position and opportunities afforded to nurses, even at strategic positions that Participant 10 reflected on was evident across the personal priorities of participants. The key priorities for participants centred around preparing and positioning nurses to be leaders in policy making, whilst surfacing cultural and structural tensions in fulfilling the policy potential of the profession.

7.4 Potential utility of the consensus statement

The government nurses were asked to consider if and how they could envisage using the statement in their work. Whilst three participants described ways in which they could potentially use the statement, five did not answer the question directly and two stated that they couldn't use it in its current form. Practical uses for the statement focused on shaping the future direction of government nurse leadership, education, and informing their national nursing strategy:

"I'm thinking I certainly will want to make sure that this [the statement] is, if not explicitly talked about within the nursing [strategy] 'cause ... I'm assuming I can use it ... when does it stop being draft?... It clearly articulates part of what I'm needing to do with my job in terms of succession planning for my own personal role" P2 (Europe, High Income)

The potential of the statement to inform future activity of the government nurse leaders was also reflected by participant 4:

"I need it [the statement]. The position is not good in my country, we face, we still, we still face a lot of difficulties, just only I mention the successful move but really, we face a lot of difficulty. So, ... your statement is very important and maybe I read it again then I also I think I make I write eh what the statements we need... it will help us in our work." P4 (Eastern Mediterranean, Low Income)

Using the statement to guide future work was built on by one participant who advocated for wide dissemination of the statement and its potential to prompt further doctoral research. They considered the statement to have potential utility as a framework for the policy and practice decisions of GCNOs, in nurse education, and using it to stimulate discussion within professional nursing associations. Connecting the statement to broader priorities was, for one participant, key to the utility of the statement:

"How would I use this? I struggled to know what I would use this for. If it is hooked to WHO commitments I could and I can then make a dotted line... to my vision and the priorities I have... that would be useful actually" P10 (Europe, High Income)

Expanding on their point, the participant stated:

"Any consensus statement for, for a government nurse would have to be about helping deliver the political priorities ... but also the professional agenda ... to make sure that the work we do is ... based on the right values" P10 (Europe, High Income)

Taking a different perspective one participant assessed the potential utility of the statement in terms of its potential to influence decision makers to invite her to policy discussions, stating:

“Clearly, I failed because I’m not at the decision making tables, so but I will be totally honest with you, I can put this [statement] up to senior management and I’m still not going to be at the decision making table. ... they’re [decision makers] not seeing that value add, and I don’t know why.” P1 (Americas, High Income)

Although the participant thought the statement would not convince decision makers to include her, she referred to the statement as a call to action:

“I think that it’s [the statement], it’s a kind of a call to action for me to try and do the best I can to be at those tables and figure out ways, creative ways to actually get there because right now I think that I, and certainly nursing, are feeling somewhat shut out.” P1 (Americas, High Income)

This reflection suggested that the statement had a catalytic effect to some extent, prompting the leader to reassess their current approach to policy influence.

7.5 Consensus Statement: future potential

The participants were asked to share their suggestions to improve the statement. Focusing on how the statement could be improved offered an insight into the extent of the trustworthiness of the consensus statement as a product of the Delphi. All participants shared positively framed perspectives and identified three key considerations for improvement of the consensus statement: refining the language, building in the value of nursing in policy leadership, and legitimising the statement through endorsement of a credible international organisation such as the World Health Organisation.

7.5.1 Refining the consensus statement: language

Reflections on the language of the statement illustrated a tension between the appetite for both standardisation internationally and local contextualisation of the messages within it, the balancing of which is perhaps challenging to reconcile. Five participants, two with English as an additional language, stated that some editing to wording would be required for the statement to be used in their local context. One participant cautioned that to preserve the meaning and rigour of the statement simplifying its language prior to dissemination would be preferable to encouraging local adaptation. In addition to practical suggestions for improvements in clarity of language and interpretation two participants proposed additional context-specific detail, such as that there should be a lobby for the insertion a Chief Nursing Officer in countries without one.

From the perspective of disseminating a single version of the statement, several participants identified refinements to improve the accessibility of the statement. Thinking about sharing the statement internationally one participant suggested:

“I think uhm, you have to translate it [the statement] in all the language and give it to everyone.” P7 (Eastern Mediterranean Region, High Income)

Another participant recommended increasing the statements accessibility by lowering the level of language:

“Because uhm, who is this draft consensus statement going to be geared towards? ... if the answer we would like all nurses to understand it I think we you would have to write it in a language that is you know looking at grade six level language ... Shorter sentences, simpler phrasing, and that sort of thing...And the truth is if you reach, if you write it for the academic, for the, you’re actually writing it for the converted” P6 (Americas, High Income)

The reflections on translation and use of accessible language demonstrate an appetite to share the statement in a form which has impact and builds a shared understanding of the approaches to progress policy influence. While standardising the messaging was valued, reflections in the suggested divergence in preferences around tone and strength of language indicative of where context sensitive approaches may yield stronger agreement. For example, in one interview a participant shared:

“It’s [the statement has] got quite soft language in it ... make it a bit louder otherwise I don’t know what kind of traction it would have cause you’ve already got things they ought to be complying with and they’re not. A soft statement is not going to make a blind bit of difference quite frankly.” P10 (Europe, High Income)

While the language used in the statement was too soft for P10, a Delphi panellist reflected that it was not soft enough (6.21). This dissonance should be interpreted with caution given that it is only between two participants. It is however, a useful illustration of international differences in what is considered to constitute an appropriate and impactful approach.

7.5.2 Refining the consensus statement: Articulating nursing’s value in policy making

Many of the strategic nurse leaders were interested in how the consensus statement could be refined to strengthen the case for nursing inclusion in policy making.

“I think it [the statement] needs guts, I think it needs a so what, the value add, the business case, the rationale and it doesn’t have to be changed a lot, it just needs to be tweaked just a little bit to be a bit more strategic to include those elements.” P1 (Americas, High Income)

Several participants recommended revisions orientated to persuade decision makers by setting out a compelling case for why a nursing perspective should be sought. Articulating the unique nursing contribution was considered by many participants as important but complex to achieve.

“Because I am a nurse, when I read it [the statement], it might make sense to me ...but sometimes it may not make sense to people who are not in nursing...who maybe they are on decision making level but they don’t know how the nurse will be involved in a policy making, they will think ... are they expert to do that. You know sometimes they, they didn’t, maybe they didn’t have the opportunity to work with nurses who are on this level” P5 (Eastern Mediterranean Region, High Income)

This quote demonstrates that even nurses in government, arguably closest to the policy apparatus, see a persisting gap in the understanding of policy makers of the legitimacy and value of nurses as policy actors. One participant described her role in helping policy makers to understand the nursing perspective as two-way translation: translating the nursing perspective to policy makers and translating the decisions made in policy for nurses.

The absence of nursing at a policy table was considered by several participants as insufficient as a reason for nurse leaders to gain access. Instead, they recommended persuading policy makers by focusing on what nursing could offer to transform the health and wellbeing of communities rather than focusing on the nursing profession:

“I think we have to be careful we don’t just say you exclude us; you need to include us. I think we need to give them a reason to include us ...So actually some evidence about what difference we can make, and I think sometimes we’re a bit short on that ... I think it needs to be more than we’re here, remember us” P2 (Europe, High Income)

While articulating a persuasive ‘why’ for being involved in policy making was recommended by some participants, one government nurse leader shared a nuanced perspective. She stated that she did not use the word ‘nursing’ when making a policy contribution. In her experience it was more influential to position nursing as part of the solution to the policy problem, rather than its focus. This use of language and lenses familiar to policy makers was considered by several participants to be impactful in cultivating political support.

The generation and nurturing of political will was described by several participants as essential to the success of their policy advocacy. The benefits of a supportive political context on the progress of policy priorities were illustrated by the following quote:

*“If I look at some of the countries that have made great leaps forward, they’ve done exactly what this consensus statement has done. They’ve looked to other countries to see examples, so when I went to **** about two years ago, the lovely chief nurse there, she is a chief nurse in the government, so very nice health minister that does listen to her, ... she’s bringing in good practice internationally and driving it forward in her country, but she’s only able to do it because she is a chief nurse and she has a health minister that is allowing her to do that. So that the system allows it, but you also have somebody there that is strong enough to do that ... so as I say it’s sheer personification if you like of your statement.” P10 (Europe, High Income)*

This example of how political support can accelerate change underlines the importance of political will and of having a nurse in a policy making position. It also exposes the impact that structures and legislature can have on the policy influence of nurses.

Five participants highlighted the need to increase the number of nurses in policy making positions to both expand nursing’s policy reach and, as two participants articulated, share the “burden” of policy engagement. The benefits of having more nurses in policy making positions across sectors was argued by one participant to provide opportunities to move beyond siloed knowledge and connect to leverage the collective expertise of the profession:

“It’s not enough to have one nurse leader in the decision making because that nurse have to have really the capacity and the knowledge to be effective in the area of nurse education, nursing practice and nursing regulation and the international direction and policy ... I think it is not enough that to have one nurse having all this burden” P5 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

Several participants built on this perspective and discussed the value of nurses in policy making positions out with health. Other participants shared the value of the support of the international community in their experiences of creating structures to establish a strategic nursing policy voice:

“I start and ... make a position for the nursing profession in ministry of health ... this is the first, the first station that can help me ... so first thing is how can effect health policy by nursing leadership. When I start I don’t know from where can I start so many experts in the region, from ICN, from WHO, they are help me.” P4 (Eastern Mediterranean, Low Income)

Quotes such as this one give a flavour of the global variation in the position and context nurse leaders are working in. Cultural norms, organisational and legislative structures all have an influence on how conducive an environment is to the progress of nursing towards policy influence. As one participant summarised:

“So many things have to be right in order for, for our nurses to be in a strong lead position. They have to be educated. They have to have systems which enable them to progress. They have to have the confidence in order to do that. Cultures must allow them to be able to do it cause its mostly women that do this job. So many things have to be in the right place.” P10 (Europe, High Income)

Several participants navigating challenges in gaining the support of policy makers offered potential alternative strategies including connection to existing socio-political commitments of the government, international collaboration to gain legitimacy, and contributing to a range of policy issues to improve networks and visibility. This creativity illustrates the persistence and resilience valued by several participants as personal attributes of a policy active leader.

7.5.3 Refining the statement: Components of a credible policy actor

Being recognised as a credible decision maker in policy making was a recurring topic of interest throughout the pre-Delphi interviews, Delphi, and post-Delphi interviews. Whilst there are many aspects to being considered a credible policy voice, the post-Delphi participants particularly picked out the use of evidence, including finance, to frame policy positions, and individually building a credible reputation with policy makers.

7.5.3.1 Framing policy positions: the power of a broader lens

The policy influence of government nurses was considered by several participants to be contingent on the existence of, and access to the wider evidence base of the profession to inform robust policy positions. Most participants described evidence-based policy arguments as an important and impactful approach to persuade external decision makers:

“We have to talk about health economics. We have to understand what is the return on investment for the nursing? So, we keep on saying general work of nursing having impact on quality, but we have to quantify this work when we are talking about policy making [with the] minister ... the problem with nursing is that sometimes ... you do not have measurable data and we cannot measure nursing workload” P7 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

This quote highlights the challenge in moving beyond articulating the potential of the nursing contribution to evidencing it. Several participants advocated for the inclusion of financial

perspectives in the consensus statement due to their experience of the positive influence of including financial costs and benefits in policy arguments:

“... if you use the financial perspective approach then you, you know see the whole picture ... and people think you are leader because you can point out the whole picture. So, I always use this strategy you know when I make a report to my minister. I will draw the map and my financial perspective or impact ... and not just from ... professional skill ... It is not popular ... but I think it's very important behind policy you know we are talking about financial issues, so we should be trained” P3 (Western Pacific, High Income)

While this quote argues for the power of evidence in promoting inclusion of nursing perspectives in policy making it also suggests that framing policy arguments with a financial lens is a skill which strategic nurse leaders may not initially hold. Indeed, a further participant conceded that calculating and conveying the value add of the nursing contribution was not innately in the core nursing skillset. The critical role of developing skills in persuading decision makers of nursing's value add was emphasised by many participants.

7.5.3.2 Underpinning policy positions: leveraging research evidence

In addition to considering the financial benefits of a proposed policy, several government nurses described how they use research evidence to strengthen their policy advocacy. They suggested that the consensus statement would benefit from explicitly highlighting the role of research and evidence in policy influence. One participant explained her perspective on the progress and impact of knowledge gaps on her policy contribution:

“When I'm advising government ministers, I'm only as good as the profession in [my country], the research internationally, but particularly in [my country] and, and I think there's a lack of maturity ... I've just been in post for two and a half years and the profession has only been in universities for a couple of decades ... so my thinking's not as mature as it could be but, in terms of being able to provide evidence-based policy and an authority about what would work and what would, didn't work and how we need to change policy ... I think we need growth of knowledge and evidence from a nursing perspective so that that then can be joined up” P2 (Europe, High Income)

The impact of the relative academic youth of nursing was a reflection particular to Participant 2, however their perspective of a need for investment in expanding the research capacity of the profession was highlighted by others. Cross-sector collaboration and consequent knowledge

exchange was identified as one mechanism to formulating robust, evidence informed policy positions.

7.5.3.3 The importance of personal credibility

Many participants reflected on the importance of evidence in persuading decision makers not only of the merits of their policy position, but their personal credibility in that position. This personal credibility was positioned as an asset which is earned rather than automatically conferred:

“Sometime people don’t understand why the nurse have to be involved in something ... You know it’s why the nurse have to be involve in nursing legislation, nursing standard, for what reason, you know. People are used to making decisions for nurses, so for nursing, so this why I think when they see somebody who have knowledge to do that, like I always have support from people when, when they know that I am knowledgeable, and I know what I am doing.”

P5 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

Credibility as a critical factor in policy influence and getting policy opportunities was also a strong message in the pre-Delphi interviews (5.4.1 and 5.4.3). The pressure for strategic nurse leaders to prove themselves capable was echoed by several participants in the post-Delphi interviews who reflected on this as something which could only be overcome by actions:

“The strategic leader need power and influence not only power and know how to use it, you know how to use it to make an impact on others eh, ... and in our, our, our situation you have to prove yourself always as nurses, ... you have to prove yourself so you have to really prepare yourself ... to get all the respect you want being a nurse is really sometimes they are overlooking your skills ... but eh what ... when you show them what you have then they become respectful of you, of what you’re doing and they eh uh because power is ok but influence is more important.” P8 (Eastern Mediterranean, Upper Middle Income)

Respect as consequent to opportunity can be problematic if there are no opportunities available for nurse leaders to demonstrate their capability. In addition to the negative impact of a lack of evidence to support a policy position, the policy influence of a nurse leader can be threatened if their reputation is marred by poor performance or relationship breakdowns:

“You have to show certain big, big achievements at a country level then you have established that trust relationship and when you are given for example a certain type of [project] you have to show a good impact because unfortunately sometimes the first impression is the last. ... I have seen that between two people, not in nursing, because they [government minister or advisor] don’t like this person, because they have bad experience ... so they won’t to call her

next time But if you are leading well this group then I think they will fund our policy ... so if I give [results] to my superiors then I would be involved in many other projects. So, it's like contagious." P7 (Eastern Mediterranean, High Income)

Securing future policy influence was described as requiring a credible reputation built through a good track record in previous projects and developing positive relationships with policy makers. Participants perceived their policy influence as contingent on being contextually sensitive, evidence informed and building political support through strategic relationships.

7.5.4 Refining the statement: the importance of legitimacy

The government nurse leaders generated a range of proposed revisions focused on what would maximise the utility of the statement for nurse leaders. Three participants noted that the statement as a product of research rather than from a recognised organisation would limit its influence. As one reflected on the transition required:

"It's something also about how do we get a good piece of research like this and actually make it tangible and real and, and not just a very pretty academic exercise." P2 (Europe, High Income)

The potential of the statement following refinement was reflected in different ways by the participants. One participant, whilst recognising the need for changes to the statement, shared how the statement might help underpin future plans to improve policy influence:

"This is a study research but then it could be go further to more ... but at this time it should be this way because we need to continue with the [redrafting]... I don't know whether later on if we take every statement and see how we can make of this you know how we can go around doing this to change it into effective policy to help the people to develop the policies that is required in that area it will help us but not right now. I can see are going the right way your statement are good" P8 (Eastern Mediterranean, Upper Middle Income)

Not unsurprisingly, transforming the statement from a research output to a credible statement through a process of endorsement was considered key to its potential legitimacy and consequent utility and influence. One GCNO, noting the statement as an original contribution to knowledge stated:

"If there's never been a consensus statement for nursing around the relationship with policy development across healthcare then that would have been my next step to say how can I get this out to the wider world. How can I get this, how can I get the ICN [International Council of

Nurses] to, to buy into this? ... I do believe that it's a very, very useful piece of work and there's value in getting it out to the wider nursing world" P6 (Americas, High Income)

These findings raise pertinent questions about knowledge translation of research products, like the consensus statement. The place and extent of refinements based on the feedback is also a point of consideration, given that any substantive change based on individual perspectives would threaten the rigour of the statement as a product of consensus.

7.5.5 Refining the statement: next steps

The government nurse leaders offered three key reflections on refinements which would, if the consensus statement were to be used in practice, strengthen its resonance and utility: simplification of language, inclusion of the business case to policymakers for nursing's involvement in policy making, and a more action-oriented approach. The purpose of the post-Delphi interviews was to strengthen the rigour of the Delphi and understand the trustworthiness of the consensus statement as a research output. As such it would not have been methodologically appropriate to update the consensus statement on the basis of individual suggestions untested in a consensus-based process. What the refinements set out by the participants do offer is a starting point for future work. The findings suggest that there is an appetite to build on the potential of the statement as a tool to strengthen their approaches to policy influence.

7.6 Chapter Summary

This final research activity explored the resonance and potential utility of the draft consensus statement with ten government nurse leaders. The participants supported and suggested extensions to the content of the consensus statement. Reflecting on the potential utility of the statement within the public policy context of their country prompted rich discussion, which touched on topics beyond the statement content including the status of nursing and leadership preparation. Perspectives on the utility of the consensus statement largely focused on its potential role in preparation of future nurse leaders. In line with the Delphi panel, the government nurse leaders highlighted the need to persuade non-nursing decision makers of the value of including nurses in high-level policymaking. Experiences, opportunities, and challenges in developing policy influence were generously shared and demonstrated congruence of thought between the literature, pre-Delphi interviews and Delphi. These common threads, together with the broader findings of the study as a whole, are explored in the Chapter 8, contextualised by the research aims and contemporary literature.

Chapter 8: Discussion and Conclusion

This final chapter provides a high-level overview of the study, before debating its merits and limitations. Before discussing the central finding of nursing's marginalisation in policy making three original contributions to knowledge are presented: potential constraints of approaches to mitigate nursing's marginalisation in policy making, the novel combination and application of theoretical lenses, and the construction and testing of the Delphi consensus statement. The discussion goes on to connect key findings relating to the research aims with the contemporary literature and theoretical perspectives. Following interpretation of the findings the contribution of the philosophical, theoretical, and methodological choices of the study is critically explored. Recommendations for policy, practice, education, and research are then offered, along with suggestions for action, before concluding.

8.1 Overview of the study

This international study was designed to understand strategic nurse leadership in public policy. The dual aims of the study were to investigate the approaches, challenges, and contribution of strategic nurse leaders to public policy internationally, and to construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives of nursing's policy influence. The primary research activity, a modified Policy Delphi study of international elite nurse leaders (Chapter 6) built an understanding of approaches and challenges in policy influence. The structured first round of the Delphi was informed by pre-Delphi interviews with key informants (Chapter 5) and an integrative review (Chapter 2) of the underdeveloped body of international empirical literature on strategic nurse leadership in public policy. The Delphi panel identified context sensitive as well as internationally shared approaches and challenges. The resulting cross-sector consensus statement synthesised the shared approaches to, and pre-requisites of policy influence, thus addressing the second research aim to develop a statement of global perspectives. Following the Delphi, the resonance and potential utility of the consensus statement was explored in semi-structured interviews with ten government nurse leaders (Chapter 7). The post-Delphi study highlighted the importance of contextualisation in strategic nurse leadership. Even where approaches and challenges appeared universal in principle, the findings suggested that there was often a degree of nuance required to weave them effectively into the local context. All three research activities unpacked the challenges, approaches, and some of the contributions of strategic nurse leaders in policy influence.

Understanding nurse leadership in public policy internationally was deepened by use of social constructionism (discussed further in 8.9.1). The tenets of social constructionism (Burr, 2015) enabled the multiple perspectives and experiences of the international nursing elite to be foregrounded. While valuable insights in variation were uncovered, the social constructionist approach, coupled with the Delphi method acted as a catalyst for some nurse leaders to reflect on and consider next steps in their own policy leadership. Understanding strategic nurse leadership in policy was also deepened by the joint lenses of CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) and bases of social power (French and Raven).

8.2 Merits and Limitations

Given how little is empirically known about the experience of strategic nurse leaders in policy the insights contributed by the diverse group of elite international strategic nurse leaders in this thesis offer a substantive contribution to the body of knowledge. In totality the study included 57 strategic nurse leaders (one nurse leader took part in both the pre-Delphi and post-Delphi interviews) from 39 countries, spanning all WHO world regions, sectors of nurse leadership, and income levels, placing it as one of the widest reaching empirical studies of strategic nurse leadership of the last 20 years. Other studies of strategic nurse leadership in policy have tended to focus on particular regions (Shariff, 2014; Juma *et al.*, 2014) or nursing sectors (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Benton González-Jurado and Beneit-Montesinos, 2013; Chiu *et al.*, 2023). Alongside the breadth of participating nurse leaders, this study benefits from strong philosophical and theoretical underpinnings. The integrative review critiqued the lack of theoretical richness in previous research (2.3.3.5). This study addressed that criticism using social constructionism with a theoretical framework informed by both the bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and CLT (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014).

This thesis provides the first empirical exploration of the bases of social power in the international literature on elite strategic nurse leadership in policy influence. Interpreting findings through a lens of power offers insights which may help scholars and nurse leaders to recognise how and where disruption of established power dynamics could support and enhance policy influence (Topp, *et al.*, 2021; Lassa *et al.*, 2022). Of the five original bases of social power: legitimate, expert, referent, reward, and coercive (French and Raven, 1959), legitimate and expert power were most prominent in the findings. This discussion therefore focuses on understanding the presence of and threats to legitimate and expert power. The extent to which a strategic nurse leader possesses legitimate or expert power is determined by their ability to leverage the power base to enact a desired change in another person (French and Raven, 1959). The findings suggest that the perceptions of legitimate

and expert power are affected by the quality of the relationship between the strategic nurse leader and the individual or group they are trying to influence. The mediating role of high-quality relationships in developing policy influence was missing from French and Raven's (1959) conceptualisation of social power, a limitation of its use in this study. The bases of social power, discussed further in 8.6.2 and 8.6.3 highlighted that nursing nor policy making exist in a vacuum, and recognised the potential importance of culture and context as mediators of the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders, providing a natural congruence with the second theoretical perspective, CLT (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*, 2014). CLT somewhat captures the interpersonal and relational elements of leadership through culturally mediated expectations (House *et al.*, 2014). Once the expectations of how a prototypical leader behaves in a particular context are established in CLT, a reasonable next step would be to consider what needs to happen to shift that expectation towards the desired future. Shifting culturally mediated expectations of leadership behaviour is not however within the scope of CLT (discussed further in 8.3).

The rigour of the core research activity, the Delphi, was strengthened by the pre- and post-Delphi interviews. The use of convenience sampling in the interviews although not without limitation gave primacy to understanding multiple perspectives rather than seeking to establish a single truth, in line with the tenets of a social constructionist study. Although limiting the post-Delphi interviews to government nurse leaders precluded analysis of a wider range of perspectives their presumed proximity to government and policymaking (ICN, 2020), provided a useful first step in understanding the resonance and practical utility of the consensus statement. The findings of the post-Delphi interviews confirmed, critiqued, and offered extensions to the consensus statement, strengthening the rigour of the Delphi study. Making substantive changes to the consensus statement based on the post-Delphi interviews would have threatened its credibility as a product of a consensus building process. The statement and suggested refinements offer a useful starting point for exploration of translating the research into action with a wider group of strategic nurse leaders. There are several available mechanisms to consider including synchronising with the second State of the World's Nursing Report, or via the biennial Global Partners Meeting on Nursing and Midwifery meeting hosted jointly by the WHO, ICN and International Confederation of Midwives (ICMD), formerly known as the Triad. While this study was not designed to test agreement between the perceptions of the nurse leaders, the wider nursing profession, and non-nursing decisionmakers, it offers an insight into the challenges faced by nurse leaders and their perceptions of the possible reasons for their apparent exclusion from policy making.

The combination of theoretical lenses in this study supported cultural humility in the interpretation of the findings. Cultural humility was first described by Tervalon and Murray-García (1998) as a continuous process of self-evaluation to identify and repair imbalances of power, and to develop reciprocal, equal partnerships. Compared to cultural competence, cultural humility puts an emphasis on the dynamic nature of lifelong learning (Greene-Moton and Minkler, 2020; Foronda, 2020). This recognition of the importance of self-reflection is helpful when considering the merits and limitations of this study. Although this study includes perspectives from more than 30 countries, two thirds of the participants were from high income countries. Regional representation was also skewed with few participants from South East Asia. Disproportionate representation from the Global North, particularly Europe, means that caution is required when interpreting the findings and making recommendations due to their limited transferability to the Global South. This limitation was not wholly unanticipated due to the known gaps in regulation, nurse education, and government nurse leadership (WHO, 2020) meaning that the total population of strategic nurse leaders was likely to be skewed towards the Global North from the outset. Although the use of social constructionism recognised the impact of historical and cultural legacies, including colonialism, on nursing's policy influence, solutions cannot be found without the voices from that context. The enablers and challenges for strategic nurse leaders in the Global South for example, may differ from the Global North and require different approaches to influence change (Büyüm *et al.*, 2020). The resulting complexity for strategic nurse leaders in balancing internationally coordinated and contextually nuanced action for policy influence was evident. Alongside identification of shared approaches and challenges, the exposure of diverging perspectives offers potentially valuable routes for future work expanding understanding of, and context sensitive approaches to, challenges in influencing policy.

International recruitment was important to the trustworthiness of the study findings in fulfilling the research aim of exemplifying global perspectives of strategic nurse leadership in policy. Due to resource constraints the study was limited to participants who self-assessed themselves as able to contribute in English. Conducting the study in English did however present challenges to rigour. Key organisations with which strategic nurse leaders engage, for example English is one of the WHO (2018) official languages and the ICN (no date) offer translations of their publications in English, French, and Spanish. There is nonetheless a risk that the use of one language, English incurred an unintended bias of excluding participants from countries where English is not a prominent additional language. The use of English also may have skewed the range of societal structures experienced by participants in the study, including religious, legislative and policy traditions which can impact the role of women and nurses. In doing so, it risks perpetuating the colonial, western dominant

perspective in nursing research (Kimani, 2023) and the findings would require further testing to understand how they interact in other societal contexts.

Translation and back translation in multiple languages was beyond the resource constraints of this study and is not an automatic indication of rigour. The challenges of translation to the rigour of research, outlined in 4.3.1, are well documented (Abfalter, Mueller-Seeger and Raich, 2020; Squires, Sadarangani, and Jones, 2020). Indeed, in their paper on cross-cultural research Wutich *et al.* (2021) argue that researcher confidence in the language of data collection reduces the risk of misinterpretation during data analysis. To support participant preparation the interview questions were shared in advance. Each Delphi round was pre-tested with a four-person panel, including a strategic nurse leader for whom English was an additional language. Their input particularly supported clarification of wording, as described in 4.5.5. An email address was also available during the Delphi for participants to seek clarification. This was used for two participants who experienced challenges in the use of Microsoft Word documents with additional functionality, specifically use of drop down and check boxes. For those two participants Microsoft Word documents without additional functionality were provided and returned successfully.

This study adds to the body of knowledge demonstrating that it is feasible to use Delphi as a mechanism to construct an intersectoral understanding between elite nurse leaders. In particular, this study's reach across world regions extends earlier region-specific Delphi studies of strategic nurse leadership (Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Shariff, 2014). The longitudinal nature of Delphi studies does however mean that participant attrition is a recognised limitation (Keeney, Hasson and McKenna, 2006; Bloor *et al.*, 2015). Despite personalised contact and the judicious use of reminders to optimise the response rate, there was a 40% attrition from consent to final round (6.2.1). Attrition is likely to have been exacerbated by the gap between the 2nd and 3rd rounds during which the consensus statement was being drafted. The characteristics of the Round 3 panel demonstrated similar patterns in distribution of responding panellists in terms of income level, and world region compared to Round 1 (Appendix 21).

Within the Delphi the threshold for consensus was set a priori to prevent inadvertent manipulation of the findings, a key point of Delphi rigour (Grant, Booth and Khodyakov, 2018). The threshold of consensus was set at $\geq 67\%$ agreement/disagreement with an interquartile range of ≤ 1 . The unintended consequence of applying the threshold of $\geq 67\%$ agreement as a mathematical percentage was that there were four statements (reported in sections 6.12, 6.13 and 6.18 in Tables 6.14, 6.15 and 6.18 respectively) which did not reach 67% agreement but represented two thirds of responding panellists. As the topics were already captured to some extent within the statement, it

would not have had a substantive impact on the content. For example, 66.7% of responding panellists in Round 3 disagreed with the statement 'Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own'. The appetite for collaboration suggested by responses to the item statement is also captured in the consensus statement (6.15.1). A mitigation for future Delphi studies is to calculate agreement based on number of respondents rather than pure application of percentages.

The merits of the Delphi include the contributions to knowledge in terms of both areas of consensus and unpacking divergence. The consensus statement offers agreed approaches which the international strategic nurse leadership community could potentially take a coordinated and standardised approach to progressing. The Delphi statements which did not reach consensus not only suggest areas for future research but could also helpfully signpost where advancement of policy influence might require further exploration to develop a context specific approach.

8.3 Contributions to knowledge

This study makes three key contributions to knowledge: one for strategic nurse leadership in policy, one theoretical, and one methodological.

First, the findings of this study highlight the pervasive marginalisation of nursing in policy making and suggest potential constraints of approaches often identified as mitigations. While experiences vary internationally and by context, the findings reveal that the policy influence ambitions of strategic nurse leaders are constrained by the work required to overcome marginalisation. Particularly, strategic nurse leaders identified challenges in accessing policy discussions and being perceived as credible and influential decisionmakers. The disconnect between the recommendations from key publications for further inclusion of nursing in policymaking (WHO, 2020; WHO, 2021; Holloway *et al.*, 2021) and the findings reported here suggests a persistent gap between the rhetoric and reality of nursing's policy influence. While the nurse leaders offered a range of approaches to improve policy influence there is a question as to whether these are sufficient to support the shift in cultural expectations required to substantively transform nursing's policy influence.

Second, the complexity of culturally mediated expectations of the strategic nurse leadership role in policy was exposed but not resolved by CLT (House *et al.*, 2014). The use of CLT highlighted that the strategic nurse leaders were perhaps experiencing layered, and sometimes conflicting expectations of effective leadership behaviour across the profession, non-nursing decision makers, and key organisations, further discussed in 8.6.1. Additionally, where the role of strategic nurse leaders spans multiple sectors, common among the Delphi panel (6.2), the expectations of their leadership will be further complicated by having intersectoral remits. The distinct purposes, responsibilities,

and policy foci of each sector (Benton *et al.*, 2017) are potentially conflicting for one nurse leader holding multiple roles. While the study found a need to shift cultural expectations of nurse leaders to establish them as credible decision makers in policy, CLT was not designed to investigate or assimilate multiple cultural expectations for an individual leader. CLT was also limited in its ability to provide a framework to support a shift in expectations in line with nursing's ambitions for policy influence.

Finally, the study offers a methodological contribution to the Delphi method. The construction and testing of a narrative synthesis of key points of consensus offers an option to strengthen the trustworthiness of the Delphi. Traditionally, few Delphi studies report post-Delphi inquiry to understand the transferability of their findings (Skulmoski, Harman, Krahn, 2007). Practical options for testing trustworthiness of the products of Delphi studies remain largely unexplored in the methodological literature (Diamond *et al.*, 2014; de Loë *et al.*, 2016; Spranger *et al.*, 2022). In their guidance on Delphi reporting Jünger *et al.* (2017) noted that 11 out of the 30 reviewed Delphi studies included either preparatory or follow up activities. They did not identify the studies, nor did they comment on whether or not the additional work was a strength of those Delphi studies. Limiting review of Delphi findings to post-hoc synthesis or reporting would have missed the opportunity taken in this study to meaningfully engage panellists and post-Delphi interviewees with the whole, rather than disparate parts of the Delphi findings. By constructing the key points of consensus into a tangible whole, the statement articulates broad approaches to improving policy influence advocated by a cross-sector group of international nurse leaders. Testing the resonance and potential utility of the statement with a cohort of government nurse leaders independent to the Delphi panel, provided an insight into its trustworthiness. The draft consensus statement provided a novel, tangible, and cohesive output exemplifying, for the first time, global perspectives of strategic nurse leaders on approaches to improve policy influence.

8.4 The state of the art of the literature

Momentum to improve strategic nurse leadership in public policy has gathered pace since commencement of this PhD, galvanised by several influential publications. The Sustainable Development Goals published by the United Nations in 2015 was a catalyst because of the subsequent recognition that achievement of the goals, particularly Universal Health Coverage, would be contingent on nurses (Benton and Shaffer, 2016; Crisp, Brownie and Refsum, 2018; Benton, Beasley and Ferguson, 2019; Sensor *et al.*, 2021; Rumsey *et al.*, 2022a). The Triple Impact report (All-Party Parliamentary Group on Global Health, 2016) brought the lack of nursing leadership in policy making nationally and internationally into sharp focus. Positioning nursing persuasively as a return

on investment for economies, global health, and gender equity, the Triple Impact Report had a catalytic effect, leading to the development of Nursing Now (Holloway *et al.*, 2021). Shortly after the publication of the Triple Impact Report, Sigma Theta Tau International (2017) published the Global Advisory Panel on the Future of Nursing (GAPFON) report. GAPFON engaged with international stakeholders to identify key global health and professional issues, as well as strategies to improve outcomes for patients, communities, and nurses. The core professional issues were synthesised into a model, which included leadership at the centre and policy/regulation. The development of the model was strengthened in its international and intersectoral approach. The regional variation in preferences and perspectives highlighted in the report (Sigma Theta Tau International, 2017), resonated with the culturally mediated leadership highlighted in this study.

Nursing Now aimed to improve the capacity and capability of nurses to contribute meaningfully to decisions relating both to their own profession, and to influence wider policy to improve population health (Crisp, 2018). To do so Nursing Now proposed a range of actions including an increase in the number of countries with GCNOs, expansion of education, and a system for sharing learning on successes and challenges internationally (Crisp, 2018), recommendations repeated in the first State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020). The landmark publication of the State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020) was highlighted as a strategic success in the evaluation of Nursing Now (Holloway *et al.*, 2021). Key to the impact of Nursing Now appeared to be the combination of an internationally coordinated approach which was balanced by enabling local adaptation.

The empirical literature on strategic nurse leadership published has continued to grow slowly since 2015, the upper date parameter of the integrative review presented in Chapter 2. In the ongoing review of the literature for this thesis, while there were a substantive body of literature reviews, commentary and editorials published, only 13 empirical papers published since 2015 were of direct relevance to understanding strategic nurse leadership in public policy (Benton and Ferguson, 2017; Varghese *et al.*, 2018; Ajuebor *et al.*, 2019; Asuquo, 2019; Benton, Beasley and Ferguson, 2019; Newman *et al.*, 2019; Wichaikhum *et al.*, 2020; Hajizadeh, Zamanzadeh and Khodayari-Zarnaq, 2021; Joarder *et al.*, 2021; Lassa *et al.*, 2022; Rumsey *et al.*, 2022a; Rumsey *et al.*, 2022b; Chiu *et al.*, 2023). Publications offering insights with an organisational rather than national focus on policy and nursing leadership, also offered insights to this discussion (MacDonnell and Buck-McFadyen, 2016; Waddell, Adams and Fawcett, 2017; Sarnkwawkum and Oumtane, 2018; Sundean *et al.*, 2018; Al Faouri, Elfaqieh and AbuAlRub, 2021; Hajizadeh, *et al.*, 2022; Etowa *et al.*, 2023; Kelly *et al.*, 2023). The small volume of research noted here was also reported by Etowa *et al.* (2023) and Chiu *et al.* (2023). Etowa *et al.* (2023) identified 10 papers published between 2000 and 2021 for their qualitative systematic review of the experiences of nurses and midwives of policy engagement in low- and

middle-income countries. Similarly, in a scoping review Chiu *et al.* (2021) identified that 7 of 28 original research studies on policy advocacy and nursing associations were published between 1980 and 2020 were published between 2015 and 2020. The paucity of available research and recognition that many more policy issues would benefit from a nursing voice than has been achieved so far (Osingada and Porta, 2020; Benton *et al.*, 2020a) suggests that gaps in understanding about strategic nurse leadership in policy remain. The need to further understand the mechanisms of policy influence in strategic nurse leadership were also highlighted by COVID-19. A global system disrupter, nursing continues to have a significant role in COVID-19 internationally, however the recognition and prominence of nursing during the acute phase of the pandemic has not translated into substantive improvement in nursing's policy influence (Morone *et al.*, 2022). Given the ongoing work to improve nursing's policy influence, this thesis offers a valuable international contribution to the body of knowledge on strategic nurse leadership in policy.

The following discussion of the key findings from this thesis draws upon contemporary and recent contributions to the literature to contextualise the findings of the study. It reflects that despite support from landmark publications (All-Party Parliamentary Group on Global Health, 2016; WHO, 2020; Holloway *et al.* 2021) for the expansion of nursing's policy influence, the challenges reported in this study relating to the marginalisation of nurses in policy making, continue to be pertinent.

8.5 Overview of key findings

The key findings of this study centre on the perceived marginalisation of nurses in policy making, its antecedents and the opportunities and approaches strategic nurse leaders use, or aspire to use, to mitigate marginalisation and become policy influential. Although the extent and manifestation of marginalisation varied internationally and contextually, its sequelae rippled across the across the challenges strategic nurse leaders face, and approaches they identified to strengthen their policy leadership. The nuances mean that there is no single solution to improving nursing's policy influence. The Delphi consensus statement, addressing the research aim to synthesise global perspectives, offers approaches identified as key to advancing nursing's policy influence. In doing so the findings not only offer potential ways forward for strategic nurse leaders, but also highlight points where contextualisation of approach or strategy is likely to be important to success.

The marginalisation of strategic nurse leaders in policy was considered to be rooted within both the profession and external perceptions of it. Although this study only investigated the perspective of strategic nurse leaders it found that realising nursing's policy influence potential required changes in both nursing itself and the culture and context surrounding policymaking. The next section begins with a discussion of marginalisation.

Figure 8.1 provides a visual overview of the key findings discussed next in 8.6 and 8.7, and their intersection with the marginalisation and policy influence of strategic nurse leaders. The centre of the figure and discussion incorporates the core themes included in the draft consensus statement: to increase policy influence requires growth in the number of policy capable nurses influencing policy, for nurses to be perceived as credible decision makers, development of a collective nursing voice, to collaborate within and beyond nursing to broaden policy influence beyond nursing specific issues, and to increase the policy capacity and capability of the profession by systematising the preparation of future strategic nurse leaders. The findings suggest that the marginalisation or influence of strategic nurse leaders in policy is not linear and is contextually sensitive. As set out in figure 8.1 the discussion explores the overlapping approaches and challenges to nursing’s policy influence through the lens of legitimate power, expert power, CLT and context.

Figure 8.1. Visual overview: key findings of policy influence in strategic nurse leadership

Following consideration of the key findings the consensus statement as a product of the Delphi is discussed in 8.8.

8.6 Marginalisation of nurses in policy making

Strategic nurse leaders identified marginalisation as an overarching challenge to developing policy influence. Although the extent and manifestation of marginalisation varied internationally, the lack of expectation for nurse leaders to participate in policy making, particularly beyond nursing specific

issues, was prominent in the findings. A range of experiences of being marginalised in policy making were described, depicted as a continuum in Figure 8.2.

Figure 8.2 Experience of marginalisation in policy

While there were examples of strategic nurse leaders being treated as equal partners in high-level policy making, these were the exception rather than the rule. More frequently, strategic nurse leaders described being seen but not heard. Inclusion of nurses in policy discussions was reported as not guaranteed, even in matters explicitly related to nursing policy, a finding unfortunately echoed by other scholars (Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Joarder *et al.*, 2021). Although this study demonstrated international variation, it was striking that marginalisation characterised the experiences of nurse leaders across the study, who all held senior strategic positions with national or international remits. For governments, institutions, and societies to have nurses in such senior roles and not consistently engage them in policy making, is intriguing, signals tokenism, and is arguably wasteful. This study offers insights into the marginalisation of nursing in policy and potential approaches to improve influence, from the perspective of some of its most senior leaders discussed through a lens of culture and bases of social power (discussed next in 8.6.1, 8.6.2, 8.6.3).

8.6.1 Cultural expectations of nurse leaders

The marginalisation of nurses in policy was perceived to be rooted in a lack of expectation that nurse leaders would be engaged in policy influence, rather than deliberately excluding them from the process. Nurse leaders were confident in the profession's ability to articulate its policy contribution they perceived that they were often seen but not heard. The paradox of being seen but not heard unfortunately reverberates through the nurse leadership literature on policy from ground to government (Khoury *et al.*, 2011; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2012; Varghese *et al.*, 2018; Etowa *et al.*, 2023). Policy making as not an expected part of strategic nurse leadership roles is disappointing but perhaps unsurprising. Nurses have often been perceived as implementers rather than influencers of policy (Salvage and White, 2019; Rasheed, Younas and Mehdi, 2020). While inclusion

of nurses in policy is advocated by key organisations (Sigma Theta Tau International, 2017; All-Party Parliamentary Group, 2018; WHO, 2020; WHO, 2021) there appears to be a mismatch between the ambition of strategic nurse leaders to influence policy and a lack of expectation from non-nursing decision makers, and to some extent the wider nursing profession. This is important because application of CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) suggests that if the expected behaviours of a prototypical nurse leader differ from those of a policy leader, it could be difficult for a strategic nurse leader to remain credible as a policy leader to both the profession and non-nursing decision makers.

Resolving the culturally mediated dissonance was considered by participants in this study to require a cultural shift in the perception of both the profession and non-nursing decision makers about the role of strategic nurse leaders in policy. While CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) was not designed to consider how to shift culturally endorsed leadership expectations it seems logical that they would be unlikely to shift without an expectation of policy participation. Changing the culturally mediated leadership expectations of strategic nurse leaders is complicated however by the multiplicity of their roles and the variation in leadership expectations between each role. Many strategic nurse leaders navigate at least a triple tension in their roles as a nurse, policy leader, and for some, woman in power. In addition, it is not uncommon for strategic nurse leaders to hold multifaceted intersectoral roles within nursing. As such they may be subject to multiple, and potentially conflicting, culturally endorsed leadership expectations of what constitutes a prototypical effective strategic nurse leader. For some nurse leaders the tension with and between the values and priorities of their different roles manifested as a disconnect or conflict between themselves and non-nursing decision makers. Nurses as not consistently expected to be active in policy making was a finding consistent with earlier work by Gallup which perceived the primary role of nursing as delivery of direct care (Khoury *et al.*, 2011). The opinion leaders in the Gallup study also ranked nurses least influential in healthcare reform, behind all other groups (Khoury *et al.*, 2011). The evidence of mismatch in the ambitions of nursing and the expectations of non-nursing decision makers was also reported by Ditlopo *et al.* (2014) and Juma, Edwards, and Spitzer (2014) study. While Kenyan nurse leaders in Juma, Edwards, and Spitzer's (2014) study felt they could make a stronger contribution to policy, some non-nursing decision-makers considered their existing engagement sufficient. Despite some variation there was limited evidence in this study that these earlier findings of a lack of expectation for nurses to engage in policy among non-nursing decision makers are outdated internationally.

In addition to non-nursing decision makers, some strategic nurse leaders in this study reported that nurses themselves did not always expect policy making to be legitimate nursing work. A lack of appetite for policy making was also reported, although somewhat more starkly, by Asuquo (2019). In their qualitative study of 12 senior Nigerian nurse leaders Asuquo (2019) depicted little enthusiasm,

and some active opposition, to moving nursing towards influencing policy. Applying a CLT lens highlights that if nurses in general do not perceive themselves as having a role in policy, the corresponding cultural expectation is reinforced. CLT would also suggest that if expectations of how excellent nurse leaders behave does not include policy influence, then nurse leaders may hesitate to act against that as a culturally mediated leadership expectation. This finding challenges perceptions in the literature (Varghese, *et al.*, 2018; Asuquo, 2019; Hajizadeh, Zamanzadeh and Khodayari-Zarnaq, 2021) and among some of the participants in this study of nurses as reticent to become policy active. It also questions the value to expanding policy influence of placing the onus on nurses as individuals to be more policy active (Anders, 2021; Thorne, 2022). What masquerades as reticence may actually be an effect of the culturally mediated constraints and expectations, such as the lack of a GCNO, prevailing dominance of medicine in policy, or male dominated policy environment. Scholars including Stilwell and Newman (2022) and Etowa *et al.* (2023) argue that such contexts can prevent nurses either from having their contribution heard or socialise them to not offer one at all. The implications of culturally mediated values on the action of strategic nurse leaders demonstrates the importance of establishing practical strategies to scaffold a shift in the perceived role of strategic nurse leaders in policy.

The culturally mediated expectations of strategic nurse leaders could be expected to be tied to the historical and cultural inequalities related to nursing and to women. Although gender inequality did not reach consensus in the Delphi as a factor impacting the ability of nurse leaders to influence policy in their nations (6.11) it was also not re-tested. Although this could be argued as a limitation of the study, the statement was framed specifically around the panellist's perception of the impact of gender inequality in their context. As the purpose of the Delphi was not to artificially force consensus it was assessed that the perception of gender inequality in their own context was unlikely to change. The gender balance of the Delphi panel, whilst potentially more representative of the strategic nurse leader population, had a proportionately larger male contribution than the gender balance of nursing at large, with 80% of the panel self-identifying as female (6.2), compared to the estimated 90% of the broader nursing workforce (WHO, 2020). Male panellists were less likely to consider gender inequality as an issue in nursing's policy influence in their country than women (6.11), potentially indicative of unconscious bias. Consequently, the lack of agreement around the impact of gender inequality should be interpreted with caution. The impact of cultural norms on leadership, and the constraints it can place on women, are well documented (Newman *et al.*, 2019; WHO, 2019). As a female dominated profession it would be logical to assume that nursing is particularly impacted by cultural norms relating to gender. Newman *et al.*'s (2019) study of the experiences of nurses reported ongoing gender related challenges. These challenges spanned

structural, educational, and cultural perspectives. The challenges for nursing are also reflected in the lack of women in Global Health Leadership roles. With women making up 90% of the nursing workforce, and nurses making up almost 60% of the health workforce (WHO, 2020), that only 23% World Health Assembly delegations were led by women in 2022 (Women in Global Health, 2023), signals ongoing challenges for women and nursing in reaching the most senior roles in health. The link between cultural and gendered expectations, nursing, and influence, was ably demonstrated during COVID-19, discussed further in 8.6.3. The focus on healthcare raised the profile of nursing but the contribution of the profession at a strategic level has been critiqued as largely superficial (Daly *et al.*, 2020; Rasmussen *et al.*, 2022). Instead of updating the mainstream image and understanding of nursing work as hoped by Bennett, James and Kelly (2020), Mohammed *et al.* (2021) argue that the pandemic reinforced historical images of nurse as angel or vocational hero.

Although many nurse leaders, including those in this study, overcome low expectations and make high-impact policy contributions the approaches and challenges offered in this study predominantly focused on positioning for, rather than the act of, policy influence. The focus on antecedents to policy influence is congruent with the finding of nurses as seen but not heard, and the need for a shift to consider nurses as credible decision-makers. The ability of strategic nurse leaders to occupy the liminal space between policymakers and the nursing profession appears to be important to managing the conflicting culturally mediated leadership expectations. Stilwell and Newman (2022) called for nurses to act to dismantle traditional expectations of themselves. Their call to action echoed the findings in this study of a need to show rather than tell non-nursing decision makers the value of including nurses in policy making. By focusing on the outcomes of including nurses in policy making could support a reframing of the culturally mediated expectations of nursing in policy.

8.6.2 Legitimate power in strategic nurse leadership

The need for a shift in culturally mediated leadership expectations intersects with the findings that suggest that legitimate power shapes policy influence of strategic nurse leaders. Legitimate power requires both the role and the person holding the role to be considered to have the right to exercise the authority within the context at hand (French and Raven, 1959). A key approach recommended by nurse leaders in this study was to make the case to policy makers for their inclusion. In the post-Delphi interviews, government nurse leaders called for the consensus statement to be more persuasive about why nurse leaders need a voice in the policy discussions they are seeking to influence. They reflected on their personal challenges in seeking recognition as policy actors and used language that did not always infer possession of legitimate power. In one example a government minister was described as ‘allowing’ a strategic nurse leader to influence policy (7.5.2), suggesting a reliance on more powerful decision makers for access. That strategic nurse leaders,

assumed to be in a role close to policy making, perceived a need to persuade decision makers of their value in policy suggests that their legitimate power cannot be assumed. Key sources of and challenges to legitimate power included the presence and stability of strategic nurse leadership roles, their structural position, and the scope of their policy focus.

8.6.2.1 Strategic nurse leadership roles as a route to legitimate power

The lack of expectation of nurses to participate in policy making was linked to the presence and permanence of strategic nurse leadership roles, with a particular focus on government nurse leadership. This study identified four role related signals that the legitimate power of strategic nurse leaders in policy was either absent or restricted:

- Absence of a formal role, with or without proxy voices, where advice is provided by non-nurses who speak on behalf of the profession,
- A token position that is structurally excluded from policy making decisions or holds limited legitimate power within the hierarchy,
- Restricted scope, limited to nursing specific policy input, and
- Unstable role, making it difficult to take risks.

The presence of each signal appeared to be dependent on several variables including the culturally endorsed leadership expectations within that context, and the broader political environment. While there was international variation the findings in this study did not suggest that any world region or income level provided immunity from threats to legitimate power of strategic nurse leadership roles. It was however noted that all four indicators were more frequently discussed in relation to government nurse leaders. Strategic nurse leaders from other sectors more frequently described being seen but not heard, with limited legitimate power, and restricted scope.

The small number of strategic nurse leaders nationally and internationally was considered problematic for policy influence. Nurse leaders called for more nurses to be appointed to strategic policy making positions. In addition to a lack of posts, a small number of strategic nurse leaders in this study also identified lack of resources for existing strategic nurse leaders as a concern, also previously reported by Splane and Huffman Splane (1994) among GCNOs. Distribution of resources is intimately bound to the legitimate power of a role in making decisions about resources (French and Raven, 1959). Without legitimate power or policy influence, nurse leaders are unlikely to secure more resources. While creation of roles for strategic nurse leaders can be helpful in expanding the capacity of the profession to input into policy, broad remits and little resource threatens potential impact and requires creative and collaborative leadership. Such collaboration can enable leaders to

borrow from the legitimate power and resources of other groups to deliver impact and is discussed further in 8.7.

The ambition of nurse leaders in this study to expand legitimate power through appointing more nurses to policy making positions is consistent with calls from key organisations (Sigma Theta Tau, 2017; ICN, 2020) and publications including the Strategic Direction for Nursing and Midwifery 2021-2025 (WHO, 2021), the State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020), and the Global Advisory Panel on the Future of Nursing and Midwifery (Sigma Theta Tau International, 2017). Newman *et al.* (2019) contend that increasing the number of GCNO positions provides an external facing signal of the importance of the profession. In this study the perceived benefits of increasing the number of strategic nurse leaders included increased visibility and expanded impact while distributing the workload and responsibility currently concentrated on a few individuals. Practical implications of the diminutive size of the strategic nurse leadership population were illustrated in the frequency with which participants in this study reported holding dual or multiple leadership roles. A small number of strategic nurse leaders also touched on feeling professionally isolated, particularly when faced with diametrically competing professional and policy priorities.

Calls in this study to increase the number of nurses in policy making positions included increasing the number of countries with a GCNO. The lack of a GCNO was considered to render nursing essentially voiceless within government. Even where a country has a nursing 'point of contact' in place of a GCNO, the ICN (2020) reported that the contact was not always a nurse, nor in possession of legitimate power to influence policy. The exact number of GCNOs is elusive. The State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020) noted GCNO positions in 71% (82/115) responding countries. Given that only 59% (115/194) of all WHO member states submitted data (WHO, 2020), it would be unwise to extrapolate the percentage of GCNOs at a global level. Countries with capacity to respond to the report may have been more likely to have structures to support roles such as the GCNO, meaning that the reported 71% countries with a GCNO has been drawn from a skewed distribution of member states. The ICN (2020) consider there to be little evidence of substantive improvement in GCNO numbers since Splane and Huffman Splane (1994) identified 98 in their landmark study of 173 countries (56.6%). The number of designated GCNO positions in Splane and Huffman Splane (1994) would have been less than 98 because they used an inclusive definition of GCNO which encompassed government nurse leaders with varying titles, resources, and remits. Given the desirability and focus on securing more GCNO roles internationally, it seems logical that key nursing organisations would continue to lobby for their insertion. Conversely, in view of an apparently stagnant GCNO population, and reflections that even when present their legitimate power is not

guaranteed (ICN, 2020), nursing would arguably benefit from assessing other routes to building legitimate power for policy influence.

Although expanding the number of strategic nurse leadership roles was popular as a strategy to improving policy influence both in this study and key organisations (Sigma Theta Tau International, 2017; ICN, 2020), the precarity of some roles was recognised to make it difficult for affected nurse leaders to influence policy and take risks (6.18). This is important because risk taking is reported as a key feature of policy influence strategies (Aviram, Cohen, Beeri, 2019). Even where strategic nurse leadership roles were present, 54.2% (13/24) Delphi panellists in Round 3 indicated that strategic roles in their country were unstable (section 6.18, Table 6.18). Examples of precarity included the absence, demotion, dismissal, and removal of roles. In an example of ongoing fragility, the Canadian GCNO was reinstated in 2022 after a decade, and two prior eliminations during budget cuts (Health Canada, 2022; Canadian Nurses Association, 2022). While welcomed by the nursing community, the GCNO role is fixed term for two years (Health Canada, 2022), suggesting ongoing fragility of the role. Instability reduces opportunities to build networks, develop a deep understanding of the policy arena from the perspective of a strategic nurse leader, or engage in policy discourse, all required to enhance policy influence (Weible *et al.*, 2012) and build legitimate power.

The precarity in both position and permanence of GCNO roles suggests that the value of strategic nurse leadership roles is contested. The marginalisation of strategic nurse leaders identified in this study raises questions about the commitment of some institutions and governments to the rhetoric of meaningfully engaging nurses in policy making positions in high-level decision making. There is however little empirical literature describing the benefits of appointing strategic nurse leaders, perhaps making it more difficult for non-nursing decision makers to understand the return on their investment in such roles. Even within government nurse leadership, understanding the role and impact is at a relatively early stage. The State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020, p59) observed that "the existence of a high-level nursing position within the national government does not necessarily lead to actions". This reflects suggestions in this study and Salvage, Montayre and Gunn (2019) that nurse leaders in strategic positions with access to policy discussion are not always effective in their role. In a self-report questionnaire investigating the implementation of WHO (2016) Global Strategic Directions for Strengthening of Nursing and Midwifery 2016-2020 (WHO, 2016) over half of the 35 responding government nurse leaders (30 GCNOs and 5 in other positions) indicated that development and implementation of national advocacy plans focused on policy makers had not been started (Ajuebor *et al.*, 2019). Ajuebor *et al.* (2019) also reported that 14% (5/35) hadn't started raising the level of involvement of nurses and midwives in policy and decision making, with 69% (24/35) in progress and 17% (6/35) self-assessed as complete. A limitation of Ajuebor *et al.*'s

(2019) study was that 'complete' was not operationally defined, pointing to a broader question about what achievement of policy influence looks like. Ajuebor *et al.*'s (2019) focus on delivery of structures and processes missed the opportunity to understand particular successes and challenges and international variation in delivering on the Global Strategic Directions (WHO, 2016). Importantly, Ajuebor *et al.* (2019) also did not explore the outcomes related to delivery of the processes meaning that an informed case about the need to deliver on the Global Strategic Directions was not possible. Despite its limitations, Ajuebor *et al.*'s (2019) finding that substantial progress was still to be made in engaging nurses in policy supports the ongoing relevance of the findings of this study.

While it is important to scrutinise the impact of strategic nurse leadership roles, careful interpretation is required given the constraints on legitimate power and culturally endorsed leadership expectations, discussed earlier (8.6.1). Only 10 empirical studies with a primary focus on government nurse leaders and policy have been published in two decades (Salmon and Rambo, 2002; Hennessy and Hicks, 2003; Swenson *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2006; Shariff and Potgieter, 2012; McCarthy *et al.*, 2013; Aarabi, Cheraghi and Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Ditlopo *et al.*, 2014; Juma, Edwards and Spitzer, 2014; Ajuebor, *et al.*, 2019). None have assessed the return on investment of government nurse leaders, critical evidence to support sustainability in a fiscally pressured context. In sum, the appointment and protection of GCNO roles is championed as a route to improving nursing's policy influence capacity. Ambitions for role presence to translate into policy influence requires that role to possess legitimate power in a policy context. This study has found however that the legitimate power of strategic nurse leaders is not assured and suggests that improving the power of existing roles may be more fruitful than focusing on expanding the number of potentially tokenistic roles.

8.6.2.2 Position of nurse leaders in hierarchies

Structural exclusion was reported by half of Delphi panellists as having an impact on their legitimate power as a policy actor, demonstrating expected international variation. Some denied structural exclusion but reflected that their elite job title had limited use as a lever to access broader policy discussions. The disconnect between position and influence is indicative of a lack of legitimate power for that role, and/or those nurses in that context. The position of nurse leaders in organisational and government structures was perceived to shape their opportunities to develop strategic relationships and access high-level policy discussions, echoing findings from other studies (Varghese *et al.*, 2018; Ayala, 2020; Hajizadeh, Zamanzadeh and Khodayari-Zarnaq, 2021). Holding a lower position in the hierarchy was associated with an increasing degree of separation from the key decision makers in this study. The consequence of being held in a lower position in the hierarchy was reflected by strategic nurse leaders who had experienced demotion of their role. They reported that

after the change in position in the hierarchy they were more likely to be excluded from final discussions in top-down decision making, reducing their legitimate power. In contrast, structural enablers such as mandates for the inclusion of all disciplines in government policy discussions, appeared to improve access and legitimate power in policy making. Where structural enablers were not present nurse leaders described connecting strategically with individuals and groups with access to resources or influence that they did not hold, thereby circumventing barriers associated with hierarchy (discussed further in 8.7). These findings add further weight to the interpretation that challenges in policy influence are unlikely to be resolved solely by being in or expanding the number of elite nurse leadership positions. The extent to which the policy influence of nurse leaders is contingent on position in the hierarchy, access to, and relationships with senior non-nursing decision makers was out of scope for this study but an important point for future investigation. Particularly, as later discussed in 8.7.2, it could be useful to map the social networks of strategic nurse leaders and non-nursing decision makers. Social network analysis could enable exploration of patterns of connection and associated influence, which support strategic nurse leaders to influence policy even where they are in disadvantaged positions in the hierarchy.

8.6.2.3 Legitimate power and nursing's policy focus

Nurse leaders in this study described ambitions to expand policy influence beyond nursing specific issues. Challenging that ambition, some nurse leaders described nurses as being limited to, and then criticised for, contributing to nursing specific policy issues. Inclusion of nurses in policy discussions was reported as not guaranteed, even in policy explicitly related to nursing, a finding unfortunately echoed by other scholars (Aarabi, Cheraghi, Ghiyasvandian, 2014; Joarder *et al.*, 2021). While some nurse leaders in this study criticised the profession for not being proactive enough in engaging in and broadening their policy making involvement, French and Raven (1959) offer a caution. The bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) hypothesise that if an actor attempts to exert legitimate power beyond the cultural, role, or personal limits of that power their power be reduced, and they will also be less attractive as an actor. This has important implications for the approaches nurses take in expanding their policy influence beyond areas aligned with their legitimate power and culturally endorsed leadership expectations.

In contrast to the restrictions on nursing's legitimate power in policy, doctors were described in this study as enjoying apparently unfettered access to policy discussions and a halo effect around their contributions, even in the absence of evidence for their position (5.5.3.2, 6.10, 7.3.1). While the prevailing dominance of medicine is an unsurprising finding, it cannot be assumed to be an inert historical hangover. In their review of the literature and interviews as part of a wider Bangladeshi policy analysis Joarder *et al.* (2021) reported that medical dominance was actively used to restrict

the scope of nursing practice, and associated influence. The disproportionate power of medicine was also reported in Lassa *et al.*'s (2022) Nigerian study where the use of medicalised language was considered a deliberate tactic to retain the dominance of the biomedical model in framing policy making. The use of language to create and hold on to power is well recognised in the literature (Statham, 2022). The biomedical model holds that health is the "absence of disease" (Farre and Rapley, 2017, p.5) and while it dominates, policymaking is likely to continue to miss the opportunity to maximise nursing's contribution to a broader definition of population health, thereby perpetuating traditional power imbalances (Carrier, 2020). This contrast between medicine and nursing in policy influence highlights differences in legitimate power. The unquestioning acceptance of the policy participation of doctors, even in issues beyond healthcare, could be considered indicative of expansive legitimate power. This is a key issue for nursing and underlines the need to clearly articulate the distinct value add of nursing input into policy issues not explicitly linked to the profession. While it may be prudent for nurses to understand where and how a lack of nursing input into policy benefits other groups, it is important to recognise the role of institutionalised perpetuation of medical dominance. Where it is set in policy or legislate that positions above a particular point in the hierarchy are accessible only to medical applicants, nurses being perceived as competent will be insufficient to secure them positions with legitimate power until the policy or legislate changes.

The findings of this study suggest that there is a disconnect between the ongoing calls to include nurses in wider policy issues (WHO, 2020) and the real-world constraints contributing to a focus on nursing-specific policy. Out with restrictions placed through historical or cultural legacy strategic nurse leaders in this study considered the policy focus of nursing to tend towards introspection. Some nurse leaders interpreted a nursing-centric policy focus as both a cause and effect of their marginalisation in policy. If nursing's policy focus is limited to the profession, this could contribute to a cycle in which nursing is not expected to contribute to broader policy issues and consequently doesn't contribute, further reinforcing the expectation that they don't. From a theoretical perspective this would reinforce a culturally mediated leadership expectation which does not involve nurses participating in policy discussions out with nursing and reduces their legitimate power to do so. That is not to say that critical professional policy issues are not important. The combination of the size of the profession, the ongoing challenges in working conditions, and a prevailing narrative of nursing as a low status profession likely means that there will be critical internal policy issues on an ongoing basis. The challenge is to balance the voice of professional issues with a confident, robust policy contribution which has sufficient legitimate power to mobilise nursing knowledge and make an impactful policy contribution towards Greer *et al.*'s (2023) ambition of Health for All Policies.

8.6.3 Expert power and policy influence

While the relevance of legitimate power to the challenges and approaches of nurse leaders in policy was pervasive in the findings of this study, holding a position with recognised authority was not the sole antecedent to policy influence. Nurse leaders in this study reported that they were often not expected to have sufficient expertise to contribute to policy. Specifically, they described being perceived as not qualified, capable or knowledgeable enough to contribute to policy making. This lack of expectation links back to culturally mediated leadership expectations of what prototypical strategic nurse leaders do (8.6.1) but is also indicative of a lack of expert power. Expert power is the extent to which a strategic nurse leader is perceived to possess the knowledge required to contribute to policy, and to be truthful about that knowledge (French and Raven, 1959). Nursing is routinely rated as most trusted profession in some countries in the Global North (Roy Morgan, 2021; Ipsos, 2023a; Brenan and Jones, 2024), however social discourse in some countries reflects an outdated view of the educational preparation and acumen of nurses (Elmorshedy *et al.*, 2020; Joarder *et al.*, 2021). Persisting perceptions of nursing as a low-skilled job (Elmorshedy *et al.*, 2020; Joarder *et al.*, 2021) rather than a safety-critical profession (Royal College of Nursing, 2023) is linked to culturally mediated inequalities for women and nurses (Teresa-Morales *et al.*, 2022; Baduge, 2023). The resulting narrative of nurses as trusted caregivers but not leaders with high value expertise illustrates Teresa-Morales *et al.*'s (2022, p. 18) depiction of nursing as an “unknown profession” and threatens the profession’s expert power.

Nurse leaders reported that they were rarely sought out for their input to policy, consistent with Mason *et al.*'s (2018) findings in their replication of the Woodhull study (Sigma Theta Tau International, 1997), a content analysis of American media articles. Mason *et al.* (2018) reported that 24% of quotes in the reviewed healthcare articles were from policymakers, compared to 21% for doctors, 4% for patients or families, and 2% for nurses, down from 4% in the original study (Sigma Theta Tau International, 1997). None of the articles focused on healthcare policy used nurses as a source. Mason, Glickstein, and Westphaln (2018) explored reasons for nursing’s invisibility in the media in a subsequent interview study with ten journalists. The journalists agreed that nurses had relevant perspectives to share, particularly referencing the role of nurses as caregivers. Lack of status and understanding of the expertise of nurses compared to doctors was perceived to contribute to the absence of the nursing voice. The implication that an article sourcing nurses would be less credible than one quoting doctors is illustrative of a lack of expert power. Compounding the impact of lower perceived professional standing of nurses and understanding of their potential contribution on being sought out, the journalists highlighted that nurses were rarely promoted as

expert sources. Consequently, even if the journalists perceived nurses as expert in a particular area, timely identification of, and access to the right nurse leaders was problematic (Mason, Glickstein and Westphaln, 2018). These findings suggest that there is an urgent need to increase the visibility of proactive, capable, and credible strategic nurse leaders in their role as policy actors.

The findings in this study of tension between the rhetoric and reality of the visibility of strategic nurse leaders in high level policy fora were also demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic. While COVID-19 raised the profile of clinical nursing (Chiu *et al.*, 2023), the visibility of strategic nurse leadership in pandemic decision-making forums was arguably limited (Daly *et al.*, 2020; Santillan-Garcia, Zaforteza-Lallemand and Castro-Sanchez, 2020; Popoola, 2021; Morone *et al.*, 2022; Rasmussen *et al.*, 2022). In their editorial, Rasmussen *et al.* (2022) drew attention to differences between medical and nursing representation at government coronavirus briefings internationally. Within Scotland, analysis of Scottish Government recorded updates found that the Chief Nursing Officer addressed the country during 15.6% (33/212) of the First Minister's coronavirus updates between 12th March 2020 and 17th December 2021 (inclusive) (Scottish Government, 2021). In contrast, the Chief Medical Officer or deputy Chief Medical Officer spoke during 50.5% (107/212) of the updates (Scottish Government, 2021). While the Chief Nursing Officer appeared significantly less than the Chief Medical Officer, they were visible in the early days of the pandemic, with first appearance of the Chief Nursing Officer at a First Minister coronavirus update on 7th April 2020. In contrast, in the United States of America (USA) the White House Coronavirus Task Force was still without a nurse in August 2020, more than six months after the taskforce was convened (Dermenchyan and Choi, 2020). The combination of variable visibility of nurses out with direct care giving, and the perpetual call to increase policy influence of nursing demonstrates the continued relevance of the findings of this thesis. Improving the visibility of nurse leaders in policy is however only part of what needs to be a multifactorial strategy to strengthen expert power.

Strengthening both the perception of, and actual expert power were priorities for nurse leaders in this study. Being perceived as capable of policy influence was considered a primary gateway to opportunities for influence. Nurse leaders who had successfully influenced policy appeared to have overcome the lack of understanding of, or confidence in, nursing expertise, primarily through building their personal credibility and integrity as a policy actor. Strengthening preparation of future strategic nurse leaders through education and mentorship was important to nurse leaders in this study. While improving the knowledge and skills of nurses may seem a logical step in improving expert power and consequently policy influence, it may also disrupt existing power structures. Not all non-nursing decision makers want more policy capable nurses (Joarder *et al.*, 2021). The sections that follow critically discuss approaches offered to improve the expert power of strategic nurse

leaders, broadly centred around better equipping nurses across the career pathway to become effective policy actors.

8.6.3.1 Demonstrating policy capability to build expert power

While perception of policy capability was considered an important gatekeeper to opportunities, the strategic nurse leaders recognised actual capability as critical to influencing policy. Where nurse leaders surmounted challenges in being perceived as capable, and successfully accessed policy discussions, they described the quality of their contributions as critical to their future as a policy actor. While a poor contribution could limit careers and future opportunities, a high-quality policy contribution was considered to have the potential to improve the standing of a strategic nurse leader as a recognised policy actor. An impactful contribution improved perceptions of their credibility and capability. As a result, a successful contribution was reported to generate subsequent opportunities, further developing their policy competence through increased practice. Conversely, a poor contribution compromised their personal credibility and reduced the likelihood of subsequent opportunities to contribute to policy. This suggestion of a self-reinforcing cycle where high performance stimulates more opportunity to practice, and poor performance limits future opportunities to develop and practice the skills to influence policy, supports the findings of the literature review (2.4.2). Strategic nurse leaders were mindful of the consequences of a misstep in the cycle on their career. The impact was expanded beyond the individual in Sundean *et al.*'s (2018) study which cautioned that a nurse leader unprepared to perform at board level risked the reputation of future nurse leaders. The potential of a subpar policy contribution to erode expert power was sobering. The findings of this thesis did suggest however that it might be possible for nursing to incrementally scaffold a shift in external perception. High quality policy contributions could increase the legitimate and expert power of individual strategic nurse leaders, which they may be able to leverage in subsequent policy influence.

Strategic nurse leaders described quality of policy contribution as contingent on both its content and the knowledge and skills of the nurse leader in viewing and positioning policy issues within the broader socio-political context. Understanding how a policy issue interacts with multiple contexts was considered important to developing credible, well timed, and context sensitive policy positions. Some strategic nurse leaders also used their knowledge of the broader context to identify potentially competing agendas, an approach to policy influence also recommended by the broader policy literature (Oliver and Cairney, 2019).

Some nurse leaders in this study reflected on success using knowledge of the broader socio-political environment to translate the nursing policy contribution into messaging which resonated with their

target audience. Transforming nursing perspectives into policymaker priorities is also an approach supported by Stilwell and Newman (2022). Strategies to improving the impact of policy positions included moving away from focusing on the right of nursing to be heard, towards framing the nursing policy contribution around the priorities of non-nursing decision makers. Embodying this approach Rumsey *et al.* (2022a) sought to promote nursing's potential in the policymaking required to deliver Universal Health Coverage in the South Pacific. Rumsey *et al.* (2022a) published an article in the Lancet Regional Health for the Western Pacific, a non-nursing journal with reach beyond the profession. They persuasively set out the case for how nursing could enable policymakers to fulfil the 6 political 'asks' of Universal Health Coverage. By taking their potential contribution and situating it credibly within a context relevant to the target group, Rumsey *et al.* (2022a) articulated the value offered by nursing, but also the risk of ignoring its potential contribution to current policy challenges. Improving the socio-political literacy of strategic nurse leaders could support expansion of the expert power of nursing into policy issues beyond their traditional scope of influence.

8.6.3.2 Integrating policy and leadership education into initial preparation for practice

Becoming a capable policy actor required access to quality, level-appropriate leadership, and policy education. The Delphi identified a need to improve access to high quality education provision internationally. The importance of improving education across the career pathway was perceived as a route to improving perceptions of nursing's expert power. Initial preparation for practice, while equipping nurses for entry to rather than immediate formal leadership of, was considered a key opportunity for building expectations of policy leadership into the professional identities of new nurses. This strategy is important given that both this study and Staebler *et al.*'s (2017) reported that nurses do not always see the relevance of being policy capable to their practice. Policy education has not, however, been traditionally prominent in nursing curricula. While integration of policy curricula may appear a pedestrian finding in the context of this thesis, the broader literature suggests that delivery would require planning and resourcing, including preparation of faculty (Staebler *et al.*, 2017; Anderson *et al.*, 2020). In Staebler *et al.*'s (2017) survey in the USA, almost one third (31.7%) of 514 nursing faculty reported that policy related curricula was not a priority for their nursing schools. Policy curricula was also omitted from the Global Alliance for Leadership in Nursing Education and Science (GANES, 2019, p.19) on the basis it was "not a common prescription in the literature". This is challenged by a small body of literature in favour of integrating policy education meaningfully into nursing curricula (Ellenbecker *et al.*, 2017; Turale and Kunaviktikul, 2019; Anderson *et al.*, 2020). While improving formal policy education is perhaps not particularly controversial, curriculum changes in regulated professional education are not straightforward. Ambitions for change are also tempered by recognition of practical constraints in relation to faculty

competence and confidence in developing and delivering policy education (Staebler *et al.*, 2017; Anderson *et al.*, 2020). Formal education is however only one component of learning to lead in policy. The following sections focus on approaches to ongoing professional development, including for established nurse leaders.

8.6.3.3 Approaches to preparing nurses for strategic leadership roles

In addition to initial education to build the foundations for development of future strategic nurse leaders, this study highlighted the importance of infrastructure to deliberately prepare nurses for strategic leadership. Most commonly nurse leaders described the value of structured education programmes, and experiential learning opportunities, for example through mentorship, consistent with the findings of Newman *et al.*, (2019). In their mixed methods study nurses in Newman *et al.*'s (2019) identified a need to develop the confidence and competence of nurses for leadership by increasing access to funded leadership development education. Experiences of the availability and quality of preparation varied internationally. The State of the World's Nursing Report (WHO, 2020) reported that half of all participating countries reported availability of a nursing leadership development programme.

One approach to the calls in this study for increased access to development for future nurse leaders is scaling up existing nurse leadership programmes (Newman *et al.*, 2019; Salvage, Montayre and Gunn, 2019; Salvage and White, 2019). Nursing specific programmes can offer a safe environment in which nurse leaders can grow and learn with their peers (Rumsey, 2022b). Connections made during such programmes can lead to the development of sustainable networks within nursing (Benton and Ferguson, 2017). Nursing only programmes cannot however provide opportunities to develop networks or collaborative strategic relationships beyond the profession, identified in this study as central antecedents to policy influence.

Strategic nurse leaders in this study provided clear direction that preparation for future nurse leaders should include equipping them to navigate complex contexts, in a sometimes hostile environment. The apparently impervious nature of some policy discussions was suggested to be unlocked by effective reciprocal relationships (discussed further in 8.7.2). Multidisciplinary leadership education could offer an opportunity to learn from and build networks with future leaders across professional and disciplinary boundaries. Such opportunities could meet Stilwell and Newman's (2022, p.26) call for nurses to "be socialised to work as equal partners in problem solving". Interprofessional leadership education could create the conditions for government nurse leaders and their non-nursing counterparts to expect nurses to "work on a par with other health professional leadership in making strategic decisions", a Global Strategic Directions for Nursing and

Midwifery (WHO, 2021, p. 16) policy priority. Interprofessional education is already well embedded in many nurse education programmes in recognition of the critical role of teamwork in health care (Frenk *et al.*, 2022). This is however often limited to education with other health profession students, rather than disciplines who produce non-nursing decision makers. This study suggests that strategic nurse leaders are likely to benefit from exposure to disciplines beyond health.

The uni-professional nature of nursing specific programmes may compromise nursing's capacity to adopt an outward facing approach to policy making recommended both in this study and the literature (Salvage and White, 2019; Sarnkwawkum and Oumtanee, 2018). By developing together in a multidisciplinary learning environment future non-nursing leaders would have an opportunity to connect with and better understand the potential contribution of nursing in policy. A siloed approach to leadership development, therefore, seems counterintuitive. There is a need to critically consider whether pursuing nursing-only leadership and policy preparation should be the primary mechanism for developing future leaders of nursing. Such debate adds to Benton, Al-Maaitah, and Gharaibah's (2017) call for robust longer-term evaluation of the impact of nurse leadership programmes on the policy influence of their graduates. Such debate and scholarship are important to inform effective development and delivery of future approaches to policy education.

In addition to formal education, nurse leaders in this study advocated for mentorship and experiential learning opportunities to prepare future strategic nurse leaders. The benefits of experiential learning in preparing for elite roles were also reported by Kelly *et al.* (2023) in their study of executive nurse directors. Echoing the consensus in this thesis on the need for development of a defined leadership pathway, the executive nurse directors in Kelly *et al.* (2023) study described the impact of lack of systematised opportunity on their preparedness to take up the role. Level appropriate experiences are required across the career pathway. Early career nurse leaders could for example, focus on influencing policy within their clinical area and organisation. Nurse leaders preparing for national level roles would require commensurate exposure to strategic policy making. These considerations are in line with Benton, Al-Maaitah and Gharaibah's (2017) integrative review where they highlight the importance of developing policy competence across the career continuum. Enabling nurses to influence policy effectively at micro, meso, and macro levels would not only better prepare future strategic nurse leaders, but harnessing the quantitative capacity of the profession could offer a route to build comprehensive expectations of nurses as policy actors.

At the macro level of policy influence participants were mindful of the small numbers of elite leaders who can provide mentoring and experiential opportunities and recommended thoughtful deployment to maximise impact. International mentorship programmes such as the Sigma Theta Tau

Global Leadership Mentoring Community (Rosser *et al.*, 2020) are one option to expand capacity particularly in countries or regions with few experienced strategic nurse leaders. The model of international dyads of mentor and mentee can offer the strategic mentorship required and enable leaders to build broader networks (Rosser *et al.*, 2020). While cross-cultural pairings can challenge taken for granted knowledge, they are acknowledged as limited in their ability to support mentees in navigating contextual and cultural nuances (Rosser *et al.*, 2020). Context-sensitive mentorship, particularly valued by participants in this study, provides an opportunity to learn from an existing leader in the field, preferably in the same country. The benefits of such a nuanced approach are well described by Rumsey *et al.*, (2022b) who reported success in provision of strategic leadership support tailored to the collectivist culture of the South Pacific. The findings here talk to the potential benefits of leveraging the potential of the international nursing community to support the development of future nurse leaders. That said, international education opportunities may be limited in their ability to provide context sensitive leadership development, recognised in this study as key to policy influence.

8.7 Shifting culture and bases of social power through connection and collaboration

The discussion of challenges to the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders suggests that the behaviour of a prototypical strategic nurse leader is not always perceived to include policy leadership. It has also described restrictions on the legitimate and expert power of nurses relating to perceived authority and capability as a policy actor. Strategic relationships within and beyond nursing were offered as a critical mitigation to the challenges faced by strategic nurse leaders in accessing and influencing policy discussions. Relationships were valued as the primary mechanism to broaden networks including with non-nursing decision makers, nurse leaders in other sectors, and international peers. Networks enabled communication and opportunities for collaboration. In line with Lu (2015) collaboration was highlighted as key to otherwise inaccessible resources. Strategic nurse leaders could for example borrow legitimacy from credible collaborators, unlocking access or visibility in policy conversations otherwise out of reach. The subsequent credible policy contributions they make could then scaffold their own legitimate and expert power.

8.7.1 A collective voice for influence

The development of a collective nursing voice was popular as a suggested approach to strengthening the policy influence of strategic nurse leaders (6.22). Nurse leaders, particularly in resource limited settings, valued the opportunity to borrow legitimacy from resources and policy positions of the global nursing community, consistent with the findings of Newman *et al.* (2019). A small number of nurse leaders from the Global North did not consider their own policy influence as dependent on

engagement with their international peers. There was however consensus, in line with Newman *et al.* (2019), on the value of networking and active connection across sectors, and the international nursing community to advance policy influence.

Ambitions for development of a collective voice were threatened by some suggestion in this study of division, conflict, and lack of collaboration within the profession. Reflections on the negative impact of within group conflict on policy influence are consistent with Truijens and Hanegraaff (2020) argument that within group conflict limits the policy influence of that group. Where there is a split in perspective and conflict about a policy position, policymakers are less likely to progress either side, because of the consequent lack of support (Truijens and Hanegraaff, 2020). Fragmentation of the nursing policy voice, including through lack of intersectoral collaboration, was perceived to provide an opportunity for more dominant groups, or those with competing agendas to discredit and disregard the nursing contribution.

The findings of this study illustrated diverging perceptions of cross-sectoral understanding within nursing, with 50% of the Delphi panel in Round 3 agreeing that there was a clear understanding of the roles of different sectors (6.13, Table 6.15). Lack of cross-sectoral understanding was identified by Splane and Huffman Splane (1994), as constraining the ability of nursing to construct a collective voice. There were also split perceptions about whether or not nurse leaders take a coordinated approach to working together (6.13, Table 6.15). This finding is partly reflected in Chiu, Duncan and Whyte (2020) observation of little evidence of collaboration between sectors of nursing during an election campaign. The benefits to policy influence of developing cross-sector understanding was aptly demonstrated by the nurse leaders in Abhicharttibutra *et al.*'s (2014) study. Upon encountering an immovable block in progression of influencing policy on a workforce shortage through the nation's health ministry, the cross-sector collaboration of nurse leaders, reframed the policy position from an education perspective and the deans of nurse education in the group were subsequently successful in securing influence via the ministry of university affairs (Abhicharttibutra *et al.*, 2014). This example demonstrates the potential power of a shared vision on the policy influence of a collaborative which understands both the policy system and the resources available to them. Demonstrating the real-world return on investment of international networks Rumsey *et al.* (2022b) described the critical role of the South Pacific Chief Nursing and Midwifery Officers Alliance in enabling the region to strengthen its global influence. The positive impact of the Alliance on the status, representation, and influence of nursing in policy was evidenced through their contributions to key international strategies and the two most recent WHO chief nursing and midwifery officers being from the region (Rumsey *et al.*, 2022b). In the context of an increasingly globalised and

inequitable world, it makes sense for strategic nurse leaders to connect. The findings of this study suggest that intersectoral networks are under-developed and under used, in part argued by Benton and Ferguson (2016) as due to lack of confidence in communicating messages to large audiences. While the benefits of cross-sector and international collaboration for policy influence appear non-controversial, translating the ambition into reality requires further development. Nurse leaders can take deliberate steps to develop strategically valuable networks which leverage understanding of intersectoral roles, remits, responsibilities, and resources to maximise impact.

The breadth of policy interests, priorities, and perspectives across nursing means that potential targets for nursing's policy influence or collective voice are not one dimensional. The findings suggested that nursing's policy influence would benefit from construction of a shared policy vision or set of general principles that offer directionality, rather than prescription. More than 60% of Delphi panellists indicated that their country did not have a national policy vision for nursing. Collectively constructing a shared policy agenda with defined policy interests, priorities and actions as set out by Halpin (2015) could move nursing on from the reactive approach to policy noted in this study. The proactive co-design of a broad policy agenda could enable strategic nurse leaders to collectively forecast key policy issues for progression. The resulting agenda could then act as a reference point for strategic nurse leaders to identify and advance collective policy priorities contextualised to their own cultural and sectoral context.

8.7.2 Connecting beyond the profession

Networking and collaboration with groups and decision makers out with nursing was a prominent approach recommended by nurse leaders in this study and is reflected as one of Weible *et al.*'s (2012) conditions for policy influence. Some nurse leaders seemed confident in navigating networks to influence policy. Others described the policy discussions they wanted to access as inaccessible to nurses. This focus on the concept of policy making happening at particular policy tables is not reflected in the networked approach advocated by some senior strategic nurse leaders, or in Weible *et al.*'s (2012) work on policy influence.

Clarifying the structure and features of networks successfully influencing policy areas of interest to strategic nurse leaders could help identify existing connections of value and expose strategically important opportunities for development. Social network analysis has previously been used as a method to understand information flows and teamwork within and between groups of nurses (Benton and Ferguson, 2017; Bae, Farasat, Nikolaev, *et al.*, 2017), as well as more widely, for example in health policy (Lewis, 2006). Benton and Ferguson (2014) used social network analysis to understand the connectivity of strategic nurse leaders. The study identified that international

connections between nurse leaders were often not well developed or were contingent on accessing networks via international organisations. Broadening its use to map the broader social networks engaged in policy influence as proposed by Topp *et al.* (2021) could enable analysis of power and relationships within the network. Saatchi, Pallotti and Sullivan's (2023) argument for using social network analysis not only as a descriptive tool to understand the impact of interventions on the network could be applied to strategic nurse leaders in policy. A social network analysis based intervention could enable evaluation of the effect of changes in approach to policy influence to provide a more complete understanding of what works and in what context (Saatchi, Pallotti and Sullivan, 2023). Breaking the cycle identified in this study of nurses as not expected to participate in policy, of having the authority or expertise to influence policy requires an understanding of how the system interacts with nursing.

Credibly articulating return on investment of a potential policy position was considered by some nurse leaders to generate better quality relationships and opportunities to influence policy. This finding is consistent with Petridou, Becker and Sparf's (2021) social network analysis of policy entrepreneurs, individuals effective in progressing policy issues. The study reported that successful entrepreneurs were more likely to be credible, be skilled in understanding how to engage others, and had strong political relationships (Petridou, Becker and Sparf, 2021). The observations of Petridou, Becker and Sparf (2021) were echoed by nurse leaders in this study. The focus on quality of relationships was highlighted by Ruggiano *et al.* (2014). They reported that connections within a network were more likely to share resources when policy positions were translated in a way which aligned with the priorities of network or policy actors. The resulting reciprocal dialogue was reported by Ruggiano *et al.* (2014) to strengthen policy advocacy. Shifting the focus of connecting with non-nursing decision makers away from focusing on transmitting the need to include nurses towards engagement which articulates the nursing contribution in the context of the priorities of their target audience potentially marks a valuable transition in nursing's approach to policy influence.

8.8 The potential role of a consensus statement in progressing policy influence

The Delphi consensus statement is a novel and tangible output of this study. It demonstrates that development of internationally shared written statement presenting actionable areas to improve nursing's policy influence is feasible. Locating common ground suggests a coordinated approach to development of policy influence is possible even in the context of a profession which is internationally variable in terms of cohesion, opportunities, and priorities. The areas of divergence uncovered in the Delphi provide helpful signposts to where approaches to policy influence would particularly benefit future research or deliberate contextualisation in operationalisation. While the

consensus statement described an agreed shared approach to strengthening policy influence the study also captured the sensitivity and flexibility required to contextualise the operationalisation of any statement within the nuances of international nursing. One example of this contextualisation was variation in qualifying words, such as 'must', preferred within the statement and their implications for securing commitment to act.

The request in both the Delphi and post-Delphi interviews for the statement to be re-orientated towards persuading non-nursing decision makers of the value of nursing's policy contribution was intriguing. It was particularly striking that government nurse leaders, presumed to be in positions close to policy making, perceived a need to make the case for the return on investment of including nurses in policy making. This finding suggests that the place of government nurse leaders as credible policy actors is at an early stage in some countries, important for their legitimate power, adding further weight to earlier discussion about the variation in policy influence of strategic nurse leaders (8.6.1, 8.6.2). There is an argument that the ask to orientate the statement to policymakers suggests that strategic nurse leaders perceive that upfronting the 'why' of including nursing rather than what nursing can actually contribute to policy discussions, misses a critical opportunity to demonstrate expert power. The consensus statement offered a shared vision for an international approach to the development of policy influence. Where nurse leaders perceive a need to articulate their potential contribution it is likely that a contextualised and compelling policy brief on the policy issue, as advocated by Benton *et al.* (2020b) will yield more opportunities to contribute than a broad-based consensus statement or unidimensional approach reiterating why nursing should be included. Such approaches to development of policy competence could offer a mechanism for strategic nurse leaders to be agile and relevant in their policy influence as policy priorities and policymakers change.

The consensus statement offers an internationally agreed set of approaches to strengthen policy influence in strategic nurse leadership, an underdeveloped field of research. The use of consensus building methods is common in the context of insufficient empirical work (Rosenfeld, Nnachet, and Corrigan, 2015) or where there is no clear way forward (de Loë *et al.*, 2016). Although this thesis took deliberate steps to promote rigour (8.9.4), scholars have long criticised the range of consensus building methods for lacking consistency in methodological rigour. This critique bears out in the literature which has demonstrated wide variation in reporting quality of Delphi studies (Diamond, *et al.*, 2014; de Loë *et al.*, 2016; Jünger *et al.*, 2017), threatening the trustworthiness of the findings. Lack of trustworthiness is a critical point given that products built through consensus building methods, such as the consensus statement, are often used as tools to influence change in policy and practice (La Brooy, Pratt, Kelaher, 2020; Arakawa and Bader, 2022). Endorsement of the consensus statement was one approach perceived by government nurse leaders as offering a route to

increasing its influence. Seeking the endorsement of an influential organisation or institution is consistent with Jünger *et al.* (2017) who recommend endorsement as part of the dissemination process for rigorously developed products of Delphi studies.

The exploration of the trustworthiness of the consensus statement through the final round of the Delphi and post-Delphi study provided useful insights into how it resonated with strategic nurse leaders. It would not, however have been appropriate to further refine the statement on the basis of individual without designing another opportunity to preserve its trustworthiness as a product of consensus building. This is particularly relevant to this consensus statement given the international and intersectoral variation in perspectives and need for cultural alignment in approaches to improving policy influence. As such, to have used the comments to refine the consensus statement would not only have been methodologically flawed but would have missed the opportunity to strengthen the shared policy voice through wider engagement, and robust refinement of the statement.

Testing the consensus statement in this study indicated an appetite among strategic nurse leaders for a tangible synthesis of policy influence enablers. Other scholars studying the policy engagement of nurses have also constructed outputs from modified Delphi studies including an empowerment model (Shariff, 2015b), a policy participation model (Wichaikhum *et al.*, 2020), and a framework for nurse manager policy participation (Hajizadeh *et al.*, 2022). Investigating the resonance and potential utility of the statement in both the final round of the Delphi and post-Delphi interviews was key in developing the trustworthiness of the study. Shariff (2015b, p4) and Hajizadeh *et al.* (2022, p.4334) reported validation of their models. The four Delphi panellists who participated in the post-Delphi validation of Shariff's (2015b) East African model indicated that it seemed to offer a practical and useful approach. Taking a similar approach Hajizadeh *et al.* (2022) finalised their framework to support nurse manager participation in health policy with an expert panel (n=15) following a two round modified Delphi with 20 panellists in Iran. Contrastingly, Wichaikhum *et al.* (2020) did not report any testing of their framework, developed in Thailand following a three-round modified Delphi. Arguably the testing of the statement in this thesis was the most robust gathering views on the statement from both the Delphi panel as well as in depth interviews with government nurse leaders who had not taken part in the Delphi.

The rigour of the consensus statement is also strengthened by the transparent mapping of the statement to the original data. Insufficient detail threatens rigour, particularly in understanding the decisions taken by the researcher that led to constructing a synthesised output of a Delphi (Jünger *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, the trustworthiness of Shariff's (2015b) empowerment model for policy

participation is compromised by insufficient detail about how the data generated in the Delphi informed decisions about the hierarchy of the model structure. For example, Shariff's (2015b) model suggests that strategic nurse leaders develop skills in 'structures and processes' before 'visibility'. 'Structures and processes' include activity by the nurse leader to influence inclusion in policymaking structures (Shariff, 2015b). 'Visibility', at the pinnacle of the model, was defined as being visibly policy-active and engaging with the media (Shariff, 2015b). Placing structures and processes before visibility (Shariff, 2015b) conflicts with the findings of this thesis. While the importance of understanding structures and processes early in leadership development was recognised, the findings of this thesis suggest that expecting strategic nurse leaders to influence substantive structural or process change before they are perceived as a credible policy actor may be premature. The structure of Shariff's (2015b) model may be appropriate for the Eastern African region it was developed within; however, no narrative is provided to support interpretation of hierarchy of the model. Without the contextual detail and link to the data to understand how decisions were made, the trustworthiness and potential utility of the model is uncertain.

The consensus statement in this study focused on shifting culture, structures and processes to position and prepare strategic nurse leaders to be and, crucially, be perceived as, credible policy actors. One striking difference between the consensus statement and the outputs of Shariff (2015b) Wichaikhum *et al.* (2020), and Hajizadeh *et al.* (2022) is that collaboration and engagement beyond the profession was markedly absent from the other models and framework. This is important given the findings relating to the importance of understanding and strengthening the intersections and networks between the profession and non-nursing policy actors. The consensus statement in this thesis was also framed as a cohesive whole for an intersectoral audience. Contrastingly, Wichaikhum *et al.* (2020) presented actions segmented by sector with the notable exception of regulation. The actions suggested in Wichaikhum *et al.*'s (2020) framework to improve policy participation were more operationally focused than the higher-level system enablers for policy influence described in the consensus statement. The consensus statement in this thesis is the first empirically constructed consensus statement which synthesises global, cross-sectoral perspectives, on the development of policy influence of strategic nurse leaders.

8.9 Reflections on the research process

8.9.1 Reflections on the use of social constructionism

At the outset of this PhD the discourse around nursing and policy appeared to me as often deficit based, focused on what nursing couldn't do or wasn't doing in policy. I was interested in how the conversation could be moved on in a way which was relevant and tangible to nurse leaders working

at a national or international level. Positioning this study within social constructionism enabled an inclusive approach to understanding multiple realities of strategic nurse leaders internationally. Through the critical stance towards taken for granted knowledge, one of the four tenets of social constructionism (Burr, 2015), the marginalisation of nursing in policy and the associated links to historical and cultural norms and inequalities, such as the dominance of medicine (8.6.2.3), were re-examined and contextual nuances recognised. An interlinked critique of social constructionism is that it does not actively challenge antecedents to marginalisation as the shared reality is constructed through the work (Phillips, 2023), and as such could risk perpetuating inequalities within the findings. This critique underlines the need for the findings of this thesis to be interpreted as one valuable but contextually situated contribution to understanding strategic nurse leadership in policy.

The iterative approach of the Delphi as the central method was congruent with social constructionist tenet of enabling interaction between the individual and the group. The resulting construction, debate, and refinement of a shared understanding of international nurse leadership in public policy, demonstrates the ability of the Delphi to deliver on the social constructionist tenet of knowledge sustained through social processes. In the final tenet of pairing knowledge and social action, the study offered insights into how prevailing power dynamics interact with the challenges, approaches, and contributions of strategic nurse leaders in policy.

8.9.2 Reflections on theoretical perspectives

The bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) and CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) have provided a novel lens through which to interpret the findings of this study. The bases of social power (French and Raven, 1959) exposed the challenges for nurse leaders in their legitimate and expert power particularly and drew out where nurse leaders were focused in developing their influence. French and Raven's (1959) interpretation of power as in the eye of the beholder provided an opportunity to enact the social constructionist tenet of challenging previously accepted knowledge. This yielded interesting perspectives on otherwise seemingly innocuous suggestions to improve policy influence, for example, the proposition of increasing the number of GCNOs. Although the bases of social power provide a useful theoretical perspective, this study highlighted the limitations of the bases in understanding the implications of the quality of interpersonal relationships on the power of leaders. Relationships, while implicit in the bases of social power are not explicitly considered in the original bases, missing the opportunity to incorporate the power of the quality of the relationships themselves, identified in this study as a critical approach in policy influence.

CLT was not tested in this study, rather it borrowed CLT's assumption that culturally mediated leadership expectations would vary internationally and by context (House *et al.*, 2004; House *et al.*,

2014). Divergent findings were illuminated by the application of CLT's lens of leadership 'success' as contingent on leaders meeting or exceeding culturally mediated expectations of how effective leaders behave (House *et al.*, 2014). CLT (House *et al.*, 2014) could not however provide a framework to understand how to shift culturally mediated expectations from the current to future state, recognised as a key finding in this study. The depth and explanatory power offered by theory in this study supports Chiu's (2021) contention that strategic nurse leadership scholarship in policy would benefit from an expanded use of theory.

8.9.3 Reflections on the methods

Delphi studies have been criticised as limited in relation to the potential application of their outputs (Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn, 2007). Belton *et al.*'s (2019) argument that the transferability of Delphi findings may be a more pertinent consideration than generalisability resonates with the social constructionist epistemology and design of this study. Exploring the potential transferability of the content of the consensus statement through post-Delphi interviews was a helpful first step in line with Skulmoski, Hartman and Krahn's (2007) calls for post-Delphi investigation. The interviews with government nurse leaders generated rich data and also offered insights into strategic nurse leadership, identified by Rasheed, Younas and Mehdi's (2020) as an under-studied population. A larger, multi-professional post-Delphi inquiry could have sought the perspectives of non-nursing decision makers on the resonance and potential utility of the statement. Researching the perspectives of non-nursing decision makers would be one useful next step in the development of evidence informed and impactful approaches to improve policy influence.

Researching elite nurse leaders was a privilege, and a humbling challenge. Accessing the strategic nurse leaders benefited from having the sponsorship of an international strategic nurse leader, and the credibility it conferred on the study. The use of sponsorship in this study could be interpreted as mirroring approaches described by strategic nurse leaders in scaffolding credibility by leveraging networks. The reach of the study, while not complete, was significant. The participation of strategic nurse leaders from 39 countries from across all world regions and income levels, means that the study includes contributions from 20% of WHO member states (39/194).

8.9.4 Reflections on reflexivity and rigour

The three overarching frameworks used to strengthen the rigour of the study were trustworthiness criteria (Lincoln and Guba, 1985), reflexive awareness (Green and Thorogood, 2018), and authenticity criteria (Guba and Lincoln, 1989), detailed in 3.6 and 4.7. The resulting framework to proactively manage the rigour of the study enabled an understanding of the impact of practical research decisions on rigour, as well as how my interpretation and perceived reality of nurse

leadership in public policy shaped the study. The strategies identified in Chapter 3 were deployed as planned in Chapter 4.

Use of Green and Thorogood's (2018) four dimensions of reflexivity (3.6) structured my understanding the impact of the decisions I made in terms of theory and methodology on the research. Alongside comprehensive methodology and methods chapters, methodological openness was practised through regular reflection points with challenge from the supervisory team and building of an audit trail. Theoretical openness was developed through the debating of potential theoretical perspectives with the supervisory team. It was subsequently enhanced through thick description in the methodology and methods chapters and description of key limitations earlier in this chapter.

The dimensions of reflexivity resonated with the social constructionist tenets in requiring deliberate consideration of the impact of the social setting, and broader social context within which the research sat (Green and Thorogood, 2018). Considering these perspectives enabled me to better appreciate the intersection between the research, my developing understanding, and the broader conversation about strategic nurse leadership internationally. My reflexive journal suggests a shift in my assumptions and thinking over time. At the outset I appreciated the existence of international variation but considered nursing to be relatively powerful, or at least improving. Over time and with proactive challenge, my assumptions have moved towards a greater recognition of the extent to which context and culture mediate the influence, and level of challenge nurse leaders navigate to influence policy. While such reflexivity is useful it is not a panacea. A multipronged approach to engagement with my supervisory team, the research process, and dialogue in the literature enabled timely identification, exploration, and resolution of emerging challenges in the thesis.

The authenticity criteria set out by Guba and Lincoln (1989), clarified by Nolan *et al.* (2003) offered a structure to explore the extent that engagement in the research might change the perspectives of participants. Although there was representation across world regions and income levels (8.2) the unintended bias towards high income countries has implications for fairness. This is particularly in relation to hearing from nurse leaders in the Global South, who have often been neglected in the literature (Salvage and White, 2019). Where the methods used in this study did provide explicit fairness was in the Delphi's iterative approach. While the Delphi removed group power dynamics it still enabled opportunities for panellists to amend or clarify their judgements. The final round of the Delphi and post-Delphi interviews also gave opportunity for fairness in the ability for both panellists and post-Delphi interviewees to comment on the draft consensus statement.

The ontological and educative authenticity of the study encompass the impact of the research on participants' personal understanding of the topic, and their understanding of the perspectives of others respectively, were fulfilled to some extent in the execution of the study (Nolan *et al.*, 2003). The between round feedback during the Delphi provided offered panellists an opportunity to understand the similarities and differences in the views and experiences of the cross-sectoral panel of international peers. While the study did not capture data on how this changed people's perspectives, it provides evidence of the opportunity provided to the panel. The review of the draft consensus statement in the post-Delphi interviews offered government nurse leaders an insight into the perspectives of the Delphi panel. The post-Delphi interviews captured some evidence of the educative impact of exposure to other perspectives. Some of the government nurse leaders for example reflected on the difference between the ambitions of the consensus statement and their individual priorities and challenges in policy leadership.

Two of the authenticity criteria relate to encouraging action: catalytic authenticity, the extent to which participation in the research provided a rationale for change, and tactical authenticity, the extent to which it provided the means to enact change (Nolan, 2003). The construction of a consensus statement provides some preliminary evidence of catalytic authenticity in the development of shared approaches for change. Government nurse leaders reflecting on the resonance of the statement offered their own priorities for advancing their policy influence. These reflections offer an insight into the potential tactical authenticity of the consensus statement.

8.10 Implications and recommendations

This study has extended the body of knowledge on strategic nurse leadership and public policy. It has highlighted the intersectional position of strategic nurse leaders as elite in the context of their role and profession while marginalised within policy making. The findings have a range of potential implications for policy, practice, education, and research. Key points are elaborated in the following section.

Policy

The marginalisation of nurses in high level policy making foregrounds an opportunity for policymakers internationally to deliver on longstanding ambitions to provide a framework for sustainable and meaningful involvement of strategic nurse leaders in policy making. While there was international variation this study highlighted a tension in balancing context sensitive and standardised approaches to strengthening nurse leadership in public policy. Areas of international and cross-sectoral consensus set out in the consensus statement constructed during the Delphi

could offer a starting point for the international strategic nurse leadership community to plan coordinated approaches on points of common ground.

- International and cross-sectoral nursing collectives such as the Global Partners Meeting on Nursing and Midwifery (formerly known as the Triad) could consider using the learning from the draft consensus statement as a basis for co-construction of shared priority actions to best position strategic nurse leaders to influence policy.
- In addition to the presence of strategic nurse leadership roles governments could review the extent to which their structures deliver on existing policy commitments to meaningfully include strategic nurse leaders in policy making at all levels.

Practice

Implications and recommendations for practice consider three dimensions of practice: nursing, strategic nurse leadership, and the practice of non-nursing decision makers. The findings of this study have foregrounded the importance of connectivity within and beyond the profession. They have also called for a shift in culturally endorsed leadership expectations to align the rhetoric and reality of nurses as policy actors.

- Nurses build their understanding of policy influence as a core feature of the profession through engagement with relevant policy opportunities across the career continuum. For nurses seeking to become strategic nurse leaders, experiential learning through engaging in national and international opportunities should form a key part of their preparation.
- Nurse leaders should continue to network across professional boundaries to develop active policy networks which support them to develop legitimate power for policy influence. The impact of international networks on policy influence should be robustly evaluated.
- Non-nursing decision makers connect with strategic nurse leaders to understand the reciprocal benefits of including nursing expertise in policy making.

Education

High quality preparation of future nurse leaders is key to improving the policy influence of the profession. Equipping strategic nurse leaders to be policy confident could break the cycle of few opportunities to influence policy, reinforcing lack of preparedness, and consequent poor performance, further compounding the lack of opportunities to influence policy in the future. While preparation was not contentious the findings did raise some questions about the structure and function of approaches to preparation.

- Policy competence should be built across the career continuum through formal and experiential education and mentoring. Maximising the policy capability and capacity of the nursing profession would support succession planning, build expectation of nurses as policy actors at all levels, and equip future strategic nurse leaders for impactful influence at national and global fora.
- Experienced strategic nurse leaders should consider what mentoring or experiential learning opportunities they can offer to support the development of future nurse leaders.
- Educators responsible for preparation of future strategic nurse leaders could consider the opportunities for interdisciplinary learning to support strategic nurse leaders and non-nursing decision makers to work better together.

Research

This study has extended the small body of knowledge on the experiences of strategic nurse leaders in influencing policy. It did not however include the perspectives of non-nursing decision makers, which could be crucial to the required shift in legitimate and expert power, as well as in the perceived leadership expectations of nursing in policy. The findings suggest an appetite for future research to be action oriented, with the ability to practically inform the direction of strategic nurse leadership in policy influence.

- Future research should explore the expected role and impact of strategic nurse leaders in policy making from the perspective of non-nursing decision makers. This empirical work could inform the design of an intervention to shift culturally mediated leadership expectations of strategic nurse leaders in policy making.
- Researchers and policy makers could use social network analysis to understand existing the power, resources, and relationships within policy networks. Social network analysis could also help strategic nurse leaders identify targets for developing their network for policy influence and understand the impact of changes they make to their network.
- Researchers could investigate the return on investment of strategic nurse leaders in policy. Being able to articulate the value add of strategic nurse leaders in policy could be a powerful lever for policy influence and for developing a defined leadership pathway for future strategic nurse leaders.

8.11 Concluding Remarks

This international study has extended the relatively underdeveloped body of knowledge around strategic nurse leadership and policy influence. The study successfully achieved its first aim to understand the challenges, approaches, and contribution of strategic nurse leaders to public policy.

In achieving its second aim it is the first study to construct a consensus statement exemplifying international and cross-sectoral perspectives on strategic nurse leadership in public policy.

Marginalisation in policy was foregrounded by participants to different extents internationally. As a consequence of being marginalised, strategic nurse leaders in this study primarily focused on access to rather than influence of policy. They called for change to enable nursing to become a credible policy actor. The strength of consensus on the need for change to support nurses to become policy influential suggested a gap between reality and long-standing rhetoric calling for expansion of nursing involvement in policymaking (All-Party Parliamentary Group on Global Health, 2016; Sigma Theta Tau International, 2017; WHO, 2020; Holloway *et al.*, 2021; WHO, 2021). While all the strategic nurse leaders in this study were in positions which might be assumed to be well-placed to influence policy, their pursuit of policy influence required navigation of a fleet of interlinking paradoxes: of being expected to lead but excluded, of being seen but not heard, of being large in size but narrow in influence, of being constrained to nursing-specific issues but criticised for being nursing centric, of wanting change but perceiving resistance. The ongoing calls to include nurses in policy making are welcome however the paradoxes indicate that realising the ambitions for nursing's policy influence requires action both within and beyond nursing.

The findings in this study of nurses challenge the implicit message in the rhetoric for inclusion of nursing as a policy ready profession. While many nurse leaders are skilful policy actors, at the level of the profession policy influence appears to be fragile and person dependent. Increasing the number and capability of strategic nurse leaders to credibly contribute to policy was popular in this study. The findings suggest however that while important, growing capacity and capability would be insufficient for policy influence due to culturally mediated constraints and prevailing power dynamics. Building the legitimate and expert power required to influence policy requires skilled strategic nurse leaders who use their deep contextual knowledge to deploy a range of technical and relational approaches to articulate the nursing policy contribution in a way which aligns with the priorities of others. Even with the most skilful strategic nurse leaders, realising nursing's potential in policy making also requires a shift in the culturally mediated perceptions of what a prototypical strategic nurse leader does. Building in policy leadership as an internationally expected part of a strategic nurse leader's role could help organisations and governments meaningfully leverage the latent expertise of nurses for the benefit of communities and health systems.

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Appendix 1: Ethical Approval

Ref: AS/ESB

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML3 0QA
Tel +44 (0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

19th January, 2015

Dear Prof Tolson

Outcome of UEC1 Application – Reviewed on 19th January, 2015

Thank you for your recent submission.

I can confirm your submission was reviewed, where the outcome has been:

- **APPROVED**

This outcome requires no further action.

Feedback is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Professor Austyn Snowden
Chair
School of Health Nursing & Midwifery Ethics Committee

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery

Dr Heather Simpson, Interim Dean

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity, Charity number SC002520

Ref: MC/ESB

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery

Hamilton Campus

Caird Building

HAMILTON

ML3 0QA

Tel +44 (0)1698 283100

Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

20th March, 2017

Meghan Bateson

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

[REDACTED]

Dear Meghan

Outcome of School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee

Title of study: - Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public health and healthcare policy: an international study

Thank you for your recent submission to the above Committee.

I can confirm your submission was reviewed by the Committee, where the outcome has been:

- **AMENDMENTS APPROVED**

This outcome requires no further action.

Feedback from the Committee is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Dr Maureen Crowley
Chair
School of Health Nursing & Midwifery Ethics Committee

cc Prof Debbie Tolson

Karen Wilson MSc, RGN, RM, DipDN, RNT, Dean of School

xxxxx 2015

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

Dear Colleague,

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) in partnership with the International Council of Nurses (ICN) are undertaking a project entitled ***Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.***

The twin aims of the study are:-

- to investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges and contribution to public policy;
- to construct a position statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

Nurse leaders are located in a range of sectors or domains and as such we are seeking to understand the unique and shared responsibilities and opportunities they have to shape public policy.

A literature review and key informant interviews will be undertaken to illuminate the range of nurse leaders' policy experiences, challenges and solutions. A subsequent participatory phase, composing a meeting in Scotland, will map and explore the fit of the emergent model of nurse policy leadership to two tracer conditions (dementia and diabetes) to refine the model and build a consensus statement.

The key informants will be experienced nurse leaders, like you, from across the world, selected because they currently hold or have held leadership roles in at least two of the domains of interest in the past ten years (education, regulation, service delivery, working in government, professional associations and trade unions).

We would like to invite you to be a key informant to help us with the first stage of the study.

Yours truly,

Dear

Further to the informal approach by David Benton and your expressed interest in being involved you are now cordially invited to take part in a structured telephone or Skype interview. Prior to the interview you will receive a short briefing paper to help you to prepare for the interview.

The interview will be undertaken by an experienced researcher, and with your permission, the interview will be audio recorded so that it can be transcribed and analysed.

The interview will take approximately 30 to 45 minutes to complete and will be conducted in English. If you are willing to be a key informant for the study, the research team will be pleased to assist you to make the practical arrangements for the interview.

On behalf of the project team, we thank you for your potential support and very much appreciate the time that you have taken to consider our request.

Yours truly

Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.

Participant Consent Form

You are now cordially requested to formally consent to be a Key Informant and take part in an individual structured telephone or Skype interview.

The interview will be undertaken by an experienced researcher, and with your permission, the interview will be audio recorded so that it can be selectively transcribed and analysed. The interview will take approximately 45 to 60 minutes to complete and will be conducted in English. Your identity and the identity of any individuals and organisations named within the interview will be removed from the interview transcript, and confidentially will be respected during project reporting.

Please initial the box

1) I confirm that I have read the letter of invitation and understand the project information.

2) I understand that I am a voluntary participant in the research and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without explanation or redress.

3) I understand that findings from the Key Informant Interview will be used to draft a consensus statement that will be refined by others using consensus development methods. The findings from the larger study may be published in professional journals, and included at conferences.

4) I agree to take part in the study.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of interviewer Date Signature

Thank you for your participation and if you have further questions please do not hesitate to get in touch.

Appendix 6: Pre-Delphi Interview Schedule

Thank you for considering participating in a key informant interview to investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges and contribution to public policy.

During the interview we will ask you: -

- to briefly tell us about your current job and other relevant strategic and policy influencing leadership roles that you have had within the last 10 years?
For example, in Education, Government, a Trade Union, a Professional Association, a Service Setting (Hospital, Health system) a Regulatory Body.
- some questions about the role of government level nurses and how in your current role you link with government nurses in terms of influencing public policy.
- your thoughts on the roles of other nurse leaders in terms of policy shaping
- from your perspective as a '*...current role....*' what you see as the unique and shared contribution to public policy of nurses from different organisations?
- which organisations /groups/ individuals come to mind in terms of your own policy influencing leadership and it would be useful to share some examples
- what you see as the main challenges for government nurse leaders in terms of leading in a political environment?
- about the main opportunities for government nurse leaders in terms of leading in a political environment?
- to give an example of something that you have achieved in terms of influencing public policy-and explain how you did this.
- reflecting on your own strategic leadership explain and illustrate the leadership approaches that you believe are effective in terms of influencing public policy? In other words what has worked well for you?
- what preparation / experience equips nurse leaders to be effective in policy influencing
- if you agree with the statement that policy know how and policy competence among nurse leaders is low compared to other professions.
- to share your views on co-ordination of action by nurses and nurse leaders in terms of influencing healthcare policy.
- to comment on the statement- 'nurse leaders who harness the political capital of a range of organisations and colleagues are more effective in shaping policy than nurse leaders who do not'.

Appendix 7: Pre-Delphi Interview Indexed Excerpt

Transcript excerpt	Coding
<p>Reflecting on your current or previous strategic leadership can you please describe the leadership approaches that you believe are effective in terms of influencing policy?</p> <p>P8. I've always been in leadership roles, and I think that leadership approaches that are effective is good listening¹, building confidence² and trust³ and building the team⁴. Because once you lose trust with people you can get it back but it's difficult³. So, you know I think you know the secret to my success are always being able to really be able to build a team around a position that needs to change⁵ or being in hand or needs to be created because you can't, one person can't do it all. One person cannot do it all⁵. You know if you want to really make change that's sustainable you've got to bring a lot of people around the table with you where you've got to be the person that motivates people internally and externally⁶, that has the confidence and trust in you to, to say you know when 'X' said we're going to do this, she is going to do it, and she is going to make sure that everybody feels good about doing it so that there's some positive outcomes⁷ and good with conflict⁸. I think the other thing of being an effective leader is it's going to be complex so you've got to learn how to manage complex change⁹ and you've got to be able to review and change and look within yourself and say you know this looks like it didn't go well, how can I take this, learn from this and revamp it so we go back a different way¹⁰. So also, be resilient and not giving up. If I go around the world and I see people that are like I'm so sad, I'm so tired, I'm burned out, well maybe the light was never lit you know¹¹. Because don't tell me that because the issue is even if there's just a little bit of a smoke and flame left you ought to be able to blow on it and bring it back to life¹¹. You know we got too much to do now, you can't just give up¹². You've got to be clever because in policy making and politics timing is everything. Timing is everything¹³. That's why you have to be internally and externally aware of what's going on in your environment¹⁴ so you don't look like [stupid] when you go and ask for something stupid that shouldn't even have been brought up in the context of what the country is going through or what the government is going through¹⁵.</p>	<p>¹Need for listening</p> <p>²Building confidence, ⁴team</p> <p>³Fragility of trust</p> <p>⁴Building a team.</p> <p>⁵One person can't do it all</p> <p>⁶Leadership skill in inclusive engagement</p> <p>⁷Leadership integrity</p> <p>⁸Conflict management</p> <p>⁹Managing complexity</p> <p>¹⁰Reflecting on action</p> <p>¹¹Resilience</p> <p>¹²Urgency within nursing in politics</p> <p>¹³Timing as leadership skill</p> <p>¹⁴Understanding broader picture</p> <p>¹⁵Risks to credibility</p>

“Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study”

Policy Delphi – Round 1 Questionnaire

Demographic Information

Please answer the questions below by either typing in the grey box or, for the multiple-choice questions, please click the grey box next to your chosen answer.

1. Please state the country in which you are currently employed as a nurse leader
2. Which of the following best describe your current leadership role? You can tick more than one box.
 - Education
 - Government
 - Trade union
 - Professional Nursing Association
 - Professional Regulation
 - Healthcare Providing Organisation
 - Other: please describe:
3. How long have you been in your current role? Please tick one box only.
 - More than 6 months
 - Less than a year
 - 1-4 years
 - 5-9 years
 - 10+ years
4. Which, if any, of the following best describe your previous leadership roles over the last five years? You can tick more than one box.
 - Education
 - Government
 - Trade union
 - Professional Nursing Association
 - Professional Regulation
 - Healthcare Providing Organisation
 - None
 - Other: please describe
5. Are you male or female? Please tick one box only.
 - Male
 - Female

Appendix 8: Delphi Round 1 Questionnaire

The Public Policy Influence of Nursing

The following statements are in relation to the public policy influence of nursing. They have been developed from the research literature and interviews with international strategic nurse leaders.

Please choose only **one** of the available options to show the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements. For each statement choose your answer by checking the box on the appropriate column. When considering your answer please choose the most appropriate option for the country where you currently work as a nurse leader.

	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Nurse leaders seek support from healthcare and other disciplines to achieve influence.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Nurses are marginalised (seen and treated as less important than other disciplines) in policy making	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	We don't need to change anything about nursing policy influence at a national level.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	Nurses around the world have the same opportunities to contribute to public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
10	Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11	Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12	Nurses are rarely at the policy making table	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13	In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14	Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15	An agreed structure is required to facilitate the collaboration of different sectors of nursing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix 8: Delphi Round 1 Questionnaire

The Public Policy Influence of Nursing continued.

	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
16	All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17	There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18	Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
19	Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
21	Nursing has an effective political voice	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
22	Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23	Policy influence is not a priority in nursing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
24	There are unique public health policy issues in my country.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
25	There is no benefit from nurse leaders from different countries working together.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
26	National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
27	The impact of the contribution that nurse leadership can make to public policy is directly related to their networks and how they manage their networks.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
28	Nurses make an important contribution to public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
29	Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
30	Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
31	Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
32	A collective international nursing voice would strengthen my policy influence in my country.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix 8: Delphi Round 1 Questionnaire

Development of Strategic Nurse Leadership

The following items are about the development of strategic nurse leadership and have been drawn from the research literature and interviews with international nurse leaders.

Please **choose only one** of the available options to show the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements. Please choose your answer thinking about the situation in the country where you work as a nurse leader.

	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
33	Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
34	Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
35	Cultural understanding is important to effective global policy influence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
36	There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
37	Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
38	Succession planning needs more resources in order to be provided systematically.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
39	Effective nursing leadership in the policy process requires a range of approaches	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
40	Nurses need to be formally educated to take up strategic nurse leadership roles	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
41	There should be a standardised mentorship programme for potential nurse leaders.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
42	Nurse leadership preparation begins at the pre-registration (student) stage.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
43	There should be a strategic plan for developing the capability and capacity of nursing for policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
44	Understanding the public health context (situation) is important to effective policy influence.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
45	Policy and leadership education is available in my country.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
46	There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix 8: Delphi Round 1 Questionnaire

47. Please list up to five main barriers or obstacles to nurses making an effective leadership contribution to public health policy. Please provide your answer by typing in the grey box.

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

48. Please list up to five things that would help nurse leaders to make a stronger contribution to public policy. Please provide your answer by typing in the grey box.

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

Please feel free to write any other comments in the grey box below:

To submit your response please save the completed questionnaire to your files and send as an email attachment to [REDACTED]

by Friday 20th March 2015.

Personal details withheld.

Many thanks for taking the time to complete this questionnaire.

Appendix 9: Delphi Invitation Letter

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML9 0QA
Tel +44 (0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

xxxxx 2015

Dear Colleague,

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) in partnership with the International Council of Nurses (ICN) are undertaking a project entitled ***Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.***

The twin aims of the study are: -

- to investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges and contribution to public policy;
- to construct a position statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

To address these aims we have undertaken key informant interviews and a literature review. These will be used to inform a Delphi process which aims to explore international perspectives on high level nurse leadership. The emergent position statement will be refined at a global summit on nurse leadership in 2015.

As part of this study, we would like to invite you, as a nurse leader, to participate in the three round Delphi process. This will involve you completing three semi-structured questionnaires over a twelve week period. Each questionnaire will take a maximum of 30 minutes to complete.

It is entirely up to you whether or not you take part. Before deciding, please read the enclosed information sheet which explains what the study involves. If you would like more details about this study or to enquire about taking part, please contact Meghan Bateson at: [REDACTED] If you have any further queries the lead researcher Professor Debbie Tolson will be pleased to hear from you. Professor Tolson can be contacted at: [REDACTED]

On behalf of the project team, we thank you for your potential support and very much appreciate the time that you have taken to consider our request.

Yours truly

Personal details withheld.

Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public health and healthcare policy: an international study

We would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

Who is conducting the study?

The researcher conducting this study is Meghan Bateson, supervised by Professor Debbie Tolson. The study is part of an PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) being undertaken at the University of the West of Scotland

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to explore strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy internationally.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to be invited because you have been identified as having an interest and relevant experience in strategic nurse leadership and public policy.

What would I have to do if I agreed to take part?

If you decide to take part, you will be asked to participate in a three round Delphi study. Participants will be asked to commit to participating in all three rounds of the study and will be sent three questionnaires over a 12 week period. Each questionnaire should take a maximum of thirty minutes to complete. The questionnaires will be completed electronically and returned via email to the researcher. One reminder will be sent out to participants who do not complete the questionnaire by the due date. All participants will be sent all three questionnaires.

Please be aware that the Delphi will be conducted in English language only and will therefore require participants to be confident reading and writing in English.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you whether or not you decide to take part. If you do decide to participate you will be given this information sheet to keep and asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw from the study at any time and without giving a reason. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your rights or relationships with the collaborating organisations of this research. If you do decide to withdraw, please notify the project team at [REDACTED] in order to ensure you are not sent any further correspondence relating to the study.

Appendix 10: Delphi Participant Information Sheet

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Your identity will be kept strictly confidential and known only to the researchers. All emails you receive and send in relation to the study will be between you and the research team only. No email distribution lists will be used, and your identity will not be known to the other participants in the study. The Chief Executive Officer of the International Council of Nurses will not know the identities of the study participants.

The information obtained will remain confidential and will be stored within a locked filing cabinet. The data will be held in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998), which means that we will keep it safely and cannot reveal it to other people. Personal data will not be kept for any longer than 12 months after the end of the study.

Insights gathered from you and other participants will be used in writing up the findings of this study. Although direct quotes from you may be used in the report or other publication, your name and other identifying information will be kept anonymous.

Will the study benefit me?

It may not benefit you directly but, by taking part in this research, you will be contributing to the development of knowledge about international strategic nurse leadership in influencing public policy.

What if something goes wrong?

If you want to complain at any time about anything related to this research study please contact the University of the West of Scotland Dean of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Karen Wilson at [REDACTED]

What will happen to the findings of the research study?

The findings may be submitted for publication in peer review journals and presented at conferences. The final report of this study will be available to participants on request.

Who is organising and funding the study?

This study is a joint project between the University of the West of Scotland and the International Council of Nurses.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given favourable opinion by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

If you have any further questions

If you have any questions or would like more information, please contact Meghan Bateson at [REDACTED]

For further queries please contact Professor Debbie Tolson at: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking the time to consider this opportunity.

Personal details withheld.

Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.

Participant Consent Form

You are now cordially requested to formally consent to being a panellist on the Policy Delphi study.

The Policy Delphi will be conducted in three rounds. It is anticipated that at each round the questionnaire will take a maximum of 30 minutes to complete. The questionnaires will be presented in English. Your identity and the identity of any individuals and organisations named within the questionnaires will be removed from the data, and confidentially will be respected during project reporting.

Please initial the box

- 1) I confirm that I have read the letter of invitation and understand the participant information sheet dated 17.12.14 (version 1.0) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

- 2) I understand that I am a voluntary participant in the research and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without my legal rights being affected.

- 3) I understand that findings from the Policy Delphi will be used to draft a consensus statement. The findings may be published in professional journals, and included at conferences; however, my name and other identifying information will be kept anonymous.

- 4) I agree to take part in the study.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of researcher Date Signature

Thank you for your participation and if you have further questions please do not hesitate to get in touch.

Appendix 12: Delphi cover letter

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML9 0QA
Tel +44 (0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

xxxxx 2015

Dear [insert name],

***Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy:
an international study.***

Round [insert number here] Questionnaire

Please find attached the first questionnaire associated with the above named study. Please complete the questionnaire and return to Meghan Bateson by email [REDACTED].

The return date for this questionnaire is xx/xx/xx. We will send out one reminder a one week before the due date. A further prompt will be sent on the day after the return date to give those who have not responded a final opportunity to do so.

If you do not have time to complete the questionnaire on this particular round you will still be sent subsequent round material unless you indicate a wish to withdraw. You will receive the [insert round number here] questionnaire two weeks after the return date on xx/xx/xx. [insert the following sentence if sending at round 1] The third questionnaire will be sent on xx/xx/xx.

Detailed completion instructions are provided on the questionnaire. If you require any further information or clarification about anything related to the study, please contact Meghan Bateson at [REDACTED].

Thank you once again for your support in this important study.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for taking the time to consider this opportunity.

Appendix 13: Delphi Round 1 Feedback

“Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study”

Quantitative Results from Round 1

The results of the responses to the 46 statements provided in Round 1 are detailed here. Please note that this is for information only and does not require action. Please complete the Round 2 questionnaire, attached as a separate document to this email, and return to [REDACTED]

Of the 46 statements in Round 1, 28 achieved consensus and these are shaded in grey in the tables below. The criteria for each statement to achieve consensus is as follows:

- At least 67% participants hold the same opinion, which may be agreement or disagreement with the statement
- AND**
- The responses must have an interquartile range (IQR) of less than or equal to one. The IQR shows the spread of the responses. An IQR of one means that 50% of responses were within 1 answer choice of the median (middle) answer.

The Public Policy Influence of Nursing

Items which achieved consensus are shaded in grey.

	Statement	Median	IQR
1	Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy.	Disagree	1
2	There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	Agree	1
3	Nurse leaders seek support from healthcare and other disciplines to achieve influence.	Agree	0
4	Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	Agree	1
5	Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy.	Agree	1
6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	Agree	0.25
7	Nurses are marginalised (seen and treated as less important than other disciplines) in policy making.	Agree	1
8	We don't need to change anything about nursing policy influence at a national level.	Agree	1
9	Nurses around the world have the same opportunities to contribute to public policy.	Disagree	1
10	Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	Disagree	1
11	Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	Disagree	1
12	Nurses are rarely at the policy making table.	Agree	1

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 13: Delphi Round 1 Feedback

The Public Policy Influence of Nursing - continued.

Items which achieved consensus are shaded in grey.

	Statement	Median	IQR
13	In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.	Agree	1
14	Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	Disagree	1
15	An agreed structure is required to facilitate the collaboration of different sectors of nursing.	Agree	0.25
16	All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities.	Agree	1
17	There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy.	Agree	1
18	Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	Disagree	1
19	Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy.	Agree	1
20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	Agree	1
21	Nursing has an effective political voice	Disagree	1
22	Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing.	Agree	1
23	Policy influence is not a priority in nursing.	Disagree	1
24	There are unique public health policy issues in my country.	Agree	1
25	There is no benefit from nurse leaders from different countries working together.	Strongly Disagree	1
26	National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.	Agree / Disagree	1
27	The impact of the contribution that nurse leadership can make to public policy is directly related to their networks and how they manage their networks.	Agree	1
28	Nurses make an important contribution to public policy.	Agree	1
29	Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy.	Disagree	1
30	Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health.	Strongly Agree	1
31	Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions.	Agree	2
32	A collective international nursing voice would strengthen my policy influence in my country.	Agree / Strongly Agree	1

Appendix 13: Delphi Round 1 Feedback

Development of Strategic Nurse Leadership

Items which reached consensus (agreement of response) are shaded in grey.

	Statement	Median	IQR
33	Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	Agree	1
34	Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence	Agree	1
35	Cultural understanding is important to effective global policy influence	Agree	1
36	There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	Strongly Agree	1
37	Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	Disagree	1
38	Succession planning needs more resources in order to be provided systematically.	Agree	0
39	Effective nursing leadership in the policy process requires a range of approaches	Agree	1
40	Nurses need to be formally educated to take up strategic nurse leadership roles	Agree	1
41	There should be a standardised mentorship programme for potential nurse leaders.	Agree	1
42	Nurse leadership preparation begins at the pre-registration (student) stage.	Agree	1
43	There should be a strategic plan for developing the capability and capacity of nursing for policy	Agree	1
44	Understanding the public health context (situation) is important to effective policy influence.	Strongly Agree	1
45	Policy and leadership education is available in my country.	Agree	0
46	There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	Agree	1

Many thanks for all the responses received.

In addition to the quantitative results we received 323 qualitative comments about barriers (obstacles) and things which would help the nursing contribution to public policy. These were content analysed and are presented to you in the Round 2 questionnaire.

Please complete the Round 2 questionnaire
(attached to this email as a separate document) and return to [REDACTED] .

Many thanks for your continued support

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 14: Delphi Round 2 Questionnaire

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

“Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study”

Policy Delphi – Round 2 Questionnaire

We were delighted to receive the responses to the Round 1 questionnaire. The quantitative results from Round 1 have been provided for your information as a separate document attached to this email. 28 of the 46 statements in Round 1 achieved consensus (agreement of response). The criteria for each statement to achieve consensus is as follows:

- At least 67% participants hold the same opinion, which may be agreement or disagreement with the statement
- AND**
- The responses must have an interquartile range (IQR) of less than or equal to one. The IQR shows the spread of the responses. An IQR of one means that 50% of responses were within one answer choice of the median (middle) answer.

The 18 statements which did not achieve consensus (agreement of response) were considered to show diversity of opinion. In order to understand this diversity these statements are presented again in this questionnaire for your consideration. This is followed by statements which were developed from thematic analysis of participant responses to the open ended questions in Round 1 and one open ended question.

Statements which did not achieve consensus (agreement of response)

The following statements did not reach consensus. Please reflect on your Round 1 answer, which we have provided for your convenience, and confirm or update your choice. For each statement choose your answer from the options in the drop down box. To help us understand any differences in opinion it would be helpful if you could provide reasons behind some or all of your answers. An explanation would be particularly helpful if you disagree with the median response. When considering your answer please choose the most appropriate option for the country where you currently work as a nurse leader.

Statement	My Round 2 Answer	My Round 1 Answer	Group Median	IQR
Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			

Appendix 14: Delphi Round 2 Questionnaire

Statement	My Round 2 Answer	My Round 1 Answer	Median	IQR
Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nursing has an effective political voice.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.	Choose an item.		Disagree / Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
There are unique public health policy issues in my country.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions	Choose an item.	Strongly Agree	Agree	2
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			

Appendix 14: Delphi Round 2 Questionnaire

New Statements for Consideration

The following statements were developed from participant responses to the open ended questions in Round 1. Please show the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements by choosing your answer from the drop down box. To help us understand any differences in opinion please use the comment box to provide an explanation of the reasons for some or all of your choices. When considering your answer please choose the most appropriate option for the country where you currently work as a nurse leader.

Statement	My Answer	Comments
In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing.	Choose an item.	
In my country gender inequality has an impact on the ability of nurse leaders to influence public policy.	Choose an item.	
Nurse leaders are not in a stable position which makes it difficult to develop policy influence and to take risks.	Choose an item.	
The hierarchy within nursing is complicated and this adversely affects policy contribution.	Choose an item.	
In my country we do not have enough strong professional nurse leaders.	Choose an item.	
There are not enough nurses in policy making positions in my country.	Choose an item.	
There is a need for more nurse research which is designed to support policy making decisions.	Choose an item.	
Nursing needs a more visible and positive media profile nationally and internationally.	Choose an item.	
In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision making process.	Choose an item.	
It is difficult to gain access to the decision makers in policy.	Choose an item.	
Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.	Choose an item.	
Nurse leaders do not take an active role in policy making.	Choose an item.	
Nurses lack interest in policy making	Choose an item.	
Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy.	Choose an item.	
Involvement in policy making is not perceived by nurses as beneficial.	Choose an item.	
Nursing is reactive rather than proactive in policy making.	Choose an item.	
The quality of education on policy needs to be improved.	Choose an item.	
In my country access to education on policy needs to be cheaper and more accessible.	Choose an item.	
Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes	Choose an item.	
In my country the education system needs to change to make nurses fit for purpose for participating in policy making.	Choose an item.	
There is a need to embed an expectation amongst nursing students that they should be able to understand and engage with policy making.	Choose an item.	

Appendix 14: Delphi Round 2 Questionnaire

Statement	My Answer	Comments
Policy and leadership education should be provided by professional nursing associations and organisations as well as educational institutions.	Choose an item.	
Mentorship should be provided by nurse leaders who know and understand the culture and environment where the person being mentored works.	Choose an item.	
There is a need for a defined leadership career pathway to enable more deliberate succession planning.	Choose an item.	
We need more nurse leaders who have a clinical academic profile.	Choose an item.	
In my country there is a clear policy vision for nursing	Choose an item.	
Succession planning should be undertaken on the basis of the nurse's competence, attributes and ability to lead, not their clinical skill.	Choose an item.	
In my country nurses are often forced into leadership because there is no one else to do the job.	Choose an item.	
The political stability of my country has a significant impact on the nursing contribution to public policy.	Choose an item.	
Corruption affects policy making in my country.	Choose an item.	
The policy process in my country is slow and dysfunctional.	Choose an item.	
Nurses who are active in public policy need to be more visible.	Choose an item.	
Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.	Choose an item.	

In Round 1 there was agreement that to increase policy influence nursing needs to focus on broader policy issues, yet there was disagreement about whether there should be a focus on professional issues or patients and communities.

What do you think the policy focus of nursing should be? (please answer in grey box below)

Please feel free to write any other comments in the grey box below:

To submit your response please save the completed questionnaire
and send as an email attachment to [REDACTED] [by Friday 5th June 2015](#)

Many thanks for taking the time to complete this questionnaire.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 15: Delphi Round 2 Feedback

“Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study”

Quantitative Results from Round 2

The results of the responses to the statements provided in Round 2 are detailed here. Please note that this is for information only and does not require action. Please complete the Round 3 questionnaire, attached as a separate document to this email, and return to [REDACTED].

Quantitative Results of Round 2

- Of the 18 statements which did not achieve consensus (agreement of response) in Round 1, 8 achieved consensus in Round 2 and these are shaded grey in the Round 1 tables below.
- Of the 33 new statements provided in Round 2, 19 achieved consensus and are shaded grey in the Round 2 tables below.

The criteria for each statement to achieve consensus is as follows:

- At least 67% participants hold the same opinion, which may be agreement or disagreement with the statement
AND
- The responses must have an interquartile range (IQR) of less than or equal to one. The IQR shows the spread of the responses. An IQR of one means that 50% of responses were within one answer choice of the median (middle) answer.

Round 1 Statements

The following statements did not reach consensus in Round 1 and were reconsidered in Round 2. Items which achieved consensus are shaded in grey.

Statement	Median	IQR
Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	Disagree	1
Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	Disagree	1
Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	Disagree	1
There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	Agree / Disagree	1
Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy.	Agree	1
Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy.	Disagree	1
Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy.	Agree	1
There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy.	Agree	0.3
Nursing has an effective political voice.	Disagree	1

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 15: Delphi Round 2 Feedback

Round 1 Statements continued.

Statement	Median	IQR
National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.	Agree / Disagree	1
Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	Agree	1
Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	Agree	1
Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	Agree	1
Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	Disagree	1
There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	Agree	1
There are unique public health policy issues in my country.	Agree	1
In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.	Agree	1
Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions	Agree	1

Round 2 Statements

The following statements were developed from participant responses to the open ended questions in Round 1. Items which achieved consensus are shaded in grey.

Statement	Median	IQR
In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing.	Agree / Strongly Agree	1
In my country gender inequality has an impact on the ability of nurse leaders to influence public policy.	Agree	1
Nurse leaders are not in a stable position which makes it difficult to develop policy influence and to take risks.	Agree	1
The hierarchy within nursing is complicated and this adversely affects policy contribution.	Disagree	1
In my country we do not have enough strong professional nurse leaders.	Agree	1
There are not enough nurses in policy making positions in my country.	Agree	0
There is a need for more nurse research which is designed to support policy making decisions.	Agree	1
Nursing needs a more visible and positive media profile nationally and internationally.	Agree	1
In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision making process.	Agree	1
It is difficult to gain access to the decision makers in policy.	Agree	1
Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.	Agree	1

Appendix 15: Delphi Round 2 Feedback

Round 2 Statements continued.

Items which achieved consensus are shaded in grey.

Statement	Median	IQR
Nurse leaders do not take an active role in policy making.	Agree	1
Nurses lack interest in policy making	Agree	1
Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy.	Agree	1
Involvement in policy making is not perceived by nurses as beneficial.	Disagree / Agree	1
Nursing is reactive rather than proactive in policy making.	Agree	0
The quality of education on policy needs to be improved.	Agree	1
In my country access to education on policy needs to be cheaper and more accessible.	Agree	0
Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes	Agree / Strongly Agree	1
In my country the education system needs to change to make nurses fit for purpose for participating in policy making.	Agree	0
There is a need to embed an expectation amongst nursing students that they should be able to understand and engage with policy making.	Agree	1
Policy and leadership education should be provided by professional nursing associations and organisations as well as educational institutions.	Agree	1
Mentorship should be provided by nurse leaders who know and understand the culture and environment where the person being mentored works.	Agree	1
There is a need for a defined leadership career pathway to enable more deliberate succession planning.	Agree	0
We need more nurse leaders who have a clinical academic profile.	Agree	1
In my country there is a clear policy vision for nursing	Disagree	1
Succession planning should be undertaken on the basis of the nurse's competence, attributes and ability to lead, not their clinical skill.	Agree	1
In my country nurses are often forced into leadership because there is no one else to do the job.	Disagree	1
The political stability of my country has a significant impact on the nursing contribution to public policy.	Agree	1
Corruption affects policy making in my country.	Agree	1
The policy process in my country is slow and dysfunctional.	Agree	1
Nurses who are active in public policy need to be more visible.	Agree	0
Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.	Strongly Agree	1

Many thanks for all the responses received. The qualitative comments provided were very useful in helping us understand the results of Round 2 and contributed to the construction of the draft consensus statement presented in Round 3.

Please complete the Round 3 questionnaire
(attached to this email as a separate document) and return to [REDACTED]

Many thanks for your continued support

“Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study”

Policy Delphi – Round 3 Questionnaire

We were delighted to receive the responses to the Round 2 questionnaire. The quantitative results from Round 2 have been provided for your information as a separate document attached to this email. For the final round of this Policy Delphi we have constructed a draft consensus statement which incorporates the key findings from Rounds 1 and 2. In this round we would like you to:

- Read the draft consensus statement.
- Answer 8 short questions about the statement.
- Consider 8 statements which did not achieve consensus (agreement of response) in Round 2.

The Draft Consensus Statement

The advancement of public health and wellbeing through policy making must be informed by nursing expertise. Ensuring that this expertise is used effectively for the benefit of global health requires more nurse leaders to hold policy making positions and to possess policy influence, the development of which is a key priority for the nursing profession.

To improve policy influence nurses must be recognised as active and influential decision makers. To achieve this there is a need to establish a credible and collective nursing voice developed through international collaboration of strategic nurse leaders. National nursing strategies will inform this collaboration by providing clarity and direction of vision tailored to the needs of each country. This will enable the application of cultural and contextual understanding to internationally shared priorities which will ensure the formulation of responses which are effective and appropriate at a national level.

Proactively expanding the scope of nursing’s policy activity beyond issues directly related to the profession will progress nursing’s policy influence. The credibility of nurse leaders’ contributions across a wider range of issues relevant to society will be strengthened by collaboration out with nursing and health care. Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking.

Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles. Additionally, an overarching plan to improve the capacity and capability of nursing for policy making would provide a framework to optimise the quality and impact of the nursing contribution to policy. This framework is expected to include the development of a defined leadership pathway and structures for systematic succession planning.

Appendix 16: Delphi Round 3 Questionnaire

Questions about the Draft Consensus Statement

Statement	My Answer	Comments
This statement would be useful to nurse leaders.	Choose an item.	
This statement would be useful to me in influencing policy.	Choose an item.	
This statement reflects my views.	Choose an item.	

Is the statement easy to understand?	Choose an item.
If not, please provide the word, phrase or sentence which is difficult to understand.	

<p>In your opinion, what are the most important key messages in the statement? (please choose up to three)</p> <p>1.</p> <p>2.</p> <p>3.</p>

In your opinion, is there anything missing from the statement?	Choose an item.
If 'Yes', please explain what you consider to be missing.	

Does the statement need further editing (changes)?	Choose an item.
If 'Yes' please explain what edits (changes) you think would strengthen the statement? (please provide up to three)	
<p>1.</p> <p>2.</p> <p>3.</p>	

Can you imagine using this statement in your work?	Choose an item.
If 'Yes', please give up to two examples of how you imagine using this statement in your work.	
<p>1.</p> <p>2.</p>	
If no, please explain the reasons for your answer.	

Appendix 16: Delphi Round 3 Questionnaire

Statements which did not achieve consensus (agreement of response) in Round 2

The following statements did not reach consensus in Round 2. Please reflect on your Round 2 answer, which we have provided for your convenience, and confirm or update your choice. For each statement choose your answer from the options in the drop-down box. To help us understand any differences in opinion it would be helpful if you could provide reasons behind some or all of your responses. When considering your answer please choose the most appropriate option for the country where you currently work as a nurse leader.

Statement	My Round 3 Answer	My Round 2 Answer	Median	IQR
Nurse leaders are not in a stable position which makes it difficult to develop policy influence and to take risks.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
The hierarchy within nursing is complicated and this adversely affects policy contribution.	Choose an item.		Agree / Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
It is difficult to gain access to the decision makers in policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurse leaders do not take an active role in policy making.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Nurses lack interest in policy making	Choose an item.		Agree / Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy.	Choose an item.		Agree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			
Involvement in policy making is not perceived by nurses as beneficial.	Choose an item.		Disagree	1
	The reason(s) for my answer is/are:			

Please feel free to write any other comments in the grey box below

To submit your response please save the completed questionnaire and send as an email attachment to [REDACTED] by [Friday 27th November 2015](#)

Many thanks for taking the time to complete this questionnaire.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 17: Post-Delphi Interview Invitation Letter

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML9 0QA
Tel +44 (0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

xxxxx 2017

Dear Colleague,

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS) is undertaking a project entitled ***Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.***

The twin aims of the study are:-

- to investigate strategic nurse leadership approaches, challenges and contribution to public policy;
- to construct a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on nurse leadership and policy influence.

The study comprises several strands of research. A Delphi study, informed by a literature review and key informant interviews, was conducted with a panel of international strategic nurse leaders. The Delphi constructed a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on effective nurse leadership and policy influence. We would like to invite you to contribute to the final stage of the study which will consider the potential application and usefulness of the consensus statement which emerged from the Delphi study.

Participants in the study will be experienced nurse leaders, like you, from across the world, selected because they currently hold or have held strategic leadership roles in government in the past ten years.

If you decide to take part, you will be invited to take part in one telephone or Skype interview. Prior to the interview you will receive a short briefing paper to help you to prepare for the interview. With your permission, the interview will be audio recorded so that it can be transcribed and analysed. The interview will take approximately 30 minutes to complete and will be conducted in English. If you are willing to participate in the study, the research team will be pleased to assist you to make the practical arrangements for the interview.

We thank you for your potential support and very much appreciate the time that you have taken to consider our request.

Yours truly,

***Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity,
contribution and influence on public health and healthcare policy:
an international study***

We would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and discuss with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

Who is conducting the study?

The researcher conducting this study is Meghan Bateson, supervised by Professor Debbie Tolson. The study is part of an PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) being undertaken at the University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of this study is to explore strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy internationally.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to be invited because you have been identified as having an interest and relevant experience in strategic nurse leadership and public policy.

What would I have to do if I agreed to take part?

The study comprises several strands of research. A Delphi study has been undertaken which developed a consensus statement exemplifying global perspectives on effective nurse leadership and policy influence. The part of the study you are being invited to participate in forms the consideration of potential usefulness of the consensus statement which emerged from the Delphi.

If you decide to take part, you will be asked to participate in one interview. The interview will be conducted in English by either telephone or Skype. Participants will consider the consensus statement which emerged from the Delphi in the context of their leadership role.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you whether or not you decide to take part. If you do decide to participate you will be given this information sheet to keep and asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw from the study at any time and without giving a reason. A decision to withdraw at any time, or a decision not to take part, will not affect your rights or relationships with the collaborating organisations of this research.

Appendix 18: Post-Delphi Interview Participant Information Sheet

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Your identity and the identity of any individuals and organisations named within the interview will be removed from the interview transcript, and confidentiality will be respected during project reporting. Insights gathered from you and other participants will be used in writing up the findings of this study. Although direct quotes from you may be used in the report or other publication, your name and other identifying information will be kept anonymous.

The information obtained during the interview will remain confidential and will be stored in a locked filing cabinet. The data will be held in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998), which means that we will keep it safely and cannot reveal it to other people. Personal data will not be kept for any longer than 12 months after the end of the study.

Will the study benefit me?

It may not benefit you directly but, by taking part in this research, you will be contributing to the development of knowledge about international strategic nurse leadership in influencing public policy.

What if something goes wrong?

If you want to complain at any time about anything related to this research study please contact the Dean of Health Nursing and Midwifery, Karen Wilson at [REDACTED]

What will happen to the findings of the research study?

The findings may be submitted for publication in peer review journals and presented at conferences. The final study report will be available to participants on request.

Who is organising and funding the study?

This study is being conducted by the University of the West of Scotland.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given favourable opinion by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee.

If you have any further questions

If you have any questions or would like more information, please contact Meghan Bateson at [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking the time to consider this opportunity.

Personal details withheld.

Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public policy: an international study.

Participant Consent Form

Your support and contribution to this study is greatly appreciated. You are now cordially requested to formally consent to participating in the study by taking part in an individual telephone or Skype interview.

The interview will be conducted in English and last no longer than 30 minutes. Papers will be circulated to you in advance of the interview for you to read and consider. Your identity and the identity of any individuals and organisations named within the interviews will be removed from the data and confidentiality will be respected during project reporting.

Please initial the box

- 1) I confirm that I have read the letter of invitation and understand the participant information sheet dated 22.12.2016 (version 1.0) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2) I understand that I am a voluntary participant in the research and that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without my legal rights being affected.
- 3) I understand that findings from the study may be published in professional journals, and included at conferences.
- 4) I understand that my interview will be recorded using audio / audiovisual equipment
- 5) I agree to take part in the study.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of interviewer Date Signature

Thank you for your participation and if you have further questions please do not hesitate to get in touch.

Appendix 20: Post-Delphi interview briefing paper and interview schedule

Understanding strategic nurse leadership, opportunity, contribution and influence on public health and healthcare policy: an international study

To help prepare for your interview please read the draft consensus statement and interview questions which appear below.

The Draft Consensus Statement

The advancement of public health and wellbeing through policy making must be informed by nursing expertise. Ensuring that this expertise is used effectively for the benefit of global health requires more nurse leaders to hold policy making positions and to possess policy influence, the development of which is a key priority for the nursing profession.

To improve policy influence nurses must be recognised as active and influential decision makers. To achieve this there is a need to establish a credible and collective nursing voice developed through international collaboration of strategic nurse leaders. National nursing strategies will inform this collaboration by providing clarity and direction of vision tailored to the needs of each country. This will enable the application of cultural and contextual understanding to internationally shared priorities which will ensure the formulation of responses which are effective and appropriate at a national level.

Proactively expanding the scope of nursing's policy activity beyond issues directly related to the profession will progress nursing's policy influence. The credibility of nurse leaders' contributions across a wider range of issues relevant to society will be strengthened by collaboration out with nursing and health care. Infrastructure is required to support effective collaboration and networking.

Leadership and policy education is required to prepare nurses for strategic leadership roles. Additionally, an overarching plan to improve the capacity and capability of nursing for policy making would provide a framework to optimise the quality and impact of the nursing contribution to policy. This framework is expected to include the development of a defined leadership pathway and structures for systematic succession planning.

The questions you will be asked:-

- Please confirm your details – name, job title, number of years in your role, country of employment
- What do you consider to be the key messages from the consensus statement?
- Which of the key messages arising from the consensus statement are a priority for nurse leaders?
- Thinking about your leadership role how could you use such a statement?
- How might nurses use this in different sectors and settings in your country?
- You'll notice that at the end of paragraph three there is a statement about infrastructure being required to support effective collaboration and networking. What tools or resources would enable you to progress this in your country?
- What advice would you give me in terms of next steps for the statement?
- Is there anything else you would like to add?

If you have any queries about the consensus statement or the questions above prior to your interview please contact Meghan Bateson at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 21: Delphi panel composition

World Region

Region	Total Panel No. (n=40)	Round 3 panellists No. (n=24)
Africa	20% (8/40)	16.7% (4/24)
Americas	10% (4/40)	12.5% (3/24)
South-East Asia	2.5% (1/40)	4.2% (1/24)
Europe	42.5% (17/40)	37.5% (9/24)
Eastern Mediterranean	10% (4/40)	8.3% (2/24)
Western Pacific	15% (6/40)	20.8% (5/24)

Income level

Region	Total Panel No. (n=40)	Round 3 panellists No. (n=24)
Africa	20% (8/40)	16.7% (4/24)
Americas	10% (4/40)	12.5% (3/24)
South-East Asia	2.5% (1/40)	4.2% (1/24)
Europe	42.5% (17/40)	37.5% (9/24)
Eastern Mediterranean	10% (4/40)	8.3% (2/24)
Western Pacific	15% (6/40)	20.8% (5/24)

Sector of leadership in Round 3

Single sector roles in total panel: 57.5% (23/40)

Single sector roles in Round 3 panel: 62.5% (15/24)

Combined roles in total panel: 42.5% (17/40)

Combined roles in Round 3 panel: 37.5% (9/24)

Sector	Single Sector Roles Total Panel (n=23)	Single Sector Roles Round 3 (n=15)	Combined Roles Total Panel (n=17)	Combined Roles No. (n=9)
Education	8 (34.8%)	6 (40%)	9	5
Government	4 (17.4%)	3 (20%)	7	3
Health Providing Organisation	0	0	8	4
Professional Nursing Association	4 (17.4%)	1 (6.7%)	11	6
Professional Regulation	6 (26.1%)	4 (26.7%)	6	2
Other: Non-governmental organisation	1 (4.34%)	1 (6.7%)	0	0
Trade Union	0	0	2	1

Appendix 22: Delphi Round 1 statements mapped to integrative review and pre-Delphi findings

	Round 1 Statement	Pre-Delphi interviews	Integrative review
1	Nursing is currently unable to articulate its potential contribution to public policy	X	X
2	There is a clear understanding within the profession of the roles of nurse leaders from different sectors in influencing public policy.	X	
3	Nurse leaders seek support from healthcare and other disciplines to achieve influence.	X	
4	Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	X	
5	Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy.	X	X
6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	X	
7	Nurses are marginalised (seen and treated as less important than other disciplines) in policy making.	X	X
8	We don't need to change anything about nursing policy influence at a national level.		X
9	Nurses around the world have the same opportunities to contribute to public policy.		X
10	Nursing should focus policy efforts more on patients and communities rather than on professional issues.	X	X
11	Nurse leaders work together in a coordinated way to influence public policy.	X	
12	Nurses are rarely at the policy making table.		X
13	In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.		X
14	Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence	X	
15	An agreed structure is required to facilitate the collaboration of different sectors of nursing.	X	
16	All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities.	X	X
17	There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy.	X	
18	Disciplines such as nursing can effectively influence public policy on their own.	X	
19	Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy	X	
20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	X	X
21	Nursing has an effective political voice.	X	X
22	Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing.	X	
23	Policy influence is not a priority in nursing	X	
	Round 1 Statement	Pre-Delphi interviews	Integrative review

Appendix 22: Delphi Round 1 statements mapped to integrative review and pre-Delphi findings

24	There are unique public health policy issues in my country.		X
25	There is no benefit from nurse leaders from different countries working together.	X	
26	National structures and systems exclude nurses from the policy processes.		X
27	Nursing has a strong, credible professional image which helps them to influence public policy.	X	X
28	Nurses make an important contribution to public policy.	X	
29	Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy.	X	
30	Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health.	X	X
31	Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions.	X	
32	A collective international nursing voice would strengthen my policy influence in my country.	X	
33	Personal leadership qualities are more useful than formal leadership education.	X	
34	Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence.	X	
35	Cultural understanding is important to effective global policy influence.		X
36	There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	X	
37	Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	X	
38	Succession planning needs more resources in order to be provided systematically.	X	
39	Effective nursing leadership in the policy process requires a range of approaches		X
40	Nurses need to be formally educated to take up strategic nurse leadership roles.	X	
41	There should be a standardised mentorship programme for potential nurse leaders.	X	
42	Nurse leadership preparation begins at the pre-registration (student) stage.	X	X
43	There should be a strategic plan for developing the capability and capacity of nursing for policy.	X	
44	Understanding the public health context (situation) is important to effective policy influence.		X
45	Policy and leadership education is available in my country.	X	X
46	There is enough time for potential nurse leaders to develop their leadership skills.	X	

Appendix 23: Mapping of Delphi Round 1 Content Analysis to Round 2 Statements

Appendix 23. Barriers and facilitators of nursing policy influence: mapping of Round 1 analysis to Round 2 statements

Round 1 Content Analysis			Round 2 Statement
Theme	Subtheme	Category	
Preparing nurses for leadership in policy making	Towards sustainable participation in policy making	Mentorship for policy leadership	R2 23. Mentorship should be provided by nurse leaders who know and understand the culture and environment where the person being mentored works.
		Succession planning for strategic nurse leadership	R2 24. There is a need for a defined leadership career pathway to enable more deliberate succession planning. R2 27. Succession planning should be undertaken on the basis of the nurse's competence, attributes and ability to lead, not their clinical skill. R2 28. In my country nurses are often forced into leadership because there is no one else to do the job.
		Establishing a profession-wide expectation of policy participation at every level	R2 13. Nurses lack interest in policy making R2 14. Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy. R2 15. Involvement in policy making is not perceived by nurses as beneficial. R2 25. We need more nurse leaders who have a clinical academic profile.
		Enabling nurses to feel prepared to contribute to policy	R2 11. Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.
		Personal leadership qualities	-

Appendix 23: Mapping of Delphi Round 1 Content Analysis to Round 2 Statements

Theme	Subtheme	Category	Round 2 Statement
Preparing nurses for leadership in policy making	Improving provision and access to quality leadership and policy education	Increase resources for developing and accessing education	R2 18. In my country access to education on policy needs to be cheaper and more accessible. R2 22. Policy and leadership education should be provided by professional nursing associations and organisations as well as educational institutions.
		Lack of capacity and capability	R2 20. In my country the education system needs to change to make nurses fit for purpose for participating in policy making.
		Embedding leadership and policy education at every level	R2 19. Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes R2 21. There is a need to embed an expectation amongst nursing students that they should be able to understand and engage with policy making.
		Improving the quality of leadership & policy education	R2 17. The quality of education on policy needs to be improved.

Appendix 23: Mapping of Delphi Round 1 Content Analysis to Round 2 Statements

.Theme	Subtheme	Category	Round 2 Statement
Positioning nursing as a policy capable profession	Recognising nurses as legitimate policy influencers	Making and taking opportunities to contribute to policy	R2 12. Nurse leaders do not take an active role in policy making. R2 16. Nursing is reactive rather than proactive in policy making.
		Developing and using evidence in policy	R2 7. There is a need for more nurse research which is designed to support policy making decisions.
		External perception of the role of nursing in policy	R2 9. In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision making process.
		Adopting a policy focus beyond nursing	Addressed in Round 1, Statements 6, 10 & 20.
		Influence of traditional role on policy contribution	R2 1. In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing. R2 2. In my country gender inequality has an impact on the ability of nurse leaders to influence public policy.
	Intraprofessional challenges in optimising policy contribution	Developing a unified nursing voice in policy	Addressed in Round 1, Statement 30
		Complex nursing structure & hierarchy	R2 4. The hierarchy within nursing is complicated and this adversely affects policy contribution.
		Need for a strategic plan	R2 26. In my country there is a clear policy vision for nursing R2 33. Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.
		Lack of time for policy participation	Addressed in Round 1, Statement 29

Appendix 23: Mapping of Delphi Round 1 Content Analysis to Round 2 Statements

Theme	Subtheme	Category	Round 2 Statement
Positioning nursing as a policy capable profession	Improving the visibility of nurse leadership in policy	More nurses in stable policy making positions	R2 3. Nurse leaders are not in a stable position which makes it difficult to develop policy influence and to take risks R2 5. In my country we do not have enough strong professional nurse leaders.
		Increasing collaboration and networking intra- and inter-professionally	Addressed in Round 1, Statements 3, 11, 15, 16, 18, 22, 25
		Strengthening the visibility and media profile of nursing	R2 32. Nurses who are active in public policy need to be more visible. R2 8. Nursing needs a more visible and positive media profile nationally and internationally.
	Political challenges	Effect of political stability on influence of nurse leaders	R2 29. The political stability of my country has a significant impact on the nursing contribution to public policy.
		Accessibility of decision makers	R2 10. It is difficult to gain access to the decision makers in policy.
		Corruption in policy	R2 30. Corruption affects policy making in my country.
		Political processes	R2 31. The policy process in my country is slow and dysfunctional.

Appendix 24: Mapping items which achieved consensus to consensus statement

The following tables set out the statements that reached consensus and of them, which were included in the consensus statement.

ID	Round 1 Statement	Included in Consensus statement
1	Nursing is currently unable to articulate it's potential contribution to public policy	
3	Nurse leaders seek support from healthcare and other disciplines to achieve influence.	X
4	Nurse leaders focus on nursing issues within policy making because of a lack of confidence in other policy topics.	
5	Nursing has low status and struggles to influence public policy	
6	Nurse leaders focus their effort on policies that directly affect nurses and nursing services.	
7	Nurses are marginalised (seen and treated as less important than other disciplines) in policy making	
8	We don't need to change anything about nursing policy influence at a national level.	X
9	Nurses around the world have the same opportunities to contribute to public policy	
12	Nurses are rarely at the policy making table.	
13	In my country there are public health policy priorities which are shared in the global nursing community.	
14	Relationships and networks are more important than evidence in policy influence.	
15	An agreed structure is required to facilitate the collaboration of different sectors of nursing.	X
16	All nurse leaders within my country must proactively collaborate to identify and address unique and shared public health priorities.	X
17	There is a public expectation that nurses contribute to public policy	X
20	To increase its policy influence nursing must contribute to broader policy issues which may not be directly related to nursing.	X
22	Now is a good time for collaborating with other professional groups outside of nursing.	
23	Policy influence is not a priority in nursing.	X
25	There is no benefit from nurse leaders from different countries working together.	X
27	The impact of the contribution that nurse leadership can make to public policy is directly related to their networks and how they manage their networks.	X
28	Nurses make an important contribution to public policy.	X
29	Nurse leaders do not have enough time to contribute effectively to public policy.	
30	Nursing can develop a collective voice for global health.	X
31	Nurses make an effective contribution to strategic policy discussions.	X
32	A collective international nursing voice would strengthen my policy influence in my country.	X
34	Nursing must collaborate with stakeholders out with the profession in order to optimise policy influence	X
35	Cultural understanding is important to effective global policy influence	X

Appendix 24: Mapping items which achieved consensus to consensus statement

ID	Round 1 Statement	Included in Consensus Statement
36	There should be systematic succession planning for strategic nurse leadership roles.	X
37	Nursing as a profession is already well equipped to participate in public policy	X
38	Succession planning needs more resources in order to be provided systematically.	X
39	Effective nursing leadership in the policy process requires a range of approaches	
40	Nurses need to be formally educated to take up strategic nurse leadership roles	X
41	There should be a standardised mentorship programme for potential nurse leaders.	
42	Nurse leadership preparation begins at the pre-registration (student) stage.	
43	There should be a strategic plan for developing the capability and capacity of nursing for policy	X
44	Understanding the public health context (situation) is important to effective policy influence.	X
45	Policy and leadership education is available in my country.	

ID	Round 2 Statement	Included in Consensus Statement
R2: 1	In my country medicine has a stronger voice than nursing.	
R2: 6	There are not enough nurses in policy making positions in my country.	X
R2: 7	There is a need for more nurse research which is designed to support policy making decisions.	
R2: 8	Nursing needs a more visible and positive media profile nationally and internationally.	
R2: 9	In my country there needs to be a change in the culture of policy making to recognise nurses as key players in the decision making process.	X
R2: 11	Nurse leaders do not feel adequately prepared for contributing to general and public health policy.	X
R2: 14	Generally, nurses do not expect that they or their colleagues should understand the importance and prioritise their contribution to health policy.	
R2: 16	Nursing is reactive rather than proactive in policy making.	
R2: 17	The quality of education on policy needs to be improved.	
R2: 18	In my country access to education on policy needs to be cheaper and more accessible.	
R2: 19	Policy related education should be embedded into all undergraduate and postgraduate nursing programmes	X
R2: 20	In my country the education system needs to change to make nurses fit for purpose for participating in policy making.	
R2: 21	There is a need to embed an expectation amongst nursing students that they should be able to understand and engage with policy making.	

Appendix 24: Mapping items which achieved consensus to consensus statement

ID	Round 2 Statement	Included in Consensus Statement
R2: 22	Policy and leadership education should be provided by professional nursing associations and organisations as well as educational institutions.	
R2: 23	Mentorship should be provided by nurse leaders who know and understand the culture and environment where the person being mentored works.	
R2: 24	There is a need for a defined leadership career pathway to enable more deliberate succession planning.	X
R2: 25	We need more nurse leaders who have a clinical academic profile.	
R2: 27	Succession planning should be undertaken on the basis of the nurse's competence, attributes, and ability to lead, not their clinical skill.	
R2: 29	The political stability of my country has a significant impact on the nursing contribution to public policy.	
R2: 32	Nurses who are active in public policy need to be more visible.	X
R2: 33	Every country should have a regularly updated nursing strategy which sets out the vision and priorities of the profession as a whole.	X